

Finite Difference Equations Obtained:
(Sorted by derivative and error)

"--- Derivative Order: 1 - x1=1 ---"

$$\begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{I} & \mathbf{1} + \mathbf{I} \\ 0 & \mathbf{1} \end{bmatrix}$$

$$\begin{bmatrix} 1 & \frac{1}{2} - \frac{\mathbf{I}}{2} \\ -\frac{3}{2} + \frac{3\mathbf{I}}{2} & -\mathbf{I} \end{bmatrix}$$

$$\frac{d}{dx1} u(x1) = \frac{2 u_{il+1} + (1 - \mathbf{I}) u_{il+1+1} + (-3 + 3\mathbf{I}) u_{il} - 2 \mathbf{I} u_{il+1}}{2 \Delta x1}, O(\Delta x1^3), \text{ Quadrant 1}$$

Error order:, 3, Error:, 1.2572043154561172743 $\times 10^{-9}$, New Error:, 1.2562019630633476128 $\times 10^{-18}$
 Error order:, 3, Error:, 1.2562019630633476128 $\times 10^{-18}$, New Error:, 1.2562009611110437206 $\times 10^{-27}$
 Error order:, 3, Error:, 1.2562009611110437206 $\times 10^{-27}$, New Error:, 1.2562009601090918167 $\times 10^{-36}$
 Error order:, 3, Error:, 1.2562009601090918167 $\times 10^{-36}$, New Error:, 1.2562009601080898647 $\times 10^{-45}$
 Error order:, 3, Error:, 1.2562009601080898647 $\times 10^{-45}$, New Error:, 1.2562009601080888628 $\times 10^{-54}$

$$\frac{d^2}{dx1^2} u(x1) = \frac{2 u_{il+21} + (2 - 2\mathbf{I}) u_{il+1+21} - \mathbf{I} u_{il+2+21} + (-6 + 6\mathbf{I}) u_{il+1} + 2 \mathbf{I} u_{il+1+1} - (2 + 2\mathbf{I}) u_{il+2+1} - 9 \mathbf{I} u_{il} + (6 + 6\mathbf{I}) u_{il+1} - 2 u_{il+2}}{2 \Delta x1^2}, O(\Delta x1^3), \text{ Quadrant 1}$$

Error order:, 3, Error:, 2.5093898507934185427 $\times 10^{-9}$, New Error:, 2.5073891478310331589 $\times 10^{-18}$
 Error order:, 3, Error:, 2.5073891478310331589 $\times 10^{-18}$, New Error:, 2.5073871479262349712 $\times 10^{-27}$
 Error order:, 3, Error:, 2.5073871479262349712 $\times 10^{-27}$, New Error:, 2.5073871459263309714 $\times 10^{-36}$
 Error order:, 3, Error:, 2.5073871459263309714 $\times 10^{-36}$, New Error:, 2.5073871459243310674 $\times 10^{-45}$
 Error order:, 3, Error:, 2.5073871459243310674 $\times 10^{-45}$, New Error:, 2.5073871459243290675 $\times 10^{-54}$

$$\frac{\partial^2}{\partial x1 \partial x2} u(x1, x2) = \frac{2 u_{il+1, i2+1} + (1 - \mathbf{I}) u_{il+1, i2+1+1} + (-3 + 3\mathbf{I}) u_{il+1, i2} - 2 \mathbf{I} u_{il+1, i2+1} + (1 - \mathbf{I}) u_{il+1+1, i2+1} - \mathbf{I} u_{il+1+1, i2+1+1} + 3 \mathbf{I} u_{il+1+1, i2} - (1 + \mathbf{I}) u_{il+1+1, i2+1} + (-3 + 3\mathbf{I}) u_{il, i2+1} + 3 \mathbf{I} u_{il, i2+1+1} - 9 \mathbf{I} u_{il, i2} + (3 + 3\mathbf{I}) u_{il, i2+1} - 2 \mathbf{I} u_{il+1, i2+1} - (1 + \mathbf{I}) u_{il+1, i2+1+1} + (3 + 3\mathbf{I}) u_{il+1, i2} - 2 u_{il+1, i2+1}}{2 \Delta x1 \Delta x2},$$

$O(\Delta x1^3 \Delta x2^3)$, Quadrant 1

Error order:, 3, Error:, 1.4615394908821114374 $\times 10^{-8}$, New Error:, 1.4599266635994244984 $\times 10^{-17}$
 Error order:, 3, Error:, 1.4599266635994244984 $\times 10^{-17}$, New Error:, 1.4599250516628790459 $\times 10^{-26}$
 Error order:, 3, Error:, 1.4599250516628790459 $\times 10^{-26}$, New Error:, 1.4599250500509433913 $\times 10^{-35}$
 Error order:, 3, Error:, 1.4599250500509433913 $\times 10^{-35}$, New Error:, 1.4599250500493314556 $\times 10^{-44}$
 Error order:, 3, Error:, 1.4599250500493314556 $\times 10^{-44}$, New Error:, 1.4599250500493298437 $\times 10^{-53}$

$$\frac{d^3}{dx1^3} u(x1) = \frac{4 u_{il+31} + (6 - 6\mathbf{I}) u_{il+1+31} - 6 \mathbf{I} u_{il+2+31} - (1 + \mathbf{I}) u_{il+3+31} + (-18 + 18\mathbf{I}) u_{il+21} + 24 \mathbf{I} u_{il+1+21} - (3 + 3\mathbf{I}) u_{il+2+21} - 6 u_{il+3+21} - 54 \mathbf{I} u_{il+1} + (9 + 9\mathbf{I}) u_{il+1+1} + 24 u_{il+2+1} + (-6 + 6\mathbf{I}) u_{il+3+1} + (27 + 27\mathbf{I}) u_{il} - 54 u_{il+1} + (18 - 18\mathbf{I}) u_{il+2} + 4 \mathbf{I} u_{il+3}}{4 \Delta x1^3}, O(\Delta x1^3), \text{ Quadrant 1}$$

Error order:, 3, Error:, 3.7565716323009313871 $\times 10^{-9}$, New Error:, 3.7535765686093310756 $\times 10^{-18}$
 Error order:, 3, Error:, 3.7535765686093310756 $\times 10^{-18}$, New Error:, 3.7535735747398727114 $\times 10^{-27}$
 Error order:, 3, Error:, 3.7535735747398727114 $\times 10^{-27}$, New Error:, 3.7535735717460044481 $\times 10^{-36}$

Error order:, 3, *Error:*, 3.7535735717460044481 $\times 10^{-36}$, *New Error:*, 3.7535735717430105799 $\times 10^{-45}$
Error order:, 3, *Error:*, 3.7535735717430105799 $\times 10^{-45}$, *New Error:*, 3.7535735717430075860 $\times 10^{-54}$

$$\frac{\partial^3}{\partial x I^2 \partial x^2} u(xI, x2) = \frac{1}{4 \Delta x I^2 \Delta x^2} (4 u_{iI+2I, i2+1} + (2 - 2I) u_{iI+2I, i2+1+1} + (-6 + 6I) u_{iI+2I, i2} - 4 I u_{iI+2I, i2+1} + (4 - 4I) u_{iI+1+2I, i2+1} - 4 I u_{iI+1+2I, i2+1+1} + 12 I u_{iI+1+2I, i2} - (4 + 4I) u_{iI+1+2I, i2+1} - 2 I u_{iI+2+2I, i2+1} - (1 + I) u_{iI+2+2I, i2+1+1} + (3 + 3I) u_{iI+2+2I, i2} - 2 u_{iI+2+2I, i2+1} + (-12 + 12I) u_{iI+L, i2+1} + 12 I u_{iI+1, i2+1+1} - 36 I u_{iI+1, i2} + (12 + 12I) u_{iI+1, i2+1} + 4 I u_{iI+1+1, i2+1} + (2 + 2I) u_{iI+1+1, i2+1+1} - (6 + 6I) u_{iI+1+1, i2} + 4 u_{iI+1+1, i2+1} - (4 + 4I) u_{iI+2+1, i2+1} - 4 u_{iI+2+1, i2+1+1} + 12 u_{iI+2+1, i2} + (-4 + 4I) u_{iI+2+1, i2+1} - 18 I u_{iI, i2+1} - (9 + 9I) u_{iI, i2+1+1} + (27 + 27I) u_{iI, i2} - 18 u_{iI, i2+1} + (12 + 12I) u_{iI+1, i2+1} + 12 u_{iI+1, i2+1+1} - 36 u_{iI+1, i2} + (12 - 12I) u_{iI+1, i2+1} - 4 u_{iI+2, i2+1} + (-2 + 2I) u_{iI+2, i2+1+1} + (6 - 6I) u_{iI+2, i2} + 4 I u_{iI+2, i2+1}), $O(\Delta x I^3 \Delta x^3)$, *Quadrant I*
Error order:, 3, *Error:*, 1.7926893705876773203 $\times 10^{-8}$, *New Error:*, 1.7908134284885071498 $\times 10^{-17}$
Error order:, 3, *Error:*, 1.7908134284885071498 $\times 10^{-17}$, *New Error:*, 1.7908115535284095914 $\times 10^{-26}$
Error order:, 3, *Error:*, 1.7908115535284095914 $\times 10^{-26}$, *New Error:*, 1.7908115516534504764 $\times 10^{-35}$
Error order:, 3, *Error:*, 1.7908115516534504764 $\times 10^{-35}$, *New Error:*, 1.7908115516515755173 $\times 10^{-44}$
Error order:, 3, *Error:*, 1.7908115516515755173 $\times 10^{-44}$, *New Error:*, 1.7908115516515736423 $\times 10^{-53}$$$

$$\frac{\partial^3}{\partial x I \partial x^2 \partial x^3} u(xI, x2, x3) = \frac{1}{4 \Delta x I \Delta x^2 \Delta x^3} (4 u_{iI+1, i2+1, i3+1} + (2 - 2I) u_{iI+1, i2+1, i3+1+1} + (-6 + 6I) u_{iI+1, i2+1, i3} - 4 I u_{iI+1, i2+1, i3+1} + (2 - 2I) u_{iI+1, i2+1+1, i3+1} - 2 I u_{iI+1, i2+1+1, i3+1+1} + 6 I u_{iI+1, i2+1+1, i3} - (2 + 2I) u_{iI+1, i2+1+1, i3+1} + (-6 + 6I) u_{iI+1, i2, i3+1} + 6 I u_{iI+1, i2, i3+1+1} - 18 I u_{iI+1, i2, i3} + (6 + 6I) u_{iI+1, i2, i3+1} - 4 I u_{iI+1, i2+1, i3+1} - (2 + 2I) u_{iI+1, i2+1, i3+1+1} + (6 + 6I) u_{iI+1, i2+1, i3} - 4 u_{iI+1, i2+1, i3+1} + (2 - 2I) u_{iI+1+1, i2+1, i3+1} - 2 I u_{iI+1+1, i2+1, i3+1+1} + 6 I u_{iI+1+1, i2+1, i3} - (2 + 2I) u_{iI+1+1, i2+1, i3+1} - 2 I u_{iI+1+1, i2+1+1, i3+1} - (1 + I) u_{iI+1+1, i2+1+1, i3+1+1} + (3 + 3I) u_{iI+1+1, i2+1+1, i3} - 2 u_{iI+1+1, i2+1+1, i3+1} + 6 I u_{iI+1+1, i2, i3+1} + (3 + 3I) u_{iI+1+1, i2, i3+1+1} - (9 + 9I) u_{iI+1+1, i2, i3} + 6 u_{iI+1+1, i2, i3+1} - (2 + 2I) u_{iI+1+1, i2+1, i3+1} - 2 u_{iI+1+1, i2+1, i3+1+1} + 6 u_{iI+1+1, i2+1, i3} + (-2 + 2I) u_{iI+1+1, i2+1, i3+1} + (-6 + 6I) u_{iI, i2+1, i3+1} + 6 I u_{iI, i2+1, i3+1+1} - 18 I u_{iI, i2+1, i3} + (6 + 6I) u_{iI, i2+1, i3+1} + 6 I u_{iI, i2+1+1, i3+1} + (3 + 3I) u_{iI, i2+1+1, i3+1+1} - (9 + 9I) u_{iI, i2+1+1, i3} + 6 u_{iI, i2+1+1, i3+1} - 18 I u_{iI, i2, i3+1} - (9 + 9I) u_{iI, i2, i3+1+1} + (27 + 27I) u_{iI, i2, i3} - 18 u_{iI, i2, i3+1} + (6 + 6I) u_{iI, i2+1, i3+1} + 6 u_{iI, i2+1, i3+1+1} - 18 u_{iI, i2+1, i3} + (6 - 6I) u_{iI, i2+1, i3+1} - 4 I u_{iI+1, i2+1, i3+1} - (2 + 2I) u_{iI+1, i2+1, i3+1+1} + (6 + 6I) u_{iI+1, i2+1, i3} - 4 u_{iI+1, i2+1, i3+1} - (2 + 2I) u_{iI+1, i2+1+1, i3+1} - 2 u_{iI+1, i2+1+1, i3+1+1} + 6 u_{iI+1, i2+1+1, i3} + (-2 + 2I) u_{iI+1, i2+1+1, i3+1} + (6 + 6I) u_{iI+1, i2, i3+1} + 6 u_{iI+1, i2, i3+1+1} - 18 u_{iI+1, i2, i3} + (6 - 6I) u_{iI+1, i2+1, i3+1} - 4 u_{iI+1, i2+1, i3+1} + (-2 + 2I) u_{iI+1, i2+1, i3+1+1} + (6 - 6I) u_{iI+1, i2+1, i3} + 4 I u_{iI+1, i2+1, i3+1}), $O(\Delta x I^3 \Delta x^2 \Delta x^3)$, *Quadrant I*
Error order:, 3, *Error:*, 1.7471565763844110933 $\times 10^{-7}$, *New Error:*, 1.7440255295604359329 $\times 10^{-16}$
Error order:, 3, *Error:*, 1.7440255295604359329 $\times 10^{-16}$, *New Error:*, 1.7440224013216190486 $\times 10^{-25}$
Error order:, 3, *Error:*, 1.7440224013216190486 $\times 10^{-25}$, *New Error:*, 1.7440223981933830401 $\times 10^{-34}$
Error order:, 3, *Error:*, 1.7440223981933830401 $\times 10^{-34}$, *New Error:*, 1.7440223981902548041 $\times 10^{-43}$
Error order:, 3, *Error:*, 1.7440223981902548041 $\times 10^{-43}$, *New Error:*, 1.7440223981902516758 $\times 10^{-52}$$$

$$\frac{d^4}{dx I^4} u(xI) = \frac{1}{4 \Delta x I^4} (4 u_{iI+4I} + (8 - 8I) u_{iI+1+4I} - 12 I u_{iI+2+4I} - (4 + 4I) u_{iI+3+4I} - u_{iI+4+4I} + (-24 + 24I) u_{iI+3I} + 56 I u_{iI+1+3I} + (12 + 12I) u_{iI+2+3I} - 12 u_{iI+3+3I} + (-4 + 4I) u_{iI+4+3I} - 108 I u_{iI+2I} - (36 + 36I) u_{iI+1+2I} + 66 u_{iI+2+2I} + (12 - 12I) u_{iI+3+2I} + 12 I u_{iI+4+2I} + (108 + 108I) u_{iI+1} - 108 u_{iI+1+1} + (-36 + 36I) u_{iI+2+1} - 56 I u_{iI+3+1} + (8 + 8I) u_{iI+4+1} - 81 u_{iI} + (108 - 108I) u_{iI+1} + 108 I u_{iI+2} - (24 + 24I) u_{iI+3} + 4 u_{iI+4}), $O(\Delta x I^3)$, *Quadrant I*
Error order:, 3, *Error:*, 4.9987646462775562459 $\times 10^{-9}$, *New Error:*, 4.9947791997462822022 $\times 10^{-18}$
Error order:, 3, *Error:*, 4.9947791997462822022 $\times 10^{-18}$, *New Error:*, 4.9947752158880541735 $\times 10^{-27}$
Error order:, 3, *Error:*, 4.9947752158880541735 $\times 10^{-27}$, *New Error:*, 4.9947752119041975358 $\times 10^{-36}$
Error order:, 3, *Error:*, 4.9947752119041975358 $\times 10^{-36}$, *New Error:*, 4.9947752119002136791 $\times 10^{-45}$
Error order:, 3, *Error:*, 4.9947752119002136791 $\times 10^{-45}$, *New Error:*, 4.9947752119002096953 $\times 10^{-54}$$$

$$\frac{\partial^4}{\partial x I^3 \partial x^2} u(xI, x2) = \frac{1}{4 \Delta x I^3 \Delta x^2} (4 u_{iI+3I, i2+1} + (2 - 2I) u_{iI+3I, i2+1+1} + (-6 + 6I) u_{iI+3I, i2} - 4 I u_{iI+3I, i2+1} + (6 - 6I) u_{iI+1+3I, i2+1} - 6 I u_{iI+1+3I, i2+1+1} + 18 I u_{iI+1+3I, i2} - (6 + 6I) u_{iI+1+3I, i2+1} - 6 I u_{iI+2+3I, i2+1} - (3 + 3I) u_{iI+2+3I, i2+1+1} + (9 + 9I) u_{iI+2+3I, i2} - 6 u_{iI+2+3I, i2+1} - (1 + I) u_{iI+3+3I, i2+1} - u_{iI+3+3I, i2+1+1} + 3 u_{iI+3+3I, i2} + (-1 + I) u_{iI+3+3I, i2+1} + (-18 + 18I) u_{iI+2I, i2+1} + 18 I u_{iI+2I, i2+1+1} - 54 I u_{iI+2I, i2} + (18 + 18I) u_{iI+2I, i2+1} + 24 I u_{iI+1+2I, i2+1} + (12 + 12I) u_{iI+1+2I, i2+1+1} - (36 + 36I) u_{iI+1+2I, i2} + 24 u_{iI+1+2I, i2+1} - (3 + 3I) u_{iI+2+2I, i2+1} - 3 u_{iI+2+2I, i2+1+1} + 9 u_{iI+2+2I, i2} + (-3 + 3I) u_{iI+2+2I, i2+1} - 6 u_{iI+3+2I, i2+1} + (-3 + 3I) u_{iI+3+2I, i2+1+1} + (9 - 9I) u_{iI+3+2I, i2} + 6 I u_{iI+3+2I, i2+1} - 54 I u_{iI+1, i2+1} - (27 + 27I) u_{iI+1, i2+1+1} + (81 + 81I) u_{iI+1, i2} - 54 u_{iI+1, i2+1} + (9 + 9I) u_{iI+1+1, i2+1} + 9 u_{iI+1+1, i2+1+1} - 27 u_{iI+1+1, i2} + (9 - 9I) u_{iI+1+1, i2+1} + 24 u_{iI+2+1, i2+1} + (12 - 12I) u_{iI+2+1, i2+1+1} + (-36 + 36I) u_{iI+2+1, i2} - 24 I u_{iI+2+1, i2+1} + (-6 + 6I) u_{iI+3+1, i2+1} + 6 I u_{iI+3+1, i2+1+1} - 18 I u_{iI+3+1, i2} + (6 + 6I) u_{iI+3+1, i2+1} + (27 + 27I) u_{iI, i2+1} + 27 u_{iI, i2+1+1} - 81 u_{iI, i2} + (27 - 27I) u_{iI, i2+1} - 54 u_{iI+1, i2+1} + (-27 + 27I) u_{iI+1, i2+1+1} + (81 - 81I) u_{iI+1, i2} + 54 I u_{iI+1, i2+1} + (18 - 18I) u_{iI+2, i2+1} - 18 I u_{iI+2, i2+1+1} + 54 I u_{iI+2, i2} - (18 + 18I) u_{iI+2, i2+1} + 4 I u_{iI+3, i2+1} + (2 + 2I) u_{iI+3, i2+1+1} - (6 + 6I) u_{iI+3, i2} + 4 u_{iI+3, i2+1}), $O(\Delta x I^3 \Delta x^2)$, *Quadrant I*
Error order:, 3, *Error:*, 2.1225114757445109335 $\times 10^{-8}$, *New Error:*, 2.1203734717108177403 $\times 10^{-17}$
Error order:, 3, *Error:*, 2.1203734717108177403 $\times 10^{-17}$, *New Error:*, 2.1203713347835803197 $\times 10^{-26}$
Error order:, 3, *Error:*, 2.1203713347835803197 $\times 10^{-26}$, *New Error:*, 2.1203713326466541601 $\times 10^{-35}$
Error order:, 3, *Error:*, 2.1203713326466541601 $\times 10^{-35}$, *New Error:*, 2.1203713326445172340 $\times 10^{-44}$
Error order:, 3, *Error:*, 2.1203713326445172340 $\times 10^{-44}$, *New Error:*, 2.1203713326445150971 $\times 10^{-53}$$$

$$\frac{\partial^4}{\partial x I^2 \partial x^2} u(xI, x2) = \frac{1}{4 \Delta x I^2 \Delta x^2} (4 u_{iI+2I, i2+2I} + (4 - 4I) u_{iI+2I, i2+1+2I} - 2 I u_{iI+2I, i2+2+2I} + (-12 + 12I) u_{iI+2I, i2+1} + 4 I u_{iI+2I, i2+1+1} - (4 + 4I) u_{iI+2I, i2+2+1} - 18 I u_{iI+2I, i2} + (12 + 12I) u_{iI+2I, i2+1} - 4 u_{iI+2I, i2+2} + (4 - 4I) u_{iI+1+2I, i2+2I} - 8 I u_{iI+1+2I, i2+1+2I} - (2 + 2I) u_{iI+1+2I, i2+2+2I} + 24 I u_{iI+1+2I, i2+1} + (4 + 4I) u_{iI+1+2I, i2+1+1} - 8 u_{iI+1+2I, i2+2+1} - (18 + 18I) u_{iI+1+2I, i2} + 24 u_{iI+1+2I, i2+1} + (-4 + 4I) u_{iI+1+2I, i2+2} - 2 I u_{iI+2+2I, i2+2+1} - (2 + 2I) u_{iI+2+2I, i2+1+2I} - u_{iI+2+2I, i2+2+2I} + (6 + 6I) u_{iI+2+2I, i2+1} + 2 u_{iI+2+2I, i2+1+1} + (-2 + 2I) u_{iI+2+2I, i2+2+1} - 9 u_{iI+2+2I, i2} + (6 - 6I) u_{iI+2+2I, i2+1} + 2 I u_{iI+2+2I, i2+2} + (-12 + 12I) u_{iI+1, i2+2I} + 24 I u_{iI+1, i2+1+2I} + (6 + 6I) u_{iI+1, i2+2+2I} - 72 I u_{iI+1, i2+1} - (12 + 12I) u_{iI+1, i2+1+1} + 24 u_{iI+1, i2+2+1} + (54 + 54I) u_{iI+1, i2} - 72 u_{iI+1, i2+1} + (12 - 12I) u_{iI+1, i2+2} + 4 I u_{iI+1+1, i2+2I} + (4 + 4I) u_{iI+1+1, i2+1+2I} + 2 u_{iI+1+1, i2+2+2I} - (12 + 12I) u_{iI+1+1, i2+1} - 4 u_{iI+1+1, i2+1+1} + (4 - 4I) u_{iI+1+1, i2+2+1} + 18 u_{iI+1+1, i2} + (-12 + 12I) u_{iI+1+1, i2+1} - 4 I u_{iI+1+1, i2+2} - (4 + 4I) u_{iI+2+1, i2+2+1} - 8 u_{iI+2+1, i2+1+2I} + (-2 + 2I) u_{iI+2+1, i2+2+2I} + 24 u_{iI+2+1, i2+1} + (4 - 4I) u_{iI+2+1, i2+1+1} + 8 I u_{iI+2+1, i2+2+1} + (-18 + 18I) u_{iI+2+1, i2} - 24 I u_{iI+2+1, i2+1} + (4 + 4I) u_{iI+2+1, i2+2} - 18 I u_{iI, i2+2I} - (18 + 18I) u_{iI, i2+1+2I} - 9 u_{iI, i2+2+2I} + (54 + 54I) u_{iI, i2+1} + 18 u_{iI, i2+1+1} + (-18 + 18I) u_{iI, i2+2+1} - 81 u_{iI, i2} + (54 - 54I) u_{iI, i2+1} + 18 I u_{iI, i2+2} + (12 + 12I) u_{iI+1, i2+2I} + 24 u_{iI+1, i2+1+2I} + (6 - 6I) u_{iI+1, i2+2+2I} - 72 u_{iI+1, i2+1} + (-12 + 12I) u_{iI+1, i2+1+1} - 24 I u_{iI+1, i2+2+1} + (54 - 54I) u_{iI+1, i2} + 72 I u_{iI+1, i2+1} - (12 + 12I) u_{iI+1, i2+2} - 4 u_{iI+2, i2+2+1} + (-4 + 4I) u_{iI+2, i2+1+2I} + 2 I u_{iI+2, i2+2+2I} + (12 - 12I) u_{iI+2, i2+1} - 4 I u_{iI+2, i2+1+1} + (4 + 4I) u_{iI+2, i2+2+1} + 18 I u_{iI+2, i2} - (12 + 12I) u_{iI+2, i2+1} + 4 u_{iI+2, i2+2}), $O(\Delta x I^3 \Delta x^2)$, *Quadrant I*
Error order:, 3, *Error:*, 2.9085189338628397187 $\times 10^{-8}$, *New Error:*, 2.9053093485997586031 $\times 10^{-17}$
Error order:, 3, *Error:*, 2.9053093485997586031 $\times 10^{-17}$, *New Error:*, 2.9053061407849884398 $\times 10^{-26}$
Error order:, 3, *Error:*, 2.9053061407849884398 $\times 10^{-26}$, *New Error:*, 2.9053061375771754423 $\times 10^{-35}$
Error order:, 3, *Error:*, 2.9053061375771754423 $\times 10^{-35}$, *New Error:*, 2.9053061375739676293 $\times 10^{-44}$
Error order:, 3, *Error:*, 2.9053061375739676293 $\times 10^{-44}$, *New Error:*, 2.9053061375739644215 $\times 10^{-53}$$$

$$\frac{\partial^4}{\partial x^2 \partial x^2 \partial x^3} u(x1, x2, x3) = \frac{1}{4 \Delta x1^2 \Delta x2 \Delta x3} (4 u_{i+2, i, i+1} + (2-2I) u_{i+2, i+1, i+1} + (-6+6I) u_{i+2, i+1, i} - 4 I u_{i+2, i+1, i+1} + (2-2I) u_{i+2, i+1, i+1} - 2 I u_{i+2, i+1, i+1} + 6 I u_{i+2, i+1, i} - (2+2I) u_{i+2, i+1, i+1} + (-6+6I) u_{i+2, i, i+1} + 6 I u_{i+2, i, i+1} - 18 I u_{i+2, i, i} + (6+6I) u_{i+2, i, i} - 4 I u_{i+2, i, i+1} - (2+2I) u_{i+2, i+1, i+1} + (6+6I) u_{i+2, i+1, i} - 4 u_{i+2, i+1, i+1} + (4-4I) u_{i+1+2, i+1, i+1} - 4 I u_{i+1+2, i+1, i+1} + 12 I u_{i+1+2, i+1, i} - (4+4I) u_{i+1+2, i+1, i+1} - 4 I u_{i+1+2, i+1, i+1} - (2+2I) u_{i+1+2, i+1, i+1} + (6+6I) u_{i+1+2, i+1, i} - 4 u_{i+1+2, i+1, i+1} + 12 I u_{i+1+2, i, i+1} + (6+6I) u_{i+1+2, i, i+1} - (18+18I) u_{i+1+2, i, i} + 12 u_{i+1+2, i, i+1} - (4+4I) u_{i+1+2, i+1, i+1} - 4 u_{i+1+2, i+1, i+1} + 12 u_{i+1+2, i+1, i} + (-4+4I) u_{i+1+2, i+1, i+1} - 2 I u_{i+2+2, i+1, i+1} - (1+I) u_{i+2+2, i+1, i+1} + (3+3I) u_{i+2+2, i+1, i} - 2 u_{i+2+2, i+1, i+1} - (1+I) u_{i+2+2, i+1, i+1} - u_{i+2+2, i+1, i+1} + 3 u_{i+2+2, i+1, i+1} + (-1+I) u_{i+2+2, i+1, i+1} + (3+3I) u_{i+2+2, i, i+1} + 3 u_{i+2+2, i, i+1} - 9 u_{i+2+2, i, i} + (3-3I) u_{i+2+2, i, i+1} - 2 u_{i+2+2, i+1, i+1} + (-1+I) u_{i+2+2, i+1, i+1} + (3-3I) u_{i+2+2, i+1, i} + 2 I u_{i+2+2, i+1, i+1} + (-12+12I) u_{i+1, i+1, i+1} + 12 I u_{i+1, i+1, i+1} - 36 I u_{i+1, i+1, i} + (12+12I) u_{i+1, i+1, i+1} + 12 I u_{i+1, i+1, i+1} + (6+6I) u_{i+1, i+1, i+1} - (18+18I) u_{i+1, i+1, i} + 12 u_{i+1, i+1, i+1} - 36 I u_{i+1, i, i+1} - (18+18I) u_{i+1, i, i+1} + (54+54I) u_{i+1, i, i} - 36 u_{i+1, i, i} + (12+12I) u_{i+1, i, i+1} + 12 u_{i+1, i, i+1} - 36 u_{i+1, i, i} + (12-12I) u_{i+1, i+1, i+1} + 4 I u_{i+1+1, i+1, i+1} + (2+2I) u_{i+1+1, i+1, i+1} - (6+6I) u_{i+1+1, i+1, i+1} + 4 u_{i+1+1, i+1, i+1} + (2+2I) u_{i+1+1, i+1, i+1} + 2 u_{i+1+1, i+1, i+1} - 6 u_{i+1+1, i+1, i+1} + (2-2I) u_{i+1+1, i+1, i+1} - (6+6I) u_{i+1+1, i, i+1} - 6 u_{i+1+1, i, i+1} + 18 u_{i+1+1, i, i} + (-6+6I) u_{i+1+1, i, i+1} + 4 u_{i+1+1, i, i+1} + (2-2I) u_{i+1+1, i, i+1} + (-6+6I) u_{i+1+1, i, i} - 4 I u_{i+2+1, i+1, i+1} - (4+4I) u_{i+2+1, i+1, i+1} - 4 u_{i+2+1, i+1, i+1} + 12 u_{i+2+1, i+1, i} + (-4+4I) u_{i+2+1, i+1, i+1} - 4 u_{i+2+1, i+1, i+1} + (-2+2I) u_{i+2+1, i+1, i+1} + (6-6I) u_{i+2+1, i+1, i+1} + 4 I u_{i+2+1, i+1, i+1} + 12 u_{i+2+1, i+1, i} + (6-6I) u_{i+2+1, i+1, i+1} + (-18+18I) u_{i+2+1, i+1, i} - 12 I u_{i+2+1, i+1, i+1} + (-4+4I) u_{i+2+1, i+1, i+1} + 4 I u_{i+2+1, i+1, i+1} - 12 I u_{i+2+1, i+1, i} + (4+4I) u_{i+2+1, i+1, i+1} - 18 I u_{i+2+1, i+1, i} - (9+9I) u_{i+2+1, i+1, i} + (27+27I) u_{i+2+1, i} - 18 u_{i+2+1, i+1, i} - (9+9I) u_{i+2+1, i+1, i} - 9 u_{i+2+1, i+1, i+1} + 27 u_{i+2+1, i+1, i} + (-9+9I) u_{i+2+1, i+1, i} + (27+27I) u_{i+2+1, i} + 27 u_{i+2+1, i} - 81 u_{i+2, i, i} + (27-27I) u_{i+2, i, i+1} - 18 u_{i+2, i, i+1} + (-9+9I) u_{i+2, i, i+1} + (27-27I) u_{i+2, i, i} + 18 I u_{i+2, i, i+1} + (12+12I) u_{i+1, i+1, i+1} + 12 u_{i+1, i+1, i+1} - 36 u_{i+1, i+1, i} + (12-12I) u_{i+1, i+1, i+1} + 12 u_{i+1, i+1, i+1} + (6-6I) u_{i+1, i+1, i+1} + (-18+18I) u_{i+1, i+1, i} - 12 I u_{i+1, i+1, i+1} - 36 u_{i+1, i, i+1} + (-18+18I) u_{i+1, i, i+1} + (54-54I) u_{i+1, i, i} + 36 I u_{i+1, i, i} + (12-12I) u_{i+1, i, i+1} - 12 I u_{i+1, i+1, i+1} + 36 I u_{i+1, i+1, i} - (12+12I) u_{i+1, i+1, i} - 4 u_{i+2, i+1, i+1} + (-2+2I) u_{i+2, i+1, i+1} + (6-6I) u_{i+2, i+1, i+1} + 4 I u_{i+2, i+1, i+1} + (-2+2I) u_{i+2, i+1, i+1} + 2 I u_{i+2, i+1, i+1} - 6 I u_{i+2, i+1, i+1} + (2+2I) u_{i+2, i+1, i+1} + (-6I) u_{i+2, i, i+1} - 6 I u_{i+2, i, i+1} + 18 I u_{i+2, i, i} - (6+6I) u_{i+2, i, i+1} + 4 I u_{i+2, i, i+1} + (2+2I) u_{i+2, i, i+1} - (6+6I) u_{i+2, i, i} + 4 u_{i+2, i, i+1}), $O(\Delta x1^3 \Delta x2^3 \Delta x3^3)$, *Quadrant I*

Error order: 3, Error: 1.8314221321671523686 × 10⁻⁷, New Error: 1.8282274128113360644 × 10⁻¹⁶
Error order: 3, Error: 1.8282274128113360644 × 10⁻¹⁶, New Error: 1.8282242208802196106 × 10⁻²⁵
Error order: 3, Error: 1.8282242208802196106 × 10⁻²⁵, New Error: 1.8282242176882912833 × 10⁻³⁴
Error order: 3, Error: 1.8282242176882912833 × 10⁻³⁴, New Error: 1.8282242176850993550 × 10⁻⁴³
Error order: 3, Error: 1.8282242176850993550 × 10⁻⁴³, New Error: 1.8282242176850961631 × 10⁻⁵²$$

$$\frac{\partial^4}{\partial x1 \partial x2 \partial x3 \partial x4} u(x1, x2, x3, x4) = \frac{1}{4 \Delta x1 \Delta x2 \Delta x3 \Delta x4} (4 u_{i+1, i+1, i+1, i+1} + (2-2I) u_{i+1, i+1, i+1, i+1} + (-6+6I) u_{i+1, i+1, i+1, i} - 4 I u_{i+1, i+1, i+1, i+1} + (2-2I) u_{i+1, i+1, i+1, i+1} - 2 I u_{i+1, i+1, i+1, i+1} + 6 I u_{i+1, i+1, i+1, i} - (2+2I) u_{i+1, i+1, i+1, i+1} + (-6+6I) u_{i+1, i+1, i, i+1} + 6 I u_{i+1, i+1, i, i+1} - 18 I u_{i+1, i+1, i, i} + (6+6I) u_{i+1, i+1, i, i} - 4 I u_{i+1, i+1, i, i+1} - (2+2I) u_{i+1, i+1, i+1, i+1} + (6+6I) u_{i+1, i+1, i+1, i} - 4 u_{i+1, i+1, i+1, i+1} + (2-2I) u_{i+1, i+1, i+1, i} - 2 I u_{i+1, i+1, i+1, i+1} + 6 I u_{i+1, i+1, i+1, i} - (2+2I) u_{i+1, i+1, i+1, i+1} + (-6+6I) u_{i+1, i+1, i+1, i} - 2 u_{i+1, i+1, i+1, i+1} - (1+I) u_{i+1, i+1, i+1, i+1} + (3+3I) u_{i+1, i+1, i+1, i} - 2 u_{i+1, i+1, i+1, i+1} + 6 I u_{i+1, i+1, i+1, i} - (2+2I) u_{i+1, i+1, i+1, i+1} + 6 I u_{i+1, i+1, i, i+1} + (3+3I) u_{i+1, i+1, i, i+1} - (9+9I) u_{i+1, i+1, i, i+1} + 6 u_{i+1, i+1, i, i+1} - (2+2I) u_{i+1, i+1, i+1, i+1} - 2 u_{i+1, i+1, i+1, i+1} + 6 u_{i+1, i+1, i+1, i} + (-2+2I) u_{i+1, i+1, i+1, i+1} + (-6+6I) u_{i+1, i+1, i+1, i+1} + 6 I u_{i+1, i+1, i+1, i+1} - 18 I u_{i+1, i+1, i+1, i+1} + (6+6I) u_{i+1, i+1, i+1, i+1} + 6 I u_{i+1, i+1, i+1, i+1} + (3+3I) u_{i+1, i+1, i+1, i+1} - (9+9I) u_{i+1, i+1, i+1, i+1} + 6 u_{i+1, i+1, i+1, i+1} - 18 I u_{i+1, i+1, i+1, i+1} - (9+9I) u_{i+1, i+1, i+1, i+1} + (27+27I) u_{i+1, i+1, i+1, i} - 18 u_{i+1, i+1, i+1, i+1} + (6+6I) u_{i+1, i+1, i+1, i+1} + 6 u_{i+1, i+1, i+1, i+1} - 18 u_{i+1, i+1, i+1, i+1} + (6-6I) u_{i+1, i+1, i+1, i+1} - 4 I u_{i+1+1, i+1, i+1, i+1} - (2+2I) u_{i+1+1, i+1, i+1, i+1} + (6+6I) u_{i+1+1, i+1, i+1, i+1} - 4 u_{i+1+1, i+1, i+1, i+1} - (2+2I) u_{i+1+1, i+1, i+1, i+1} + 2 u_{i+1+1, i+1, i+1, i+1} - 6 u_{i+1+1, i+1, i+1, i+1} + (2-2I) u_{i+1+1, i+1, i+1, i+1} - 6 u_{i+1+1, i+1, i+1, i+1} + 18 u_{i+1+1, i+1, i+1, i+1} + (-2+2I) u_{i+1+1, i+1, i+1, i+1} + (-6+6I) u_{i+1+1, i+1, i+1, i+1} + 4 u_{i+1+1, i+1, i+1, i+1} + (2-2I) u_{i+1+1, i+1, i+1, i+1} + (-6+6I) u_{i+1+1, i+1, i+1, i+1} - 4 I u_{i+1+1, i+1, i+1, i+1} - (4+4I) u_{i+1+1, i+1, i+1, i+1} - 4 u_{i+1+1, i+1, i+1, i+1} + 12 u_{i+1+1, i+1, i+1, i+1} + (-4+4I) u_{i+1+1, i+1, i+1, i+1} - 4 u_{i+1+1, i+1, i+1, i+1} + (-2+2I) u_{i+1+1, i+1, i+1, i+1} + (6-6I) u_{i+1+1, i+1, i+1, i+1} + 4 I u_{i+1+1, i+1, i+1, i+1} + 12 u_{i+1+1, i+1, i+1, i+1} + (6-6I) u_{i+1+1, i+1, i+1, i+1} + (-18+18I) u_{i+1+1, i+1, i+1, i+1} - 12 I u_{i+1+1, i+1, i+1, i+1} + (-4+4I) u_{i+1+1, i+1, i+1, i+1} + 4 I u_{i+1+1, i+1, i+1, i+1} - 12 I u_{i+1+1, i+1, i+1, i+1} + (4+4I) u_{i+1+1, i+1, i+1, i+1} - 18 I u_{i+1+1, i+1, i+1, i+1} - (9+9I) u_{i+1+1, i+1, i+1, i+1} + (27+27I) u_{i+1+1, i+1, i+1, i+1} + 27 u_{i+1+1, i+1, i+1, i+1} - 81 u_{i+1+1, i+1, i+1, i+1} + (27-27I) u_{i+1+1, i+1, i+1, i+1} - 18 u_{i+1+1, i+1, i+1, i+1} + (-9+9I) u_{i+1+1, i+1, i+1, i+1} + (27-27I) u_{i+1+1, i+1, i+1, i+1} + 18 I u_{i+1+1, i+1, i+1, i+1} + (12+12I) u_{i+1+1, i+1, i+1, i+1} + 12 u_{i+1+1, i+1, i+1, i+1} - 36 u_{i+1+1, i+1, i+1, i+1} + (12-12I) u_{i+1+1, i+1, i+1, i+1} + 12 u_{i+1+1, i+1, i+1, i+1} + (6-6I) u_{i+1+1, i+1, i+1, i+1} + (-18+18I) u_{i+1+1, i+1, i+1, i+1} - 12 I u_{i+1+1, i+1, i+1, i+1} - 36 u_{i+1+1, i+1, i+1, i+1} + (-18+18I) u_{i+1+1, i+1, i+1, i+1} + (54-54I) u_{i+1+1, i+1, i+1, i+1} + 36 I u_{i+1+1, i+1, i+1, i+1} + (12-12I) u_{i+1+1, i+1, i+1, i+1} - 12 I u_{i+1+1, i+1, i+1, i+1} + 36 I u_{i+1+1, i+1, i+1, i+1} - (12+12I) u_{i+1+1, i+1, i+1, i+1} - 4 u_{i+2, i+1, i+1, i+1} + (-2+2I) u_{i+2, i+1, i+1, i+1} + (6-6I) u_{i+2, i+1, i+1, i+1} + 4 I u_{i+2, i+1, i+1, i+1} + (-2+2I) u_{i+2, i+1, i+1, i+1} + 2 I u_{i+2, i+1, i+1, i+1} - 6 I u_{i+2, i+1, i+1, i+1} + (2+2I) u_{i+2, i+1, i+1, i+1} + (-6I) u_{i+2, i+1, i+1, i+1} - 6 I u_{i+2, i+1, i+1, i+1} + 18 I u_{i+2, i+1, i+1, i+1} - (6+6I) u_{i+2, i+1, i+1, i+1} + 4 I u_{i+2, i+1, i+1, i+1} + (2+2I) u_{i+2, i+1, i+1, i+1} - (6+6I) u_{i+2, i+1, i+1, i+1} + 4 u_{i+2, i+1, i+1, i+1}), $O(\Delta x1^3 \Delta x2^3 \Delta x3^3 \Delta x4^3)$, *Quadrant I*

Error order: 3, Error: 1.4175435571476271769 × 10⁻⁶, New Error: 1.4140562440428662818 × 10⁻¹⁵
Error order: 3, Error: 1.4140562440428662818 × 10⁻¹⁵, New Error: 1.4140527610203668904 × 10⁻²⁴
Error order: 3, Error: 1.4140527610203668904 × 10⁻²⁴, New Error: 1.4140527575373486849 × 10⁻³³
Error order: 3, Error: 1.4140527575373486849 × 10⁻³³, New Error: 1.4140527575338656667 × 10⁻⁴²
Error order: 3, Error: 1.4140527575338656667 × 10⁻⁴², New Error: 1.4140527575338621837 × 10⁻⁵¹$$

$$\frac{d^5}{dx^5} u(x1) = \frac{1}{8 \Delta x1^5} (8 u_{i+5, i} + (20-20I) u_{i+1+5, i} - 40 I u_{i+2+5, i} - (20+20I) u_{i+3+5, i} - 10 u_{i+4+5, i} + (-1+I) u_{i+5+5, i} + (-60+60I) u_{i+4+1} + 200 I u_{i+1+4+1} + (100+100I) u_{i+2+4+1} + (-25+25I) u_{i+4+4+1} + 10 I u_{i+5+4+1} - 360 I u_{i+3+1} - (300+300I) u_{i+1+3+1} + 100 u_{i+2+3+1} + (150-150I) u_{i+3+3+1} + (20+20I) u_{i+5+3+1} + (540+540I) u_{i+2+1} + (-450+450I) u_{i+2+2+1} - 100 I u_{i+3+2+1} - (100+100I) u_{i+4+2+1} + 40 u_{i+5+2+1} - 810 u_{i+1+1} + (675-675I) u_{i+1+1+1} + (300+300I) u_{i+3+1} - 200 u_{i+4+1} + (20-20I) u_{i+5+1} + (243-243I) u_{i+1} + 810 I u_{i+1} - (540+540I) u_{i+2} + 360 u_{i+3} + (-60+60I) u_{i+4} - 8 I u_{i+5}), $O(\Delta x1^3)$, *Quadrant I*

Error order: 3, Error: 6.2359838391318421882 × 10⁻⁹, New Error: 6.2310119757313899718 × 10⁻¹⁸
Error order: 3, Error: 6.2310119757313899718 × 10⁻¹⁸, New Error: 6.2310070058483709749 × 10⁻²⁷$$

Error order.: 3, *Error.*: 6.2310070058483709749 × 10⁻²⁷, *New Error.*: 6.2310070008784899398 × 10⁻³⁶
Error order.: 3, *Error.*: 6.2310070008784899398 × 10⁻³⁶, *New Error.*: 6.2310070008735200588 × 10⁻⁴⁵
Error order.: 3, *Error.*: 6.2310070008735200588 × 10⁻⁴⁵, *New Error.*: 6.2310070008735150889 × 10⁻⁵⁴

$$\frac{d^6}{dxI^6} u(xI) = \frac{1}{8 \Delta x I^6} (8 u_{il+61} + (24 - 24 I) u_{il+1+61} - 60 I u_{il+2+61} - (40 + 40 I) u_{il+3+61} - 30 u_{il+4+61} + (-6 + 6 I) u_{il+5+61} + I u_{il+6+61} + (-72 + 72 I) u_{il+51} + 312 I u_{il+1+51} + (240 + 240 I) u_{il+2+51} + 120 u_{il+3+51} + (-30 + 30 I) u_{il+4+51} + 42 I u_{il+5+51} + (6 + 6 I) u_{il+6+51} - 540 I u_{il+41} - (720 + 720 I) u_{il+1+41} - 300 u_{il+2+41} + (300 - 300 I) u_{il+3+41} - 225 I u_{il+4+41} + (30 + 30 I) u_{il+5+41} + 30 u_{il+6+41} + (1080 + 1080 I) u_{il+31} + 1080 u_{il+1+31} + (-900 + 900 I) u_{il+2+31} + 700 I u_{il+3+31} - (300 + 300 I) u_{il+4+31} - 120 u_{il+5+31} + (40 - 40 I) u_{il+6+31} - 2430 u_{il+21} + (810 - 810 I) u_{il+1+21} - 2025 I u_{il+2+21} + (900 + 900 I) u_{il+3+21} + 300 u_{il+4+21} + (-240 + 240 I) u_{il+5+21} - 60 I u_{il+6+21} + (1458 - 1458 I) u_{il+1} + 3402 I u_{il+1+1} - (810 + 810 I) u_{il+2+1} - 1080 u_{il+3+1} + (720 - 720 I) u_{il+4+1} + 312 I u_{il+5+1} - (24 + 24 I) u_{il+6+1} + 729 I u_{il} - (1458 + 1458 I) u_{il+1} + 2430 u_{il+2} + (-1080 + 1080 I) u_{il+3} - 540 I u_{il+4} + (72 + 72 I) u_{il+5} - 8 u_{il+6}), O(\Delta x I^3), \textit{ Quadrant I}$$

Error order.: 3, *Error.*: 7.4682441174815237047 × 10⁻⁹, *New Error.*: 7.4622897912950778092 × 10⁻¹⁸
Error order.: 3, *Error.*: 7.4622897912950778092 × 10⁻¹⁸, *New Error.*: 7.4622838393393664370 × 10⁻²⁷
Error order.: 3, *Error.*: 7.4622838393393664370 × 10⁻²⁷, *New Error.*: 7.462283833874131016 × 10⁻³⁶
Error order.: 3, *Error.*: 7.462283833874131016 × 10⁻³⁶, *New Error.*: 7.462283833814611483 × 10⁻⁴⁵
Error order.: 3, *Error.*: 7.462283833814611483 × 10⁻⁴⁵, *New Error.*: 7.462283833814551963 × 10⁻⁵⁴

$$\frac{d^7}{dxI^7} u(xI) = \frac{1}{16 \Delta x I^7} (16 u_{il+71} + (56 - 56 I) u_{il+1+71} - 168 I u_{il+2+71} - (140 + 140 I) u_{il+3+71} - 140 u_{il+4+71} + (-42 + 42 I) u_{il+5+71} + 14 I u_{il+6+71} + (1 + I) u_{il+7+71} + (-168 + 168 I) u_{il+61} + 896 I u_{il+1+61} + (924 + 924 I) u_{il+2+61} + 840 u_{il+3+61} + (70 - 70 I) u_{il+4+61} + 168 I u_{il+5+61} + (63 + 63 I) u_{il+6+61} + 14 u_{il+7+61} - 1512 I u_{il+51} - (2772 + 2772 I) u_{il+1+51} - 2856 u_{il+2+51} + (420 - 420 I) u_{il+3+51} - 1470 I u_{il+4+51} - (231 + 231 I) u_{il+5+51} + 168 u_{il+6+51} + (42 - 42 I) u_{il+7+51} + (3780 + 3780 I) u_{il+41} + 7560 u_{il+1+41} + (-1260 + 1260 I) u_{il+2+41} + 5600 I u_{il+3+41} + (175 + 175 I) u_{il+4+41} - 1470 u_{il+5+41} + (-70 + 70 I) u_{il+6+41} - 140 I u_{il+7+41} - 11340 u_{il+31} + (-1890 + 1890 I) u_{il+1+31} - 13230 I u_{il+2+31} - (525 + 525 I) u_{il+3+31} + 5600 u_{il+4+31} + (-420 + 420 I) u_{il+5+31} + 840 I u_{il+6+31} - (140 + 140 I) u_{il+7+31} + (10206 - 10206 I) u_{il+21} + 13608 I u_{il+1+21} + (6237 + 6237 I) u_{il+2+21} - 13230 u_{il+3+21} + (1260 - 1260 I) u_{il+4+21} - 2856 I u_{il+5+21} + (924 + 924 I) u_{il+6+21} - 168 u_{il+7+21} + 10206 I u_{il+1} - (15309 + 15309 I) u_{il+1+1} + 13608 u_{il+2+1} + (1890 - 1890 I) u_{il+3+1} + 7560 I u_{il+4+1} - (2772 + 2772 I) u_{il+5+1} + 896 u_{il+6+1} + (-56 + 56 I) u_{il+7+1} - (2187 + 2187 I) u_{il} + 10206 u_{il+1} + (-10206 + 10206 I) u_{il+2} - 11340 I u_{il+3} + (3780 + 3780 I) u_{il+4} - 1512 u_{il+5} + (168 - 168 I) u_{il+6} + 16 I u_{il+7}), O(\Delta x I^3), \textit{ Quadrant I}$$

Error order.: 3, *Error.*: 8.6955603482528190707 × 10⁻⁹, *New Error.*: 8.6886275015079082928 × 10⁻¹⁸
Error order.: 3, *Error.*: 8.6886275015079082928 × 10⁻¹⁸, *New Error.*: 8.6886205714197546671 × 10⁻²⁷
Error order.: 3, *Error.*: 8.6886205714197546671 × 10⁻²⁷, *New Error.*: 8.6886205644896692800 × 10⁻³⁶
Error order.: 3, *Error.*: 8.6886205644896692800 × 10⁻³⁶, *New Error.*: 8.6886205644827391946 × 10⁻⁴⁵
Error order.: 3, *Error.*: 8.6886205644827391946 × 10⁻⁴⁵, *New Error.*: 8.6886205644827322645 × 10⁻⁵⁴

$$\frac{d^8}{dxI^8} u(xI) = \frac{1}{16 \Delta x I^8} (16 u_{il+81} + (64 - 64 I) u_{il+1+81} - 224 I u_{il+2+81} - (224 + 224 I) u_{il+3+81} - 280 u_{il+4+81} + (-112 + 112 I) u_{il+5+81} + 56 I u_{il+6+81} + (8 + 8 I) u_{il+7+81} + u_{il+8+81} + (-192 + 192 I) u_{il+71} + 1216 I u_{il+1+71} + (1568 + 1568 I) u_{il+2+71} + 2016 u_{il+3+71} + (560 - 560 I) u_{il+4+71} + 112 I u_{il+5+71} + (168 + 168 I) u_{il+6+71} + 88 u_{il+7+71} + (8 - 8 I) u_{il+8+71} - 2016 I u_{il+61} - (4704 + 4704 I) u_{il+1+61} - 7504 u_{il+2+61} + (-1344 + 1344 I) u_{il+3+61} - 2520 I u_{il+4+61} - (1288 + 1288 I) u_{il+5+61} - 84 u_{il+6+61} + (168 - 168 I) u_{il+7+61} - 56 I u_{il+8+61} + (6048 + 6048 I) u_{il+51} + 18144 u_{il+1+51} + (4032 - 4032 I) u_{il+2+51} + 10976 I u_{il+3+51} + (4760 + 4760 I) u_{il+4+51} - 2072 u_{il+5+51} + (-1288 + 1288 I) u_{il+6+51} - 112 I u_{il+7+51} - (112 + 112 I) u_{il+8+51} - 22680 u_{il+41} + (-15120 + 15120 I) u_{il+1+41} - 22680 I u_{il+2+41} - (14280 + 14280 I) u_{il+3+41} + 10150 u_{il+4+41} + (4760 - 4760 I) u_{il+5+41} + 2520 I u_{il+6+41} + (560 + 560 I) u_{il+7+41} - 280 u_{il+8+41} + (27216 - 27216 I) u_{il+31} + 9072 I u_{il+1+31} + (34776 + 34776 I) u_{il+2+31} - 18648 u_{il+3+31} + (-14280 + 14280 I) u_{il+4+31} - 10976 I u_{il+5+31} - (1344 + 1344 I) u_{il+6+31} + 2016 u_{il+7+31} + (-224 + 224 I) u_{il+8+31} + 40824 I u_{il+21} - (40824 + 40824 I) u_{il+1+21} - 6804 u_{il+2+21} + (34776 - 34776 I) u_{il+3+21} + 22680 I u_{il+4+21} + (4032 + 4032 I) u_{il+5+21} - 7504 u_{il+6+21} + (1568 - 1568 I) u_{il+7+21} + 224 I u_{il+8+21} - (17496 + 17496 I) u_{il+1} + 64152 u_{il+1+1} + (-40824 + 40824 I) u_{il+2+1} - 9072 I u_{il+3+1} - (15120 + 15120 I) u_{il+4+1} + 18144 u_{il+5+1} + (-4704 + 4704 I) u_{il+6+1} - 1216 I u_{il+7+1} + (64 + 64 I) u_{il+8+1} + 6561 u_{il} + (-17496 + 17496 I) u_{il+1} - 40824 I u_{il+2} + (27216 + 27216 I) u_{il+3} - 22680 u_{il+4} + (6048 - 6048 I) u_{il+5} + 2016 I u_{il+6} - (192 + 192 I) u_{il+7} + 16 u_{il+8}), O(\Delta x I^3), \textit{ Quadrant I}$$

Error order.: 3, *Error.*: 9.9179473587794908377 × 10⁻⁹, *New Error.*: 9.9100399218795646322 × 10⁻¹⁸
Error order.: 3, *Error.*: 9.9100399218795646322 × 10⁻¹⁸, *New Error.*: 9.9100320175874019585 × 10⁻²⁷
Error order.: 3, *Error.*: 9.9100320175874019585 × 10⁻²⁷, *New Error.*: 9.9100320096831129512 × 10⁻³⁶
Error order.: 3, *Error.*: 9.9100320096831129512 × 10⁻³⁶, *New Error.*: 9.9100320096752086622 × 10⁻⁴⁵
Error order.: 3, *Error.*: 9.9100320096752086622 × 10⁻⁴⁵, *New Error.*: 9.9100320096752007579 × 10⁻⁵⁴

$$\frac{d^9}{dxI^9} u(xI) = \frac{1}{32 \Delta x I^9} (32 u_{il+91} + (144 - 144 I) u_{il+1+91} - 576 I u_{il+2+91} - (672 + 672 I) u_{il+3+91} - 1008 u_{il+4+91} + (-504 + 504 I) u_{il+5+91} + 336 I u_{il+6+91} + (72 + 72 I) u_{il+7+91} + 18 u_{il+8+91} + (1 - I) u_{il+9+91} + (-432 + 432 I) u_{il+81} + 3168 I u_{il+1+81} + (4896 + 4896 I) u_{il+2+81} + 8064 u_{il+3+81} + (3528 - 3528 I) u_{il+4+81} - 1008 I u_{il+5+81} + (504 + 504 I) u_{il+6+81} + 576 u_{il+7+81} + (117 - 117 I) u_{il+8+81} - 18 I u_{il+9+81} - 5184 I u_{il+71} - (14688 + 14688 I) u_{il+1+71} - 31392 u_{il+2+71} + (-13104 + 13104 I) u_{il+3+71} - 3024 I u_{il+4+71} - (6552 + 6552 I) u_{il+5+71} - 3528 u_{il+6+71} + (324 - 324 I) u_{il+7+71} - 576 I u_{il+8+71} - (72 + 72 I) u_{il+9+71} + (18144 + 18144 I) u_{il+61} + 72576 u_{il+1+61} + (39312 - 39312 I) u_{il+2+61} + 20832 I u_{il+3+61} + (30744 + 30744 I) u_{il+4+61} + 8064 u_{il+5+61} + (-6972 + 6972 I) u_{il+6+61} + 3528 I u_{il+7+61} - (504 + 504 I) u_{il+8+61} - 336 u_{il+9+61} - 81648 u_{il+51} + (-95256 + 95256 I) u_{il+1+51} - 27216 I u_{il+2+51} - (92232 + 92232 I) u_{il+3+51} - 14868 u_{il+4+51} + (35406 - 35406 I) u_{il+5+51} - 8064 I u_{il+6+51} + (6552 + 6552 I) u_{il+7+51} + 1008 u_{il+8+51} + (-504 + 504 I) u_{il+9+51} + (122472 - 122472 I) u_{il+41} - 81648 I u_{il+1+41} + (176904 + 176904 I) u_{il+2+41} + 72576 u_{il+3+41} + (-106218 + 106218 I) u_{il+4+41} + 14868 I u_{il+5+41} - (30744 + 30744 I) u_{il+6+41} + 3024 u_{il+7+41} + (3528 - 3528 I) u_{il+8+41} + 1008 I u_{il+9+41} + 244944 I u_{il+31} - (122472 + 122472 I) u_{il+1+31} - 285768 u_{il+2+31} + (188244 - 188244 I) u_{il+3+31} - 72576 I u_{il+4+31} + (92232 + 92232 I) u_{il+5+31} - 20832 u_{il+6+31} + (-13104 + 13104 I) u_{il+7+31} - 8064 I u_{il+8+31} + (672 + 672 I) u_{il+9+31} - (157464 + 157464 I) u_{il+21} + 419904 u_{il+1+21} + (-78732 + 78732 I) u_{il+2+21} + 285768 I u_{il+3+21} - (176904 + 176904 I) u_{il+4+21} + 27216 u_{il+5+21} + (39312 - 39312 I) u_{il+6+21} + 31392 I u_{il+7+21} - (4896 + 4896 I) u_{il+8+21} + 576 u_{il+9+21} + 118098 u_{il+1} + (-255879 + 255879 I) u_{il+1+1} - 419904 I u_{il+2+1} + (122472 + 122472 I) u_{il+3+1} + 81648 u_{il+4+1} + (-95256 + 95256 I) u_{il+5+1} - 72576 I u_{il+6+1} + (14688 + 14688 I) u_{il+7+1} - 3168 u_{il+8+1} + (144 - 144 I) u_{il+9+1} + (-19683 + 19683 I) u_{il} - 118098 I u_{il+1} + (157464 + 157464 I) u_{il+2} - 244944 u_{il+3} + (122472 - 122472 I) u_{il+4} + 81648 I u_{il+5} - (18144 + 18144 I) u_{il+6} + 5184 u_{il+7} + (-432 + 432 I) u_{il+8} - 32 I u_{il+9}), O(\Delta x I^3), \textit{ Quadrant I}$$

Error order.: 3, *Error.*: 1.1135419936901669006 × 10⁻⁸, *New Error.*: 1.1126541828457595019 × 10⁻¹⁷
Error order.: 3, *Error.*: 1.1126541828457595019 × 10⁻¹⁷, *New Error.*: 1.1126532953878071061 × 10⁻²⁶
Error order.: 3, *Error.*: 1.1126532953878071061 × 10⁻²⁶, *New Error.*: 1.1126532945003495080 × 10⁻³⁵
Error order.: 3, *Error.*: 1.1126532945003495080 × 10⁻³⁵, *New Error.*: 1.1126532944994620504 × 10⁻⁴⁴
Error order.: 3, *Error.*: 1.1126532944994620504 × 10⁻⁴⁴, *New Error.*: 1.1126532944994611629 × 10⁻⁵³

$$\frac{d^{10}}{dxI^{10}} u(xI) = \frac{1}{32 \Delta x I^{10}} (32 u_{il+101} + (160 - 160 I) u_{il+1+101} - 720 I u_{il+2+101} - (960 + 960 I) u_{il+3+101} - 1680 u_{il+4+101} + (-1008 + 1008 I) u_{il+5+101} + 840 I u_{il+6+101} + (240 + 240 I) u_{il+7+101} + 90 u_{il+8+101} + (10 - 10 I) u_{il+9+101} - I u_{il+10+101} + (-480 + 480 I) u_{il+91} + 4000 I u_{il+1+91} + (7200 + 7200 I) u_{il+2+91} + 14400 u_{il+3+91} + (8400 - 8400 I) u_{il+4+91} - 5040 I u_{il+5+91} + 1200 u_{il+7+91} + (450 - 450 I) u_{il+8+91} - 150 I u_{il+9+91} - (10 + 10 I) u_{il+10+91} - 6480 I u_{il+81} - (21600 + 21600 I) u_{il+1+81} - 57600 u_{il+2+81} + (-36000 + 36000 I) u_{il+3+81} + 12600 I u_{il+4+81} - (10080 + 10080 I) u_{il+5+81}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& + (786240 + 786240 I) u_{iI+12I} + 7862400 u_{iI+1+12I} + (17035200 - 17035200 I) u_{iI+2+12I} - 40768000 I u_{iI+3+12I} - (27409200 + 27409200 I) u_{iI+4+12I} - 14894880 u_{iI+5+12I} + (6406400 - 6406400 I) u_{iI+6+12I} - 14414400 I u_{iI+7+12I} - (4504500 + 4504500 I) u_{iI+8+12I} + 600600 u_{iI+9+12I} + (1261260 \\
& - 1261260 I) u_{iI+10+12I} - 655200 I u_{iI+11+12I} + (2275 + 2275 I) u_{iI+12+12I} + 68250 u_{iI+13+12I} + (13650 - 13650 I) u_{iI+14+12I} - 1820 I u_{iI+15+12I} - 7076160 u_{iI+11I} + (-29484000 + 29484000 I) u_{iI+1+11I} + 100245600 I u_{iI+2+11I} + (82227600 + 82227600 I) u_{iI+3+11I} + 42151200 u_{iI+4+11I} + (-36276240 \\
& + 36276240 I) u_{iI+5+11I} + 66066000 I u_{iI+6+11I} + (12612600 + 12612600 I) u_{iI+7+11I} - 15315300 u_{iI+8+11I} + (-8558550 + 8558550 I) u_{iI+9+11I} + 990990 I u_{iI+10+11I} - (1330875 + 1330875 I) u_{iI+11+11I} - 655200 u_{iI+12+11I} + (27300 - 27300 I) u_{iI+13+11I} - 54600 I u_{iI+14+11I} - (5460 + 5460 I) u_{iI+15+11I} \\
& + (23351328 - 23351328 I) u_{iI+10I} - 155675520 I u_{iI+1+10I} - (188107920 + 188107920 I) u_{iI+2+10I} - 134053920 u_{iI+3+10I} + (108828720 - 108828720 I) u_{iI+4+10I} - 223327104 I u_{iI+5+10I} - (26546520 + 26546520 I) u_{iI+6+10I} + 88648560 u_{iI+7+10I} + (33963930 - 33963930 I) u_{iI+8+10I} + 11171160 I u_{iI+9+10I} \\
& + (9972963 + 9972963 I) u_{iI+10+10I} + 990990 u_{iI+11+10I} + (-1261260 + 1261260 I) u_{iI+12+10I} + 360360 I u_{iI+13+10I} - (60060 + 60060 I) u_{iI+14+10I} - 24024 u_{iI+15+10I} + 116756640 I u_{iI+9I} + (291891600 + 291891600 I) u_{iI+1+9I} + 389188800 u_{iI+2+9I} + (-172972800 + 172972800 I) u_{iI+3+9I} \\
& + 594594000 I u_{iI+4+9I} + (79639560 + 79639560 I) u_{iI+5+9I} - 319118800 u_{iI+6+9I} + (-106306200 + 106306200 I) u_{iI+7+9I} - 84234150 I u_{iI+8+9I} - (42417375 + 42417375 I) u_{iI+9+9I} + 11171160 u_{iI+10+9I} + (8558550 - 8558550 I) u_{iI+11+9I} + 600600 I u_{iI+12+9I} + (900900 + 900900 I) u_{iI+13+9I} + (-40040 \\
& + 40040 I) u_{iI+15+9I} - (225173520 + 225173520 I) u_{iI+8I} - 750578400 u_{iI+1+8I} - 1167566400 I u_{iI+3+8I} - (340540200 + 340540200 I) u_{iI+4+8I} + 797837040 u_{iI+5+8I} + (318918600 - 318918600 I) u_{iI+6+8I} + 319176000 I u_{iI+7+8I} + (139542975 + 139542975 I) u_{iI+8+8I} - 84234150 u_{iI+9+8I} + (-33963930 \\
& + 33963930 I) u_{iI+10+8I} - 15315300 I u_{iI+11+8I} - (4504500 + 4504500 I) u_{iI+12+8I} + 1801800 u_{iI+13+8I} + (257400 - 257400 I) u_{iI+14+8I} + 102960 I u_{iI+15+8I} + 675520560 u_{iI+7I} + (562933800 - 562933800 I) u_{iI+1+7I} + 1313512200 I u_{iI+2+7I} + (1094593500 + 1094593500 I) u_{iI+3+7I} - 1240539300 u_{iI+4+7I} \\
& + (-917026110 + 917026110 I) u_{iI+5+7I} - 758107350 I u_{iI+6+7I} - (418628925 + 418628925 I) u_{iI+7+7I} + 319176000 u_{iI+8+7I} + (106306200 - 106306200 I) u_{iI+9+7I} + 88648560 I u_{iI+10+7I} + (12612600 + 12612600 I) u_{iI+11+7I} - 14414400 u_{iI+12+7I} - 1029600 I u_{iI+14+7I} + (102960 + 102960 I) u_{iI+15+7I} \\
& + (-788107320 + 788107320 I) u_{iI+6I} - (1970268300 + 1970268300 I) u_{iI+2+6I} + 437837400 u_{iI+3+6I} + (2079727650 - 2079727650 I) u_{iI+4+6I} + 904863960 I u_{iI+5+6I} + (1145269125 + 1145269125 I) u_{iI+6+6I} - 758107350 u_{iI+7+6I} + (-318918600 + 318918600 I) u_{iI+8+6I} - 319118800 I u_{iI+9+6I} \\
& - (26546520 + 26546520 I) u_{iI+10+6I} + 66066000 u_{iI+11+6I} + (-6406400 + 6406400 I) u_{iI+12+6I} + 4804800 I u_{iI+13+6I} - (1201200 + 1201200 I) u_{iI+14+6I} + 160160 u_{iI+15+6I} - 1418593176 I u_{iI+5I} + (1182160980 + 1182160980 I) u_{iI+1+5I} + 2364321960 u_{iI+2+5I} + (-2758375620 + 2758375620 I) u_{iI+3+5I} \\
& + 722431710 I u_{iI+4+5I} - (2423430009 + 2423430009 I) u_{iI+5+5I} + 904863960 u_{iI+6+5I} + (917026110 - 917026110 I) u_{iI+7+5I} + 797837040 I u_{iI+8+5I} + (79639560 + 79639560 I) u_{iI+9+5I} - 223327104 u_{iI+10+5I} + (36276240 - 36276240 I) u_{iI+11+5I} - 14894880 I u_{iI+12+5I} + (6966960 + 6966960 I) u_{iI+13+5I} \\
& - 1921920 u_{iI+14+5I} + (96096 - 96096 I) u_{iI+15+5I} + (967222620 + 967222620 I) u_{iI+4I} - 3224075400 u_{iI+1+4I} + (537345900 - 537345900 I) u_{iI+2+4I} - 4298767200 I u_{iI+3+4I} + (2910623625 + 2910623625 I) u_{iI+4+4I} + 722431710 u_{iI+5+4I} + (-2079727650 + 2079727650 I) u_{iI+6+4I} - 1240539300 I u_{iI+7+4I} \\
& - (340540200 + 340540200 I) u_{iI+8+4I} + 594594000 u_{iI+9+4I} + (-108828720 + 108828720 I) u_{iI+10+4I} + 42151200 I u_{iI+11+4I} - (27409200 + 27409200 I) u_{iI+12+4I} + 11138400 u_{iI+13+4I} + (-1092000 + 1092000 I) u_{iI+14+4I} - 87360 I u_{iI+15+4I} - 967222620 u_{iI+3I} + (2418056550 - 2418056550 I) u_{iI+1+3I} \\
& + 4030094250 I u_{iI+2+3I} - (44778825 + 44778825 I) u_{iI+3+3I} - 4298767200 u_{iI+4+3I} + (2758375620 - 2758375620 I) u_{iI+5+3I} + 437837400 I u_{iI+6+3I} + (1094593500 + 1094593500 I) u_{iI+7+3I} - 1167566400 u_{iI+8+3I} + (172972800 - 172972800 I) u_{iI+9+3I} - 134053920 I u_{iI+10+3I} + (82227600 \\
& + 82227600 I) u_{iI+11+3I} - 40768000 u_{iI+12+3I} + (5678400 - 5678400 I) u_{iI+13+3I} + 873600 I u_{iI+14+3I} - (29120 + 29120 I) u_{iI+15+3I} + (334807830 - 334807830 I) u_{iI+2I} + 2232052200 I u_{iI+1+2I} - (3069071775 + 3069071775 I) u_{iI+2+2I} + 4030094250 u_{iI+3+2I} + (-537345900 + 537345900 I) u_{iI+4+2I} \\
& + 2364321960 I u_{iI+5+2I} - (1970268300 + 1970268300 I) u_{iI+6+2I} + 1313512200 u_{iI+7+2I} + 389188800 I u_{iI+9+2I} - (188107920 + 188107920 I) u_{iI+10+2I} + 100245600 u_{iI+11+2I} + (-17035200 + 17035200 I) u_{iI+12+2I} - 3696000 I u_{iI+13+2I} + (235200 + 235200 I) u_{iI+14+2I} - 13440 u_{iI+15+2I} + 143489070 I u_{iI+1I} \\
& - (597871125 + 597871125 I) u_{iI+1+1I} + 2232052200 u_{iI+2+1I} + (-2418056550 + 2418056550 I) u_{iI+3+1I} - 3224075400 I u_{iI+4+1I} + (1182160980 + 1182160980 I) u_{iI+5+1I} + (-562933800 + 562933800 I) u_{iI+7+1I} - 750578400 I u_{iI+8+1I} + (291891600 + 291891600 I) u_{iI+9+1I} - 155675520 u_{iI+10+1I} + (29484000 \\
& - 29484000 I) u_{iI+11+1I} + 7862400 I u_{iI+12+1I} - (705600 + 705600 I) u_{iI+13+1I} + 76800 u_{iI+14+1I} + (-1920 + 1920 I) u_{iI+15+1I} - (14348907 + 14348907 I) u_{iI} + 143489070 u_{iI+1I} + (-334807830 + 334807830 I) u_{iI+2I} - 967222620 I u_{iI+3I} + (967222620 + 967222620 I) u_{iI+4I} - 1418593176 u_{iI+5I} + (788107320 \\
& - 788107320 I) u_{iI+6I} + 675520560 I u_{iI+7I} - (225173520 + 225173520 I) u_{iI+8I} + 116756640 u_{iI+9I} + (-23351328 + 23351328 I) u_{iI+10I} - 7076160 I u_{iI+11I} + (786240 + 786240 I) u_{iI+12I} - 120960 u_{iI+13I} + (5760 - 5760 I) u_{iI+14I} + 256 I u_{iI+15I}), O(\Delta x I^3), \text{ Quadrant } I
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& \text{Error order:}, 3, \text{ Error:}, 1.8337875492784186755 \times 10^{-8}, \text{ New Error:}, 1.8323254989467778192 \times 10^{-17} \\
& \text{Error order:}, 3, \text{ Error:}, 1.8323254989467778192 \times 10^{-17}, \text{ New Error:}, 1.8323240374757650946 \times 10^{-26} \\
& \text{Error order:}, 3, \text{ Error:}, 1.8323240374757650946 \times 10^{-26}, \text{ New Error:}, 1.8323240360142946653 \times 10^{-35} \\
& \text{Error order:}, 3, \text{ Error:}, 1.8323240360142946653 \times 10^{-35}, \text{ New Error:}, 1.8323240360128331948 \times 10^{-44} \\
& \text{Error order:}, 3, \text{ Error:}, 1.8323240360128331948 \times 10^{-44}, \text{ New Error:}, 1.8323240360128317334 \times 10^{-53}
\end{aligned}$$

"--- Derivative Order: 2 - x1=1 ---"

$$\begin{aligned}
& \begin{bmatrix} I & 1+I \\ 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix} \\
& \begin{bmatrix} -3+I & 2I \\ -4I & 3+I \end{bmatrix}
\end{aligned}$$

$$\frac{d^2}{dxI^2} u(xI) = \frac{(-3+I) u_{iI+1} + 2 I u_{iI+1+1} - 4 I u_{iI} + (3+I) u_{iI+1}}{\Delta x I^2}, O(\Delta x I^2), \text{ Quadrant } I$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& \text{Error order:}, 2, \text{ Error:}, 2.6665782326821353352 \times 10^{-6}, \text{ New Error:}, 2.6648064252674876795 \times 10^{-12} \\
& \text{Error order:}, 2, \text{ Error:}, 2.6648064252674876795 \times 10^{-12}, \text{ New Error:}, 2.6648046540494343737 \times 10^{-18} \\
& \text{Error order:}, 2, \text{ Error:}, 2.6648046540494343737 \times 10^{-18}, \text{ New Error:}, 2.6648046522782169096 \times 10^{-24} \\
& \text{Error order:}, 2, \text{ Error:}, 2.6648046522782169096 \times 10^{-24}, \text{ New Error:}, 2.6648046522764456921 \times 10^{-30} \\
& \text{Error order:}, 2, \text{ Error:}, 2.6648046522764456921 \times 10^{-30}, \text{ New Error:}, 2.6648046522764439209 \times 10^{-36}
\end{aligned}$$

$$\frac{d^4}{dxI^4} u(xI) = \frac{(8-6I) u_{iI+2I} - (4+12I) u_{iI+1+2I} - 4 u_{iI+2+2I} + (8+24I) u_{iI+1} - 4 u_{iI+1+1} + (-4+12I) u_{iI+2+1} - 16 u_{iI} + (8-24I) u_{iI+1} + (8+6I) u_{iI+2}}{\Delta x I^4}, O(\Delta x I^2), \text{ Quadrant } I$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& \text{Error order:}, 2, \text{ Error:}, 5.3118876689070178399 \times 10^{-6}, \text{ New Error:}, 5.3083581843647787866 \times 10^{-12} \\
& \text{Error order:}, 2, \text{ Error:}, 5.3083581843647787866 \times 10^{-12}, \text{ New Error:}, 5.3083546560560204415 \times 10^{-18} \\
& \text{Error order:}, 2, \text{ Error:}, 5.3083546560560204415 \times 10^{-18}, \text{ New Error:}, 5.3083546525277128569 \times 10^{-24} \\
& \text{Error order:}, 2, \text{ Error:}, 5.3083546525277128569 \times 10^{-24}, \text{ New Error:}, 5.3083546525241845493 \times 10^{-30} \\
& \text{Error order:}, 2, \text{ Error:}, 5.3083546525241845493 \times 10^{-30}, \text{ New Error:}, 5.3083546525241810210 \times 10^{-36}
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& \frac{\partial^4}{\partial x I^2 \partial x 2^2} u(xI, x2) \\
& = \frac{1}{\Delta x I^2 \Delta x 2^2} ((8-6I) u_{iI+1,i2+1} - (2+6I) u_{iI+1,i2+1+1} + (4+12I) u_{iI+1,i2} - 10 u_{iI+1,i2+1} - (2+6I) u_{iI+1+1,i2+1} - 4 u_{iI+1+1,i2+1+1} + 8 u_{iI+1+1,i2} + (-2+6I) u_{iI+1+1,i2+1} + (4+12I) u_{iI,i2+1} + 8 u_{iI,i2+1+1} - 16 u_{iI,i2} + (4-12I) u_{iI,i2+1} - 10 u_{iI+1,i2+1} + (-2+6I) u_{iI+1,i2+1+1} + (4-12I) u_{iI+1,i2} + (8 \\
& + 6I) u_{iI+1,i2+1}), O(\Delta x I^2 \Delta x 2^2), \text{ Quadrant } I
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& \text{Error order:}, 2, \text{ Error:}, 0.000022979066725567174980, \text{ New Error:}, 2.2958534446184753389 \times 10^{-11} \\
& \text{Error order:}, 2, \text{ Error:}, 2.2958534446184753389 \times 10^{-11}, \text{ New Error:}, 2.2958513923102465716 \times 10^{-17} \\
& \text{Error order:}, 2, \text{ Error:}, 2.2958513923102465716 \times 10^{-17}, \text{ New Error:}, 2.2958513902579392611 \times 10^{-23} \\
& \text{Error order:}, 2, \text{ Error:}, 2.2958513902579392611 \times 10^{-23}, \text{ New Error:}, 2.2958513902558869538 \times 10^{-29} \\
& \text{Error order:}, 2, \text{ Error:}, 2.2958513902558869538 \times 10^{-29}, \text{ New Error:}, 2.2958513902558849015 \times 10^{-35}
\end{aligned}$$

$$\frac{d^6}{dxI^6} u(xI) = \frac{1}{\Delta x I^6} \left((-18 + 26 I) u_{iI+3I} + (36 + 48 I) u_{iI+1+3I} + (36 - 12 I) u_{iI+2+3I} - 8 I u_{iI+3+3I} - (72 + 96 I) u_{iI+2I} + (-54 + 18 I) u_{iI+1+2I} - 72 I u_{iI+2+2I} - (36 + 12 I) u_{iI+3+2I} + (144 - 48 I) u_{iI+1} + 144 I u_{iI+1+1} + (54 + 18 I) u_{iI+2+1} + (-36 + 48 I) u_{iI+3+1} + 64 I u_{iI} - (144 + 48 I) u_{iI+1} + (72 - 96 I) u_{iI+2} + (18 + 26 I) u_{iI+3} \right), O(\Delta x I^2), \text{ Quadrant } I$$

Error order:, 2, *Error:*, 7.9360555396222135969 $\times 10^{-6}$, *New Error:*, 7.9307824237225829603 $\times 10^{-12}$
Error order:, 2, *Error:*, 7.9307824237225829603 $\times 10^{-12}$, *New Error:*, 7.9307771523659573690 $\times 10^{-18}$
Error order:, 2, *Error:*, 7.9307771523659573690 $\times 10^{-18}$, *New Error:*, 7.9307771470946024970 $\times 10^{-24}$
Error order:, 2, *Error:*, 7.9307771470946024970 $\times 10^{-24}$, *New Error:*, 7.9307771470893311421 $\times 10^{-30}$
Error order:, 2, *Error:*, 7.9307771470893311421 $\times 10^{-30}$, *New Error:*, 7.9307771470893258708 $\times 10^{-36}$

$$\frac{\partial^6}{\partial x I^4 \partial x^2} u(xI, x2) = \frac{1}{\Delta x I^4 \Delta x^2} \left((-18 + 26 I) u_{iI+2I, i2+1} + (12 + 16 I) u_{iI+2I, i2+1+1} - (24 + 32 I) u_{iI+2I, i2} + (30 - 10 I) u_{iI+2I, i2+1} + (24 + 32 I) u_{iI+1+2I, i2+1} + (24 - 8 I) u_{iI+1+2I, i2+1+1} + (-48 + 16 I) u_{iI+1+2I, i2} - 40 I u_{iI+1+2I, i2+1} + (12 - 4 I) u_{iI+2+2I, i2+1} - 8 I u_{iI+2+2I, i2+1+1} + 16 I u_{iI+2+2I, i2} - (12 + 4 I) u_{iI+2+2I, i2+1} - (48 + 64 I) u_{iI+1, i2+1} + (-48 + 16 I) u_{iI+1, i2+1+1} + (96 - 32 I) u_{iI+1, i2} + 80 I u_{iI+1, i2+1} + (12 - 4 I) u_{iI+1+1, i2+1} - 8 I u_{iI+1+1, i2+1+1} + 16 I u_{iI+1+1, i2} - (12 + 4 I) u_{iI+1+1, i2+1} - 40 I u_{iI+2+1, i2+1} - (24 + 8 I) u_{iI+2+1, i2+1+1} + (48 + 16 I) u_{iI+2+1, i2} + (-24 + 32 I) u_{iI+2+1, i2+1} + (48 - 16 I) u_{iI, i2+1} - 32 I u_{iI, i2+1+1} + 64 I u_{iI, i2} - (48 + 16 I) u_{iI, i2+1} + 80 I u_{iI+1, i2+1} + (48 + 16 I) u_{iI+1, i2+1+1} - (96 + 32 I) u_{iI+1, i2} + (48 - 64 I) u_{iI+1, i2+1} - (30 + 10 I) u_{iI+2, i2+1} + (-12 + 16 I) u_{iI+2, i2+1+1} + (24 - 32 I) u_{iI+2, i2} + (18 + 26 I) u_{iI+2, i2+1} \right), O(\Delta x I^2 \Delta x^2), \text{ Quadrant } I$$

Error order:, 2, *Error:*, 0.000029937822274951658152, *New Error:*, 2.9912687368746838096 $\times 10^{-11}$
Error order:, 2, *Error:*, 2.9912687368746838096 $\times 10^{-11}$, *New Error:*, 2.9912662244434726643 $\times 10^{-17}$
Error order:, 2, *Error:*, 2.9912662244434726643 $\times 10^{-17}$, *New Error:*, 2.9912662219310425094 $\times 10^{-23}$
Error order:, 2, *Error:*, 2.9912662219310425094 $\times 10^{-23}$, *New Error:*, 2.9912662219285300792 $\times 10^{-29}$
Error order:, 2, *Error:*, 2.9912662219285300792 $\times 10^{-29}$, *New Error:*, 2.9912662219285275668 $\times 10^{-35}$

$$\frac{\partial^6}{\partial x I^2 \partial x^2 \partial x^3} u(xI, x2, x3) = \frac{1}{\Delta x I^2 \Delta x^2 \Delta x^3} \left((-18 + 26 I) u_{iI+1, i2+1, i3+1} + (12 + 16 I) u_{iI+1, i2+1, i3+1+1} - (24 + 32 I) u_{iI+1, i2+1, i3} + (30 - 10 I) u_{iI+1, i2+1, i3+1} + (12 + 16 I) u_{iI+1, i2+1+1, i3+1} + (12 - 4 I) u_{iI+1, i2+1+1, i3+1+1} + (-24 + 8 I) u_{iI+1, i2+1+1, i3} - 20 I u_{iI+1, i2+1+1, i3+1} - (24 + 32 I) u_{iI+1, i2, i3+1} + (-24 + 8 I) u_{iI+1, i2, i3+1+1} + (48 - 16 I) u_{iI+1, i2, i3} + 40 I u_{iI+1, i2, i3+1} + (30 - 10 I) u_{iI+1, i2+1, i3+1} - 20 I u_{iI+1, i2+1, i3+1+1} + 40 I u_{iI+1, i2+1, i3} - (30 + 10 I) u_{iI+1, i2+1, i3+1} + (12 + 16 I) u_{iI+1+1, i2+1, i3+1} + (12 - 4 I) u_{iI+1+1, i2+1, i3+1+1} + (-24 + 8 I) u_{iI+1+1, i2+1, i3} - 20 I u_{iI+1+1, i2+1, i3+1} + (12 - 4 I) u_{iI+1+1, i2+1+1, i3+1} - 8 I u_{iI+1+1, i2+1+1, i3+1+1} + 16 I u_{iI+1+1, i2+1+1, i3} - (12 + 4 I) u_{iI+1+1, i2+1+1, i3+1} + (-24 + 8 I) u_{iI+1+1, i2, i3+1} + 16 I u_{iI+1+1, i2, i3+1+1} - 32 I u_{iI+1+1, i2, i3} + (24 + 8 I) u_{iI+1+1, i2, i3+1} - 20 I u_{iI+1+1, i2+1, i3+1} - (12 + 4 I) u_{iI+1+1, i2+1, i3+1+1} + (24 + 8 I) u_{iI+1+1, i2+1, i3} + (-12 + 16 I) u_{iI+1+1, i2+1, i3+1} - (24 + 32 I) u_{iI, i2+1, i3+1} + (-24 + 8 I) u_{iI, i2+1, i3+1+1} + (48 - 16 I) u_{iI, i2+1, i3} + 40 I u_{iI, i2+1, i3+1} + (-24 + 8 I) u_{iI, i2+1+1, i3+1} + 16 I u_{iI, i2+1+1, i3+1+1} - 32 I u_{iI, i2+1+1, i3} + (24 + 8 I) u_{iI, i2+1+1, i3+1} + (48 - 16 I) u_{iI, i2, i3+1} - 32 I u_{iI, i2, i3+1+1} + 64 I u_{iI, i2, i3} - (48 + 16 I) u_{iI, i2, i3+1} + 40 I u_{iI, i2+1, i3+1} + (24 + 8 I) u_{iI, i2+1, i3+1+1} - (48 + 16 I) u_{iI, i2+1, i3} + (24 - 32 I) u_{iI, i2+1, i3+1} + (30 - 10 I) u_{iI+1, i2+1, i3+1} - 20 I u_{iI+1, i2+1, i3+1+1} + 40 I u_{iI+1, i2+1, i3} - (30 + 10 I) u_{iI+1, i2+1, i3+1} - 20 I u_{iI+1, i2+1+1, i3+1} - (12 + 4 I) u_{iI+1, i2+1+1, i3+1+1} + (24 + 8 I) u_{iI+1, i2+1+1, i3} + (-12 + 16 I) u_{iI+1, i2+1+1, i3+1} + 40 I u_{iI+1, i2, i3+1} + (24 + 8 I) u_{iI+1, i2, i3+1+1} - (48 + 16 I) u_{iI+1, i2, i3} + (24 - 32 I) u_{iI+1, i2, i3+1} - (30 + 10 I) u_{iI+1, i2+1, i3+1} + (-12 + 16 I) u_{iI+1, i2+1, i3+1+1} + (24 - 32 I) u_{iI+1, i2+1, i3} + (18 + 26 I) u_{iI+1, i2+1, i3+1} \right), O(\Delta x I^2 \Delta x^2 \Delta x^3), \text{ Quadrant } I$$

Error order:, 2, *Error:*, 0.00017512150818244260271, *New Error:*, 1.7487738885302467962 $\times 10^{-10}$
Error order:, 2, *Error:*, 1.7487738885302467962 $\times 10^{-10}$, *New Error:*, 1.7487714490453623658 $\times 10^{-16}$
Error order:, 2, *Error:*, 1.7487714490453623658 $\times 10^{-16}$, *New Error:*, 1.7487714466058791845 $\times 10^{-22}$
Error order:, 2, *Error:*, 1.7487714466058791845 $\times 10^{-22}$, *New Error:*, 1.7487714466034397014 $\times 10^{-28}$
Error order:, 2, *Error:*, 1.7487714466034397014 $\times 10^{-28}$, *New Error:*, 1.7487714466034372619 $\times 10^{-34}$

$$\frac{d^8}{dxI^8} u(xI) = \frac{1}{\Delta x I^8} \left((28 - 96 I) u_{iI+4I} - (208 + 144 I) u_{iI+1+4I} + (-192 + 144 I) u_{iI+2+4I} + (32 + 96 I) u_{iI+3+4I} + 16 u_{iI+4+4I} + (416 + 288 I) u_{iI+3I} + (448 - 336 I) u_{iI+1+3I} + (48 + 144 I) u_{iI+2+3I} + 352 u_{iI+3+3I} + (32 - 96 I) u_{iI+4+3I} + (-768 + 576 I) u_{iI+2I} - (96 + 288 I) u_{iI+1+2I} - 936 u_{iI+2+2I} + (48 - 144 I) u_{iI+3+2I} - (192 + 144 I) u_{iI+4+2I} - (256 + 768 I) u_{iI+1} + 1408 u_{iI+1+1} + (-96 + 288 I) u_{iI+2+1} + (448 + 336 I) u_{iI+3+1} + (-208 + 144 I) u_{iI+4+1} + 256 u_{iI} + (-256 + 768 I) u_{iI+1} - (768 + 576 I) u_{iI+2} + (416 - 288 I) u_{iI+3} + (28 + 96 I) u_{iI+4} \right), O(\Delta x I^2), \text{ Quadrant } I$$

Error order:, 2, *Error:*, 0.000010539208399240578216, *New Error:*, 1.0532205613686244229 $\times 10^{-11}$
Error order:, 2, *Error:*, 1.0532205613686244229 $\times 10^{-11}$, *New Error:*, 1.0532198613240528084 $\times 10^{-17}$
Error order:, 2, *Error:*, 1.0532198613240528084 $\times 10^{-17}$, *New Error:*, 1.0532198606240084697 $\times 10^{-23}$
Error order:, 2, *Error:*, 1.0532198606240084697 $\times 10^{-23}$, *New Error:*, 1.0532198606233084253 $\times 10^{-29}$
Error order:, 2, *Error:*, 1.0532198606233084253 $\times 10^{-29}$, *New Error:*, 1.0532198606233077253 $\times 10^{-35}$

$$\frac{\partial^8}{\partial x I^4 \partial x^2} u(xI, x2) = \frac{1}{\Delta x I^4 \Delta x^2} \left((28 - 96 I) u_{iI+3I, i2+1} - (52 + 36 I) u_{iI+3I, i2+1+1} + (104 + 72 I) u_{iI+3I, i2} + (-80 + 60 I) u_{iI+3I, i2+1} - (156 + 108 I) u_{iI+1+3I, i2+1} + (-96 + 72 I) u_{iI+1+3I, i2+1+1} + (192 - 144 I) u_{iI+1+3I, i2} + (60 + 180 I) u_{iI+1+3I, i2+1} + (-96 + 72 I) u_{iI+2+3I, i2+1} + (24 + 72 I) u_{iI+2+3I, i2+1+1} - (48 + 144 I) u_{iI+2+3I, i2} + 120 u_{iI+2+3I, i2+1} + (8 + 24 I) u_{iI+3+3I, i2+1} + 16 u_{iI+3+3I, i2+1+1} - 32 u_{iI+3+3I, i2} + (8 - 24 I) u_{iI+3+3I, i2+1} + (312 + 216 I) u_{iI+2I, i2+1} + (192 - 144 I) u_{iI+2I, i2+1+1} + (-384 + 288 I) u_{iI+2I, i2} - (120 + 360 I) u_{iI+2I, i2+1} + (144 - 108 I) u_{iI+1+2I, i2+1} - (36 + 108 I) u_{iI+1+2I, i2+1+1} + (72 + 216 I) u_{iI+1+2I, i2} - 180 u_{iI+1+2I, i2+1} + (72 + 216 I) u_{iI+2+2I, i2+1} + 144 u_{iI+2+2I, i2+1+1} - 288 u_{iI+2+2I, i2} + (72 - 216 I) u_{iI+2+2I, i2+1} + 120 u_{iI+3+2I, i2+1} + (24 - 72 I) u_{iI+3+2I, i2+1+1} + (-48 + 144 I) u_{iI+3+2I, i2} - (96 + 72 I) u_{iI+3+2I, i2+1} + (-384 + 288 I) u_{iI+1, i2+1} + (96 + 288 I) u_{iI+1, i2+1+1} - (192 + 576 I) u_{iI+1, i2} + 480 u_{iI+1, i2+1} - (144 + 432 I) u_{iI+1+1, i2+1} - 288 u_{iI+1+1, i2+1+1} + 576 u_{iI+1+1, i2} + (-144 + 432 I) u_{iI+1+1, i2+1} - 180 u_{iI+2+1, i2+1} + (-36 + 108 I) u_{iI+2+1, i2+1+1} + (72 - 216 I) u_{iI+2+1, i2} + (144 + 108 I) u_{iI+2+1, i2+1} + (60 - 180 I) u_{iI+3+1, i2+1} - (96 + 72 I) u_{iI+3+1, i2+1+1} + (192 + 144 I) u_{iI+3+1, i2} + (-156 + 108 I) u_{iI+3+1, i2+1} - (64 + 192 I) u_{iI, i2+1} - 128 u_{iI, i2+1+1} + 256 u_{iI, i2} + (-64 + 192 I) u_{iI, i2+1} + 480 u_{iI+1, i2+1} + (96 - 288 I) u_{iI+1, i2+1+1} + (-192 + 576 I) u_{iI+1, i2} - (384 + 288 I) u_{iI+1, i2+1} + (-120 + 360 I) u_{iI+2, i2+1} + (192 + 144 I) u_{iI+2, i2+1+1} - (384 + 288 I) u_{iI+2, i2} + (312 - 216 I) u_{iI+2, i2+1} - (80 + 60 I) u_{iI+3, i2+1} + (-52 + 36 I) u_{iI+3, i2+1+1} + (104 - 72 I) u_{iI+3, i2} + (28 + 96 I) u_{iI+3, i2+1} \right), O(\Delta x I^2 \Delta x^2), \text{ Quadrant } I$$

Error order:, 2, *Error:*, 0.000036840708936359828904, *New Error:*, 3.6811008381959811889 $\times 10^{-11}$
Error order:, 2, *Error:*, 3.6811008381959811889 $\times 10^{-11}$, *New Error:*, 3.6810978693443932895 $\times 10^{-17}$
Error order:, 2, *Error:*, 3.6810978693443932895 $\times 10^{-17}$, *New Error:*, 3.6810978663755429000 $\times 10^{-23}$
Error order:, 2, *Error:*, 3.6810978663755429000 $\times 10^{-23}$, *New Error:*, 3.6810978663725740496 $\times 10^{-29}$
Error order:, 2, *Error:*, 3.6810978663725740496 $\times 10^{-29}$, *New Error:*, 3.6810978663725710808 $\times 10^{-35}$

$$\frac{\partial^8}{\partial x I^4 \partial x^4} u(xI, x2) = \frac{1}{\Delta x I^4 \Delta x^4} \left((28 - 96 I) u_{iI+2I, i2+2I} - (104 + 72 I) u_{iI+2I, i2+1+2I} + (-32 + 24 I) u_{iI+2I, i2+2+2I} + (208 + 144 I) u_{iI+2I, i2+1} + (-32 + 24 I) u_{iI+2I, i2+1+1} + (40 + 120 I) u_{iI+2I, i2+2+1} + (-128 + 96 I) u_{iI+2I, i2} - (80 + 240 I) u_{iI+2I, i2+1} + 100 u_{iI+2I, i2+2} - (104 + 72 I) u_{iI+1+2I, i2+2I} + (-128 + 96 I) u_{iI+1+2I, i2+1+2I} + (16 + 48 I) u_{iI+1+2I, i2+2+2I} + (256 - 192 I) u_{iI+1+2I, i2+1} + (16 + 48 I) u_{iI+1+2I, i2+1+1} + 160 u_{iI+1+2I, i2+2+1} + (64 + 192 I) u_{iI+1+2I, i2} - 320 u_{iI+1+2I, i2+1} + (40 - 120 I) u_{iI+1+2I, i2+2} + (-32 + 24 I) u_{iI+2+2I, i2+2I} + (16 + 48 I) u_{iI+2+2I, i2+1+2I} + 16 u_{iI+2+2I, i2+2+2I} - (32 + 96 I) u_{iI+2+2I, i2+1} + 16 u_{iI+2+2I, i2+1+1} + (16 - 48 I) u_{iI+2+2I, i2+2+1} + 64 u_{iI+2+2I, i2} + (-32 + 96 I) u_{iI+2+2I, i2+1} - (32 + 24 I) u_{iI+2+2I, i2+2} + (208 + 144 I) u_{iI+1, i2+1} + (256 - 192 I) u_{iI+1, i2+1+1} - (32 + 96 I) u_{iI+1, i2+2+2I} + (-512 + 384 I) u_{iI+1, i2+1} - (32 + 96 I) u_{iI+1, i2+1+1} - 320 u_{iI+1, i2+2+1} - (128$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& + 160 u_{iI+1,i2,i3,i4+1} + (32 - 96 I) u_{iI+1,i2,i3,i4+1+1} + (-64 + 192 I) u_{iI+1,i2,i3,i4} - (128 + 96 I) u_{iI+1,i2,i3,i4+1} + (-40 + 120 I) u_{iI+1,i2,i3+1,i4+1} + (64 + 48 I) u_{iI+1,i2,i3+1,i4+1+1} - (128 + 96 I) u_{iI+1,i2,i3+1,i4} + (104 - 72 I) u_{iI+1,i2,i3+1,i4+1} + 100 u_{iI+1,i2+1,i3+1,i4+1} + (20 - 60 I) u_{iI+1,i2+1,i3+1,i4+1+1} + (-40 \\
& + 120 I) u_{iI+1,i2+1,i3+1,i4} - (80 + 60 I) u_{iI+1,i2+1,i3+1,i4+1} + (20 - 60 I) u_{iI+1,i2+1,i3+1+1,i4+1} - (32 + 24 I) u_{iI+1,i2+1,i3+1+1,i4+1+1} + (64 + 48 I) u_{iI+1,i2+1,i3+1+1,i4} + (-52 + 36 I) u_{iI+1,i2+1,i3+1+1,i4+1} + (-40 + 120 I) u_{iI+1,i2+1,i3,i4+1} + (64 + 48 I) u_{iI+1,i2+1,i3,i4+1+1} - (128 + 96 I) u_{iI+1,i2+1,i3,i4} + (104 \\
& - 72 I) u_{iI+1,i2+1,i3,i4+1} - (80 + 60 I) u_{iI+1,i2+1,i3+1,i4+1} + (-52 + 36 I) u_{iI+1,i2+1,i3+1,i4+1+1} + (104 - 72 I) u_{iI+1,i2+1,i3+1,i4} + (28 + 96 I) u_{iI+1,i2+1,i3+1,i4+1}), \mathcal{O}(\Delta x I^2 \Delta x^2 \Delta x^3 \Delta x^4), \text{ Quadrant } I \\
& \text{Error order: , 2, Error: , 0.0010293804936005675275, New Error: , 1.0274144178489852034} \times 10^{-9} \\
& \text{Error order: , 2, Error: , 1.0274144178489852034} \times 10^{-9}, \text{ New Error: , 1.0274124536642651569} \times 10^{-15} \\
& \text{Error order: , 2, Error: , 1.0274124536642651569} \times 10^{-15}, \text{ New Error: , 1.0274124517000823163} \times 10^{-21} \\
& \text{Error order: , 2, Error: , 1.0274124517000823163} \times 10^{-21}, \text{ New Error: , 1.0274124516981181335} \times 10^{-27} \\
& \text{Error order: , 2, Error: , 1.0274124516981181335} \times 10^{-27}, \text{ New Error: , 1.0274124516981161693} \times 10^{-33}
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\frac{d^{10}}{dx I^{10}} u(xI) &= \frac{1}{\Delta x I^{10}} ((12 + 316 I) u_{iI+5I} + (960 + 280 I) u_{iI+1+5I} + (720 - 1040 I) u_{iI+2+5I} - (480 + 640 I) u_{iI+3+5I} + (-240 + 80 I) u_{iI+4+5I} + 32 I u_{iI+5+5I} - (1920 + 560 I) u_{iI+4I} + (-1980 + 2860 I) u_{iI+1+4I} + (480 + 640 I) u_{iI+2+4I} + (-1680 + 560 I) u_{iI+3+4I} + 1280 I u_{iI+4+4I} + (240 + 80 I) u_{iI+5+4I} \\
& + (2880 - 4160 I) u_{iI+3I} - (960 + 1280 I) u_{iI+1+3I} + (5640 - 1880 I) u_{iI+2+3I} - 2320 I u_{iI+3+3I} + (1680 + 560 I) u_{iI+4+3I} + (480 - 640 I) u_{iI+5+3I} + (3840 + 5120 I) u_{iI+2I} + (-6720 + 2240 I) u_{iI+1+2I} + 4640 I u_{iI+2+2I} - (5640 + 1880 I) u_{iI+3+2I} + (-480 + 640 I) u_{iI+4+2I} - (720 + 1040 I) u_{iI+5+2I} \\
& + (-3840 + 1280 I) u_{iI+1} - 10240 I u_{iI+1+1} + (6720 + 2240 I) u_{iI+2+1} + (960 - 1280 I) u_{iI+3+1} + (1980 + 2860 I) u_{iI+4+1} + (-960 + 280 I) u_{iI+5+1} - 1024 I u_{iI} + (3840 + 1280 I) u_{iI+1} + (-3840 + 5120 I) u_{iI+2} - (2880 + 4160 I) u_{iI+3} + (1920 - 560 I) u_{iI+4} + (-12 + 316 I) u_{iI+5}), \mathcal{O}(\Delta x I^2), \text{ Quadrant } I \\
& \text{Error order: , 2, Error: , 0.000013121472129012809028, New Error: , 1.3112753551886053532} \times 10^{-11} \\
& \text{Error order: , 2, Error: , 1.3112753551886053532} \times 10^{-11}, \text{ New Error: , 1.3112744836226409561} \times 10^{-17} \\
& \text{Error order: , 2, Error: , 1.3112744836226409561} \times 10^{-17}, \text{ New Error: , 1.3112744827510752817} \times 10^{-23} \\
& \text{Error order: , 2, Error: , 1.3112744827510752817} \times 10^{-23}, \text{ New Error: , 1.3112744827502037160} \times 10^{-29} \\
& \text{Error order: , 2, Error: , 1.3112744827502037160} \times 10^{-29}, \text{ New Error: , 1.3112744827502028444} \times 10^{-35}
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\frac{d^{12}}{dx I^{12}} u(xI) &= \frac{1}{\Delta x I^{12}} ((-352 + 936 I) u_{iI+6I} + (-3792 + 144 I) u_{iI+1+6I} + (-1680 + 5760 I) u_{iI+2+6I} + (4160 + 2880 I) u_{iI+3+6I} + (1920 - 1440 I) u_{iI+4+6I} - (192 + 576 I) u_{iI+5+6I} - 64 u_{iI+6+6I} + (7584 - 288 I) u_{iI+5I} + (5040 - 17280 I) u_{iI+1+5I} - (9360 + 6480 I) u_{iI+2+5I} + (3840 - 2880 I) u_{iI+3+5I} \\
& - (2880 + 8640 I) u_{iI+4+5I} - 4032 u_{iI+5+5I} + (-192 + 576 I) u_{iI+6+5I} + (-6720 + 23040 I) u_{iI+4I} + (18720 + 12960 I) u_{iI+1+4I} + (-18720 + 14040 I) u_{iI+2+4I} + (9120 + 27360 I) u_{iI+3+4I} - 1440 u_{iI+4+4I} + (-2880 + 8640 I) u_{iI+5+4I} + (1920 + 1440 I) u_{iI+6+4I} - (33280 + 23040 I) u_{iI+3I} + (15360 \\
& - 11520 I) u_{iI+1+3I} - (18240 + 54720 I) u_{iI+2+3I} + 19040 u_{iI+3+3I} + (9120 - 27360 I) u_{iI+4+3I} + (3840 + 2880 I) u_{iI+5+3I} + (4160 - 2880 I) u_{iI+6+3I} + (30720 - 23040 I) u_{iI+2I} + (23040 + 69120 I) u_{iI+1+2I} - 5760 u_{iI+2+2I} + (-18240 + 54720 I) u_{iI+3+2I} - (18720 + 14040 I) u_{iI+4+2I} + (-9360 \\
& + 6480 I) u_{iI+5+2I} - (1680 + 5760 I) u_{iI+6+2I} + (6144 + 18432 I) u_{iI+1} - 64512 u_{iI+1+1} + (23040 - 69120 I) u_{iI+2+1} + (15360 + 11520 I) u_{iI+3+1} + (18720 - 12960 I) u_{iI+4+1} + (5040 + 17280 I) u_{iI+5+1} - (3792 + 144 I) u_{iI+6+1} - 4096 u_{iI} + (6144 - 18432 I) u_{iI+1} + (30720 + 23040 I) u_{iI+2} + (-33280 \\
& + 23040 I) u_{iI+3} - (6720 + 23040 I) u_{iI+4} + (7584 + 288 I) u_{iI+5} + (-352 + 936 I) u_{iI+6}), \mathcal{O}(\Delta x I^2), \text{ Quadrant } I \\
& \text{Error order: , 2, Error: , 0.000015682971940383857466, New Error: , 1.5672551366591432149} \times 10^{-11} \\
& \text{Error order: , 2, Error: , 1.5672551366591432149} \times 10^{-11}, \text{ New Error: , 1.5672540949509854018} \times 10^{-17} \\
& \text{Error order: , 2, Error: , 1.5672540949509854018} \times 10^{-17}, \text{ New Error: , 1.5672540939092775905} \times 10^{-23} \\
& \text{Error order: , 2, Error: , 1.5672540939092775905} \times 10^{-23}, \text{ New Error: , 1.5672540939082358827} \times 10^{-29} \\
& \text{Error order: , 2, Error: , 1.5672540939082358827} \times 10^{-29}, \text{ New Error: , 1.5672540939082348410} \times 10^{-35}
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\frac{d^{14}}{dx I^{14}} u(xI) &= \frac{1}{\Delta x I^{14}} ((1992 + 2456 I) u_{iI+7I} + (13104 - 4928 I) u_{iI+1+7I} - (1008 + 26544 I) u_{iI+2+7I} - (26880 + 7840 I) u_{iI+3+7I} + (-10080 + 14560 I) u_{iI+4+7I} + (4032 + 5376 I) u_{iI+5+7I} + (1344 - 448 I) u_{iI+6+7I} - 128 I u_{iI+7+7I} + (-26208 + 9856 I) u_{iI+6I} + (3192 + 84056 I) u_{iI+1+6I} + (80640 \\
& + 23520 I) u_{iI+2+6I} + (5040 - 7280 I) u_{iI+3+6I} + (26880 + 35840 I) u_{iI+4+6I} + (34272 - 11424 I) u_{iI+5+6I} - 11648 I u_{iI+6+6I} - (1344 + 448 I) u_{iI+7+6I} - (4032 + 106176 I) u_{iI+5I} - (161280 + 47040 I) u_{iI+1+5I} + (22680 - 32760 I) u_{iI+2+5I} - (115920 + 154560 I) u_{iI+3+5I} + (-70560 + 23520 I) u_{iI+4+5I} \\
& - 44352 I u_{iI+5+5I} - (34272 + 11424 I) u_{iI+6+5I} + (-4032 + 5376 I) u_{iI+7+5I} + (215040 + 62720 I) u_{iI+4I} + (20160 - 29120 I) u_{iI+1+4I} + (231840 + 309120 I) u_{iI+2+4I} + (91560 - 30520 I) u_{iI+3+4I} + 226240 I u_{iI+4+4I} + (70560 + 23520 I) u_{iI+5+4I} + (-26880 + 35840 I) u_{iI+6+4I} + (10080 \\
& + 14560 I) u_{iI+7+4I} + (-161280 + 232960 I) u_{iI+3I} - (215040 + 286720 I) u_{iI+1+3I} + (-282240 + 94080 I) u_{iI+2+3I} - 452480 I u_{iI+3+3I} - (91560 + 30520 I) u_{iI+4+3I} + (115920 - 154560 I) u_{iI+5+3I} - (5040 + 7280 I) u_{iI+6+3I} + (26880 - 7840 I) u_{iI+7+3I} - (129024 + 172032 I) u_{iI+2I} + (548352 \\
& - 182784 I) u_{iI+1+2I} + 354816 I u_{iI+2+2I} + (282240 + 94080 I) u_{iI+3+2I} + (-231840 + 309120 I) u_{iI+4+2I} - (22680 + 32760 I) u_{iI+5+2I} + (-80640 + 23520 I) u_{iI+6+2I} + (1008 - 26544 I) u_{iI+7+2I} + (86016 - 28672 I) u_{iI+1} + 372736 I u_{iI+1+1} - (548352 + 182784 I) u_{iI+2+1} + (215040 - 286720 I) u_{iI+3+1} \\
& - (20160 + 29120 I) u_{iI+4+1} + (161280 - 47040 I) u_{iI+5+1} + (-3192 + 84056 I) u_{iI+6+1} - (13104 + 4928 I) u_{iI+7+1} + 16384 I u_{iI} - (86016 + 28672 I) u_{iI+1} + (129024 - 172032 I) u_{iI+2} + (161280 + 232960 I) u_{iI+3} + (-215040 + 62720 I) u_{iI+4} + (4032 - 106176 I) u_{iI+5} + (26208 + 9856 I) u_{iI+6} + (-1992 \\
& + 2456 I) u_{iI+7}), \mathcal{O}(\Delta x I^2), \text{ Quadrant } I \\
& \text{Error order: , 2, Error: , 0.000018223832378333276724, New Error: , 1.8211723520049061073} \times 10^{-11} \\
& \text{Error order: , 2, Error: , 1.8211723520049061073} \times 10^{-11}, \text{ New Error: , 1.8211711415254816071} \times 10^{-17} \\
& \text{Error order: , 2, Error: , 1.8211711415254816071} \times 10^{-17}, \text{ New Error: , 1.8211711403150025853} \times 10^{-23} \\
& \text{Error order: , 2, Error: , 1.8211711403150025853} \times 10^{-23}, \text{ New Error: , 1.8211711403137921063} \times 10^{-29} \\
& \text{Error order: , 2, Error: , 1.8211711403137921063} \times 10^{-29}, \text{ New Error: , 1.8211711403137908958} \times 10^{-35}
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\frac{d^{16}}{dx I^{16}} u(xI) &= \frac{1}{\Delta x I^{16}} ((-8432 + 5376 I) u_{iI+8I} + (-39296 + 31872 I) u_{iI+1+8I} + (39424 + 104832 I) u_{iI+2+8I} + (141568 - 5376 I) u_{iI+3+8I} + (31360 - 107520 I) u_{iI+4+8I} - (46592 + 32256 I) u_{iI+5+8I} + (-14336 + 10752 I) u_{iI+6+8I} + (1024 + 3072 I) u_{iI+7+8I} + 256 u_{iI+8+8I} + (78592 - 63744 I) u_{iI+7I} \\
& - (129536 + 344448 I) u_{iI+1+7I} + (-495488 + 18816 I) u_{iI+2+7I} + (-62720 + 215040 I) u_{iI+3+7I} - (116480 + 80640 I) u_{iI+4+7I} + (-186368 + 139776 I) u_{iI+5+7I} + (39424 + 118272 I) u_{iI+6+7I} + 31744 u_{iI+7+7I} + (1024 - 3072 I) u_{iI+8+7I} + (157696 + 419328 I) u_{iI+6I} + (990976 - 37632 I) u_{iI+1+6I} \\
& + (78400 - 268800 I) u_{iI+2+6I} + (757120 + 524160 I) u_{iI+3+6I} + (663040 - 497280 I) u_{iI+4+6I} - (3584 + 10752 I) u_{iI+5+6I} + 270592 u_{iI+6+6I} + (39424 - 118272 I) u_{iI+7+6I} - (14336 + 10752 I) u_{iI+8+6I} + (-1132544 + 43008 I) u_{iI+5I} + (-250880 + 860160 I) u_{iI+1+5I} - (1514240 + 1048320 I) u_{iI+2+5I} \\
& + (-1379840 + 1034880 I) u_{iI+3+5I} - (264320 + 792960 I) u_{iI+4+5I} - 1100288 u_{iI+5+5I} + (-3584 + 10752 I) u_{iI+6+5I} - (186368 + 139776 I) u_{iI+7+5I} + (-46592 + 32256 I) u_{iI+8+5I} + (501760 - 1720320 I) u_{iI+4I} + (931840 + 645120 I) u_{iI+1+4I} + (2652160 - 1989120 I) u_{iI+2+4I} + (528640 \\
& + 1585920 I) u_{iI+3+4I} + 2420320 u_{iI+4+4I} + (-264320 + 792960 I) u_{iI+5+4I} + (663040 + 497280 I) u_{iI+6+4I} + (-116480 + 80640 I) u_{iI+7+4I} + (31360 + 107520 I) u_{iI+8+4I} + (1490944 + 1032192 I) u_{iI+3I} + (-2981888 + 2236416 I) u_{iI+1+3I} + (28672 + 86016 I) u_{iI+2+3I} - 4401152 u_{iI+3+3I} + (528640 \\
& - 1585920 I) u_{iI+4+3I} - (1379840 + 1034880 I) u_{iI+5+3I} + (757120 - 524160 I) u_{iI+6+3I} - (62720 + 215040 I) u_{iI+7+3I} + (141568 + 5376 I) u_{iI+8+3I} + (-917504 + 688128 I) u_{iI+2I} - (1261568 + 3784704 I) u_{iI+1+2I} + 4329472 u_{iI+2+2I} + (28672 - 86016 I) u_{iI+3+2I} + (2652160 + 1989120 I) u_{iI+4+2I} \\
& + (-1514240 + 1048320 I) u_{iI+5+2I} + (78400 + 268800 I) u_{iI+6+2I} - (495488 + 18816 I) u_{iI+7+2I} + (39424 - 104832 I) u_{iI+8+2I} - (131072 + 393216 I) u_{iI+1} + 2031616 u_{iI+1+1} + (-1261568 + 3784704 I) u_{iI+2+1} - (2981888 + 2236416 I) u_{iI+3+1} + (931840 - 645120 I) u_{iI+4+1} - (250880 \\
& + 860160 I) u_{iI+5+1} + (990976 + 37632 I) u_{iI+6+1} + (-129536 + 344448 I) u_{iI+7+1} - (39296 + 31872 I) u_{iI+8+1} + 65536 u_{iI} + (-131072 + 393216 I) u_{iI+1} - (917504 + 688128 I) u_{iI+2} + (1490944 - 1032192 I) u_{iI+3} + (501760 + 1720320 I) u_{iI+4} - (1132544 + 43008 I) u_{iI+5} + (157696 - 419328 I) u_{iI+6} \\
& + (78592 + 63744 I) u_{iI+7} + (-8432 + 5376 I) u_{iI+8}), \mathcal{O}(\Delta x I^2), \text{ Quadrant } I \\
& \text{Error order: , 2, Error: , 0.000020744177324699579456, New Error: , 2.0730393811805031032} \times 10^{-11} \\
& \text{Error order: , 2, Error: , 2.0730393811805031032} \times 10^{-11}, \text{ New Error: , 2.0730380032925100550} \times 10^{-17} \\
& \text{Error order: , 2, Error: , 2.0730380032925100550} \times 10^{-17}, \text{ New Error: , 2.0730380019146225203} \times 10^{-23}
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& + u_{iI+1+L,i2+L,i3+1+L,i4+1} - I u_{iI+1+L,i2+L,i3+1+L,i4+1+1} + I u_{iI+1+L,i2+L,i3+1+L,i4} - u_{iI+1+L,i2+L,i3+1+L,i4+1} - u_{iI+1+L,i2+L,i3,i4+1} + I u_{iI+1+L,i2+L,i3,i4+1+1} - I u_{iI+1+L,i2+L,i3,i4} + u_{iI+1+L,i2+L,i3,i4+1} - I u_{iI+1+L,i2+L,i3+1,i4+1} + u_{iI+1+L,i2+L,i3+1,i4} + I u_{iI+1+L,i2+L,i3+1,i4+1} + u_{iI+1+L,i2+L,i3+1,i4+1} \\
& - I u_{iI+1+L,i2+1+L,i3+1,i4+1+1} + I u_{iI+1+L,i2+1+L,i3+1,i4} - u_{iI+1+L,i2+1+L,i3+1,i4+1} - I u_{iI+1+L,i2+1+L,i3+1,i4+1} - u_{iI+1+L,i2+1+L,i3+1,i4+1} + u_{iI+1+L,i2+1+L,i3+1,i4} + I u_{iI+1+L,i2+1+L,i3+1,i4+1} + I u_{iI+1+L,i2+1+L,i3,i4+1} + u_{iI+1+L,i2+1+L,i3,i4+1} - u_{iI+1+L,i2+1+L,i3,i4} - I u_{iI+1+L,i2+1+L,i3,i4+1} - u_{iI+1+L,i2+1+L,i3+1,i4+1} \\
& + I u_{iI+1+L,i2+1+L,i3+1,i4+1} - I u_{iI+1+L,i2+1+L,i3+1,i4} + u_{iI+1+L,i2+1+L,i3+1,i4+1} - u_{iI+1+L,i2,i3+1,i4+1} + I u_{iI+1+L,i2,i3+1,i4+1} - I u_{iI+1+L,i2,i3+1,i4} + u_{iI+1+L,i2,i3+1,i4+1} + I u_{iI+1+L,i2,i3+1,i4+1} + u_{iI+1+L,i2,i3+1,i4+1} - u_{iI+1+L,i2,i3+1,i4} - I u_{iI+1+L,i2,i3+1,i4+1} - I u_{iI+1+L,i2,i3,i4+1} - u_{iI+1+L,i2,i3,i4+1} \\
& + u_{iI+1+L,i2,i3,i4} + I u_{iI+1+L,i2,i3,i4+1} + u_{iI+1+L,i2,i3+1,i4+1} - I u_{iI+1+L,i2,i3+1,i4+1} + I u_{iI+1+L,i2,i3+1,i4} - u_{iI+1+L,i2,i3+1,i4+1} - I u_{iI+1+L,i2+1,i3+1,i4+1} - u_{iI+1+L,i2+1,i3+1,i4+1} + u_{iI+1+L,i2+1,i3+1,i4} + I u_{iI+1+L,i2+1,i3+1,i4+1} - u_{iI+1+L,i2+1,i3+1,i4} + I u_{iI+1+L,i2+1,i3+1,i4+1} - I u_{iI+1+L,i2+1,i3+1,i4} \\
& + u_{iI+1+L,i2+1,i3+1,i4+1} + u_{iI+1+L,i2+1,i3,i4+1} - I u_{iI+1+L,i2+1,i3,i4+1+1} + I u_{iI+1+L,i2+1,i3,i4} - u_{iI+1+L,i2+1,i3,i4+1} + I u_{iI+1+L,i2+1,i3+1,i4+1} + u_{iI+1+L,i2+1,i3+1,i4+1} - u_{iI+1+L,i2+1,i3+1,i4} - I u_{iI+1+L,i2+1,i3+1,i4+1} - I u_{iI+1+L,i2+1,i3+1,i4+1} + u_{iI+1+L,i2+1,i3+1,i4} + I u_{iI+1+L,i2+1,i3+1,i4+1} - u_{iI+1+L,i2+1,i3+1,i4} \\
& + I u_{iI+1+L,i2+1,i3+1,i4+1} - I u_{iI+1+L,i2+1,i3+1,i4} + u_{iI+1+L,i2+1,i3+1,i4+1} + u_{iI+1+L,i2,i3,i4+1} - I u_{iI+1+L,i2,i3,i4+1} + I u_{iI+1+L,i2,i3,i4} - u_{iI+1+L,i2,i3,i4+1} + I u_{iI+1+L,i2,i3+1,i4+1} + u_{iI+1+L,i2,i3+1,i4+1} - u_{iI+1+L,i2,i3+1,i4} - I u_{iI+1+L,i2,i3+1,i4+1} - u_{iI+1+L,i2,i3+1,i4+1} \\
& + I u_{iI+1+L,i2+1+L,i3+1,i4+1} + u_{iI+1+L,i2+1+L,i3+1,i4} - u_{iI+1+L,i2+1+L,i3+1,i4+1} - I u_{iI+1+L,i2+1+L,i3+1,i4+1} - I u_{iI+1+L,i2+1+L,i3,i4+1} - u_{iI+1+L,i2+1+L,i3,i4+1} + u_{iI+1+L,i2+1+L,i3,i4} + I u_{iI+1+L,i2+1+L,i3,i4+1} + u_{iI+1+L,i2+1+L,i3+1,i4+1} - I u_{iI+1+L,i2+1+L,i3+1,i4+1} + I u_{iI+1+L,i2+1+L,i3+1,i4} \\
& - u_{iI+1+L,i2+1+L,i3+1,i4+1} - I u_{iI+1+L,i2+1+L,i3+1,i4} - u_{iI+1+L,i2+1+L,i3+1,i4+1} + u_{iI+1+L,i2,i3+1,i4} + I u_{iI+1+L,i2,i3+1,i4+1} + I u_{iI+1+L,i2,i3,i4+1} + u_{iI+1+L,i2,i3,i4+1} - u_{iI+1+L,i2,i3,i4} - I u_{iI+1+L,i2,i3,i4+1} - u_{iI+1+L,i2,i3+1,i4+1} + I u_{iI+1+L,i2,i3+1,i4+1} + u_{iI+1+L,i2+1+L,i3+1,i4+1} \\
& + u_{iI+1+L,i2+1+L,i3+1,i4} - I u_{iI+1+L,i2+1+L,i3+1,i4+1} + I u_{iI+1+L,i2+1+L,i3+1,i4} - u_{iI+1+L,i2+1+L,i3+1,i4+1} - u_{iI+1+L,i2+1+L,i3+1,i4} + I u_{iI+1+L,i2+1+L,i3+1,i4+1} + u_{iI+1+L,i2+1+L,i3+1,i4+1} - u_{iI+1+L,i2+1+L,i3+1,i4} - I u_{iI+1+L,i2+1+L,i3+1,i4+1} - I u_{iI+1+L,i2+1+L,i3+1,i4+1} \\
& + u_{iI+1+L,i2+1+L,i3+1,i4} + I u_{iI+1+L,i2+1+L,i3+1,i4+1} + u_{iI+1+L,i2+1+L,i3+1,i4+1} - u_{iI+1+L,i2+1+L,i3+1,i4} + I u_{iI+1+L,i2+1+L,i3+1,i4+1} + u_{iI+1+L,i2+1+L,i3+1,i4+1} - u_{iI+1+L,i2+1+L,i3+1,i4} - I u_{iI+1+L,i2+1+L,i3+1,i4+1} - I u_{iI+1+L,i2+1+L,i3+1,i4+1} \\
& - u_{iI+1+L,i2+1+L,i3+1,i4+1} + u_{iI+1+L,i2+1+L,i3+1,i4} + I u_{iI+1+L,i2+1+L,i3+1,i4+1} - u_{iI+1+L,i2+1+L,i3+1,i4+1} + I u_{iI+1+L,i2+1+L,i3+1,i4} + u_{iI+1+L,i2+1+L,i3+1,i4+1} - u_{iI+1+L,i2+1+L,i3+1,i4} - I u_{iI+1+L,i2+1+L,i3+1,i4+1} - I u_{iI+1+L,i2+1+L,i3+1,i4+1} \\
& - u_{iI+1+L,i2+1+L,i3+1,i4+1} + u_{iI+1+L,i2+1+L,i3+1,i4} + I u_{iI+1+L,i2+1+L,i3+1,i4+1} - u_{iI+1+L,i2+1+L,i3+1,i4+1} + I u_{iI+1+L,i2+1+L,i3+1,i4} + u_{iI+1+L,i2+1+L,i3+1,i4+1} - u_{iI+1+L,i2+1+L,i3+1,i4} - I u_{iI+1+L,i2+1+L,i3+1,i4+1} - I u_{iI+1+L,i2+1+L,i3+1,i4+1} \\
& - u_{iI+1+L,i2+1+L,i3+1,i4+1} + u_{iI+1+L,i2+1+L,i3+1,i4} + I u_{iI+1+L,i2+1+L,i3+1,i4+1} - u_{iI+1+L,i2+1+L,i3+1,i4+1} + I u_{iI+1+L,i2+1+L,i3+1,i4} + u_{iI+1+L,i2+1+L,i3+1,i4+1} - u_{iI+1+L,i2+1+L,i3+1,i4} - I u_{iI+1+L,i2+1+L,i3+1,i4+1} - I u_{iI+1+L,i2+1+L,i3+1,i4+1} \\
& + I u_{iI+1+L,i2+1+L,i3+1,i4+1} + u_{iI+1+L,i2+1+L,i3+1,i4+1} - I u_{iI+1+L,i2+1+L,i3+1,i4+1} + I u_{iI+1+L,i2+1+L,i3+1,i4} - u_{iI+1+L,i2+1+L,i3+1,i4+1}
\end{aligned}$$

Error order:., 1, *Error:*., 0.56426149754314276401, *New Error:*., 0.00056188300137854325576

Error order:., 1, *Error:*., 0.00056188300137854325576, *New Error:*., 5.6188062790738672999 × 10⁻⁷

Error order:., 1, *Error:*., 5.6188062790738672999 × 10⁻⁷, *New Error:*., 5.6188062553392059142 × 10⁻¹⁰

Error order:., 1, *Error:*., 5.6188062553392059142 × 10⁻¹⁰, *New Error:*., 5.6188062553154712528 × 10⁻¹³

Error order:., 1, *Error:*., 5.6188062553154712528 × 10⁻¹³, *New Error:*., 5.6188062553154475182 × 10⁻¹⁶

$$\begin{aligned}
\frac{d^{15}}{dxI^{15}} u(xI) &= \frac{1}{\Delta x I^{15}} (972 ((-1 + I) u_{iI+5I+1} + (5 + 5 I) u_{iI+1+5I+1} + (10 - 10 I) u_{iI+2+5I+1} - (10 + 10 I) u_{iI+3+5I+1} + (-5 + 5 I) u_{iI+4+5I+1} + (1 + I) u_{iI+5+5I+1} - (5 + 5 I) u_{iI+4I+1} + (-15 + 15 I) u_{iI+1+4I+1} + (10 + 10 I) u_{iI+2+4I+1} + (-10 + 10 I) u_{iI+3+4I+1} + (15 + 15 I) u_{iI+4+4I+1} + (5 - 5 I) u_{iI+5+4I+1} + (10 - 10 I) u_{iI+3I+1} \\
& - (10 + 10 I) u_{iI+1+3I+1} + (20 - 20 I) u_{iI+2+3I+1} - (20 + 20 I) u_{iI+3+3I+1} + (10 - 10 I) u_{iI+4+3I+1} - (10 + 10 I) u_{iI+5+3I+1} + (10 + 10 I) u_{iI+2I+1} + (-10 + 10 I) u_{iI+1+2I+1} + (20 + 20 I) u_{iI+2+2I+1} + (-20 + 20 I) u_{iI+3+2I+1} + (10 + 10 I) u_{iI+4+2I+1} + (-10 + 10 I) u_{iI+5+2I+1} + (-5 + 5 I) u_{iI+1} - (15 + 15 I) u_{iI+1+1} + (10 \\
& - 10 I) u_{iI+2+1} - (10 + 10 I) u_{iI+3+1} + (15 - 15 I) u_{iI+4+1} + (5 + 5 I) u_{iI+5+1} - (1 + I) u_{iI} + (5 - 5 I) u_{iI+1} + (10 + 10 I) u_{iI+2} + (-10 + 10 I) u_{iI+3} - (5 + 5 I) u_{iI+4} + (1 - I) u_{iI+5}), O(\Delta x I), \textit{ Quadrant 1}
\end{aligned}$$

Error order:., 1, *Error:*., 0.018442563639381780822, *New Error:*., 0.000018396652514304633397

Error order:., 1, *Error:*., 0.000018396652514304633397, *New Error:*., 1.8396606660429988261 × 10⁻⁸

Error order:., 1, *Error:*., 1.8396606660429988261 × 10⁻⁸, *New Error:*., 1.8396606614576170819 × 10⁻¹¹

Error order:., 1, *Error:*., 1.8396606614576170819 × 10⁻¹¹, *New Error:*., 1.8396606614530317001 × 10⁻¹⁴

Error order:., 1, *Error:*., 1.8396606614530317001 × 10⁻¹⁴, *New Error:*., 1.8396606614530271147 × 10⁻¹⁷

"--- Derivative Order: 1 - x1=1 ---"

$$\begin{bmatrix} 2I & 1 + 2I & 2 + 2I \\ I & 1 + I & 2 + I \\ 0 & 1 & 2 \end{bmatrix}$$

$$\begin{bmatrix} \frac{1}{2} & -\frac{4}{5} + \frac{8I}{5} & -\frac{1}{4} + \frac{I}{4} \\ 4I & 10 - 10I & -\frac{8}{5} + \frac{4I}{5} \\ -\frac{57}{20} + \frac{57I}{20} & -4 & -\frac{1}{2} \end{bmatrix}$$

$$\frac{d}{dxI} u(xI) = \frac{10 I u_{iI+2I+1} + (-16 + 32 I) u_{iI+1+2I+1} + (-5 + 5 I) u_{iI+2+2I+1} + 80 I u_{iI+1} + (200 - 200 I) u_{iI+1+1} + (-32 + 16 I) u_{iI+2+1} + (-57 + 57 I) u_{iI} - 80 u_{iI+1} - 10 u_{iI+2}}{20 \Delta x I}, O(\Delta x I^8), \textit{ Quadrant 1}$$

Error order:., 8, *Error:*., 1.4916737917846748428 × 10⁻²⁵, *New Error:*., 1.4889992185425132608 × 10⁻⁴⁹

Error order:., 8, *Error:*., 1.4889992185425132608 × 10⁻⁴⁹, *New Error:*., 1.4889965463708643258 × 10⁻⁷³

Error order:., 8, *Error:*., 1.4889965463708643258 × 10⁻⁷³, *New Error:*., 1.4889965436986950770 × 10⁻⁹⁷

Error order:., 8, *Error:*., 1.4889965436986950770 × 10⁻⁹⁷, *New Error:*., 1.4889965436960229077 × 10⁻¹²¹

Error order:., 8, *Error:*., 1.4889965436960229077 × 10⁻¹²¹, *New Error:*., 1.4889965436960202356 × 10⁻¹⁴⁵

$$\begin{aligned}
\frac{d^2}{dxI^2} u(xI) &= \frac{1}{200 \Delta x I^2} (-50 u_{iI+4I+1} - (320 + 160 I) u_{iI+1+4I+1} - (434 + 562 I) u_{iI+2+4I+1} - (80 + 240 I) u_{iI+3+4I+1} - 25 I u_{iI+4+4I+1} - 800 u_{iI+3I+1} + (-560 + 720 I) u_{iI+1+3I+1} + (2640 + 8880 I) u_{iI+2+3I+1} + 720 I u_{iI+3+3I+1} + (80 - 240 I) u_{iI+4+3I+1} - (3770 + 570 I) u_{iI+2I+1} + (15088 + 12464 I) u_{iI+1+2I+1} - 45790 I u_{iI+2+2I+1} \\
& + (-2640 + 8880 I) u_{iI+3+2I+1} + (434 - 562 I) u_{iI+4+2I+1} - (4560 + 4560 I) u_{iI+1} + 16400 I u_{iI+1+1} + (-15088 + 12464 I) u_{iI+2+1} + (560 + 720 I) u_{iI+3+1} + (320 - 160 I) u_{iI+4+1} - 3249 I u_{iI} + (4560 - 4560 I) u_{iI+1} + (3770 - 570 I) u_{iI+2} + 800 u_{iI+3} + 50 u_{iI+4}), O(\Delta x I^8), \textit{ Quadrant 1}
\end{aligned}$$

Error order:., 8, *Error:*., 2.9773927979734028797 × 10⁻²⁵, *New Error:*., 2.9720543284281701812 × 10⁻⁴⁹

Error order:., 8, *Error:*., 2.9720543284281701812 × 10⁻⁴⁹, *New Error:*., 2.9720489947522242031 × 10⁻⁷³

Error order:., 8, *Error:*., 2.9720489947522242031 × 10⁻⁷³, *New Error:*., 2.9720489894185530478 × 10⁻⁹⁷

Error order:., 8, *Error:*., 2.9720489894185530478 × 10⁻⁹⁷, *New Error:*., 2.9720489894132193767 × 10⁻¹²¹

Error order:., 8, *Error:*., 2.9720489894132193767 × 10⁻¹²¹, *New Error:*., 2.9720489894132140430 × 10⁻¹⁴⁵

$-70000000 u_{i+13} - 1250000 u_{i+14}$), $O(\Delta x I^8)$, *Quadrant I*

Error order.: 8, *Error.*: $1.0317288391249975798 \times 10^{-24}$, *New Error.*: $1.0298789478407988438 \times 10^{-48}$
Error order.: 8, *Error.*: $1.0298789478407988438 \times 10^{-48}$, *New Error.*: $1.0298770996105969845 \times 10^{-72}$
Error order.: 8, *Error.*: $1.0298770996105969845 \times 10^{-72}$, *New Error.*: $1.0298770977623684427 \times 10^{-96}$
Error order.: 8, *Error.*: $1.0298770977623684427 \times 10^{-96}$, *New Error.*: $1.0298770977605202142 \times 10^{-120}$
Error order.: 8, *Error.*: $1.0298770977605202142 \times 10^{-120}$, *New Error.*: $1.0298770977605183659 \times 10^{-144}$

"--- Derivative Order: 2 - x1=1 ---"

$$\begin{bmatrix} 2I & 1+2I & 2+2I \\ I & 1+I & 2+I \\ 0 & 1 & 2 \end{bmatrix}$$

$$\begin{bmatrix} -\frac{47}{20} - \frac{57I}{20} & -\frac{18}{5} - \frac{62I}{5} & -\frac{13I}{5} \\ -\frac{74}{5} - \frac{114I}{5} & 94I & \frac{18}{5} - \frac{62I}{5} \\ -\frac{153I}{10} & \frac{74}{5} - \frac{114I}{5} & \frac{47}{20} - \frac{57I}{20} \end{bmatrix}$$

$$\frac{d^2}{dxI^2} u(xI) = \frac{- (47 + 57 I) u_{i+21} - (72 + 248 I) u_{i+1+21} - 52 I u_{i+2+21} - (296 + 456 I) u_{i+1} + 1880 I u_{i+1+1} + (72 - 248 I) u_{i+2+1} - 306 I u_i + (296 - 456 I) u_{i+1} + (47 - 57 I) u_{i+2}}{20 \Delta x I^2}, O(\Delta x I^7), \textit{Quadrant I}$$

Error order.: 7, *Error.*: $6.0119935951177012082 \times 10^{-22}$, *New Error.*: $6.0014240241374494457 \times 10^{-43}$
Error order.: 7, *Error.*: $6.0014240241374494457 \times 10^{-43}$, *New Error.*: $6.0014134638723144335 \times 10^{-64}$
Error order.: 7, *Error.*: $6.0014134638723144335 \times 10^{-64}$, *New Error.*: $6.0014134533120585988 \times 10^{-85}$
Error order.: 7, *Error.*: $6.0014134533120585988 \times 10^{-85}$, *New Error.*: $6.0014134533014983430 \times 10^{-106}$
Error order.: 7, *Error.*: $6.0014134533014983430 \times 10^{-106}$, *New Error.*: $6.0014134533014877827 \times 10^{-127}$

$$\frac{d^4}{dxI^4} u(xI) = \frac{1}{200 \Delta x I^4} ((-520 + 2679 I) u_{i+41} + (-10752 + 15760 I) u_{i+1+41} + (-31124 + 20300 I) u_{i+2+41} + (-12896 + 3744 I) u_{i+3+41} - 1352 u_{i+4+41} + (-12080 + 38304 I) u_{i+31} + (15384 + 17880 I) u_{i+1+31} + (425008 - 112416 I) u_{i+2+31} + 31072 u_{i+3+31} - (12896 + 3744 I) u_{i+4+31} + (-77602 + 149358 I) u_{i+21} + (741488 - 529888 I) u_{i+1+21} - 2057370 u_{i+2+21} + (425008 + 112416 I) u_{i+3+21} - (31124 + 20300 I) u_{i+4+21} + (-139536 + 90576 I) u_{i+1} + 279728 u_{i+1+1} + (741488 + 529888 I) u_{i+2+1} + (15384 - 17880 I) u_{i+3+1} - (10752 + 15760 I) u_{i+4+1} - 46818 u_i - (139536 + 90576 I) u_{i+1} - (77602 + 149358 I) u_{i+2} - (12080 + 38304 I) u_{i+3} - (520 + 2679 I) u_{i+4}), O(\Delta x I^7), \textit{Quadrant I}$$

Error order.: 7, *Error.*: $1.1976035145512769288 \times 10^{-21}$, *New Error.*: $1.1954980307125169712 \times 10^{-42}$
Error order.: 7, *Error.*: $1.1954980307125169712 \times 10^{-42}$, *New Error.*: $1.1954959270824248576 \times 10^{-63}$
Error order.: 7, *Error.*: $1.1954959270824248576 \times 10^{-63}$, *New Error.*: $1.1954959249787966181 \times 10^{-84}$
Error order.: 7, *Error.*: $1.1954959249787966181 \times 10^{-84}$, *New Error.*: $1.1954959249766929899 \times 10^{-105}$
Error order.: 7, *Error.*: $1.1954959249766929899 \times 10^{-105}$, *New Error.*: $1.1954959249766908862 \times 10^{-126}$

$$\frac{\partial^4}{\partial x I^2 \partial x^2} u(xI, x2) = \frac{1}{200 \Delta x I^2 \Delta x^2} ((-520 + 2679 I) u_{i+21,i2+21} + (-5376 + 7880 I) u_{i+1+21,i2+1+21} + (-1482 + 1222 I) u_{i+21,i2+2+21} + (-6040 + 19152 I) u_{i+21,i2+1} + (53580 - 44180 I) u_{i+21,i2+1+1} + (-8760 + 3776 I) u_{i+21,i2+2+1} + (-8721 + 7191 I) u_{i+21,i2} + (-19952 + 2280 I) u_{i+21,i2+1} - 2729 u_{i+21,i2+2} + (-5376 + 7880 I) u_{i+1+21,i2+21} + (-28160 + 17856 I) u_{i+1+21,i2+1+21} + (-6448 + 1872 I) u_{i+1+21,i2+2+21} + (-45888 + 53120 I) u_{i+1+21,i2+1} + (233120 - 67680 I) u_{i+1+21,i2+1+1} - 33344 u_{i+1+21,i2+2+1} + (-37944 + 11016 I) u_{i+1+21,i2} - (67200 + 20288 I) u_{i+1+21,i2+1} - (8760 + 3776 I) u_{i+1+21,i2+2} + (-1482 + 1222 I) u_{i+2+21,i2+21} + (-6448 + 1872 I) u_{i+2+21,i2+1+21} - 1352 u_{i+2+21,i2+2+21} + (-11856 + 7696 I) u_{i+2+21,i2+1} + 48880 u_{i+2+21,i2+1+1} - (6448 + 1872 I) u_{i+2+21,i2+2+1} - 7956 u_{i+2+21,i2} - (11856 + 7696 I) u_{i+2+21,i2+1} - (1482 + 1222 I) u_{i+2+21,i2+2} + (-6040 + 19152 I) u_{i+1,i2+21} + (-45888 + 53120 I) u_{i+1,i2+1+21} + (-11856 + 7696 I) u_{i+1,i2+2+21} + (-60160 + 134976 I) u_{i+1,i2+1} + (428640 - 278240 I) u_{i+1,i2+1+1} + (-67200 + 20288 I) u_{i+1,i2+2+1} + (-69768 + 45288 I) u_{i+1,i2} - 147776 u_{i+1,i2+1} - (19952 + 2280 I) u_{i+1,i2+2} + (53580 - 44180 I) u_{i+1+1,i2+21} + (233120 - 67680 I) u_{i+1+1,i2+1+21} + 48880 u_{i+1+1,i2+2+21} + (428640 - 278240 I) u_{i+1+1,i2+1} - 1767200 u_{i+1+1,i2+1+1} + (233120 + 67680 I) u_{i+1+1,i2+2+1} + 287640 u_{i+1+1,i2} + (428640 + 278240 I) u_{i+1+1,i2+1} + (53580 + 44180 I) u_{i+1+1,i2+2} + (-8760 + 3776 I) u_{i+2+1,i2+21} - 33344 u_{i+2+1,i2+1+21} - (6448 + 1872 I) u_{i+2+1,i2+2+21} + (-67200 + 20288 I) u_{i+2+1,i2+1} + (233120 + 67680 I) u_{i+2+1,i2+1+1} - (28160 + 17856 I) u_{i+2+1,i2+2+1} - (37944 + 11016 I) u_{i+2+1,i2} - (45888 + 53120 I) u_{i+2+1,i2+1} - (5376 + 7880 I) u_{i+2+1,i2+2} + (-8721 + 7191 I) u_{i,i2+21} + (-37944 + 11016 I) u_{i,i2+1+21} - 7956 u_{i,i2+2+21} + (-69768 + 45288 I) u_{i,i2+1} + 287640 u_{i,i2+1+1} - (37944 + 11016 I) u_{i,i2+2+1} - 46818 u_{i,i2} - (69768 + 45288 I) u_{i,i2+1} - (8721 + 7191 I) u_{i,i2+2} + (-19952 + 2280 I) u_{i+1,i2+21} - (67200 + 20288 I) u_{i+1,i2+1+21} - (11856 + 7696 I) u_{i+1,i2+2+21} - 147776 u_{i+1,i2+1} + (428640 + 278240 I) u_{i+1,i2+1+1} - (45888 + 53120 I) u_{i+1,i2+2+1} - (69768 + 45288 I) u_{i+1,i2} - (60160 + 134976 I) u_{i+1,i2+1} - (6040 + 19152 I) u_{i+1,i2+2} - 2729 u_{i+2,i2+21} - (8760 + 3776 I) u_{i+2,i2+1+21} - (1482 + 1222 I) u_{i+2,i2+2+21} - (19952 + 2280 I) u_{i+2,i2+1} + (53580 + 44180 I) u_{i+2,i2+1+1} - (5376 + 7880 I) u_{i+2,i2+2+1} - (8721 + 7191 I) u_{i+2,i2} - (6040 + 19152 I) u_{i+2,i2+1} - (520 + 2679 I) u_{i+2,i2+2}), O(\Delta x I^7 \Delta x^2), \textit{Quadrant I}$$

Error order.: 7, *Error.*: $2.8697897038565858405 \times 10^{-20}$, *New Error.*: $2.8623723221234496265 \times 10^{-41}$
Error order.: 7, *Error.*: $2.8623723221234496265 \times 10^{-41}$, *New Error.*: $2.8623649143452734894 \times 10^{-62}$
Error order.: 7, *Error.*: $2.8623649143452734894 \times 10^{-62}$, *New Error.*: $2.8623649069375049085 \times 10^{-83}$
Error order.: 7, *Error.*: $2.8623649069375049085 \times 10^{-83}$, *New Error.*: $2.8623649069300971399 \times 10^{-104}$
Error order.: 7, *Error.*: $2.8623649069300971399 \times 10^{-104}$, *New Error.*: $2.8623649069300897321 \times 10^{-125}$

$$\frac{d^6}{dxI^6} u(xI) = \frac{1}{4000 \Delta x I^6} ((177143 - 96273 I) u_{i+61} + (2105496 - 191784 I) u_{i+1+61} + (7441860 + 2378784 I) u_{i+2+61} + (8914368 + 7375360 I) u_{i+3+61} + (2976168 + 4624152 I) u_{i+4+61} + (292032 + 1005888 I) u_{i+5+61} + 70304 I u_{i+6+61} + (4126632 - 1667592 I) u_{i+51} + (15997896 - 2218944 I) u_{i+1+51} - (31597032 + 35124504 I) u_{i+2+51} - (88515552 + 149818656 I) u_{i+3+51} - (11535168 + 43342848 I) u_{i+4+51} + 2778048 I u_{i+5+51} + (-292032 + 1005888 I) u_{i+6+51} + (34022778 - 8266896 I) u_{i+41} - (84947064 + 39566328 I) u_{i+1+41} - (272041155 + 131037189 I) u_{i+2+41} + (316278192 + 1249980816 I) u_{i+3+41} - 41745624 I u_{i+4+41} + (11535168 - 43342848 I) u_{i+5+41} + (-2976168 + 4624152 I) u_{i+6+41} + (114519488 - 1430496 I) u_{i+31} - (703177968 + 302885520 I) u_{i+1+31} + (1596470832 + 2103584784 I) u_{i+2+31} - 4790222032 I u_{i+3+31} + (-316278192 + 1249980816 I) u_{i+4+31} + (88515552 - 149818656 I) u_{i+5+31} + (-8914368 + 7375360 I) u_{i+6+31} + (130509306 + 63232758 I) u_{i+21} - (365324784 + 513361008 I) u_{i+1+21} + 273086724 I u_{i+2+21} + (-1596470832 + 2103584784 I) u_{i+3+21} + (272041155 - 131037189 I) u_{i+4+21} + (31597032 - 35124504 I) u_{i+5+21} + (-7441860 + 2378784 I) u_{i+6+21} + (41574384 + 64047024 I) u_{i+1} + 7263216 I u_{i+1+1} + (365324784 - 513361008 I) u_{i+2+1} + (703177968 - 302885520 I) u_{i+3+1} + (84947064 - 39566328 I) u_{i+4+1} - (15997896 + 2218944 I) u_{i+5+1} - (2105496 + 191784 I) u_{i+6+1} + 14326308 I u_i + (-41574384 + 64047024 I) u_{i+1}$$

$O(\Delta x I^7)$, *Quadrant I*

Error order: 7, Error: 2.3761407992548094378 × 10⁻²¹, New Error: 2.3719633515514067910 × 10⁻⁴²
Error order: 7, Error: 2.3719633515514067910 × 10⁻⁴², New Error: 2.3719591777816844433 × 10⁻⁶³
Error order: 7, Error: 2.3719591777816844433 × 10⁻⁶³, New Error: 2.3719591736079183968 × 10⁻⁸⁴
Error order: 7, Error: 2.3719591736079183968 × 10⁻⁸⁴, New Error: 2.3719591736037446307 × 10⁻¹⁰⁵
Error order: 7, Error: 2.3719591736037446307 × 10⁻¹⁰⁵, New Error: 2.3719591736037404569 × 10⁻¹²⁶

$$\frac{d^{10}}{dx I^{10}} u(xI) = \frac{1}{800000 \Delta x I^{10}} \left((165801007 + 524628057 I) u_{iI+10I} + (-968447640 + 9567252440 I) u_{iI+1+10I} + (-33417363520 + 60536857540 I) u_{iI+2+10I} + (-205460807680 + 162368846720 I) u_{iI+3+10I} + (-532602369200 + 154278033360 I) u_{iI+4+10I} - (642616646528 + 53699399552 I) u_{iI+5+10I} - (358316038080 + 154708702720 I) u_{iI+6+10I} - (98362434560 + 84596695040 I) u_{iI+7+10I} - (12983039680 + 20318559040 I) u_{iI+8+10I} - (658045440 + 2266600960 I) u_{iI+9+10I} - 95051008 I u_{iI+10+10I} + (3869383880 + 19870658280 I) u_{iI+9I} + (-34104420480 + 211629806280 I) u_{iI+1+9I} + (-201824990440 + 575456638680 I) u_{iI+2+9I} + (1401397006400 + 252061764160 I) u_{iI+3+9I} + (8213080198400 + 1250070295680 I) u_{iI+4+9I} + (11855493482880 + 5810899901440 I) u_{iI+5+9I} + (4896153705600 + 4553018989440 I) u_{iI+6+9I} + (602664890880 + 1027391372800 I) u_{iI+7+9I} - (10226311680 + 24102807040 I) u_{iI+8+9I} - 29702033920 I u_{iI+9+9I} + (658045440 - 2266600960 I) u_{iI+10+9I} + (19113390880 + 307585533210 I) u_{iI+8I} + (-154726187720 + 1269908419240 I) u_{iI+1+8I} + (4879927970565 - 2465678671635 I) u_{iI+2+8I} + (18883645157600 - 9466269289120 I) u_{iI+3+8I} - (29292457482000 + 28827659515520 I) u_{iI+4+8I} - (96533824442880 + 98555419374720 I) u_{iI+5+8I} - (21937021794960 + 39026874987760 I) u_{iI+6+8I} + (774394712320 + 2314585137920 I) u_{iI+7+8I} + 1714394722560 I u_{iI+8+8I} + (10226311680 - 24102807040 I) u_{iI+9+8I} + (12983039680 - 20318559040 I) u_{iI+10+8I} + (-237222301760 + 2485846588800 I) u_{iI+7I} + (4220531437600 - 2871813303520 I) u_{iI+1+7I} + (32981885929440 - 28950324857760 I) u_{iI+2+7I} - (145891834027360 + 21918134209280 I) u_{iI+3+7I} + (-219194665024800 + 35142660366240 I) u_{iI+4+7I} + (467169585403840 + 877516898720320 I) u_{iI+5+7I} + (15230608784640 + 64068104594560 I) u_{iI+6+7I} - 60242825045760 I u_{iI+7+7I} + (-774394712320 + 2314585137920 I) u_{iI+8+7I} + (-602664890880 + 1027391372800 I) u_{iI+9+7I} + (98362434560 - 84596695040 I) u_{iI+10+7I} + (-3404439050380 + 11054660243220 I) u_{iI+6I} + (53388525102240 - 53061499391520 I) u_{iI+1+6I} + (-148757743281000 + 9621233712960 I) u_{iI+2+6I} + (-411667659355040 + 156053998063520 I) u_{iI+3+6I} + (2323416395169690 + 1475327592287190 I) u_{iI+4+6I} - (1254766542144240 + 4894866104856080 I) u_{iI+5+6I} + 945015874479400 I u_{iI+6+6I} + (-15230608784640 + 64068104594560 I) u_{iI+7+6I} + (21937021794960 - 39026874987760 I) u_{iI+8+6I} + (-4896153705600 + 4553018989440 I) u_{iI+9+6I} + (358316038080 - 154708702720 I) u_{iI+10+6I} + (-17056926557984 + 25841911164576 I) u_{iI+5I} + (230919635344480 - 152309768080640 I) u_{iI+1+5I} + (-1247276855115360 + 215151497327520 I) u_{iI+2+5I} + (3966598246408160 + 1230799103514400 I) u_{iI+3+5I} - (6345954371265200 + 7929183123330480 I) u_{iI+4+5I} + 14327489844348240 I u_{iI+5+5I} + (1254766542144240 - 4894866104856080 I) u_{iI+6+5I} + (-467169585403840 + 877516898720320 I) u_{iI+7+5I} + (96533824442880 - 98555419374720 I) u_{iI+8+5I} + (-11855493482880 + 5810899901440 I) u_{iI+9+5I} + (642616646528 - 53699399552 I) u_{iI+10+5I} + (-40008858471000 + 26356310285760 I) u_{iI+4I} + (390210308737120 - 57556595648160 I) u_{iI+1+4I} - (1320360299083460 + 456791579290780 I) u_{iI+2+4I} + (1307328169389440 + 1583298355245120 I) u_{iI+3+4I} + 2097137434974660 I u_{iI+4+4I} + (6345954371265200 - 7929183123330480 I) u_{iI+5+4I} + (-2323416395169690 + 1475327592287190 I) u_{iI+6+4I} + (219194665024800 + 35142660366240 I) u_{iI+7+4I} + (29292457482000 - 28827659515520 I) u_{iI+8+4I} + (-8213080198400 + 1250070295680 I) u_{iI+9+4I} + (532602369200 + 154278033360 I) u_{iI+10+4I} + (-42640635859200 + 4130965630080 I) u_{iI+3I} + (212266122937920 + 82988974848960 I) u_{iI+1+3I} - (111201866217920 + 106602727433280 I) u_{iI+2+3I} - 1429171561168320 I u_{iI+3+3I} + (-1307328169389440 + 1583298355245120 I) u_{iI+4+3I} + (-3966598246408160 + 1230799103514400 I) u_{iI+5+3I} + (411667659355040 + 156053998063520 I) u_{iI+6+3I} + (145891834027360 - 21918134209280 I) u_{iI+7+3I} - (18883645157600 + 9466269289120 I) u_{iI+8+3I} + (-1401397006400 + 252061764160 I) u_{iI+9+3I} + (205460807680 + 162368846720 I) u_{iI+10+3I} - (19852179890220 + 9243405553140 I) u_{iI+2I} + (16843704369120 + 19735685938080 I) u_{iI+1+2I} + 259456371864480 I u_{iI+2+2I} + (111201866217920 - 106602727433280 I) u_{iI+3+2I} + (1320360299083460 - 456791579290780 I) u_{iI+4+2I} + (1247276855115360 + 215151497327520 I) u_{iI+5+2I} + (148757743281000 + 9621233712960 I) u_{iI+6+2I} - (32981885929440 + 28950324857760 I) u_{iI+7+2I} - (4879927970565 + 2465678671635 I) u_{iI+8+2I} + (201824990440 + 575456638680 I) u_{iI+9+2I} + (33417363520 + 60536857540 I) u_{iI+10+2I} - (3244049183520 + 4997589282720 I) u_{iI+1I} - 21737593654560 I u_{iI+1+1I} + (-16843704369120 + 19735685938080 I) u_{iI+2+1I} + (-212266122937920 + 82988974848960 I) u_{iI+3+1I} - (390210308737120 + 57556595648160 I) u_{iI+4+1I} - (230919635344480 + 152309768080640 I) u_{iI+5+1I} - (53388525102240 + 53061499391520 I) u_{iI+6+1I} - (4220531437600 + 2871813303520 I) u_{iI+7+1I} + (154726187720 + 1269908419240 I) u_{iI+8+1I} + (34104420480 + 211629806280 I) u_{iI+9+1I} + (968447640 + 9567252440 I) u_{iI+10+1I} - 670729087944 I u_{iI} + (3244049183520 - 4997589282720 I) u_{iI+1I} + (19852179890220 - 9243405553140 I) u_{iI+2I} + (42640635859200 + 4130965630080 I) u_{iI+3I} + (40008858471000 + 26356310285760 I) u_{iI+4I} + (17056926557984 + 25841911164576 I) u_{iI+5I} + (3404439050380 + 11054660243220 I) u_{iI+6I} + (237222301760 + 2485846588800 I) u_{iI+7I} + (-19113390880 + 307585533210 I) u_{iI+8I} + (-3869383880 + 19870658280 I) u_{iI+9I} + (-165801007 + 524628057 I) u_{iI+10I} \right), O(\Delta x I^7), *Quadrant I*$$

Error order: 7, Error: 2.9583308423756397357 × 10⁻²¹, New Error: 2.9531298574898690531 × 10⁻⁴²
Error order: 7, Error: 2.9531298574898690531 × 10⁻⁴², New Error: 2.9531246610841247187 × 10⁻⁶³
Error order: 7, Error: 2.9531246610841247187 × 10⁻⁶³, New Error: 2.9531246558877235508 × 10⁻⁸⁴
Error order: 7, Error: 2.9531246558877235508 × 10⁻⁸⁴, New Error: 2.9531246558825271497 × 10⁻¹⁰⁵
Error order: 7, Error: 2.9531246558825271497 × 10⁻¹⁰⁵, New Error: 2.9531246558825219533 × 10⁻¹²⁶

"--- Derivative Order: 3 - xI=1 ---"

$$\begin{bmatrix} 2I & 1+2I & 2+2I \\ I & 1+I & 2+I \\ 0 & 1 & 2 \end{bmatrix}$$

$$\begin{bmatrix} \frac{747}{40} + \frac{141I}{40} & \frac{282}{5} + \frac{168I}{5} & \frac{381}{40} + \frac{381I}{40} \\ \frac{576}{5} + \frac{222I}{5} & -318 - 318I & \frac{168}{5} + \frac{282I}{5} \\ \frac{1467}{40} + \frac{1467I}{40} & \frac{222}{5} + \frac{576I}{5} & \frac{141}{40} + \frac{747I}{40} \end{bmatrix}$$

$$\frac{d^3}{dx I^3} u(xI) = \frac{3 \left((249 + 47 I) u_{iI+2I} + (752 + 448 I) u_{iI+1+2I} + (127 + 127 I) u_{iI+2+2I} + (1536 + 592 I) u_{iI+1I} - (4240 + 4240 I) u_{iI+1+1I} + (448 + 752 I) u_{iI+2+1I} + (489 + 489 I) u_{iI} + (592 + 1536 I) u_{iI+1I} + (47 + 249 I) u_{iI+2I} \right)}{40 \Delta x I^3}, O(\Delta x I^6), *Quadrant I*$$

Error order: 6, Error: 1.7115683972678871715 × 10⁻¹⁸, New Error: 1.7086264762222161504 × 10⁻³⁶
Error order: 6, Error: 1.7086264762222161504 × 10⁻³⁶, New Error: 1.7086235368335117193 × 10⁻⁵⁴
Error order: 6, Error: 1.7086235368335117193 × 10⁻⁵⁴, New Error: 1.7086235338941255457 × 10⁻⁷²
Error order: 6, Error: 1.7086235338941255457 × 10⁻⁷², New Error: 1.7086235338911861596 × 10⁻⁹⁰
Error order: 6, Error: 1.7086235338911861596 × 10⁻⁹⁰, New Error: 1.7086235338911832202 × 10⁻¹⁰⁸

$$\frac{d^6}{dx I^6} u(xI) = \frac{1}{800 \Delta x I^6} \left(9 \left((29896 + 11703 I) u_{iI+4I} + (166192 + 146896 I) u_{iI+1+4I} + (208054 + 374488 I) u_{iI+2+4I} + (38608 + 152400 I) u_{iI+3+4I} + 16129 I u_{iI+4+4I} + (354640 + 219600 I) u_{iI+3I} + (33376 - 121728 I) u_{iI+1+3I} - (1092864 + 4609440 I) u_{iI+2+3I} - 310752 I u_{iI+3+3I} + (-38608 + 152400 I) u_{iI+4+3I} + (1103194 + 1054056 I) u_{iI+2I} - (3778688 + 8025632 I) u_{iI+1+2I} + 21006592 I u_{iI+2+2I} + (1092864 - 4609440 I) u_{iI+3+2I} + (-208054 + 374488 I) u_{iI+4+2I} + (461616 + 1040592 I) u_{iI+1I} - 1436960 I u_{iI+1+1I} + (3778688 - 8025632 I) u_{iI+2+1I} - (33376 + 121728 I) u_{iI+3+1I} + (-166192 + 146896 I) u_{iI+4+1I} + 239121 I u_{iI} + (-461616 + 1040592 I) u_{iI+1I} + (-1103194 + 1054056 I) u_{iI+2I} + (-354640 + 219600 I) u_{iI+3I} + (-29896 + 11703 I) u_{iI+4I} \right) \right), O(\Delta x I^6), *Quadrant I*$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& + 55479456 \text{ I } u_{iI+3+2I,i2+2} + (-69406382 + 83468974 \text{ I } u_{iI+4+2I,i2+2I} + (-324227232 + 188406784 \text{ I } u_{iI+4+2I,i2+1+2I} + (-73982834 + 21137118 \text{ I } u_{iI+4+2I,i2+2+2I} + (-541267840 + 452045600 \text{ I } u_{iI+4+2I,i2+1} + (2469978080 - 705680160 \text{ I } u_{iI+4+2I,i2+1+1} + (-374823168 + 11314016 \text{ I } u_{iI+4+2I,i2+2+1} \\
& + (-284863038 + 81386226 \text{ I } u_{iI+4+2I,i2} - (698381536 + 97874048 \text{ I } u_{iI+4+2I,i2+1} - (103026050 + 34204510 \text{ I } u_{iI+4+2I,i2+2} + (66034560 + 280803360 \text{ I } u_{iI+1,i2+2I} + (-119049984 + 989329152 \text{ I } u_{iI+1,i2+1+2I} + (-73529952 + 190780416 \text{ I } u_{iI+1,i2+2+2I} + (93011712 + 1871625984 \text{ I } u_{iI+1,i2+1} \\
& + (2454858240 - 6369361920 \text{ I } u_{iI+1,i2+1+1} + (-575721216 + 813320448 \text{ I } u_{iI+1,i2+2+1} + (-283119264 + 734579712 \text{ I } u_{iI+1,i2} + (-1325072640 + 1325072640 \text{ I } u_{iI+1,i2+1} + (-237411456 + 163850208 \text{ I } u_{iI+1,i2+2} + (67537120 - 357803040 \text{ I } u_{iI+1+1,i2+2I} + (643758080 - 1080593920 \text{ I } u_{iI+1+1,i2+1+2I} \\
& + (182493920 - 182493920 \text{ I } u_{iI+1+1,i2+2+2I} + (850680320 - 2207170560 \text{ I } u_{iI+1+1,i2+1} + (-6092710400 + 6092710400 \text{ I } u_{iI+1+1,i2+1+1} + (1080593920 - 643758080 \text{ I } u_{iI+1+1,i2+2+1} + (702673440 - 702673440 \text{ I } u_{iI+1+1,i2} + (2207170560 - 850680320 \text{ I } u_{iI+1+1,i2+1} + (357803040 \\
& - 67537120 \text{ I } u_{iI+1+1,i2+2} + (1318098016 - 1820784032 \text{ I } u_{iI+2+1,i2+2I} + (6437056512 - 4342423040 \text{ I } u_{iI+2+1,i2+1+2I} + (1499148640 - 539361888 \text{ I } u_{iI+2+1,i2+2+2I} + (10555238912 - 10090387456 \text{ I } u_{iI+2+1,i2+1} + (-50050316800 + 18007042560 \text{ I } u_{iI+2+1,i2+1+1} + (7728127488 \\
& - 753909760 \text{ I } u_{iI+2+1,i2+2+1} + (5772312480 - 2076755616 \text{ I } u_{iI+2+1,i2} + (14564354048 + 1052890624 \text{ I } u_{iI+2+1,i2+1} + (2175980704 + 563688608 \text{ I } u_{iI+2+1,i2+2} - (2589408 + 31878944 \text{ I } u_{iI+3+1,i2+2I} + (29435392 - 106491904 \text{ I } u_{iI+3+1,i2+1+2I} + (11220704 - 19698208 \text{ I } u_{iI+3+1,i2+2+2I} + (20797440 \\
& - 206732800 \text{ I } u_{iI+3+1,i2+1} + (-374612480 + 657640960 \text{ I } u_{iI+3+1,i2+1+1} + (76587008 - 79632896 \text{ I } u_{iI+3+1,i2+2+1} + (43204128 - 75845856 \text{ I } u_{iI+3+1,i2} + (167215616 - 123328512 \text{ I } u_{iI+3+1,i2+1} + (28741600 - 14031840 \text{ I } u_{iI+3+1,i2+2} + (-48285920 + 28766080 \text{ I } u_{iI+4+1,i2+2I} + (-190785792 \\
& + 36011776 \text{ I } u_{iI+4+1,i2+1+2I} - (39762176 + 2450592 \text{ I } u_{iI+4+1,i2+2+2I} + (-342233344 + 127246592 \text{ I } u_{iI+4+1,i2+1} + (1327493120 + 81815040 \text{ I } u_{iI+4+1,i2+1+1} - (184919808 + 59166976 \text{ I } u_{iI+4+1,i2+2+1} - (153100032 + 9435744 \text{ I } u_{iI+4+1,i2} - (324017920 + 168308480 \text{ I } u_{iI+4+1,i2+1} - (44388128 \\
& + 34477696 \text{ I } u_{iI+4+1,i2+2} + (-11238687 + 59541129 \text{ I } u_{iI,i2+2I} + (-107126208 + 179818992 \text{ I } u_{iI,i2+1+2I} + (-30368367 + 30368367 \text{ I } u_{iI,i2+2+2I} + (-141559632 + 367289856 \text{ I } u_{iI,i2+1} + (1013873040 - 1013873040 \text{ I } u_{iI,i2+1+1} + (-179818992 + 107126208 \text{ I } u_{iI,i2+2+1} + (-116930169 \\
& + 116930169 \text{ I } u_{iI,i2} + (-367289856 + 141559632 \text{ I } u_{iI,i2+1} + (-59541129 + 11238687 \text{ I } u_{iI,i2+2} + (-163850208 + 237411456 \text{ I } u_{iI+1,i2+2I} + (-813320448 + 575721216 \text{ I } u_{iI+1,i2+1+2I} + (-190780416 + 73529952 \text{ I } u_{iI+1,i2+2+2I} + (-1325072640 + 1325072640 \text{ I } u_{iI+1,i2+1} + (6369361920 \\
& - 2454858240 \text{ I } u_{iI+1,i2+1+1} + (-989329152 + 119049984 \text{ I } u_{iI+1,i2+2+1} + (-734579712 + 283119264 \text{ I } u_{iI+1,i2} - (1871625984 + 93011712 \text{ I } u_{iI+1,i2+1} - (280803360 + 66034560 \text{ I } u_{iI+1,i2+2} + (-324235938 + 210609826 \text{ I } u_{iI+2,i2+2I} + (-1301818976 + 298419200 \text{ I } u_{iI+2,i2+1+2I} - (273970750 \\
& + 6240526 \text{ I } u_{iI+2,i2+2+2I} + (-2318507136 + 965939168 \text{ I } u_{iI+2,i2+1} + (9146740000 + 208345120 \text{ I } u_{iI+2,i2+1+1} - (1286881024 + 357384800 \text{ I } u_{iI+2,i2+2+1} - (1054895250 + 24028482 \text{ I } u_{iI+2,i2} - (2272120864 + 1070504832 \text{ I } u_{iI+2,i2+1} - (314310062 + 225154674 \text{ I } u_{iI+2,i2+2} + (-98626560 \\
& + 38012320 \text{ I } u_{iI+3,i2+2I} + (-365070080 + 6260480 \text{ I } u_{iI+3,i2+1+2I} - (72928480 + 17150080 \text{ I } u_{iI+3,i2+2+2I} + (-674730240 + 127358720 \text{ I } u_{iI+3,i2+1} + (2434777600 + 572569600 \text{ I } u_{iI+3,i2+1+1} - (324017920 + 168308480 \text{ I } u_{iI+3,i2+2+1} - (280803360 + 66034560 \text{ I } u_{iI+3,i2} - (547252480 \\
& + 414723840 \text{ I } u_{iI+3,i2+1} - (71348480 + 77984160 \text{ I } u_{iI+3,i2+2} + (-7994145 + 1508935 \text{ I } u_{iI+4,i2+2I} - (27724736 + 4592752 \text{ I } u_{iI+4,i2+1+2I} - (5283073 + 2310511 \text{ I } u_{iI+4,i2+2+2I} + (-52848432 + 277376 \text{ I } u_{iI+4,i2+1} + (176379760 + 77138320 \text{ I } u_{iI+4,i2+1+1} - (22194064 + 17238848 \text{ I } u_{iI+4,i2+2+1} \\
& - (20341911 + 8896377 \text{ I } u_{iI+4,i2} - (35674240 + 38992080 \text{ I } u_{iI+4,i2+1} - (4319159 + 6894063 \text{ I } u_{iI+4,i2+2})), O(\Delta x I^6 \Delta x 2^6), \textit{Quadrant 1}
\end{aligned}$$

Error order:., 6, Error:., 6.0033337023639590807 × 10⁻¹⁷, New Error:., 5.9886484970618160271 × 10⁻³⁵
Error order:., 6, Error:., 5.9886484970618160271 × 10⁻³⁵, New Error:., 5.9886338298505990332 × 10⁻⁵³
Error order:., 6, Error:., 5.9886338298505990332 × 10⁻⁵³, New Error:., 5.9886338151834057954 × 10⁻⁷¹
Error order:., 6, Error:., 5.9886338151834057954 × 10⁻⁷¹, New Error:., 5.9886338151687386022 × 10⁻⁸⁹
Error order:., 6, Error:., 5.9886338151687386022 × 10⁻⁸⁹, New Error:., 5.9886338151687239350 × 10⁻¹⁰⁷

"--- Derivative Order: 4 - xI=1 ---"

$$\begin{bmatrix} 2 \text{ I} & 1 + 2 \text{ I} & 2 + 2 \text{ I} \\ \text{ I} & 1 + \text{ I} & 2 + \text{ I} \\ 0 & 1 & 2 \end{bmatrix}$$

$$\begin{bmatrix} -\frac{663}{10} + 36 \text{ I} & -\frac{1266}{5} + 54 \text{ I} & -\frac{543}{10} \\ -\frac{2046}{5} + 126 \text{ I} & 1662 & -\frac{1266}{5} - 54 \text{ I} \\ -\frac{1503}{10} & -\frac{2046}{5} - 126 \text{ I} & -\frac{663}{10} - 36 \text{ I} \end{bmatrix}$$

$$\frac{d^4}{dx I^4} u(xI) = \frac{3((-221 + 120 \text{ I } u_{iI+2I} + (-844 + 180 \text{ I } u_{iI+1+2I} - 181 u_{iI+2+2I} + (-1364 + 420 \text{ I } u_{iI+1} + 5540 u_{iI+1+1} - (844 + 180 \text{ I } u_{iI+2+1} - 501 u_{iI} - (1364 + 420 \text{ I } u_{iI+1} - (221 + 120 \text{ I } u_{iI+2})), O(\Delta x I^5), \textit{Quadrant 1}$$

Error order:., 5, Error:., 3.8678955625657199737 × 10⁻¹⁵, New Error:., 3.8614422158098047113 × 10⁻³⁰
Error order:., 5, Error:., 3.8614422158098047113 × 10⁻³⁰, New Error:., 3.8614357678549663804 × 10⁻⁴⁵
Error order:., 5, Error:., 3.8614357678549663804 × 10⁻⁴⁵, New Error:., 3.8614357614070169309 × 10⁻⁶⁰
Error order:., 5, Error:., 3.8614357614070169309 × 10⁻⁶⁰, New Error:., 3.8614357614005689815 × 10⁻⁷⁵
Error order:., 5, Error:., 3.8614357614005689815 × 10⁻⁷⁵, New Error:., 3.8614357614005625335 × 10⁻⁹⁰

$$\begin{aligned}
\frac{d^8}{dx I^8} u(xI) &= \frac{1}{100 \Delta x I^8} (9((34441 - 53040 \text{ I } u_{iI+4I} + (329848 - 282120 \text{ I } u_{iI+1+4I} + (759938 - 347280 \text{ I } u_{iI+2+4I} + (305528 - 65160 \text{ I } u_{iI+3+4I} + 32761 u_{iI+4+4I} + (502088 - 513000 \text{ I } u_{iI+3I} + (-297448 + 129600 \text{ I } u_{iI+1+3I} + (-8441504 + 1719360 \text{ I } u_{iI+2+3I} - 516008 u_{iI+3+3I} + (305528 \\
& + 65160 \text{ I } u_{iI+4+3I} + (1905538 - 1266000 \text{ I } u_{iI+2I} + (-13563744 + 4331520 \text{ I } u_{iI+1+2I} + 35906708 u_{iI+2+2I} - (8441504 + 1719360 \text{ I } u_{iI+3+2I} + (759938 + 347280 \text{ I } u_{iI+4+2I} + (1366728 - 420840 \text{ I } u_{iI+1} - 1477288 u_{iI+1+1} - (13563744 + 4331520 \text{ I } u_{iI+2+1} - (297448 + 129600 \text{ I } u_{iI+3+1} + (329848 \\
& + 282120 \text{ I } u_{iI+4+1} + 251001 u_{iI} + (1366728 + 420840 \text{ I } u_{iI+1} + (1905538 + 1266000 \text{ I } u_{iI+2} + (502088 + 513000 \text{ I } u_{iI+3} + (34441 + 53040 \text{ I } u_{iI+4}))), O(\Delta x I^5), \textit{Quadrant 1}
\end{aligned}$$

Error order:., 5, Error:., 7.6742129943670316943 × 10⁻¹⁵, New Error:., 7.6614090401934255451 × 10⁻³⁰
Error order:., 5, Error:., 7.6614090401934255451 × 10⁻³⁰, New Error:., 7.6613962469372460565 × 10⁻⁴⁵
Error order:., 5, Error:., 7.6613962469372460565 × 10⁻⁴⁵, New Error:., 7.6613962341440005689 × 10⁻⁶⁰
Error order:., 5, Error:., 7.6613962341440005689 × 10⁻⁶⁰, New Error:., 7.6613962341312073235 × 10⁻⁷⁵
Error order:., 5, Error:., 7.6613962341312073235 × 10⁻⁷⁵, New Error:., 7.6613962341311945302 × 10⁻⁹⁰

$$\begin{aligned}
\frac{\partial^8}{\partial x I^4 \partial x 2^4} u(xI, x2) &= \frac{1}{100 \Delta x I^4 \Delta x 2^4} (9((34441 - 53040 \text{ I } u_{iI+2I,i2+2I} + (164924 - 141060 \text{ I } u_{iI+1+2I,i2+2I} + (40001 - 21720 \text{ I } u_{iI+2I,i2+2+2I} + (251044 - 256500 \text{ I } u_{iI+2I,i2+1} + (-1224340 + 664800 \text{ I } u_{iI+2I,i2+1+1} + (208124 - 61500 \text{ I } u_{iI+2I,i2+2+1} + (110721 - 60120 \text{ I } u_{iI+2I,i2} + (351844 \\
& - 70860 \text{ I } u_{iI+2I,i2+1} + 63241 u_{iI+2I,i2+2} + (164924 - 141060 \text{ I } u_{iI+1+2I,i2+2I} + (679936 - 303840 \text{ I } u_{iI+1+2I,i2+1+2I} + (152764 - 32580 \text{ I } u_{iI+1+2I,i2+2+2I} + (1075616 - 600000 \text{ I } u_{iI+1+2I,i2+1} + (-4675760 + 997200 \text{ I } u_{iI+1+2I,i2+1+1} + 744736 u_{iI+1+2I,i2+2+1} + (422844 - 90180 \text{ I } u_{iI+1+2I,i2} + (1226816 \\
& + 108960 \text{ I } u_{iI+1+2I,i2+1} + (208124 + 61500 \text{ I } u_{iI+1+2I,i2+2} + (40001 - 21720 \text{ I } u_{iI+2+2I,i2+2I} + (152764 - 32580 \text{ I } u_{iI+2+2I,i2+1+2I} + 32761 u_{iI+2+2I,i2+2+2I} + (246884 - 76020 \text{ I } u_{iI+2+2I,i2+1} - 1002740 u_{iI+2+2I,i2+1+1} + (152764 + 32580 \text{ I } u_{iI+2+2I,i2+2+1} + 90681 u_{iI+2+2I,i2} + (246884 \\
& + 76020 \text{ I } u_{iI+2+2I,i2+1} + (40001 + 21720 \text{ I } u_{iI+2+2I,i2+2} + (251044 - 256500 \text{ I } u_{iI+1,i2+2I} + (1075616 - 600000 \text{ I } u_{iI+1,i2+1+2I} + (246884 - 76020 \text{ I } u_{iI+1,i2+2+2I} + (1684096 - 1145760 \text{ I } u_{iI+1,i2+1} + (-7556560 + 2326800 \text{ I } u_{iI+1,i2+1+1} + (1226816 - 108960 \text{ I } u_{iI+1,i2+2+1} + (683364 - 210420 \text{ I } u_{iI+1,i2} \\
& + 2036896 u_{iI+1,i2+1} + (351844 + 70860 \text{ I } u_{iI+1,i2+2} + (-1224340 + 664800 \text{ I } u_{iI+1+1,i2+2I} + (-4675760 + 997200 \text{ I } u_{iI+1+1,i2+1+2I} - 1002740 u_{iI+1+1,i2+2+2I} + (-7556560 + 2326800 \text{ I } u_{iI+1+1,i2+1} + 30691600 u_{iI+1+1,i2+1+1} - (4675760 + 997200 \text{ I } u_{iI+1+1,i2+2+1} - 2775540 u_{iI+1+1,i2} - (7556560 \\
& + 2326800 \text{ I } u_{iI+1+1,i2+1} - (1224340 + 664800 \text{ I } u_{iI+1+1,i2+2} + (208124 - 61500 \text{ I } u_{iI+2+1,i2+2I} + 744736 u_{iI+2+1,i2+1+2I} + (152764 + 32580 \text{ I } u_{iI+2+1,i2+2+2I} + (1226816 - 108960 \text{ I } u_{iI+2+1,i2+1} - (4675760 + 997200 \text{ I } u_{iI+2+1,i2+1+1} + (679936 + 303840 \text{ I } u_{iI+2+1,i2+2+1} + (422844 + 90180 \text{ I } u_{iI+2+1,i2}
\end{aligned}$$

$$+ 910608960 \text{ I } u_{il+3, i2+1} - (49401448 + 173623560 \text{ I}) u_{il+3, i2+2} - (13976261 + 7588920 \text{ I}) u_{il+4, i2+1} - (38615404 + 38566380 \text{ I}) u_{il+4, i2+1+21} - (6233821 + 9600240 \text{ I}) u_{il+4, i2+2+21} - (69254324 + 57881340 \text{ I}) u_{il+4, i2+1} + (190803140 + 293841600 \text{ I}) u_{il+4, i2+1+1} - (19521004 + 50965140 \text{ I}) u_{il+4, i2+2+1} - (17254941 + 26573040 \text{ I}) u_{il+4, i2} - (24700724 + 86811780 \text{ I}) u_{il+4, i2+1} - (1246661 + 15854760 \text{ I}) u_{il+4, i2+2}), O(\Delta x I^5 \Delta x 2^5), \text{ Quadrant } I$$

Error order.: 5, Error.: 9.6818331581739453723 × 10⁻¹⁴, New Error.: 9.6593197635168944971 × 10⁻²⁹
Error order.: 5, Error.: 9.6593197635168944971 × 10⁻²⁹, New Error.: 9.6592972763444647350 × 10⁻⁴⁴
Error order.: 5, Error.: 9.6592972763444647350 × 10⁻⁴⁴, New Error.: 9.6592972538573185068 × 10⁻⁵⁹
Error order.: 5, Error.: 9.6592972538573185068 × 10⁻⁵⁹, New Error.: 9.6592972538348313606 × 10⁻⁷⁴
Error order.: 5, Error.: 9.6592972538348313606 × 10⁻⁷⁴, New Error.: 9.6592972538348088734 × 10⁻⁸⁹

--- Derivative Order: 5 - x1=1 ---

$$\begin{bmatrix} 2 \text{ I} & 1 + 2 \text{ I} & 2 + 2 \text{ I} \\ \text{ I} & 1 + \text{ I} & 2 + \text{ I} \\ 0 & 1 & 2 \end{bmatrix}$$

$$\begin{bmatrix} 90 - 210 \text{ I} & 456 - 642 \text{ I} & 120 - 120 \text{ I} \\ 630 - 960 \text{ I} & -3360 + 3360 \text{ I} & 642 - 456 \text{ I} \\ 252 - 252 \text{ I} & 960 - 630 \text{ I} & 210 - 90 \text{ I} \end{bmatrix}$$

$$\frac{d^5}{dx I^5} u(xI) = \frac{(90 - 210 \text{ I}) u_{il+21} + (456 - 642 \text{ I}) u_{il+1+21} + (120 - 120 \text{ I}) u_{il+2+21} + (630 - 960 \text{ I}) u_{il+1} + (-3360 + 3360 \text{ I}) u_{il+1+1} + (642 - 456 \text{ I}) u_{il+2+1} + (252 - 252 \text{ I}) u_{il} + (960 - 630 \text{ I}) u_{il+1} + (210 - 90 \text{ I}) u_{il+2}}{\Delta x I^5}, O(\Delta x I^4), \text{ Quadrant } I$$

Error order.: 4, Error.: 7.0048405252874011429 × 10⁻¹², New Error.: 6.9936418420908435042 × 10⁻²⁴
Error order.: 4, Error.: 6.9936418420908435042 × 10⁻²⁴, New Error.: 6.9936306523731546691 × 10⁻³⁶
Error order.: 4, Error.: 6.9936306523731546691 × 10⁻³⁶, New Error.: 6.9936306411834459409 × 10⁻⁴⁸
Error order.: 4, Error.: 6.9936306411834459409 × 10⁻⁴⁸, New Error.: 6.9936306411722562322 × 10⁻⁶⁰
Error order.: 4, Error.: 6.9936306411722562322 × 10⁻⁶⁰, New Error.: 6.9936306411722450425 × 10⁻⁷²

$$\frac{d^{10}}{dx I^{10}} u(xI) = \frac{1}{\Delta x I^{10}} (- (36000 + 37800 \text{ I}) u_{il+41} - (187560 + 307080 \text{ I}) u_{il+1+41} - (233028 + 657504 \text{ I}) u_{il+2+41} - (44640 + 263520 \text{ I}) u_{il+3+41} - 28800 \text{ I} u_{il+4+41} - (289800 + 437400 \text{ I}) u_{il+31} + (148320 + 331560 \text{ I}) u_{il+1+31} + (1094760 + 6645240 \text{ I}) u_{il+2+31} + 372600 \text{ I} u_{il+3+31} + (44640 - 263520 \text{ I}) u_{il+4+31} - (585180 + 1360800 \text{ I}) u_{il+21} + (2032056 + 9614808 \text{ I}) u_{il+1+21} - 26418960 \text{ I} u_{il+2+21} + (-1094760 + 6645240 \text{ I}) u_{il+3+21} + (233028 - 657504 \text{ I}) u_{il+4+21} - (166320 + 801360 \text{ I}) u_{il+1} + 749880 \text{ I} u_{il+1+1} + (-2032056 + 9614808 \text{ I}) u_{il+2+1} + (-148320 + 331560 \text{ I}) u_{il+3+1} + (187560 - 307080 \text{ I}) u_{il+4+1} - 127008 \text{ I} u_{il} + (166320 - 801360 \text{ I}) u_{il+1} + (585180 - 1360800 \text{ I}) u_{il+2} + (289800 - 437400 \text{ I}) u_{il+3} + (36000 - 37800 \text{ I}) u_{il+4}), O(\Delta x I^4), \text{ Quadrant } I$$

Error order.: 4, Error.: 1.3870420913874204716 × 10⁻¹¹, New Error.: 1.3848246183531037867 × 10⁻²³
Error order.: 4, Error.: 1.3848246183531037867 × 10⁻²³, New Error.: 1.3848224026553489118 × 10⁻³⁵
Error order.: 4, Error.: 1.3848224026553489118 × 10⁻³⁵, New Error.: 1.3848224004396529312 × 10⁻⁴⁷
Error order.: 4, Error.: 1.3848224004396529312 × 10⁻⁴⁷, New Error.: 1.3848224004374372353 × 10⁻⁵⁹
Error order.: 4, Error.: 1.3848224004374372353 × 10⁻⁵⁹, New Error.: 1.3848224004374350196 × 10⁻⁷¹

$$\frac{\partial^{10}}{\partial x I^5 \partial x 2^5} u(xI, x2) = \frac{1}{\Delta x I^5 \Delta x 2^5} (- (36000 + 37800 \text{ I}) u_{il+21, i2+21} - (93780 + 153540 \text{ I}) u_{il+21, i2+1+21} - (14400 + 36000 \text{ I}) u_{il+21, i2+2+21} - (144900 + 218700 \text{ I}) u_{il+21, i2+1} + (403200 + 1008000 \text{ I}) u_{il+21, i2+1+1} - (37980 + 175860 \text{ I}) u_{il+21, i2+2+1} - (30240 + 75600 \text{ I}) u_{il+21, i2} - (45900 + 258300 \text{ I}) u_{il+21, i2+1} - 52200 \text{ I} u_{il+21, i2+2} - (93780 + 153540 \text{ I}) u_{il+1+21, i2+21} - (204228 + 585504 \text{ I}) u_{il+1+21, i2+1+21} - (22320 + 131760 \text{ I}) u_{il+1+21, i2+2+21} - (329040 + 842220 \text{ I}) u_{il+1+21, i2+1} + (624960 + 3689280 \text{ I}) u_{il+1+21, i2+1+1} - 620100 \text{ I} u_{il+1+21, i2+2+1} - (46872 + 276696 \text{ I}) u_{il+1+21, i2} + (33300 - 903600 \text{ I}) u_{il+1+21, i2+1} + (37980 - 175860 \text{ I}) u_{il+1+21, i2+2} - (14400 + 36000 \text{ I}) u_{il+2+21, i2+21} - (22320 + 131760 \text{ I}) u_{il+2+21, i2+1+21} - 28800 \text{ I} u_{il+2+21, i2+2+21} - (39600 + 190800 \text{ I}) u_{il+2+21, i2+1} + 806400 \text{ I} u_{il+2+21, i2+1+1} + (22320 - 131760 \text{ I}) u_{il+2+21, i2+2+1} - 60480 \text{ I} u_{il+2+21, i2} + (39600 - 190800 \text{ I}) u_{il+2+21, i2+1} + (14400 - 36000 \text{ I}) u_{il+2+21, i2+2} - (144900 + 218700 \text{ I}) u_{il+1, i2+21} - (329040 + 842220 \text{ I}) u_{il+1, i2+1+21} - (39600 + 190800 \text{ I}) u_{il+1, i2+2+21} - (524700 + 1209600 \text{ I}) u_{il+1, i2+1} + (1108800 + 5342400 \text{ I}) u_{il+1, i2+1+1} - (33300 + 903600 \text{ I}) u_{il+1, i2+2+1} - (83160 + 400680 \text{ I}) u_{il+1, i2} - 1318500 \text{ I} u_{il+1, i2+1} + (45900 - 258300 \text{ I}) u_{il+1, i2+2} + (403200 + 1008000 \text{ I}) u_{il+1+1, i2+21} + (624960 + 3689280 \text{ I}) u_{il+1+1, i2+1+21} + 806400 \text{ I} u_{il+1+1, i2+2+21} + (1108800 + 5342400 \text{ I}) u_{il+1+1, i2+1} - 22579200 \text{ I} u_{il+1+1, i2+1+1} + (-624960 + 3689280 \text{ I}) u_{il+1+1, i2+2+1} + 1693440 \text{ I} u_{il+1+1, i2} + (-1108800 + 5342400 \text{ I}) u_{il+1+1, i2+1} + (-403200 + 1008000 \text{ I}) u_{il+1+1, i2+2} - (37980 + 175860 \text{ I}) u_{il+2+1, i2+21} - 620100 \text{ I} u_{il+2+1, i2+1+21} + (22320 - 131760 \text{ I}) u_{il+2+1, i2+2+21} - (33300 + 903600 \text{ I}) u_{il+2+1, i2+1} + (-624960 + 3689280 \text{ I}) u_{il+2+1, i2+1+1} + (204228 - 585504 \text{ I}) u_{il+2+1, i2+2+1} + (46872 - 276696 \text{ I}) u_{il+2+1, i2} + (329040 - 842220 \text{ I}) u_{il+2+1, i2+1} + (93780 - 153540 \text{ I}) u_{il+2+1, i2+2} - (30240 + 75600 \text{ I}) u_{il, i2+21} - (46872 + 276696 \text{ I}) u_{il, i2+1+21} - 60480 \text{ I} u_{il, i2+2+21} - (83160 + 400680 \text{ I}) u_{il, i2+1} + 1693440 \text{ I} u_{il, i2+1+1} + (46872 - 276696 \text{ I}) u_{il, i2+2+1} - 127008 \text{ I} u_{il, i2} + (83160 - 400680 \text{ I}) u_{il, i2+1} + (30240 - 75600 \text{ I}) u_{il, i2+2} - (45900 + 258300 \text{ I}) u_{il+1, i2+21} + (33300 - 903600 \text{ I}) u_{il+1, i2+1+21} + (39600 - 190800 \text{ I}) u_{il+1, i2+2+21} - 1318500 \text{ I} u_{il+1, i2+1} + (-1108800 + 5342400 \text{ I}) u_{il+1, i2+1+1} + (329040 - 842220 \text{ I}) u_{il+1, i2+2+1} + (83160 - 400680 \text{ I}) u_{il+1, i2} + (524700 - 1209600 \text{ I}) u_{il+1, i2+1} + (144900 - 218700 \text{ I}) u_{il+1, i2+2} - 52200 \text{ I} u_{il+2, i2+21} + (37980 - 175860 \text{ I}) u_{il+2, i2+1+21} + (14400 - 36000 \text{ I}) u_{il+2, i2+2+21} + (45900 - 258300 \text{ I}) u_{il+2, i2+1} + (-403200 + 1008000 \text{ I}) u_{il+2, i2+1+1} + (93780 - 153540 \text{ I}) u_{il+2, i2+2+1} + (30240 - 75600 \text{ I}) u_{il+2, i2} + (144900 - 218700 \text{ I}) u_{il+2, i2+1} + (36000 - 37800 \text{ I}) u_{il+2, i2+2}), O(\Delta x I^4 \Delta x 2^4), \text{ Quadrant } I$$

Error order.: 4, Error.: 1.1142552834284725416 × 10⁻¹⁰, New Error.: 1.1117337021096263363 × 10⁻²²
Error order.: 4, Error.: 1.1117337021096263363 × 10⁻²², New Error.: 1.1117311833865505478 × 10⁻³⁴
Error order.: 4, Error.: 1.1117311833865505478 × 10⁻³⁴, New Error.: 1.1117311808678303281 × 10⁻⁴⁶
Error order.: 4, Error.: 1.1117311808678303281 × 10⁻⁴⁶, New Error.: 1.1117311808653116079 × 10⁻⁵⁸
Error order.: 4, Error.: 1.1117311808653116079 × 10⁻⁵⁸, New Error.: 1.1117311808653090891 × 10⁻⁷⁰

$$\frac{d^{15}}{dx I^{15}} u(xI) = \frac{1}{\Delta x I^{15}} ((-11178000 + 4158000 \text{ I}) u_{il+61} + (-122050800 + 17625600 \text{ I}) u_{il+1+61} - (450577080 + 30070440 \text{ I}) u_{il+2+61} - (647091936 + 178902648 \text{ I}) u_{il+3+61} - (302447520 + 145035360 \text{ I}) u_{il+4+61} - (55468800 + 39398400 \text{ I}) u_{il+5+61} - (3456000 + 3456000 \text{ I}) u_{il+6+61} + (-176904000 + 32238000 \text{ I}) u_{il+51} - (494974800 + 22064400 \text{ I}) u_{il+1+51} + (2530890360 + 609644880 \text{ I}) u_{il+2+51} + (7351929360 + 3574374480 \text{ I}) u_{il+3+51} + (1675031400 + 1204308000 \text{ I}) u_{il+4+51} - (156168000 + 156168000 \text{ I}) u_{il+5+51} - (39398400 + 55468800 \text{ I}) u_{il+6+51} + (-959509800 + 2608200 \text{ I}) u_{il+41} + (3733626960 + 712466280 \text{ I}) u_{il+1+41} + (5780157408 + 2691874944 \text{ I}) u_{il+2+41} - (40451283360 + 29165951880 \text{ I}) u_{il+3+41} + (2411687520 + 2411687520 \text{ I}) u_{il+4+41} + (1204308000 + 1675031400 \text{ I}) u_{il+5+41} - (145035360 + 302447520 \text{ I}) u_{il+6+41} - (2041540200 + 369921600 \text{ I}) u_{il+31} + (16183223280 + 6330331440 \text{ I}) u_{il+1+31} - (61088823000 + 39613173120 \text{ I}) u_{il+2+31} + (110931076800 + 110931076800 \text{ I}) u_{il+3+31} - (29165951880 + 40451283360 \text{ I}) u_{il+4+31} + (3574374480 + 7351929360 \text{ I}) u_{il+5+31} - (178902648 + 647091936 \text{ I}) u_{il+6+31} - (1391145840 + 552076560 \text{ I}) u_{il+21} + (5252366592 + 3414342456 \text{ I}) u_{il+1+21} + (5376417120 + 5376417120 \text{ I}) u_{il+2+21} - (39613173120 + 61088823000 \text{ I}) u_{il+3+21} + (2691874944 + 5780157408 \text{ I}) u_{il+4+21} + (609644880 + 2530890360 \text{ I}) u_{il+5+21} - (30070440 + 450577080 \text{ I}) u_{il+6+21} - (365783040 + 240045120 \text{ I}) u_{il+1} - (713331360 + 713331360 \text{ I}) u_{il+1+1} + (3414342456 + 5252366592 \text{ I}) u_{il+2+1} + (6330331440 + 16183223280 \text{ I}) u_{il+3+1} + (712466280 + 3733626960 \text{ I}) u_{il+4+1} - (22064400 + 494974800 \text{ I}) u_{il+5+1} + (17625600 - 122050800 \text{ I}) u_{il+6+1} - (32006016 + 32006016 \text{ I}) u_{il} - (240045120 + 365783040 \text{ I}) u_{il+1} - (552076560 + 1391145840 \text{ I}) u_{il+2}$$

$$\frac{d^6}{dxI^6} u(xI) = \frac{(126 + 486 I) u_{il+2+1} + (216 + 1764 I) u_{il+1+2+1} + 396 I u_{il+2+2+1} + (288 + 2268 I) u_{il+1} - 10080 I u_{il+1+1} + (-216 + 1764 I) u_{il+2+1} + 648 I u_{il} + (-288 + 2268 I) u_{il+1} + (-126 + 486 I) u_{il+2}}{\Delta x I^6}, O(\Delta x I^3), \text{ Quadrant I}$$

Error order:, 3, *Error:*, 9.9646354689187115399 × 10⁻⁹, *New Error:*, 9.9497266903631048510 × 10⁻¹⁸
Error order:, 3, *Error:*, 9.9497266903631048510 × 10⁻¹⁸, *New Error:*, 9.9497117927544502542 × 10⁻²⁷
Error order:, 3, *Error:*, 9.9497117927544502542 × 10⁻²⁷, *New Error:*, 9.9497117778568527638 × 10⁻³⁶
Error order:, 3, *Error:*, 9.9497117778568527638 × 10⁻³⁶, *New Error:*, 9.9497117778419551663 × 10⁻⁴⁵
Error order:, 3, *Error:*, 9.9497117778419551663 × 10⁻⁴⁵, *New Error:*, 9.9497117778419402687 × 10⁻⁵⁴

$$\frac{d^{12}}{dxI^{12}} u(xI) = \frac{1}{\Delta x I^{12}} ((-220320 + 122472 I) u_{il+4+1} + (-1660176 + 654480 I) u_{il+1+4+1} + (-3449952 + 861840 I) u_{il+2+4+1} + (-1397088 + 171072 I) u_{il+3+4+1} - 156816 u_{il+4+4+1} + (-2131920 + 851472 I) u_{il+3+1} + (1920672 - 544320 I) u_{il+1+3+1} + (31996944 - 3891888 I) u_{il+2+3+1} + 1666656 u_{il+3+3+1}$$

$$- (1397088 + 171072 I) u_{il+4+3+1} + (-5690736 + 1469664 I) u_{il+2+1} + (41159664 - 5234544 I) u_{il+1+2+1} - 118875600 u_{il+2+2+1} + (31996944 + 3891888 I) u_{il+3+2+1} - (3449952 + 861840 I) u_{il+4+2+1} + (-2939328 + 373248 I) u_{il+1} + 2610144 u_{il+1+1} + (41159664 + 5234544 I) u_{il+2+1} + (1920672$$

$$+ 544320 I) u_{il+3+1} - (1660176 + 654480 I) u_{il+4+1} - 419904 u_{il} - (2939328 + 373248 I) u_{il+1} - (5690736 + 1469664 I) u_{il+2} - (2131920 + 851472 I) u_{il+3} - (220320 + 122472 I) u_{il+4}), O(\Delta x I^3), \text{ Quadrant I}$$

Error order:, 3, *Error:*, 1.9691784830868957511 × 10⁻⁸, *New Error:*, 1.9662322619243776795 × 10⁻¹⁷
Error order:, 3, *Error:*, 1.9662322619243776795 × 10⁻¹⁷, *New Error:*, 1.9662293179079565514 × 10⁻²⁶
Error order:, 3, *Error:*, 1.9662293179079565514 × 10⁻²⁶, *New Error:*, 1.9662293149639423365 × 10⁻³⁵
Error order:, 3, *Error:*, 1.9662293149639423365 × 10⁻³⁵, *New Error:*, 1.9662293149609983223 × 10⁻⁴⁴
Error order:, 3, *Error:*, 1.9662293149609983223 × 10⁻⁴⁴, *New Error:*, 1.9662293149609953783 × 10⁻⁵³

$$\frac{\partial^{12}}{\partial x I^6 \partial x 2^6} u(xI, x2) = \frac{1}{\Delta x I^6 \Delta x 2^6} ((-220320 + 122472 I) u_{il+2+1, i2+2+1} + (-830088 + 327240 I) u_{il+2+1, i2+1+2+1} + (-192456 + 49896 I) u_{il+2+1, i2+2+2+1} + (-1065960 + 425736 I) u_{il+2+1, i2+1} + (4898880 - 1270080 I) u_{il+2+1, i2+1+1} + (-884520 + 117288 I) u_{il+2+1, i2+2+1} + (-314928 + 81648 I) u_{il+2+1, i2} + (-1138536$$

$$+ 145800 I) u_{il+2+1, i2+1} - 252072 u_{il+2+1, i2+2} + (-830088 + 327240 I) u_{il+1+2+1, i2+2+1} + (-3065040 + 762048 I) u_{il+1+2+1, i2+1+2+1} + (-698544 + 85536 I) u_{il+1+2+1, i2+2+2+1} + (-3938544 + 997920 I) u_{il+1+2+1, i2+1} + (17781120 - 2177280 I) u_{il+1+2+1, i2+1+1} - 3158352 u_{il+1+2+1, i2+2+1} + (-1143072$$

$$+ 139968 I) u_{il+1+2+1, i2} - (4062960 + 18144 I) u_{il+1+2+1, i2+1} - (884520 + 117288 I) u_{il+1+2+1, i2+2} + (-192456 + 49896 I) u_{il+2+2+1, i2+2+1} + (-698544 + 85536 I) u_{il+2+2+1, i2+1+2+1} - 156816 u_{il+2+2+1, i2+2+2+1} + (-898128 + 114048 I) u_{il+2+2+1, i2+1} + 3991680 u_{il+2+2+1, i2+1+1} - (698544 + 85536 I) u_{il+2+2+1, i2+2+1}$$

$$- 256608 u_{il+2+2+1, i2} - (898128 + 114048 I) u_{il+2+2+1, i2+1} - (192456 + 49896 I) u_{il+2+2+1, i2+2} + (-1065960 + 425736 I) u_{il+1, i2+2+1} + (-3938544 + 997920 I) u_{il+1, i2+1+2+1} + (-898128 + 114048 I) u_{il+1, i2+2+2+1} + (-5060880 + 1306368 I) u_{il+1, i2+1} + (22861440 - 2903040 I) u_{il+1, i2+1+1} + (-4062960$$

$$+ 18144 I) u_{il+1, i2+2+1} + (-1469664 + 186624 I) u_{il+1, i2} - 5226768 u_{il+1, i2+1} - (1138536 + 145800 I) u_{il+1, i2+2} + (4898880 - 1270080 I) u_{il+1+1, i2+2+1} + (17781120 - 2177280 I) u_{il+1+1, i2+1+2+1} + 3991680 u_{il+1+1, i2+2+2+1} + (22861440 - 2903040 I) u_{il+1+1, i2+1} - 101606400 u_{il+1+1, i2+1+1} + (17781120$$

$$+ 2177280 I) u_{il+1+1, i2+2+1} + 6531840 u_{il+1+1, i2} + (22861440 + 2903040 I) u_{il+1+1, i2+1} + (4898880 + 1270080 I) u_{il+1+1, i2+2} + (-884520 + 117288 I) u_{il+2+1, i2+2+1} - 3158352 u_{il+2+1, i2+1+2+1} - (698544 + 85536 I) u_{il+2+1, i2+2+2+1} + (-4062960 + 18144 I) u_{il+2+1, i2+1} + (17781120 + 2177280 I) u_{il+2+1, i2+1+1}$$

$$- (3065040 + 762048 I) u_{il+2+1, i2+2+1} - (1143072 + 139968 I) u_{il+2+1, i2} - (3938544 + 997920 I) u_{il+2+1, i2+1} - (830088 + 327240 I) u_{il+2+1, i2+2} + (-314928 + 81648 I) u_{il, i2+2+1} + (-1143072 + 139968 I) u_{il, i2+1+2+1} - 256608 u_{il, i2+2+2+1} + (-1469664 + 186624 I) u_{il, i2+1} + 6531840 u_{il, i2+1+1} - (1143072$$

$$+ 139968 I) u_{il, i2+2+1} - 419904 u_{il, i2} - (1469664 + 186624 I) u_{il, i2+1} - (314928 + 81648 I) u_{il, i2+2} + (-1138536 + 145800 I) u_{il+1, i2+2+1} - (4062960 + 18144 I) u_{il+1, i2+1+2+1} - (898128 + 114048 I) u_{il+1, i2+2+2+1} - 5226768 u_{il+1, i2+1} + (22861440 + 2903040 I) u_{il+1, i2+1+1} - (3938544 + 997920 I) u_{il+1, i2+2+1}$$

$$- (1469664 + 186624 I) u_{il+1, i2} - (5060880 + 1306368 I) u_{il+1, i2+1} - (1065960 + 425736 I) u_{il+1, i2+2} - 252072 u_{il+2, i2+2+1} - (884520 + 117288 I) u_{il+2, i2+1+2+1} - (192456 + 49896 I) u_{il+2, i2+2+2+1} - (1138536 + 145800 I) u_{il+2, i2+1} + (4898880 + 1270080 I) u_{il+2, i2+1+1} - (830088 + 327240 I) u_{il+2, i2+2+1}$$

$$- (314928 + 81648 I) u_{il+2, i2} - (1065960 + 425736 I) u_{il+2, i2+1} - (220320 + 122472 I) u_{il+2, i2+2}), O(\Delta x I^3 \Delta x 2^3), \text{ Quadrant I}$$

Error order:, 3, *Error:*, 1.1415063567287454251 × 10⁻⁷, *New Error:*, 1.1391428163135938039 × 10⁻¹⁶
Error order:, 3, *Error:*, 1.1391428163135938039 × 10⁻¹⁶, *New Error:*, 1.1391404552219270752 × 10⁻²⁵
Error order:, 3, *Error:*, 1.1391404552219270752 × 10⁻²⁵, *New Error:*, 1.1391404528608378578 × 10⁻³⁴
Error order:, 3, *Error:*, 1.1391404528608378578 × 10⁻³⁴, *New Error:*, 1.1391404528584767686 × 10⁻⁴³
Error order:, 3, *Error:*, 1.1391404528584767686 × 10⁻⁴³, *New Error:*, 1.1391404528584744075 × 10⁻⁵²

"--- Derivative Order: 7 - xI=1 ---"

$$\begin{bmatrix} 2I & 1 + 2I & 2 + 2I \\ I & 1 + I & 2 + I \\ 0 & 1 & 2 \end{bmatrix}$$

$$\begin{bmatrix} -567 - 441 I & -2016 - 1764 I & -441 - 441 I \\ -2268 - 2016 I & 10080 + 10080 I & -1764 - 2016 I \\ -567 - 567 I & -2016 - 2268 I & -441 - 567 I \end{bmatrix}$$

$$\frac{d^7}{dxI^7} u(xI) = \frac{-(567 + 441 I) u_{il+2+1} - (2016 + 1764 I) u_{il+1+2+1} - (441 + 441 I) u_{il+2+2+1} - (2268 + 2016 I) u_{il+1} + (10080 + 10080 I) u_{il+1+1} - (1764 + 2016 I) u_{il+2+1} - (567 + 567 I) u_{il} - (2016 + 2268 I) u_{il+1} - (441 + 567 I) u_{il+2}}{\Delta x I^7}, O(\Delta x I^2), \text{ Quadrant I}$$

Error order:, 2, *Error:*, 0.000010567315282530862313, *New Error:*, 1.0553277046386361650 × 10⁻¹¹
Error order:, 2, *Error:*, 1.0553277046386361650 × 10⁻¹¹, *New Error:*, 1.0553263017488474885 × 10⁻¹⁷
Error order:, 2, *Error:*, 1.0553263017488474885 × 10⁻¹⁷, *New Error:*, 1.0553263003459586332 × 10⁻²³
Error order:, 2, *Error:*, 1.0553263003459586332 × 10⁻²³, *New Error:*, 1.0553263003445557443 × 10⁻²⁹
Error order:, 2, *Error:*, 1.0553263003445557443 × 10⁻²⁹, *New Error:*, 1.0553263003445543415 × 10⁻³⁵

$$\frac{d^{14}}{dxI^{14}} u(xI) = \frac{1}{\Delta x I^{14}} ((127008 + 500094 I) u_{il+4+1} + (730296 + 3778488 I) u_{il+1+4+1} + (1063692 + 8001504 I) u_{il+2+4+1} + (222264 + 3333960 I) u_{il+3+4+1} + 388962 I u_{il+4+4+1} + (793800 + 4286520 I) u_{il+3+1} - (508032 + 4191264 I) u_{il+1+3+1} - (4635792 + 68584320 I) u_{il+2+3+1} - 3429216 I u_{il+3+3+1} + (-222264$$

$$+ 3333960 I) u_{il+4+3+1} + (1222452 + 10287648 I) u_{il+2+1} - (4508784 + 77728896 I) u_{il+1+2+1} + 237758976 I u_{il+2+2+1} + (4635792 - 68584320 I) u_{il+3+2+1} + (-1063692 + 8001504 I) u_{il+4+2+1} + (285768 + 4858056 I) u_{il+1} - 4445280 I u_{il+1+1} + (4508784 - 77728896 I) u_{il+2+1} + (508032 - 4191264 I) u_{il+3+1}$$

$$+ (-730296 + 3778488 I) u_{il+4+1} + 642978 I u_{il} + (-285768 + 4858056 I) u_{il+1} + (-1222452 + 10287648 I) u_{il+2} + (-793800 + 4286520 I) u_{il+3} + (-127008 + 500094 I) u_{il+4}), O(\Delta x I^2), \text{ Quadrant I}$$

Error order:, 2, *Error:*, 0.000020841098739371834808, *New Error:*, 2.0813412156535171424 × 10⁻¹¹
Error order:, 2, *Error:*, 2.0813412156535171424 × 10⁻¹¹, *New Error:*, 2.0813384488424826519 × 10⁻¹⁷
Error order:, 2, *Error:*, 2.0813384488424826519 × 10⁻¹⁷, *New Error:*, 2.0813384460756734583 × 10⁻²³

Error order:., 2, Error:., 2.0813384460756734583 × 10⁻²³, New Error:., 2.0813384460729066491 × 10⁻²⁹

Error order:., 2, Error:., 2.0813384460729066491 × 10⁻²⁹, New Error:., 2.0813384460729038823 × 10⁻³⁵

$$\frac{\partial^{14}}{\partial x I^7 \partial x^2} u(xI, x2) = \frac{1}{\Delta x I^7 \Delta x^2} ((127008 + 500094 I) u_{iI+2I, i2+2I} + (365148 + 1889244 I) u_{iI+2I, i2+1+2I} + (55566 + 444528 I) u_{iI+2I, i2+2+2I} + (396900 + 2143260 I) u_{iI+2I, i2+1} - (1270080 + 10160640 I) u_{iI+2I, i2+1+1} + (111132 + 1920996 I) u_{iI+2I, i2+2+1} + (71442 + 571536 I) u_{iI+2I, i2} + (142884 + 2175012 I) u_{iI+2I, i2+1} + 515970 I u_{iI+2I, i2+2} + (365148 + 1889244 I) u_{iI+1+2I, i2+2I} + (952560 + 7112448 I) u_{iI+1+2I, i2+1+2I} + (111132 + 1666980 I) u_{iI+1+2I, i2+2+2I} + (1016064 + 8065008 I) u_{iI+1+2I, i2+1} - (2540160 + 38102400 I) u_{iI+1+2I, i2+1+1} + 7175952 I u_{iI+1+2I, i2+2+1} + (142884 + 2143260 I) u_{iI+1+2I, i2} + (63504 + 8128512 I) u_{iI+1+2I, i2+1} + (-111132 + 1920996 I) u_{iI+1+2I, i2+2} + (55566 + 444528 I) u_{iI+2+2I, i2+2I} + (111132 + 1666980 I) u_{iI+2+2I, i2+1+2I} + 388962 I u_{iI+2+2I, i2+2+2I} + (111132 + 1889244 I) u_{iI+2+2I, i2+1} - 8890560 I u_{iI+2+2I, i2+1+1} + (-111132 + 1666980 I) u_{iI+2+2I, i2+2+1} + 500094 I u_{iI+2+2I, i2} + (-111132 + 1889244 I) u_{iI+2+2I, i2+1} + (-55566 + 444528 I) u_{iI+2+2I, i2+2} + (396900 + 2143260 I) u_{iI+1, i2+2I} + (1016064 + 8065008 I) u_{iI+1, i2+1+2I} + (111132 + 1889244 I) u_{iI+1, i2+2+2I} + (1079568 + 9144576 I) u_{iI+1, i2+1} - (2540160 + 43182720 I) u_{iI+1, i2+1+1} + (-63504 + 8128512 I) u_{iI+1, i2+2+1} + (142884 + 2429028 I) u_{iI+1, i2} + 9208080 I u_{iI+1, i2+1} + (-142884 + 2175012 I) u_{iI+1, i2+2} - (1270080 + 10160640 I) u_{iI+1+1, i2+2I} - (2540160 + 38102400 I) u_{iI+1+1, i2+1+2I} - 8890560 I u_{iI+1+1, i2+2+2I} - (2540160 + 43182720 I) u_{iI+1+1, i2+1} + 203212800 I u_{iI+1+1, i2+1+1} + (2540160 - 38102400 I) u_{iI+1+1, i2+2+1} - 11430720 I u_{iI+1+1, i2} + (2540160 - 43182720 I) u_{iI+1+1, i2+1} + (1270080 - 10160640 I) u_{iI+1+1, i2+2} + (111132 + 1920996 I) u_{iI+2+1, i2+2I} + 7175952 I u_{iI+2+1, i2+1+2I} + (-111132 + 1666980 I) u_{iI+2+1, i2+2+2I} + (-63504 + 8128512 I) u_{iI+2+1, i2+1} + (2540160 - 38102400 I) u_{iI+2+1, i2+1+1} + (-952560 + 7112448 I) u_{iI+2+1, i2+2+1} + (-142884 + 2143260 I) u_{iI+2+1, i2} + (-1016064 + 8065008 I) u_{iI+2+1, i2+1} + (-365148 + 1889244 I) u_{iI+2+1, i2+2} + (71442 + 571536 I) u_{iI, i2+2I} + (142884 + 2143260 I) u_{iI, i2+1+2I} + 500094 I u_{iI, i2+2+2I} + (142884 + 2429028 I) u_{iI, i2+1} - 11430720 I u_{iI, i2+1+1} + (-142884 + 2143260 I) u_{iI, i2+2+1} + 642978 I u_{iI, i2} + (-142884 + 2429028 I) u_{iI, i2+1} + (-71442 + 571536 I) u_{iI, i2+2} + (142884 + 2175012 I) u_{iI+1, i2+2I} + (63504 + 8128512 I) u_{iI+1, i2+1+2I} + (-111132 + 1889244 I) u_{iI+1, i2+2+2I} + 9208080 I u_{iI+1, i2+1} + (2540160 - 43182720 I) u_{iI+1, i2+1+1} + (-1016064 + 8065008 I) u_{iI+1, i2+2+1} + (-142884 + 2429028 I) u_{iI+1, i2} + (-1079568 + 9144576 I) u_{iI+1, i2+1} + (-396900 + 2143260 I) u_{iI+1, i2+2} + 515970 I u_{iI+2, i2+2I} + (-111132 + 1920996 I) u_{iI+2, i2+1+2I} + (-55566 + 444528 I) u_{iI+2, i2+2+2I} + (-142884 + 2175012 I) u_{iI+2, i2+1} + (1270080 - 10160640 I) u_{iI+2, i2+1+1} + (-365148 + 1889244 I) u_{iI+2, i2+2+1} + (-71442 + 571536 I) u_{iI+2, i2} + (-396900 + 2143260 I) u_{iI+2, i2+1} + (-127008 + 500094 I) u_{iI+2, i2+2}), O(\Delta x I^2 \Delta x^2), Quadrant I$$

Error order:., 2, Error:., 0.000089730010696006477989, New Error:., 8.9569730744761001328 × 10⁻¹¹

Error order:., 2, Error:., 8.9569730744761001328 × 10⁻¹¹, New Error:., 8.9569570608569621242 × 10⁻¹⁷

Error order:., 2, Error:., 8.9569570608569621242 × 10⁻¹⁷, New Error:., 8.9569570448433573154 × 10⁻²³

Error order:., 2, Error:., 8.9569570448433573154 × 10⁻²³, New Error:., 8.9569570448273437106 × 10⁻²⁹

Error order:., 2, Error:., 8.9569570448273437106 × 10⁻²⁹, New Error:., 8.9569570448273276970 × 10⁻³⁵

"--- Derivative Order: 8 - xI=1 ---"

$$\begin{bmatrix} 2I & 1+2I & 2+2I \\ I & 1+I & 2+I \\ 0 & 1 & 2 \end{bmatrix}$$

$$\begin{bmatrix} 504 & 2016 & 504 \\ 2016 & -10080 & 2016 \\ 504 & 2016 & 504 \end{bmatrix}$$

$$\frac{d^8}{dx I^8} u(xI) = \frac{504 (u_{iI+2I} + 4 u_{iI+1+2I} + u_{iI+2+2I} + 4 u_{iI+1} - 20 u_{iI+1+1} + 4 u_{iI+2+1} + u_{iI} + 4 u_{iI+1} + u_{iI+2})}{\Delta x I^8}, O(\Delta x I), Quadrant I$$

Error order:., 1, Error:., 0.0074697349399279692867, New Error:., 7.4622912807742267245 × 10⁻⁶

Error order:., 1, Error:., 7.4622912807742267245 × 10⁻⁶, New Error:., 7.4622838408288442494 × 10⁻⁹

Error order:., 1, Error:., 7.4622838408288442494 × 10⁻⁹, New Error:., 7.4622838333889025794 × 10⁻¹²

Error order:., 1, Error:., 7.4622838333889025794 × 10⁻¹², New Error:., 7.4622838333814626378 × 10⁻¹⁵

Error order:., 1, Error:., 7.4622838333814626378 × 10⁻¹⁵, New Error:., 7.4622838333814551978 × 10⁻¹⁸

$$\frac{d^{16}}{dx I^{16}} u(xI) = \frac{1}{\Delta x I^{16}} (254016 (u_{iI+4I} + 8 u_{iI+1+4I} + 18 u_{iI+2+4I} + 8 u_{iI+3+4I} + u_{iI+4+4I} + 8 u_{iI+3I} - 8 u_{iI+1+3I} - 144 u_{iI+2+3I} - 8 u_{iI+3+3I} + 8 u_{iI+4+3I} + 18 u_{iI+2I} - 144 u_{iI+1+2I} + 468 u_{iI+2+2I} - 144 u_{iI+3+2I} + 18 u_{iI+4+2I} + 8 u_{iI+1} - 8 u_{iI+1+1} - 144 u_{iI+2+1} - 8 u_{iI+3+1} + 8 u_{iI+4+1} + u_{iI} + 8 u_{iI+1} + 18 u_{iI+2} + 8 u_{iI+3} + u_{iI+4})), O(\Delta x I), Quadrant I$$

Error order:., 1, Error:., 0.014717255935389223581, New Error:., 0.000014687938789892694055

Error order:., 1, Error:., 0.000014687938789892694055, New Error:., 1.4687909501996043768 × 10⁻⁸

Error order:., 1, Error:., 1.4687909501996043768 × 10⁻⁸, New Error:., 1.4687909472708176347 × 10⁻¹¹

Error order:., 1, Error:., 1.4687909472708176347 × 10⁻¹¹, New Error:., 1.4687909472678888480 × 10⁻¹⁴

Error order:., 1, Error:., 1.4687909472678888480 × 10⁻¹⁴, New Error:., 1.4687909472678859192 × 10⁻¹⁷

$$\frac{\partial^{16}}{\partial x I^8 \partial x^2} u(xI, x2) = \frac{1}{\Delta x I^8 \Delta x^2} (254016 (u_{iI+2I, i2+2I} + 4 u_{iI+2I, i2+1+2I} + u_{iI+2I, i2+2+2I} + 4 u_{iI+2I, i2+1} - 20 u_{iI+2I, i2+1+1} + 4 u_{iI+2I, i2+2+1} + u_{iI+2I, i2} + 4 u_{iI+2I, i2+1} + u_{iI+2I, i2+2} + 4 u_{iI+1+2I, i2+2I} + 16 u_{iI+1+2I, i2+1+2I} + 4 u_{iI+1+2I, i2+2+2I} + 16 u_{iI+1+2I, i2+1} - 80 u_{iI+1+2I, i2+1+1} + 16 u_{iI+1+2I, i2+2+1} + 4 u_{iI+1+2I, i2} + 16 u_{iI+1+2I, i2+1} + 4 u_{iI+1+2I, i2+2} + u_{iI+2+2I, i2+2I} + 4 u_{iI+2+2I, i2+1+2I} + u_{iI+2+2I, i2+2+2I} + 4 u_{iI+2+2I, i2+1} - 20 u_{iI+2+2I, i2+1+1} + 4 u_{iI+2+2I, i2+2+1} + u_{iI+2+2I, i2} + 4 u_{iI+2+2I, i2+1} + u_{iI+2+2I, i2+2} + 4 u_{iI+1, i2+2I} + 16 u_{iI+1, i2+1+2I} + 4 u_{iI+1, i2+2+2I} + 16 u_{iI+1, i2+1} - 80 u_{iI+1, i2+1+1} + 16 u_{iI+1, i2+2+1} + 4 u_{iI+1, i2} + 16 u_{iI+1, i2+1} - 20 u_{iI+1+1, i2+2I} - 80 u_{iI+1+1, i2+1+2I} - 20 u_{iI+1+1, i2+2+2I} - 80 u_{iI+1+1, i2+1} + 400 u_{iI+1+1, i2+1+1} - 80 u_{iI+1+1, i2+2+1} - 20 u_{iI+1+1, i2} - 80 u_{iI+1+1, i2+1} - 20 u_{iI+1+1, i2+2} + 4 u_{iI+2+1, i2+2I} + 16 u_{iI+2+1, i2+1+2I} + 4 u_{iI+2+1, i2+2+2I} + 16 u_{iI+2+1, i2+1} - 80 u_{iI+2+1, i2+1+1} + 16 u_{iI+2+1, i2+2+1} + 4 u_{iI+2+1, i2} + 16 u_{iI+2+1, i2+1} + 4 u_{iI+2+1, i2+2} + u_{iI, i2+2I} + 4 u_{iI, i2+1+2I} + u_{iI, i2+2+2I} + 4 u_{iI, i2+1} - 20 u_{iI, i2+1+1} + 4 u_{iI, i2+2+1} + u_{iI, i2} + 4 u_{iI, i2+1} + u_{iI, i2+2} + 4 u_{iI+1, i2+2I} + 16 u_{iI+1, i2+1+2I} + 4 u_{iI+1, i2+2+2I} + 16 u_{iI+1, i2+1} - 80 u_{iI+1, i2+1+1} + 16 u_{iI+1, i2+2+1} + 4 u_{iI+1, i2} + 16 u_{iI+1, i2+1} + 4 u_{iI+1, i2+2} + u_{iI+2, i2+2I} + 4 u_{iI+2, i2+1+2I} + u_{iI+2, i2+2+2I} + 4 u_{iI+2, i2+1} - 20 u_{iI+2, i2+1+1} + 4 u_{iI+2, i2+2+1} + u_{iI+2, i2} + 4 u_{iI+2, i2+1} + u_{iI+2, i2+2})), O(\Delta x I \Delta x^2), Quadrant I$$

Error order:., 1, Error:., 0.048733084600601705821, New Error:., 0.000048611840394357078100

Error order:., 1, Error:., 0.000048611840394357078100, New Error:., 4.8611719301249993929 × 10⁻⁸

Error order:., 1, Error:., 4.8611719301249993929 × 10⁻⁸, New Error:., 4.8611719180157037819 × 10⁻¹¹

Error order:., 1, Error:., 4.8611719180157037819 × 10⁻¹¹, New Error:., 4.8611719180035944863 × 10⁻¹⁴

Error order:., 1, Error:., 4.8611719180035944863 × 10⁻¹⁴, New Error:., 4.8611719180035823770 × 10⁻¹⁷

"--- Derivative Order: 1 - x1=1 ---"

$$\begin{bmatrix} 3 I & 1 + 3 I & 2 + 3 I & 3 + 3 I \\ 2 I & 1 + 2 I & 2 + 2 I & 3 + 2 I \\ I & 1 + I & 2 + I & 3 + I \\ 0 & 1 & 2 & 3 \end{bmatrix}$$

$$\begin{bmatrix} \frac{1}{3} & -\frac{9}{10} + \frac{9I}{2} & -\frac{198}{65} - \frac{171I}{65} & \frac{1}{6} - \frac{I}{6} \\ \frac{9}{10} - \frac{36I}{5} & -\frac{702}{5} - \frac{351I}{5} & -\frac{351}{4} + \frac{351I}{4} & \frac{171}{65} + \frac{198I}{65} \\ -\frac{72}{5} + \frac{9I}{5} & \frac{351}{2} - \frac{351I}{2} & \frac{351}{5} + \frac{702I}{5} & -\frac{9}{2} + \frac{9I}{10} \\ -\frac{215}{52} + \frac{215I}{52} & -\frac{9}{5} + \frac{72I}{5} & \frac{36}{5} - \frac{9I}{10} & -\frac{I}{3} \end{bmatrix}$$

$$\frac{d}{dxI} u(xI) = \frac{1}{780 \Delta xI} (260 u_{iI+3I} + (-702 + 3510 I) u_{iI+1+3I} - (2376 + 2052 I) u_{iI+2+3I} + (130 - 130 I) u_{iI+3+3I} + (702 - 5616 I) u_{iI+2I} - (109512 + 54756 I) u_{iI+1+2I} + (-68445 + 68445 I) u_{iI+2+2I} + (2052 + 2376 I) u_{iI+3+2I} + (-11232 + 1404 I) u_{iI+1} + (136890 - 136890 I) u_{iI+1+1} + (54756 + 109512 I) u_{iI+2+1} + (-3510 + 702 I) u_{iI+3+1} + (-3225 + 3225 I) u_{iI} + (-1404 + 11232 I) u_{iI+1} + (5616 - 702 I) u_{iI+2} - 260 I u_{iI+3}), O(\Delta xI^{15}), \textit{ Quadrant I}$$

Error order:, 15, *Error:*, 1.6226279692116436406 $\times 10^{-48}$, *New Error:*, 1.6180665719427792883 $\times 10^{-93}$
Error order:, 15, *Error:*, 1.6180665719427792883 $\times 10^{-93}$, *New Error:*, 1.6180620169692529467 $\times 10^{-138}$
Error order:, 15, *Error:*, 1.6180620169692529467 $\times 10^{-138}$, *New Error:*, 1.6180620124142858380 $\times 10^{-183}$
Error order:, 15, *Error:*, 1.6180620124142858380 $\times 10^{-183}$, *New Error:*, 1.6180620124097308709 $\times 10^{-228}$
Error order:, 15, *Error:*, 1.6180620124097308709 $\times 10^{-228}$, *New Error:*, 1.6180620124097263160 $\times 10^{-273}$

$$\frac{d^2}{dxI^2} u(xI) = \frac{1}{304200 \Delta xI^2} (33800 u_{iI+6I} + (-182520 + 912600 I) u_{iI+1+6I} - (6531408 + 2997540 I) u_{iI+2+6I} + (8904272 - 6933056 I) u_{iI+3+6I} + (1082376 + 5423112 I) u_{iI+4+6I} + (-575640 + 42120 I) u_{iI+5+6I} - 16900 I u_{iI+6+6I} + (182520 - 1460160 I) u_{iI+5I} - (9253764 + 7830108 I) u_{iI+1+5I} + (238083300 - 316249596 I) u_{iI+2+5I} + (-44457660 + 66324960 I) u_{iI+3+5I} + (271939356 - 9523332 I) u_{iI+4+5I} + 7939620 I u_{iI+5+5I} + (575640 + 42120 I) u_{iI+6+5I} - (18443646 + 3577392 I) u_{iI+4I} + (-345838896 + 500579352 I) u_{iI+1+4I} + (5261859954 + 7053640542 I) u_{iI+2+4I} + (10226942388 - 3596136804 I) u_{iI+3+4I} - 5478241977 I u_{iI+4+4I} - (271939356 + 9523332 I) u_{iI+5+4I} + (-1082376 + 5423112 I) u_{iI+6+4I} + (-838500 + 64903020 I) u_{iI+3I} + (624817908 - 414269856 I) u_{iI+1+3I} + (-21183209208 + 6386005224 I) u_{iI+2+3I} + 3741342800 I u_{iI+3+3I} - (10226942388 + 3596136804 I) u_{iI+4+3I} + (44457660 + 66324960 I) u_{iI+5+3I} - (8904272 + 6933056 I) u_{iI+6+3I} + (77940954 + 4605822 I) u_{iI+2I} + (-753497316 + 1568923668 I) u_{iI+1+2I} - 21518697330 I u_{iI+2+2I} + (21183209208 + 6386005224 I) u_{iI+3+2I} + (-5261859954 + 7053640542 I) u_{iI+4+2I} - (238083300 + 316249596 I) u_{iI+5+2I} + (6531408 - 2997540 I) u_{iI+6+2I} + (31695300 - 40751100 I) u_{iI+1} + 754811460 I u_{iI+1+1} + (753497316 + 1568923668 I) u_{iI+2+1} - (624817908 + 414269856 I) u_{iI+3+1} + (345838896 + 500579352 I) u_{iI+4+1} + (9253764 - 7830108 I) u_{iI+5+1} + (182520 + 912600 I) u_{iI+6+1} - 10400625 I u_{iI} - (31695300 + 40751100 I) u_{iI+1} + (-77940954 + 4605822 I) u_{iI+2} + (838500 + 64903020 I) u_{iI+3} + (18443646 - 3577392 I) u_{iI+4} - (182520 + 1460160 I) u_{iI+5} - 33800 u_{iI+6}), O(\Delta xI^{15}), \textit{ Quadrant I}$$

Error order:, 15, *Error:*, 3.2387783816599673464 $\times 10^{-48}$, *New Error:*, 3.2296737962929726314 $\times 10^{-93}$
Error order:, 15, *Error:*, 3.2296737962929726314 $\times 10^{-93}$, *New Error:*, 3.2296647045294469993 $\times 10^{-138}$
Error order:, 15, *Error:*, 3.2296647045294469993 $\times 10^{-138}$, *New Error:*, 3.2296646954376962835 $\times 10^{-183}$
Error order:, 15, *Error:*, 3.2296646954376962835 $\times 10^{-183}$, *New Error:*, 3.2296646954286045328 $\times 10^{-228}$
Error order:, 15, *Error:*, 3.2296646954286045328 $\times 10^{-228}$, *New Error:*, 3.2296646954285954410 $\times 10^{-273}$

$$\frac{\partial^2}{\partial xI \partial x2} u(xI, x2) = \frac{1}{304200 \Delta xI \Delta x2} (33800 u_{iI+3I, i2+3I} + (-91260 + 456300 I) u_{iI+3I, i2+1+3I} - (308880 + 266760 I) u_{iI+3I, i2+2+3I} + (16900 - 16900 I) u_{iI+3I, i2+3+3I} + (91260 - 730080 I) u_{iI+3I, i2+2I} - (14236560 + 7118280 I) u_{iI+3I, i2+1+2I} + (-8897850 + 8897850 I) u_{iI+3I, i2+2+2I} + (266760 + 308880 I) u_{iI+3I, i2+3+2I} + (-1460160 + 182520 I) u_{iI+3I, i2+1} + (17795700 - 17795700 I) u_{iI+3I, i2+1+1} + (7118280 + 14236560 I) u_{iI+3I, i2+2+1} + (-456300 + 91260 I) u_{iI+3I, i2+3+1} + (-419250 + 419250 I) u_{iI+3I, i2} + (-182520 + 1460160 I) u_{iI+3I, i2+1} + (730080 - 91260 I) u_{iI+3I, i2+2} - 33800 I u_{iI+3I, i2+3} + (-91260 + 456300 I) u_{iI+1+3I, i2+3I} - (5913648 + 2464020 I) u_{iI+1+3I, i2+1+3I} + (4435236 - 3449628 I) u_{iI+1+3I, i2+2+3I} + (182520 + 273780 I) u_{iI+1+3I, i2+3+3I} + (9609678 + 3203226 I) u_{iI+1+3I, i2+2I} + (134535492 - 172974204 I) u_{iI+1+3I, i2+1+2I} - (96096780 + 144145170 I) u_{iI+1+3I, i2+2+2I} + (-4890132 + 2767284 I) u_{iI+1+3I, i2+3+2I} + (1478412 - 20204964 I) u_{iI+1+3I, i2+1} + (192193560 + 288290340 I) u_{iI+1+3I, i2+1+1} + (-211412916 + 57658068 I) u_{iI+1+3I, i2+2+1} - 6406452 I u_{iI+1+3I, i2+3+1} - (4527900 + 6791850 I) u_{iI+1+3I, i2} - (19219356 + 6406452 I) u_{iI+1+3I, i2+1} + (-739206 + 10102482 I) u_{iI+1+3I, i2+2} + (456300 + 91260 I) u_{iI+1+3I, i2+3} - (308880 + 266760 I) u_{iI+2+3I, i2+3I} + (4435236 - 3449628 I) u_{iI+2+3I, i2+1+3I} + (717336 + 4875552 I) u_{iI+2+3I, i2+2+3I} + (-287820 + 21060 I) u_{iI+2+3I, i2+3+3I} + (-6595992 + 5951556 I) u_{iI+2+3I, i2+2I} + (73920600 + 177409440 I) u_{iI+2+3I, i2+1+2I} + (151537230 - 11088090 I) u_{iI+2+3I, i2+2+2I} - 4928040 I u_{iI+2+3I, i2+3+2I} + (14784120 + 9856080 I) u_{iI+2+3I, i2+1} + (-303074460 + 22176180 I) u_{iI+2+3I, i2+1+1} + (47309184 - 186279912 I) u_{iI+2+3I, i2+2+1} + (4890132 + 2767284 I) u_{iI+2+3I, i2+3+1} + (7140150 - 522450 I) u_{iI+2+3I, i2} + (13191984 - 11903112 I) u_{iI+2+3I, i2+1} - (7392060 + 4928040 I) u_{iI+2+3I, i2+2} + (-266760 + 308880 I) u_{iI+2+3I, i2+3} + (16900 - 16900 I) u_{iI+3+3I, i2+3I} + (182520 + 273780 I) u_{iI+3+3I, i2+1+3I} + (-287820 + 21060 I) u_{iI+3+3I, i2+2+3I} - 16900 I u_{iI+3+3I, i2+3+3I} - (319410 + 410670 I) u_{iI+3+3I, i2+2I} + (-10677420 + 3559140 I) u_{iI+3+3I, i2+1+2I} + 8897850 I u_{iI+3+3I, i2+2+2I} + (287820 + 21060 I) u_{iI+3+3I, i2+3+2I} + (-638820 + 821340 I) u_{iI+3+3I, i2+1} - 17795700 I u_{iI+3+3I, i2+1+1} + (10677420 + 3559140 I) u_{iI+3+3I, i2+2+1} + (-182520 + 273780 I) u_{iI+3+3I, i2+3+1} + 419250 I u_{iI+3+3I, i2} + (638820 + 821340 I) u_{iI+3+3I, i2+1} + (319410 - 410670 I) u_{iI+3+3I, i2+2} - (16900 + 16900 I) u_{iI+3+3I, i2+3} + (91260 - 730080 I) u_{iI+2I, i2+3I} + (9609678 + 3203226 I) u_{iI+2I, i2+1+3I} + (-6595992 + 5951556 I) u_{iI+2I, i2+2+3I} - (319410 + 410670 I) u_{iI+2I, i2+3+3I} - (15523326 + 3942432 I) u_{iI+2I, i2+2I} + (-192193560 + 288290340 I) u_{iI+2I, i2+1+2I} + (168169365 + 216217755 I) u_{iI+2I, i2+2+2I} + (7392060 - 4928040 I) u_{iI+2I, i2+3+2I} + 32032260 I u_{iI+2I, i2+1} - (336338730 + 432435510 I) u_{iI+2I, i2+1+1} + (326729052 - 115316136 I) u_{iI+2I, i2+2+1} + (739206 + 10102482 I) u_{iI+2I, i2+3+1} + (7923825 + 10187775 I) u_{iI+2I, i2} + (31046652 + 7884864 I) u_{iI+2I, i2+1} - 16016130 I u_{iI+2I, i2+2} - (730080 + 91260 I) u_{iI+2I, i2+3} - (14236560 + 7118280 I) u_{iI+1+2I, i2+3I} + (134535492 - 172974204 I) u_{iI+1+2I, i2+1+3I} + (73920600 + 177409440 I) u_{iI+1+2I, i2+2+3I} + (-10677420 + 3559140 I) u_{iI+1+2I, i2+3+3I} + (-192193560 + 288290340 I) u_{iI+1+2I, i2+2I} + (4497329304 + 5996439072 I) u_{iI+1+2I, i2+1+2I} + (5621661630 - 1873887210 I) u_{iI+1+2I, i2+2+2I} - (47309184 + 186279912 I) u_{iI+1+2I, i2+3+2I} + (653458104 + 230632272 I) u_{iI+1+2I, i2+1} + (-11243323260 + 3747774420 I) u_{iI+1+2I, i2+1+1} - 7495548840 I u_{iI+1+2I, i2+2+1} + (211412916 + 57658068 I) u_{iI+1+2I, i2+3+1} + (264882150 - 88294050 I) u_{iI+1+2I, i2} + (384387120 - 576580680 I) u_{iI+1+2I, i2+1} - (326729052 + 115316136 I) u_{iI+1+2I, i2+2} + (-7118280 + 14236560 I) u_{iI+1+2I, i2+3} + (-8897850 + 8897850 I) u_{iI+2+2I, i2+3I} - (96096780 + 144145170 I) u_{iI+2+2I, i2+1+3I} + (151537230 - 11088090 I) u_{iI+2+2I, i2+2+3I} + 8897850 I u_{iI+2+2I, i2+3+3I} + (168169365 + 216217755 I) u_{iI+2+2I, i2+2I} + (5621661630 - 1873887210 I) u_{iI+2+2I, i2+1+2I} - 4684718025 I u_{iI+2+2I, i2+2+2I} - (151537230 + 11088090 I) u_{iI+2+2I, i2+3+2I} + (336338730 - 432435510 I) u_{iI+2+2I, i2+1} + 9369436050 I u_{iI+2+2I, i2+1+1} - (5621661630 + 1873887210 I) u_{iI+2+2I, i2+2+1} + (96096780 - 144145170 I) u_{iI+2+2I, i2+3+1} - 220735125 I u_{iI+2+2I, i2} - (336338730 + 432435510 I) u_{iI+2+2I, i2+1} + (-168169365 + 216217755 I) u_{iI+2+2I, i2+2} + (8897850 + 8897850 I) u_{iI+2+2I, i2+3} + (266760 + 308880 I) u_{iI+3+2I, i2+3I} + (-4890132 + 2767284 I) u_{iI+3+2I, i2+1+3I} - 4928040 I u_{iI+3+2I, i2+2+3I} + (287820 + 21060 I) u_{iI+3+2I, i2+3+3I} + (7392060 - 4928040 I) u_{iI+3+2I, i2+2I} - (47309184 + 186279912 I) u_{iI+3+2I, i2+1+2I} - (151537230 + 11088090 I) u_{iI+3+2I, i2+2+2I} + (-717336 + 4875552 I) u_{iI+3+2I, i2+3+2I} - (13191984 + 11903112 I) u_{iI+3+2I, i2+1} + (303074460 + 22176180 I) u_{iI+3+2I, i2+1+1} + (-73920600 + 177409440 I) u_{iI+3+2I, i2+2+1} - (4435236 + 3449628 I) u_{iI+3+2I, i2+3+1} - (7140150 + 522450 I) u_{iI+3+2I, i2} + (-14784120 + 9856080 I) u_{iI+3+2I, i2+1} + (6595992 + 5951556 I) u_{iI+3+2I, i2+2} + (308880 - 266760 I) u_{iI+3+2I, i2+3} + (-1460160 + 182520 I) u_{iI+1, i2+3I} + (1478412 - 20204964 I) u_{iI+1, i2+1+3I} + (14784120 + 9856080 I) u_{iI+1, i2+2+3I} + (-638820 + 821340 I) u_{iI+1, i2+3+3I} + 32032260 I u_{iI+1, i2+2I} + (653458104 + 230632272 I) u_{iI+1, i2+1+2I} + (336338730 - 432435510 I) u_{iI+1, i2+2+2I} - (13191984 + 11903112 I) u_{iI+1, i2+3+2I} + (62093304 - 15769728 I) u_{iI+1, i2+1} + (-672677460 + 864871020 I) u_{iI+1, i2+1+1} - (384387120 + 576580680 I) u_{iI+1, i2+2+1} + (19219356 - 6406452 I) u_{iI+1, i2+3+1} + (15847650 - 20375550 I) u_{iI+1, i2} - 64064520 I u_{iI+1, i2+1} + (-31046652 + 7884864 I) u_{iI+1, i2+2} + (182520 + 1460160 I) u_{iI+1, i2+3} + (17795700 - 17795700 I) u_{iI+1+1, i2+3I} + (192193560 + 288290340 I) u_{iI+1+1, i2+1+3I} + (-303074460 + 22176180 I) u_{iI+1+1, i2+2+3I} - 17795700 I u_{iI+1+1, i2+3+3I} - (336338730$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& - (110003235030 + 514959046290 I) u_{i+3+1,i2+1} + (7546754492550 + 4758735290400 I) u_{i+3+1,i2+1+1} + (-4506364391490 + 3893181073470 I) u_{i+3+1,i2+2+1} - (76994870274 + 161194007232 I) u_{i+3+1,i2+3+1} - (97392090852 + 61412250816 I) u_{i+3+1,i2} + (-512084409750 + 122691028050 I) u_{i+3+1,i2+1} \\
& + (111717197865 + 256038071445 I) u_{i+3+1,i2+2} + (12636457650 - 3426385050 I) u_{i+3+1,i2+3} + (5711360900 + 6212188500 I) u_{i,i2+3+1} + (-97392090852 + 61412250816 I) u_{i,i2+1+3+1} - (6397109460 + 100949507820 I) u_{i,i2+2+3+1} + 5961774700 u_{i,i2+3+3+1} + (148927828770 - 101183548410 I) u_{i,i2+2+1} \\
& - (1118433171492 + 3671722392156 I) u_{i,i2+1+2+1} - 3072952946700 u_{i,i2+2+2+1} + (-6397109460 + 100949507820 I) u_{i,i2+3+2+1} - (237005104140 + 242934132420 I) u_{i,i2+1} + 5750377296300 u_{i,i2+1+1} + (-1118433171492 + 3671722392156 I) u_{i,i2+2+1} - (97392090852 + 61412250816 I) u_{i,i2+3+1} \\
& - 74209551752 u_{i,i2} + (-237005104140 + 242934132420 I) u_{i,i2+1} + (148927828770 + 101183548410 I) u_{i,i2+2} + (5711360900 - 6212188500 I) u_{i,i2+3} + (38576898000 + 1143193500 I) u_{i+1,i2+3+1} + (-110003235030 + 514959046290 I) u_{i+1,i2+1+3+1} - (350901306900 + 301463515800 I) u_{i+1,i2+2+3+1} \\
& + (19040285250 - 19516605750 I) u_{i+1,i2+3+3+1} + (144398096550 - 810686345400 I) u_{i+1,i2+2+1} - (15591807749700 + 8065152552600 I) u_{i+1,i2+1+2+1} + (-9814175075250 + 10059690975750 I) u_{i+1,i2+2+2+1} + (310040055000 + 343346971500 I) u_{i+1,i2+3+2+1} - 1552204660500 u_{i+1,i2+1} + (18365139497250 \\
& - 18824570241750 I) u_{i+1,i2+1+1+1} + (8447865655320 + 15387810775740 I) u_{i+1,i2+2+1} + (-512084409750 + 122691028050 I) u_{i+1,i2+3+1} + (-237005104140 + 242934132420 I) u_{i+1,i2} + (38345108400 + 1551730956300 I) u_{i+1,i2+1} + (806871780000 - 164380934250 I) u_{i+1,i2+2} - (2095834500 \\
& + 38536884000 I) u_{i+1,i2+3} - (2991654000 + 20254313250 I) u_{i+2,i2+3+1} + (279186460425 + 9547075125 I) u_{i+2,i2+1+3+1} + (-124804982250 + 211313407500 I) u_{i+2,i2+2+3+1} - (11964418875 + 8128785375 I) u_{i+2,i2+3+3+1} - 436838761125 u_{i+2,i2+2+1} + (-2761801839810 + 8893581285420 I) u_{i+2,i2+1+2+1} \\
& + (6166971763875 + 4189922670375 I) u_{i+2,i2+2+2+1} + (150481127700 - 193868692650 I) u_{i+2,i2+3+2+1} + (144398096550 + 810686345400 I) u_{i+2,i2+1} - (11540174884875 + 7840548363375 I) u_{i+2,i2+1+1} + (7250868810900 - 5843649456450 I) u_{i+2,i2+2+1} + (111717197865 + 256038071445 I) u_{i+2,i2+3+1} \\
& + (148927828770 + 101183548410 I) u_{i+2,i2} + (806871780000 - 164380934250 I) u_{i+2,i2+1} - (160914429900 + 406121471325 I) u_{i+2,i2+2} + (-19932095250 + 4679613000 I) u_{i+2,i2+3} - 959592500 u_{i+3,i2+3+1} + (2354641650 - 12879279450 I) u_{i+3,i2+1+3+1} + (8942967000 + 7233826500 I) u_{i+3,i2+2+3+1} \\
& + (-458833750 + 499068750 I) u_{i+3,i2+3+3+1} + (-2991654000 + 20254313250 I) u_{i+3,i2+2+1} + (393442709400 + 188959691700 I) u_{i+3,i2+1+2+1} + (236502483750 - 257241318750 I) u_{i+3,i2+2+2+1} - (7958290500 + 8304849000 I) u_{i+3,i2+3+2+1} + (38576898000 - 1143193500 I) u_{i+3,i2+1} + (-442564053750 \\
& + 481372368750 I) u_{i+3,i2+1+1} - (221287634100 + 376210996200 I) u_{i+3,i2+2+1} + (12636457650 - 3426385050 I) u_{i+3,i2+3+1} + (5711360900 - 6212188500 I) u_{i+3,i2} - (2095834500 + 38536884000 I) u_{i+3,i2+1} + (-19932095250 + 4679613000 I) u_{i+3,i2+2} + (80470000 + 956212500 I) u_{i+3,i2+3}),
\end{aligned}$$

$O(\Delta x I^{14} \Delta x 2^{14})$, *Quadrant I*

$$\begin{aligned}
& \text{Error order:}, 14, \text{ Error:}, 7.2858650386918016700 \times 10^{-42}, \text{ New Error:}, 7.2553843360599586534 \times 10^{-84} \\
& \text{Error order:}, 14, \text{ Error:}, 7.2553843360599586534 \times 10^{-84}, \text{ New Error:}, 7.2553539192688893057 \times 10^{-126} \\
& \text{Error order:}, 14, \text{ Error:}, 7.2553539192688893057 \times 10^{-126}, \text{ New Error:}, 7.2553538888521620584 \times 10^{-168} \\
& \text{Error order:}, 14, \text{ Error:}, 7.2553538888521620584 \times 10^{-168}, \text{ New Error:}, 7.2553538888217453312 \times 10^{-210} \\
& \text{Error order:}, 14, \text{ Error:}, 7.2553538888217453312 \times 10^{-210}, \text{ New Error:}, 7.2553538888217149145 \times 10^{-252}
\end{aligned}$$

"--- Derivative Order: 3 - x1=1 ---"

$$\begin{bmatrix}
3 I & 1 + 3 I & 2 + 3 I & 3 + 3 I \\
2 I & 1 + 2 I & 2 + 2 I & 3 + 2 I \\
I & 1 + I & 2 + I & 3 + I \\
0 & 1 & 2 & 3
\end{bmatrix}$$

$$\begin{bmatrix}
\frac{593}{234} - \frac{13577 I}{450} & \frac{2583453}{6500} + \frac{653019 I}{6500} & -\frac{783789}{3250} + \frac{872907 I}{3250} & -\frac{13627}{900} - \frac{13627 I}{900} \\
-\frac{7957473}{13000} - \frac{2031231 I}{13000} & -\frac{327627}{50} + \frac{116163 I}{10} & \frac{1529109}{200} + \frac{1529109 I}{200} & \frac{872907}{3250} - \frac{783789 I}{3250} \\
-\frac{34419}{250} + \frac{274773 I}{250} & -\frac{1350909}{100} - \frac{1350909 I}{100} & \frac{116163}{10} - \frac{327627 I}{50} & \frac{653019}{6500} + \frac{2583453 I}{6500} \\
\frac{2905559}{23400} + \frac{2905559 I}{23400} & \frac{274773}{250} - \frac{34419 I}{250} & -\frac{2031231}{13000} - \frac{7957473 I}{13000} & -\frac{13577}{450} + \frac{593 I}{234}
\end{bmatrix}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\frac{d^3}{dx I^3} u(xI) &= \frac{1}{117000 \Delta x I^3} \left((296500 - 3530020 I) u_{i+3+1} + (46502154 + 11754342 I) u_{i+1+3+1} + (-28216404 + 31424652 I) u_{i+2+3+1} - (1771510 + 1771510 I) u_{i+3+3+1} - (71617257 + 18281079 I) u_{i+2+1} + (-766647180 + 1359107100 I) u_{i+1+2+1} + (894528765 + 894528765 I) u_{i+2+2+1} + (31424652 \right. \\
& - 28216404 I) u_{i+3+2+1} + (-16108092 + 128593764 I) u_{i+1+1} - (1580563530 + 1580563530 I) u_{i+1+1+1} + (1359107100 - 766647180 I) u_{i+2+1} + (11754342 + 46502154 I) u_{i+3+1} + (14527795 + 14527795 I) u_{i+1} + (128593764 - 16108092 I) u_{i+1+1} - (18281079 + 71617257 I) u_{i+2} + (-3530020 \\
& \left. + 296500 I) u_{i+3} \right), O(\Delta x I^{13}), \text{ Quadrant I}
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& \text{Error order:}, 13, \text{ Error:}, 4.0070656295380069922 \times 10^{-41}, \text{ New Error:}, 3.9959190038042074374 \times 10^{-80} \\
& \text{Error order:}, 13, \text{ Error:}, 3.9959190038042074374 \times 10^{-80}, \text{ New Error:}, 3.9959078727119105413 \times 10^{-119} \\
& \text{Error order:}, 13, \text{ Error:}, 3.9959078727119105413 \times 10^{-119}, \text{ New Error:}, 3.9959078615808337633 \times 10^{-158} \\
& \text{Error order:}, 13, \text{ Error:}, 3.9959078615808337633 \times 10^{-158}, \text{ New Error:}, 3.9959078615697026866 \times 10^{-197} \\
& \text{Error order:}, 13, \text{ Error:}, 3.9959078615697026866 \times 10^{-197}, \text{ New Error:}, 3.9959078615696915555 \times 10^{-236}
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\frac{d^6}{dx I^6} u(xI) &= \frac{1}{6844500000 \Delta x I^6} \left((-6186564475200 + 1046650930000 I) u_{i+6+1} + (55280951007840 - 160668371260080 I) u_{i+1+6+1} + (1114706371660416 + 655524101618748 I) u_{i+2+6+1} + (-1688278389418400 + 1135376957089440 I) u_{i+3+6+1} - (157227745751064 + 989892641620368 I) u_{i+4+6+1} \right. \\
& + (105654727114560 - 5683443414480 I) u_{i+5+6+1} + 3138247680100 I u_{i+6+6+1} + (-85767091192080 + 247390009631640 I) u_{i+5+1} + (1454889696895440 + 1417331850669540 I) u_{i+1+5+1} + (-45607964683562784 + 49562776799635392 I) u_{i+2+5+1} + (10009674774482400 - 10288664443674000 I) u_{i+3+5+1} \\
& + (-47791865933086464 + 877573991079288 I) u_{i+4+5+1} - 1385659096957980 I u_{i+5+5+1} - (105654727114560 + 5683443414480 I) u_{i+6+5+1} + (2846579334917184 + 1404230670928143 I) u_{i+4+1} + (71442458368177104 - 72419054028359688 I) u_{i+1+4+1} - (738233781639607890 \\
& + 1223609996890204560 I) u_{i+2+4+1} + (-1737411426171878400 + 506445595450239600 I) u_{i+3+4+1} + 936765282902118345 I u_{i+4+4+1} + (47791865933086464 + 877573991079288 I) u_{i+5+4+1} + (157227745751064 - 989892641620368 I) u_{i+6+4+1} + (3560041021258400 - 8962035258282480 I) u_{i+3+1} \\
& + (-77636181331216800 + 21998986371680400 I) u_{i+1+3+1} + (3124143599349261600 - 804887268497200800 I) u_{i+2+3+1} - 390937424540619600 I u_{i+3+3+1} + (1737411426171878400 + 506445595450239600 I) u_{i+4+3+1} - (10009674774482400 + 10288664443674000 I) u_{i+5+3+1} + (1688278389418400 \\
& + 1135376957089440 I) u_{i+6+3+1} - (8913299815971126 + 337742477387408 I) u_{i+2+1} + (188323947969322464 - 170380829941313472 I) u_{i+1+2+1} + 2903879204704925460 I u_{i+2+2+1} - (3124143599349261600 + 804887268497200800 I) u_{i+3+2+1} + (738233781639607890 - 1223609996890204560 I) u_{i+4+2+1} \\
& + (45607964683562784 + 49562776799635392 I) u_{i+5+2+1} + (-1114706371660416 + 655524101618748 I) u_{i+6+2+1} + (-2102198900087520 + 1634168783253240 I) u_{i+1+1} - 29128379129064540 I u_{i+1+1+1} - (188323947969322464 + 170380829941313472 I) u_{i+2+1} + (77636181331216800 \\
& + 21998986371680400 I) u_{i+3+1} - (71442458368177104 + 72419054028359688 I) u_{i+4+1} + (-1454889696895440 + 1417331850669540 I) u_{i+5+1} - (55280951007840 + 160668371260080 I) u_{i+6+1} + 211056827562025 I u_{i+1} + (2102198900087520 + 1634168783253240 I) u_{i+1+1} + (8913299815971126 \\
& - 337742477387408 I) u_{i+2} - (3560041021258400 + 8962035258282480 I) u_{i+3} + (-2846579334917184 + 1404230670928143 I) u_{i+4} + (85767091192080 + 247390009631640 I) u_{i+5} + (6186564475200 - 1046650930000 I) u_{i+6}), O(\Delta x I^{13}), \text{ Quadrant I}
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& \text{Error order:}, 13, \text{ Error:}, 7.9662381714592953293 \times 10^{-41}, \text{ New Error:}, 7.9440781462405912702 \times 10^{-80} \\
& \text{Error order:}, 13, \text{ Error:}, 7.9440781462405912702 \times 10^{-80}, \text{ New Error:}, 7.9440560170965882571 \times 10^{-119} \\
& \text{Error order:}, 13, \text{ Error:}, 7.9440560170965882571 \times 10^{-119}, \text{ New Error:}, 7.9440559949674751066 \times 10^{-158} \\
& \text{Error order:}, 13, \text{ Error:}, 7.9440559949674751066 \times 10^{-158}, \text{ New Error:}, 7.9440559949453459935 \times 10^{-197} \\
& \text{Error order:}, 13, \text{ Error:}, 7.9440559949453459935 \times 10^{-197}, \text{ New Error:}, 7.9440559949453238644 \times 10^{-236}
\end{aligned}$$

$$- 416085111 I u_{i+1+1} + (319483008 + 65468052 I) u_{i+2+1} + (-4770486 + 9691041 I) u_{i+3+1} + 2209124 I u_i + (19927980 + 9133224 I) u_{i+1} + (5339691 - 14618751 I) u_{i+2} - (686920 + 432268 I) u_{i+3}), O(\Delta x I^{10}), \text{ Quadrant 1}$$

Error order:, 10, Error:, 1.2265231063608464361 × 10⁻³⁰, New Error:, 1.2231853104674791103 × 10⁻⁶⁰
 Error order:, 10, Error:, 1.2231853104674791103 × 10⁻⁶⁰, New Error:, 1.2231819772219133270 × 10⁻⁹⁰
 Error order:, 10, Error:, 1.2231819772219133270 × 10⁻⁹⁰, New Error:, 1.2231819738886723074 × 10⁻¹²⁰
 Error order:, 10, Error:, 1.2231819738886723074 × 10⁻¹²⁰, New Error:, 1.2231819738853390664 × 10⁻¹⁵⁰
 Error order:, 10, Error:, 1.2231819738853390664 × 10⁻¹⁵⁰, New Error:, 1.2231819738853357332 × 10⁻¹⁸⁰

"--- Derivative Order: 7 - x1=1 ---"

$$\begin{bmatrix} 3 I & 1 + 3 I & 2 + 3 I & 3 + 3 I \\ 2 I & 1 + 2 I & 2 + 2 I & 3 + 2 I \\ I & 1 + I & 2 + I & 3 + I \\ 0 & 1 & 2 & 3 \end{bmatrix}$$

$$\left[\begin{array}{cccccc} -\frac{1512938}{195} + \frac{5327714 I}{195} & -\frac{458968797}{1300} & -\frac{171517731 I}{1300} & \frac{76695318}{325} & -\frac{78359694 I}{325} & \frac{11382119}{780} + \frac{11382119 I}{780} \\ \frac{601742211}{1300} + \frac{326063997 I}{1300} & \frac{31599918}{5} & -\frac{45573822 I}{5} & -\frac{26915427}{4} & -\frac{26915427 I}{4} & -\frac{78359694}{325} + \frac{76695318 I}{325} \\ \frac{90244014}{325} - \frac{207959598 I}{325} & \frac{193478607}{20} + \frac{193478607 I}{20} & -\frac{45573822}{5} + \frac{31599918 I}{5} & -\frac{171517731}{1300} & -\frac{458968797 I}{1300} & \\ -\frac{35749511}{780} - \frac{35749511 I}{780} & -\frac{207959598}{325} + \frac{90244014 I}{325} & \frac{326063997}{1300} + \frac{601742211 I}{1300} & \frac{5327714}{195} & -\frac{1512938 I}{195} & \end{array} \right]$$

$$\frac{d^7}{dx I^7} u(xI) = \frac{1}{3900 \Delta x I^7} (7 ((-4322680 + 15222040 I) u_{i+3+1} - (196700913 + 73507599 I) u_{i+1+3+1} + (131477688 - 134330904 I) u_{i+2+3+1} + (8130085 + 8130085 I) u_{i+3+3+1} + (257889519 + 139741713 I) u_{i+2+1} + (3521133720 - 5078225880 I) u_{i+1+2+1} - (3748934475 + 3748934475 I) u_{i+2+2+1} + (-134330904 + 131477688 I) u_{i+3+2+1} + (154704024 - 356502168 I) u_{i+1+1} + (5389761195 + 5389761195 I) u_{i+1+1+1} + (-5078225880 + 3521133720 I) u_{i+2+1} - (73507599 + 196700913 I) u_{i+3+1} - (25535365 + 25535365 I) u_i + (-356502168 + 154704024 I) u_{i+1} + (139741713 + 257889519 I) u_{i+2} + (15222040 - 4322680 I) u_{i+3})), O(\Delta x I^9), \text{ Quadrant 1}$$

Error order:, 9, Error:, 3.0155215575587863132 × 10⁻²⁷, New Error:, 3.0073996305921636324 × 10⁻⁵⁴
 Error order:, 9, Error:, 3.0073996305921636324 × 10⁻⁵⁴, New Error:, 3.0073915196236883335 × 10⁻⁸¹
 Error order:, 9, Error:, 3.0073915196236883335 × 10⁻⁸¹, New Error:, 3.0073915115127308068 × 10⁻¹⁰⁸
 Error order:, 9, Error:, 3.0073915115127308068 × 10⁻¹⁰⁸, New Error:, 3.0073915115046198493 × 10⁻¹³⁵
 Error order:, 9, Error:, 3.0073915115046198493 × 10⁻¹³⁵, New Error:, 3.0073915115046117384 × 10⁻¹⁶²

"--- Derivative Order: 8 - x1=1 ---"

$$\begin{bmatrix} 3 I & 1 + 3 I & 2 + 3 I & 3 + 3 I \\ 2 I & 1 + 2 I & 2 + 2 I & 3 + 2 I \\ I & 1 + I & 2 + I & 3 + I \\ 0 & 1 & 2 & 3 \end{bmatrix}$$

$$\left[\begin{array}{cccccc} -\frac{641718}{13} - \frac{507654 I}{5} & \frac{17951472}{13} & -\frac{7516656 I}{13} & -\frac{154098}{65} + \frac{87691338 I}{65} & -\frac{5414976}{65} & \\ -\frac{25566912}{13} + \frac{29799504 I}{65} & \frac{33421878}{5} + \frac{212056866 I}{5} & \frac{187168464}{5} & -\frac{154098}{65} - \frac{87691338 I}{65} & & \\ \frac{53359362}{65} + \frac{31181094 I}{13} & -\frac{256533984}{5} & \frac{33421878}{5} - \frac{212056866 I}{5} & \frac{17951472}{13} + \frac{7516656 I}{13} & & \\ \frac{2871792}{13} & \frac{53359362}{65} - \frac{31181094 I}{13} & -\frac{25566912}{13} - \frac{29799504 I}{65} & -\frac{641718}{13} + \frac{507654 I}{5} & & \end{array} \right]$$

$$\frac{d^8}{dx I^8} u(xI) = \frac{1}{65 \Delta x I^8} (126 ((-25465 + 52377 I) u_{i+3+1} + (712360 - 298280 I) u_{i+1+3+1} + (-1223 + 695963 I) u_{i+2+3+1} - 42976 u_{i+3+3+1} + (-1014560 + 236504 I) u_{i+2+1} + (3448289 + 21878883 I) u_{i+1+2+1} + 19311032 u_{i+2+2+1} - (1223 + 695963 I) u_{i+3+2+1} + (423487 + 1237345 I) u_{i+1} - 26467792 u_{i+1+1} + (3448289 - 21878883 I) u_{i+2+1} + (712360 + 298280 I) u_{i+3+1} + 113960 u_i + (423487 - 1237345 I) u_{i+1} - (1014560 + 236504 I) u_{i+2} + (-25465 + 52377 I) u_{i+3})), O(\Delta x I^8), \text{ Quadrant 1}$$

Error order:, 8, Error:, 6.5723896780113468262 × 10⁻²⁴, New Error:, 6.5549115792917449954 × 10⁻⁴⁸
 Error order:, 8, Error:, 6.5549115792917449954 × 10⁻⁴⁸, New Error:, 6.5548941244769156194 × 10⁻⁷²
 Error order:, 8, Error:, 6.5548941244769156194 × 10⁻⁷², New Error:, 6.5548941070221240531 × 10⁻⁹⁶
 Error order:, 8, Error:, 6.5548941070221240531 × 10⁻⁹⁶, New Error:, 6.5548941070046692616 × 10⁻¹²⁰
 Error order:, 8, Error:, 6.5548941070046692616 × 10⁻¹²⁰, New Error:, 6.5548941070046518068 × 10⁻¹⁴⁴

"--- Derivative Order: 9 - x1=1 ---"

$$\begin{bmatrix} 3I & 1+3I & 2+3I & 3+3I \\ 2I & 1+2I & 2+2I & 3+2I \\ I & 1+I & 2+I & 3+I \\ 0 & 1 & 2 & 3 \end{bmatrix}$$

$$\begin{bmatrix} \frac{23278374}{65} + \frac{1925154I}{13} & -\frac{137000808}{65} + \frac{305368056I}{65} & -\frac{211741614}{65} - \frac{218237166I}{65} & \frac{13415976}{65} - \frac{13415976I}{65} \\ \frac{250405344}{65} - \frac{355205088I}{65} & -\frac{572126814}{5} - \frac{436461858I}{5} & -\frac{451177776}{5} + \frac{451177776I}{5} & \frac{218237166}{65} + \frac{211741614I}{65} \\ -\frac{457771986}{65} - \frac{247619106I}{65} & \frac{590210712}{5} - \frac{590210712I}{5} & \frac{436461858}{5} + \frac{572126814I}{5} & -\frac{305368056}{65} + \frac{137000808I}{65} \\ -\frac{6087312}{13} + \frac{6087312I}{13} & \frac{247619106}{65} + \frac{457771986I}{65} & \frac{355205088}{65} - \frac{250405344I}{65} & -\frac{1925154}{13} - \frac{23278374I}{65} \end{bmatrix}$$

$$\frac{d^9}{dx^9} u(xI) = \frac{1}{65 \Delta x I^9} (378 ((61583 + 25465 I) u_{iI+3I} + (-362436 + 807852 I) u_{iI+1+3I} - (560163 + 577347 I) u_{iI+2+3I} + (35492 - 35492 I) u_{iI+3+3I} + (662448 - 939696 I) u_{iI+2I} - (19676319 + 15010593 I) u_{iI+1+2I} + (-15516696 + 15516696 I) u_{iI+2+2I} + (577347 + 560163 I) u_{iI+3+2I} - (1211037 + 655077 I) u_{iI+1} + (20298252 - 20298252 I) u_{iI+1+1} + (15010593 + 19676319 I) u_{iI+2+1} + (-807852 + 362436 I) u_{iI+3+1} + (-80520 + 80520 I) u_{iI} + (655077 + 1211037 I) u_{iI+1} + (939696 - 662448 I) u_{iI+2} - (25465 + 61583 I) u_{iI+3})), O(\Delta x I^7), \text{ Quadrant 1}$$

Error order: 7, Error: 1.2599302267067206779 × 10⁻²⁰, New Error: 1.2566330402911581039 × 10⁻⁴¹
 Error order: 7, Error: 1.2566330402911581039 × 10⁻⁴¹, New Error: 1.2566297474271466747 × 10⁻⁶²
 Error order: 7, Error: 1.2566297474271466747 × 10⁻⁶², New Error: 1.2566297441342869819 × 10⁻⁸³
 Error order: 7, Error: 1.2566297441342869819 × 10⁻⁸³, New Error: 1.2566297441309941222 × 10⁻¹⁰⁴
 Error order: 7, Error: 1.2566297441309941222 × 10⁻¹⁰⁴, New Error: 1.2566297441309908293 × 10⁻¹²⁵

--- Derivative Order: 10 - xI=1 ---

$$\begin{bmatrix} 3I & 1+3I & 2+3I & 3+3I \\ 2I & 1+2I & 2+2I & 3+2I \\ I & 1+I & 2+I & 3+I \\ 0 & 1 & 2 & 3 \end{bmatrix}$$

$$\begin{bmatrix} -1067220 + \frac{4772124I}{13} & -\frac{63322560}{13} - \frac{185440752I}{13} & \frac{179695908}{13} + \frac{5291244I}{13} & \frac{11347056I}{13} \\ \frac{28295568}{13} + \frac{242666928I}{13} & 408124332 - 45598140I & -370609344I & -\frac{179695908}{13} + \frac{5291244I}{13} \\ \frac{271763100}{13} - \frac{70600572I}{13} & 463152816I & -408124332 - 45598140I & \frac{63322560}{13} - \frac{185440752I}{13} \\ -\frac{22238496I}{13} & -\frac{271763100}{13} - \frac{70600572I}{13} & -\frac{28295568}{13} + \frac{242666928I}{13} & 1067220 + \frac{4772124I}{13} \end{bmatrix}$$

$$\frac{d^{10}}{dx^{10}} u(xI) = \frac{1}{13 \Delta x I^{10}} (252 ((-55055 + 18937 I) u_{iI+3I} - (251280 + 735876 I) u_{iI+1+3I} + (713079 + 20997 I) u_{iI+2+3I} + 45028 I u_{iI+3+3I} + (112284 + 962964 I) u_{iI+2I} + (21054033 - 2352285 I) u_{iI+1+2I} - 19118736 I u_{iI+2+2I} + (-713079 + 20997 I) u_{iI+3+2I} + (1078425 - 280161 I) u_{iI+1} + 23892804 I u_{iI+1+1} - (21054033 + 2352285 I) u_{iI+2+1} + (251280 - 735876 I) u_{iI+3+1} - 88248 I u_{iI} - (1078425 + 280161 I) u_{iI+1} + (-112284 + 962964 I) u_{iI+2} + (55055 + 18937 I) u_{iI+3})), O(\Delta x I^6), \text{ Quadrant 1}$$

Error order: 6, Error: 2.0981568512777595916 × 10⁻¹⁷, New Error: 2.0927797471774649774 × 10⁻³⁵
 Error order: 6, Error: 2.0927797471774649774 × 10⁻³⁵, New Error: 2.0927743769763467687 × 10⁻⁵³
 Error order: 6, Error: 2.0927743769763467687 × 10⁻⁵³, New Error: 2.0927743716061525475 × 10⁻⁷¹
 Error order: 6, Error: 2.0927743716061525475 × 10⁻⁷¹, New Error: 2.0927743716007823533 × 10⁻⁸⁹
 Error order: 6, Error: 2.0927743716007823533 × 10⁻⁸⁹, New Error: 2.0927743716007769831 × 10⁻¹⁰⁷

--- Derivative Order: 11 - xI=1 ---

$$\begin{bmatrix} 3I & 1+3I & 2+3I & 3+3I \\ 2I & 1+2I & 2+2I & 3+2I \\ I & 1+I & 2+I & 3+I \\ 0 & 1 & 2 & 3 \end{bmatrix}$$

$$\begin{bmatrix} \frac{17497788}{13} - \frac{30670332I}{13} & \frac{2095981272}{65} + \frac{1125703656I}{65} & -\frac{1630077372}{65} + \frac{1489819716I}{65} & -\frac{19967640}{13} - \frac{19967640I}{13} \\ -\frac{2133103896}{65} - \frac{1878933672I}{65} & -623724948 + 745870356I & 632032632 + 632032632I & \frac{1489819716}{65} - \frac{1630077372I}{65} \\ -\frac{1681420356}{65} + \frac{2665918332I}{65} & -755076168 - 755076168I & 745870356 - 623724948I & \frac{1125703656}{65} + \frac{2095981272I}{65} \\ \frac{34038312}{13} + \frac{34038312I}{13} & \frac{2665918332}{65} - \frac{1681420356I}{65} & -\frac{1878933672}{65} - \frac{2133103896I}{65} & -\frac{30670332}{13} + \frac{17497788I}{13} \end{bmatrix}$$

$$\frac{d^{11}}{dx^{11}} u(xI) = \frac{1}{65 \Delta x I^{11}} (924 ((94685 - 165965 I) u_{il+31} + (2268378 + 1218294 I) u_{il+1+31} + (-1764153 + 1612359 I) u_{il+2+31} - (108050 + 108050 I) u_{il+3+31} - (2308554 + 2033478 I) u_{il+21} + (-43876755 + 52469235 I) u_{il+1+21} + (44461170 + 44461170 I) u_{il+2+21} + (1612359 - 1764153 I) u_{il+3+21} + (-1819719 + 2885193 I) u_{il+1} - (53116830 + 53116830 I) u_{il+1+1} + (52469235 - 43876755 I) u_{il+2+1} + (1218294 + 2268378 I) u_{il+3+1} + (184190 + 184190 I) u_{il} + (2885193 - 1819719 I) u_{il+1} - (2033478 + 2308554 I) u_{il+2} + (-165965 + 94685 I) u_{il+3}), O(\Delta x I^5), \text{ Quadrant I}$$

Error order.: 5, Error.: 2.9808091312433540961 × 10⁻¹⁴, New Error.: 2.9733842371902315009 × 10⁻²⁹
 Error order.: 5, Error.: 2.9733842371902315009 × 10⁻²⁹, New Error.: 2.9733768215605295039 × 10⁻⁴⁴
 Error order.: 5, Error.: 2.9733768215605295039 × 10⁻⁴⁴, New Error.: 2.9733768141449090584 × 10⁻⁵⁹
 Error order.: 5, Error.: 2.9733768141449090584 × 10⁻⁵⁹, New Error.: 2.9733768141374934380 × 10⁻⁷⁴
 Error order.: 5, Error.: 2.9733768141374934380 × 10⁻⁷⁴, New Error.: 2.9733768141374860224 × 10⁻⁸⁹

--- Derivative Order: 12 - x1=1 ---

$$\begin{bmatrix} 3 I & 1 + 3 I & 2 + 3 I & 3 + 3 I \\ 2 I & 1 + 2 I & 2 + 2 I & 3 + 2 I \\ I & 1 + I & 2 + I & 3 + I \\ 0 & 1 & 2 & 3 \end{bmatrix}$$

$$\begin{bmatrix} \frac{13471920}{13} + 5089392 I & -\frac{892140480}{13} + \frac{231517440 I}{13} & \frac{53588304}{13} - \frac{865895184 I}{13} & \frac{56282688}{13} \\ \frac{1053803520}{13} - \frac{13571712 I}{13} & -122444784 - 1833079248 I & -1722010752 & \frac{53588304}{13} + \frac{865895184 I}{13} \\ -\frac{218843856}{13} - \frac{1111183920 I}{13} & 1967499072 & -122444784 + 1833079248 I & -\frac{892140480}{13} - \frac{231517440 I}{13} \\ -\frac{83825280}{13} & -\frac{218843856}{13} + \frac{1111183920 I}{13} & \frac{1053803520}{13} + \frac{13571712 I}{13} & \frac{13471920}{13} - 5089392 I \end{bmatrix}$$

$$\frac{d^{12}}{dx^{12}} u(xI) = \frac{1}{13 \Delta x I^{12}} (99792 ((135 + 663 I) u_{il+31} + (-8940 + 2320 I) u_{il+1+31} + (537 - 8677 I) u_{il+2+31} + 564 u_{il+3+31} + (10560 - 136 I) u_{il+21} - (15951 + 238797 I) u_{il+1+21} - 224328 u_{il+2+21} + (537 + 8677 I) u_{il+3+21} - (2193 + 11135 I) u_{il+1} + 256308 u_{il+1+1} + (-15951 + 238797 I) u_{il+2+1} - (8940 + 2320 I) u_{il+3+1} - 840 u_{il} + (-2193 + 11135 I) u_{il+1} + (10560 + 136 I) u_{il+2} + (135 - 663 I) u_{il+3}), O(\Delta x I^4), \text{ Quadrant I}$$

Error order.: 4, Error.: 3.5190600775778162265 × 10⁻¹¹, New Error.: 3.5106469497625257931 × 10⁻²³
 Error order.: 4, Error.: 3.5106469497625257931 × 10⁻²³, New Error.: 3.5106385467096974901 × 10⁻³⁵
 Error order.: 4, Error.: 3.5106385467096974901 × 10⁻³⁵, New Error.: 3.5106385383066547286 × 10⁻⁴⁷
 Error order.: 4, Error.: 3.5106385383066547286 × 10⁻⁴⁷, New Error.: 3.5106385382982516859 × 10⁻⁵⁹
 Error order.: 4, Error.: 3.5106385382982516859 × 10⁻⁵⁹, New Error.: 3.5106385382982432828 × 10⁻⁷¹

--- Derivative Order: 13 - x1=1 ---

$$\begin{bmatrix} 3 I & 1 + 3 I & 2 + 3 I & 3 + 3 I \\ 2 I & 1 + 2 I & 2 + 2 I & 3 + 2 I \\ I & 1 + I & 2 + I & 3 + I \\ 0 & 1 & 2 & 3 \end{bmatrix}$$

$$\begin{bmatrix} -5887728 - 4490640 I & 55683936 - 86419872 I & 63767088 + 74943792 I & -4590432 + 4590432 I \\ -82228608 + 76640256 I & 1918700784 + 1755241488 I & 1759133376 - 1759133376 I & -74943792 - 63767088 I \\ 95900112 + 67958352 I & -1922592672 + 1922592672 I & -1755241488 - 1918700784 I & 86419872 - 55683936 I \\ 5987520 - 5987520 I & -67958352 - 95900112 I & -76640256 + 82228608 I & 4490640 + 5887728 I \end{bmatrix}$$

$$\frac{d^{13}}{dx^{13}} u(xI) = \frac{1}{\Delta x I^{13}} (-5887728 + 4490640 I) u_{il+31} + (55683936 - 86419872 I) u_{il+1+31} + (63767088 + 74943792 I) u_{il+2+31} + (-4590432 + 4590432 I) u_{il+3+31} + (-82228608 + 76640256 I) u_{il+21} + (1918700784 + 1755241488 I) u_{il+1+21} + (1759133376 - 1759133376 I) u_{il+2+21} - (74943792 + 63767088 I) u_{il+3+21} + (95900112 + 67958352 I) u_{il+1} + (-1922592672 + 1922592672 I) u_{il+1+1} - (1755241488 + 1918700784 I) u_{il+2+1} + (86419872 - 55683936 I) u_{il+3+1} + (5987520 - 5987520 I) u_{il} - (67958352 + 95900112 I) u_{il+1} + (-76640256 + 82228608 I) u_{il+2} + (4490640 + 5887728 I) u_{il+3}), O(\Delta x I^3), \text{ Quadrant I}$$

Error order.: 3, Error.: 3.3188341759942307507 × 10⁻⁸, New Error.: 3.3113966272522501638 × 10⁻¹⁷
 Error order.: 3, Error.: 3.3113966272522501638 × 10⁻¹⁷, New Error.: 3.3113891980520772575 × 10⁻²⁶
 Error order.: 3, Error.: 3.3113891980520772575 × 10⁻²⁶, New Error.: 3.3113891906228854267 × 10⁻³⁵
 Error order.: 3, Error.: 3.3113891906228854267 × 10⁻³⁵, New Error.: 3.3113891906154562349 × 10⁻⁴⁴
 Error order.: 3, Error.: 3.3113891906154562349 × 10⁻⁴⁴, New Error.: 3.3113891906154488057 × 10⁻⁵³

--- Derivative Order: 14 - x1=1 ---

$$\begin{bmatrix} 3 I & 1 + 3 I & 2 + 3 I & 3 + 3 I \\ 2 I & 1 + 2 I & 2 + 2 I & 3 + 2 I \\ I & 1 + I & 2 + I & 3 + I \\ 0 & 1 & 2 & 3 \end{bmatrix}$$

$$\begin{bmatrix} 6985440 - 465696 I & 16765056 + 97796160 I & -96399072 - 9779616 I & -6519744 I \\ 8382528 - 103384512 I & -2451889440 + 54486432 I & 2397403008 I & 96399072 - 9779616 I \\ -104781600 + 15367968 I & -2506375872 I & 2451889440 + 54486432 I & -16765056 + 97796160 I \\ 7451136 I & 104781600 + 15367968 I & -8382528 - 103384512 I & -6985440 - 465696 I \end{bmatrix}$$

$$\frac{d^{14}}{dx^{14}} u(xI) = \frac{1}{\Delta x^{14}} \left((6985440 - 465696 I) u_{i+31} + (16765056 + 97796160 I) u_{i+1+31} - (96399072 + 9779616 I) u_{i+2+31} - 6519744 I u_{i+3+31} + (8382528 - 103384512 I) u_{i+21} + (-2451889440 + 54486432 I) u_{i+1+21} + 2397403008 I u_{i+2+21} + (96399072 - 9779616 I) u_{i+3+21} + (-104781600 + 15367968 I) u_{i+1} - 2506375872 I u_{i+1+1} + (2451889440 + 54486432 I) u_{i+2+1} + (-16765056 + 97796160 I) u_{i+3+1} + 7451136 I u_{i+1} + (104781600 + 15367968 I) u_{i+1} - (8382528 + 103384512 I) u_{i+2} - (6985440 + 465696 I) u_{i+3} \right), O(\Delta x^2), \text{ Quadrant 1}$$

Error order:, 2, *Error:*, 0.000023461840836019523846, *New Error:*, 2.3415104255008565166 × 10⁻¹¹
Error order:, 2, *Error:*, 2.3415104255008565166 × 10⁻¹¹, *New Error:*, 2.3415057565056810444 × 10⁻¹⁷
Error order:, 2, *Error:*, 2.3415057565056810444 × 10⁻¹⁷, *New Error:*, 2.3415057518366905286 × 10⁻²³
Error order:, 2, *Error:*, 2.3415057518366905286 × 10⁻²³, *New Error:*, 2.3415057518320215381 × 10⁻²⁹
Error order:, 2, *Error:*, 2.3415057518320215381 × 10⁻²⁹, *New Error:*, 2.3415057518320168691 × 10⁻³⁵

"--- Derivative Order: 15 - x1=1 ---"

$$\begin{bmatrix} 3 I & 1 + 3 I & 2 + 3 I & 3 + 3 I \\ 2 I & 1 + 2 I & 2 + 2 I & 3 + 2 I \\ I & 1 + I & 2 + I & 3 + I \\ 0 & 1 & 2 & 3 \end{bmatrix}$$

$$\begin{bmatrix} -2328480 + 2328480 I & -37721376 - 29338848 I & 37721376 - 29338848 I & 2328480 + 2328480 I \\ 29338848 + 37721376 I & 817296480 - 817296480 I & -817296480 - 817296480 I & -29338848 + 37721376 I \\ 29338848 - 37721376 I & 817296480 + 817296480 I & -817296480 + 817296480 I & -29338848 - 37721376 I \\ -2328480 - 2328480 I & -37721376 + 29338848 I & 37721376 + 29338848 I & 2328480 - 2328480 I \end{bmatrix}$$

$$\frac{d^{15}}{dx^{15}} u(xI) = \frac{1}{\Delta x^{15}} \left((-2328480 + 2328480 I) u_{i+31} - (37721376 + 29338848 I) u_{i+1+31} + (37721376 - 29338848 I) u_{i+2+31} + (2328480 + 2328480 I) u_{i+3+31} + (29338848 + 37721376 I) u_{i+21} + (817296480 - 817296480 I) u_{i+1+21} - (817296480 + 817296480 I) u_{i+2+21} + (-29338848 + 37721376 I) u_{i+3+21} + (29338848 - 37721376 I) u_{i+1} + (817296480 + 817296480 I) u_{i+1+1} + (-817296480 + 817296480 I) u_{i+2+1} - (29338848 + 37721376 I) u_{i+3+1} - (2328480 + 2328480 I) u_{i+1} + (-37721376 + 29338848 I) u_{i+1} + (37721376 + 29338848 I) u_{i+2} + (2328480 - 2328480 I) u_{i+3} \right), O(\Delta x), \text{ Quadrant 1}$$

Error order:, 1, *Error:*, 0.011054500241232092766, *New Error:*, 0.000011037980492628687618
Error order:, 1, *Error:*, 0.000011037980492628687618, *New Error:*, 1.1037963985242060830 × 10⁻⁸
Error order:, 1, *Error:*, 1.1037963985242060830 × 10⁻⁸, *New Error:*, 1.1037963968734686559 × 10⁻¹¹
Error order:, 1, *Error:*, 1.1037963968734686559 × 10⁻¹¹, *New Error:*, 1.1037963968718179185 × 10⁻¹⁴
Error order:, 1, *Error:*, 1.1037963968718179185 × 10⁻¹⁴, *New Error:*, 1.1037963968718162677 × 10⁻¹⁷

"--- Derivative Order: 1 - x1=1 ---"

$$\begin{bmatrix} 4 I & 1 + 4 I & 2 + 4 I & 3 + 4 I & 4 + 4 I \\ 3 I & 1 + 3 I & 2 + 3 I & 3 + 3 I & 4 + 3 I \\ 2 I & 1 + 2 I & 2 + 2 I & 3 + 2 I & 4 + 2 I \\ I & 1 + I & 2 + I & 3 + I & 4 + I \\ 0 & 1 & 2 & 3 & 4 \end{bmatrix}$$

$$\begin{bmatrix} \frac{I}{4} & -\frac{16}{17} - \frac{208 I}{17} & -18 + 36 I & \frac{208}{25} - \frac{144 I}{25} & -\frac{1}{8} + \frac{I}{8} \\ \frac{16}{3} - 16 I & 544 - 1632 I & \frac{48960}{13} - \frac{73440 I}{13} & \frac{2720}{3} - \frac{2720 I}{3} & \frac{144}{25} - \frac{208 I}{25} \\ 90 I & 4896 - 9792 I & -29835 + 29835 I & \frac{73440}{13} - \frac{48960 I}{13} & -36 + 18 I \\ -16 - 48 I & 2720 - 2720 I & 9792 - 4896 I & 1632 - 544 I & \frac{208}{17} + \frac{16 I}{17} \\ -\frac{237961}{44200} + \frac{237961 I}{44200} & 48 + 16 I & -90 & 16 - \frac{16 I}{3} & -\frac{1}{4} \end{bmatrix}$$

$$\frac{d}{dx} u(xI) = \frac{1}{132600 \Delta x} \left(33150 I u_{i+41} - (124800 + 1622400 I) u_{i+1+41} + (-2386800 + 4773600 I) u_{i+2+41} + (1103232 - 763776 I) u_{i+3+41} + (-16575 + 16575 I) u_{i+4+41} + (707200 - 2121600 I) u_{i+31} + (72134400 - 216403200 I) u_{i+1+31} + (499392000 - 749088000 I) u_{i+2+31} + (120224000 - 120224000 I) u_{i+3+31} + (763776 - 1103232 I) u_{i+4+31} + 11934000 I u_{i+21} + (649209600 - 1298419200 I) u_{i+1+21} + (-3956121000 + 3956121000 I) u_{i+2+21} + (749088000 - 499392000 I) u_{i+3+21} + (-4773600 + 2386800 I) u_{i+4+21} - (2121600 + 6364800 I) u_{i+1} + (360672000 - 360672000 I) u_{i+1+1} + (1298419200 - 649209600 I) u_{i+2+1} + (216403200 - 72134400 I) u_{i+3+1} + (1622400 + 124800 I) u_{i+4+1} + (-713883 + 713883 I) u_{i+1} + (6364800 + 2121600 I) u_{i+1} - 11934000 u_{i+2} + (2121600 - 707200 I) u_{i+3} - 33150 u_{i+4} \right), O(\Delta x^{24}), \text{ Quadrant 1}$$

Error order:, 24, *Error:*, 8.4763810322430552917 × 10⁻⁷⁹, *New Error:*, 8.4439394165822550142 × 10⁻¹⁵¹
Error order:, 24, *Error:*, 8.4439394165822550142 × 10⁻¹⁵¹, *New Error:*, 8.4439070371898719003 × 10⁻²²³
Error order:, 24, *Error:*, 8.4439070371898719003 × 10⁻²²³, *New Error:*, 8.4439070048105416608 × 10⁻²⁹⁵
Error order:, 24, *Error:*, 8.4439070048105416608 × 10⁻²⁹⁵, *New Error:*, 8.4439070047781623307 × 10⁻³⁶⁷

Error order: 24, Error: 8.4439070047781623307 × 10⁻³⁶⁷, New Error: 8.4439070047781299513 × 10⁻⁴³⁹

$$\frac{d^2}{dx^2} u(xI) = \frac{1}{8791380000 \Delta x I^2} \left(-549461250 u_{iI+8I} + (53782560000 - 4137120000 I) u_{iI+1+8I} + (-1466548200000 + 123353100000 I) u_{iI+2+8I} + (8067880454400 + 3313171180800 I) u_{iI+3+8I} - (9922604357250 + 13088742293250 I) u_{iI+4+8I} + (1041726816000 + 7114191552000 I) u_{iI+5+8I} + (277322323824 - 961305754032 I) u_{iI+6+8I} + (-5626483200 + 30945657600 I) u_{iI+7+8I} - 274730625 I u_{iI+8+8I} + (70331040000 + 23443680000 I) u_{iI+7I} + (3643423680000 + 1508669760000 I) u_{iI+1+7I} - (326822932800000 + 65029161600000 I) u_{iI+2+7I} + (-413647359091200 + 145229197401600 I) u_{iI+3+7I} + (2088199702118400 + 3698008175097600 I) u_{iI+4+7I} + (266266494374400 - 343308503116800 I) u_{iI+5+7I} + (48392877062400 - 197486458540800 I) u_{iI+6+7I} + 2184950976000 I u_{iI+7+7I} + (5626483200 + 30945657600 I) u_{iI+8+7I} - (2396139460000 + 1500395520000 I) u_{iI+6I} - (345703263360000 + 286048751040000 I) u_{iI+1+6I} - (24425271953550000 + 18250244512110000 I) u_{iI+2+6I} - (114665338043776000 + 150284310992192000 I) u_{iI+3+6I} - (183838522637766000 + 440189168982426000 I) u_{iI+4+6I} - (30934826174304000 + 138148490447136000 I) u_{iI+5+6I} - 16859601000814000 I u_{iI+6+6I} - (48392877062400 + 197486458540800 I) u_{iI+7+6I} - (277322323824 + 961305754032 I) u_{iI+8+6I} + (25530167520000 + 8369393760000 I) u_{iI+5I} + (288845444160000 - 1418560528320000 I) u_{iI+1+5I} - (220189769092800000 + 217492941594240000 I) u_{iI+2+5I} + (-77129612703936000 + 6805488950208000 I) u_{iI+3+5I} + (855735385583520000 + 4513611092971968000 I) u_{iI+4+5I} + 139720014266227200 I u_{iI+5+5I} + (30934826174304000 - 138148490447136000 I) u_{iI+6+5I} - (266266494374400 + 343308503116800 I) u_{iI+7+5I} + (-1041726816000 + 7114191552000 I) u_{iI+8+5I} - (86237798421450 + 23665221450 I) u_{iI+4I} + (13455973790937600 + 6728678517100800 I) u_{iI+1+4I} - (737741204283704400 + 999045201377293200 I) u_{iI+2+4I} + (2436378457754372352 + 6934916433823832064 I) u_{iI+3+4I} - 18383456298864651150 I u_{iI+4+4I} + (-855735385583520000 + 4513611092971968000 I) u_{iI+5+4I} + (183838522637766000 - 440189168982426000 I) u_{iI+6+4I} + (-2088199702118400 + 3698008175097600 I) u_{iI+7+4I} + (9922604357250 - 13088742293250 I) u_{iI+8+4I} + (76967239315200 - 23299742169600 I) u_{iI+3I} + (-5225288546649600 + 3120875483980800 I) u_{iI+1+3I} - (191742776167392000 + 670480962115680000 I) u_{iI+2+3I} + 744273814491584000 I u_{iI+3+3I} + (-2436378457754372352 + 6934916433823832064 I) u_{iI+4+3I} + (77129612703936000 + 6805488950208000 I) u_{iI+5+3I} + (114665338043776000 - 150284310992192000 I) u_{iI+6+3I} + (413647359091200 + 1452291974016000 I) u_{iI+7+3I} + (-8067880454400 + 3313171180800 I) u_{iI+8+3I} + (-26524225962000 + 4984079958000 I) u_{iI+2I} - (2622666338323200 + 64066816569600 I) u_{iI+1+2I} - 149648757869286000 I u_{iI+2+2I} + (191742776167392000 - 670480962115680000 I) u_{iI+3+2I} + (737741204283704400 - 999045201377293200 I) u_{iI+4+2I} + (220189769092800000 - 217492941594240000 I) u_{iI+5+2I} + (24425271953550000 - 18250244512110000 I) u_{iI+6+2I} + (326822932800000 - 65029161600000 I) u_{iI+7+2I} + (1466548200000 + 123353100000 I) u_{iI+8+2I} + (6058296691200 + 3029148345600 I) u_{iI+1I} + 469943353152000 I u_{iI+1+1I} + (2622666338323200 - 64066816569600 I) u_{iI+2+1I} + (5225288546649600 + 3120875483980800 I) u_{iI+3+1I} + (-13455973790937600 + 6728678517100800 I) u_{iI+4+1I} - (288845444160000 + 1418560528320000 I) u_{iI+5+1I} + (345703263360000 - 286048751040000 I) u_{iI+6+1I} + (-3643423680000 + 1508669760000 I) u_{iI+7+1I} - (53782560000 + 4137120000 I) u_{iI+8+1I} - 509628937689 I u_{iI} + (-6058296691200 + 3029148345600 I) u_{iI+1I} + (26524225962000 + 4984079958000 I) u_{iI+2I} - (76967239315200 + 23299742169600 I) u_{iI+3I} + (86237798421450 - 23665221450 I) u_{iI+4I} + (-25530167520000 + 8369393760000 I) u_{iI+5I} + (2396139460000 - 1500395520000 I) u_{iI+6I} + (-70331040000 + 23443680000 I) u_{iI+7I} + 549461250 u_{iI+8I} \right), O(\Delta x I^{24}), \text{ Quadrant I}$$

Error order: 24, Error: 1.6918924216054002578 × 10⁻⁷⁸, New Error: 1.6854170492180149729 × 10⁻¹⁵⁰
 Error order: 24, Error: 1.6854170492180149729 × 10⁻¹⁵⁰, New Error: 1.6854105862654434931 × 10⁻²²²
 Error order: 24, Error: 1.6854105862654434931 × 10⁻²²², New Error: 1.6854105798025033255 × 10⁻²⁹⁴
 Error order: 24, Error: 1.6854105798025033255 × 10⁻²⁹⁴, New Error: 1.6854105797960403854 × 10⁻³⁶⁶
 Error order: 24, Error: 1.6854105797960403854 × 10⁻³⁶⁶, New Error: 1.6854105797960339224 × 10⁻⁴³⁸

--- Derivative Order: 2 - x1=1 ---

4 I	1 + 4 I	2 + 4 I	3 + 4 I	4 + 4 I
3 I	1 + 3 I	2 + 3 I	3 + 3 I	4 + 3 I
2 I	1 + 2 I	2 + 2 I	3 + 2 I	4 + 2 I
I	1 + I	2 + I	3 + I	4 + I
0	1	2	3	4

$-\frac{226911}{88400}$	$-\frac{237961 I}{88400}$	$\frac{751448}{5525}$	$+\frac{666384 I}{5525}$	$-\frac{2022309}{11050}$	$-\frac{6265827 I}{11050}$	$-\frac{757232}{27625}$	$+\frac{4076376 I}{27625}$	$-\frac{58109 I}{22100}$
$\frac{1726888}{16575}$	$+\frac{11245328 I}{49725}$	$\frac{3524496}{325}$	$+\frac{7402592 I}{325}$	$\frac{1223784}{65}$	$+\frac{1272744 I}{13}$	$\frac{11068528 I}{585}$	$\frac{757232}{27625}$	$+\frac{4076376 I}{27625}$
$-\frac{1942749}{2210}$	$-\frac{2141649 I}{2210}$	$\frac{15223752}{325}$	$+\frac{48853656 I}{325}$	$-\frac{6126597 I}{10}$	$-\frac{1223784}{65}$	$+\frac{1272744 I}{13}$	$\frac{2022309}{11050}$	$-\frac{6265827 I}{11050}$
$\frac{3276976}{5525}$	$+\frac{2080488 I}{5525}$	$\frac{3453776 I}{65}$	$-\frac{15223752}{325}$	$+\frac{48853656 I}{325}$	$-\frac{3524496}{325}$	$+\frac{7402592 I}{325}$	$-\frac{751448}{5525}$	$+\frac{666384 I}{5525}$
$-\frac{112305269 I}{1989000}$	$-\frac{3276976}{5525}$	$+\frac{2080488 I}{5525}$	$\frac{1942749}{2210}$	$-\frac{2141649 I}{2210}$	$-\frac{1726888}{16575}$	$+\frac{11245328 I}{49725}$	$\frac{226911}{88400}$	$-\frac{237961 I}{88400}$

$$\frac{d^2}{dx^2} u(xI) = \frac{1}{3978000 \Delta x I^2} \left(-10210995 + 10708245 I \right) u_{iI+4I} + (541042560 + 479796480 I) u_{iI+1+4I} - (728031240 + 2255697720 I) u_{iI+2+4I} + (-109041408 + 586998144 I) u_{iI+3+4I} - 10459620 I u_{iI+4+4I} + (414453120 + 899626240 I) u_{iI+3I} + (43139831040 + 90607726080 I) u_{iI+1+3I} + (74895580800 + 389459664000 I) u_{iI+2+3I} + 75265990400 I u_{iI+3+3I} + (109041408 + 586998144 I) u_{iI+4+3I} - (3496948200 + 3854968200 I) u_{iI+2I} + (186338724480 + 597968749440 I) u_{iI+1+2I} - 2437160286600 I u_{iI+2+2I} + (-74895580800 + 389459664000 I) u_{iI+3+2I} + (728031240 - 2255697720 I) u_{iI+4+2I} + (2359422720 + 1497951360 I) u_{iI+1I} + 211371091200 I u_{iI+1+1I} + (-186338724480 + 597968749440 I) u_{iI+2+1I} + (-43139831040 + 90607726080 I) u_{iI+3+1I} + (-541042560 + 479796480 I) u_{iI+4+1I} - 224610538 I u_{iI} + (-2359422720 + 1497951360 I) u_{iI+1I} + (3496948200 - 3854968200 I) u_{iI+2I} + (-414453120 + 899626240 I) u_{iI+3I} + (10210995 - 10708245 I) u_{iI+4I} \right), O(\Delta x I^{23}), \text{ Quadrant I}$$

Error order: 23, Error: 6.4536571284201408409 × 10⁻⁷⁵, New Error: 6.4290028663150269423 × 10⁻¹⁴⁴
 Error order: 23, Error: 6.4290028663150269423 × 10⁻¹⁴⁴, New Error: 6.4289782592522178711 × 10⁻²¹³
 Error order: 23, Error: 6.4289782592522178711 × 10⁻²¹³, New Error: 6.4289782346452022010 × 10⁻²⁸²
 Error order: 23, Error: 6.4289782346452022010 × 10⁻²⁸², New Error: 6.4289782346205951854 × 10⁻³⁵¹
 Error order: 23, Error: 6.4289782346205951854 × 10⁻³⁵¹, New Error: 6.4289782346205705784 × 10⁻⁴²⁰

--- Derivative Order: 3 - x1=1 ---

4 I	1 + 4 I	2 + 4 I	3 + 4 I	4 + 4 I
3 I	1 + 3 I	2 + 3 I	3 + 3 I	4 + 3 I
2 I	1 + 2 I	2 + 2 I	3 + 2 I	4 + 2 I
I	1 + I	2 + I	3 + I	4 + I
0	1	2	3	4

$$\begin{bmatrix} \frac{213902293}{5304000} + \frac{680733 I}{353600} & -\frac{162716042}{82875} + \frac{7019834 I}{82875} & \frac{25206789}{4420} + \frac{16512609 I}{5525} & -\frac{9718926}{10625} - \frac{556522898 I}{414375} & \frac{107075459}{5304000} + \frac{107075459 I}{5304000} \\ -\frac{617604974}{248625} - \frac{250513858 I}{248625} & -\frac{410622668}{1625} - \frac{463490108 I}{4875} & -\frac{286146828}{325} - \frac{196883472 I}{325} & -\frac{421549756}{2925} - \frac{421549756 I}{2925} & -\frac{556522898}{414375} - \frac{9718926 I}{10625} \\ \frac{76197768}{5525} + \frac{5828247 I}{4420} & -\frac{2356533264}{1625} - \frac{1292444772 I}{1625} & \frac{459424233}{100} + \frac{459424233 I}{100} & -\frac{196883472}{325} - \frac{286146828 I}{325} & \frac{16512609}{5525} + \frac{25206789 I}{4420} \\ -\frac{193403218}{27625} + \frac{77146618 I}{82875} & -\frac{371511116}{975} - \frac{371511116 I}{975} & -\frac{1292444772}{1625} - \frac{2356533264 I}{1625} & -\frac{463490108}{4875} - \frac{410622668 I}{1625} & \frac{7019834}{82875} - \frac{162716042 I}{82875} \\ \frac{22773831179}{79560000} + \frac{22773831179 I}{79560000} & \frac{77146618}{82875} - \frac{193403218 I}{27625} & \frac{5828247}{4420} + \frac{76197768 I}{5525} & -\frac{250513858}{248625} - \frac{617604974 I}{248625} & \frac{680733}{353600} + \frac{213902293 I}{5304000} \end{bmatrix}$$

$$\frac{d^3}{dx^3} u(xI) = \frac{1}{79560000 \Delta x I^3} \left((3208534395 + 153164925 I) u_{iI+4I} + (-156207400320 + 6739040640 I) u_{iI+1+4I} + (453722202000 + 237781569600 I) u_{iI+2+4I} - (72775317888 + 106852396416 I) u_{iI+3+4I} + (1606131885 + 1606131885 I) u_{iI+4+4I} - (197633591680 + 80164434560 I) u_{iI+3I} - (20104085825280 + 7564158562560 I) u_{iI+1+3I} - (70048743494400 + 48197073945600 I) u_{iI+2+3I} - (11466153363200 + 11466153363200 I) u_{iI+3+3I} - (106852396416 + 72775317888 I) u_{iI+4+3I} + (1097247859200 + 104908446000 I) u_{iI+2I} - (115375868605440 + 63278096037120 I) u_{iI+1+2I} + (365517919774800 + 365517919774800 I) u_{iI+2+2I} - (48197073945600 + 70048743494400 I) u_{iI+3+2I} + (237781569600 + 453722202000 I) u_{iI+4+2I} + (-557001267840 + 74060753280 I) u_{iI+1I} - (30315307065600 + 30315307065600 I) u_{iI+1+1I} - (63278096037120 + 115375868605440 I) u_{iI+2+1I} - (7564158562560 + 20104085825280 I) u_{iI+3+1I} + (6739040640 - 156207400320 I) u_{iI+4+1I} + (22773831179 + 22773831179 I) u_{iI} + (74060753280 - 557001267840 I) u_{iI+1I} + (104908446000 + 1097247859200 I) u_{iI+2I} - (80164434560 + 197633591680 I) u_{iI+3I} + (153164925 + 3208534395 I) u_{iI+4I} \right), O(\Delta x I^{22}), \text{ Quadrant 1}$$

Error order: 22, Error: 3.5894732872115139188 × 10⁻⁷¹, New Error: 3.5757876082805621734 × 10⁻¹³⁷
 Error order: 22, Error: 3.5757876082805621734 × 10⁻¹³⁷, New Error: 3.5757739487508244828 × 10⁻²⁰³
 Error order: 22, Error: 3.5757739487508244828 × 10⁻²⁰³, New Error: 3.5757739350913208610 × 10⁻²⁶⁹
 Error order: 22, Error: 3.5757739350913208610 × 10⁻²⁶⁹, New Error: 3.5757739350776613574 × 10⁻³³⁵
 Error order: 22, Error: 3.5757739350776613574 × 10⁻³³⁵, New Error: 3.5757739350776476979 × 10⁻⁴⁰¹

"--- Derivative Order: 4 - xI=1 ---"

$$\begin{bmatrix} 4I & 1+4I & 2+4I & 3+4I & 4+4I \\ 3I & 1+3I & 2+3I & 3+3I & 4+3I \\ 2I & 1+2I & 2+2I & 3+2I & 4+2I \\ I & 1+I & 2+I & 3+I & 4+I \\ 0 & 1 & 2 & 3 & 4 \end{bmatrix}$$

$$\begin{bmatrix} -\frac{11310333127}{39780000} + \frac{1222831049 I}{4972500} & \frac{5200152388}{414375} - \frac{16432976258 I}{1243125} & -\frac{63158797197}{1105000} + \frac{19053482099 I}{1105000} & \frac{92133162946}{6215625} + \frac{17850865972 I}{6215625} & -\frac{622579391}{2340000} \\ \frac{9565005284}{414375} - \frac{11065187626 I}{1243125} & \frac{166456619464}{73125} - \frac{71702641292 I}{73125} & \frac{629167478}{65} - \frac{2788783966 I}{1625} & \frac{27554776532}{14625} & \frac{92133162946}{6215625} - \frac{17850865972 I}{6215625} \\ -\frac{22191006479}{221000} + \frac{16678009739 I}{221000} & \frac{116877295842}{8125} - \frac{31865175334 I}{8125} & -\frac{59133008877}{1000} & \frac{629167478}{65} + \frac{2788783966 I}{1625} & -\frac{63158797197}{1105000} - \frac{19053482099 I}{1105000} \\ \frac{50176459438}{1243125} - \frac{56282745476 I}{1243125} & \frac{68804657756}{14625} & \frac{116877295842}{8125} + \frac{31865175334 I}{8125} & \frac{166456619464}{73125} + \frac{71702641292 I}{73125} & \frac{5200152388}{414375} + \frac{16432976258 I}{1243125} \\ -\frac{554759931179}{198900000} & \frac{50176459438}{1243125} + \frac{56282745476 I}{1243125} & -\frac{22191006479}{221000} - \frac{16678009739 I}{221000} & \frac{9565005284}{414375} + \frac{11065187626 I}{1243125} & -\frac{11310333127}{39780000} - \frac{1222831049 I}{4972500} \end{bmatrix}$$

$$\frac{d^4}{dx^4} u(xI) = \frac{1}{198900000 \Delta x I^4} \left((-56551665635 + 48913241960 I) u_{iI+4I} + (2496073146240 - 2629276201280 I) u_{iI+1+4I} + (-11368583495460 + 3429626777820 I) u_{iI+2+4I} + (2948261214272 + 571227711104 I) u_{iI+3+4I} - 52919248235 u_{iI+4+4I} + (4591202536320 - 1770430020160 I) u_{iI+3I} + (452762004942080 - 195031184314240 I) u_{iI+1+3I} + (1925252482680000 - 341347157438400 I) u_{iI+2+3I} + 374744960835200 u_{iI+3+3I} + (2948261214272 - 571227711104 I) u_{iI+4+3I} + (-19971905831100 + 15010208765100 I) u_{iI+2I} + (2861156202212160 - 780059492176320 I) u_{iI+1+2I} - 11761555465635300 u_{iI+2+2I} + (1925252482680000 + 341347157438400 I) u_{iI+3+2I} - (11368583495460 + 3429626777820 I) u_{iI+4+2I} + (8028233510080 - 9005239276160 I) u_{iI+1I} + 935743345481600 u_{iI+1+1I} + (2861156202212160 + 780059492176320 I) u_{iI+2+1I} + (452762004942080 + 195031184314240 I) u_{iI+3+1I} + (2496073146240 + 2629276201280 I) u_{iI+4+1I} - 554759931179 u_{iI} + (8028233510080 + 9005239276160 I) u_{iI+1I} - (19971905831100 + 15010208765100 I) u_{iI+2I} + (4591202536320 + 1770430020160 I) u_{iI+3I} - (56551665635 + 48913241960 I) u_{iI+4I} \right), O(\Delta x I^{21}), \text{ Quadrant 1}$$

Error order: 21, Error: 1.7156430323279653755 × 10⁻⁶⁷, New Error: 1.7091155418669203430 × 10⁻¹³⁰
 Error order: 21, Error: 1.7091155418669203430 × 10⁻¹³⁰, New Error: 1.7091090268221998293 × 10⁻¹⁹³
 Error order: 21, Error: 1.7091090268221998293 × 10⁻¹⁹³, New Error: 1.7091090203071675387 × 10⁻²⁵⁶
 Error order: 21, Error: 1.7091090203071675387 × 10⁻²⁵⁶, New Error: 1.7091090203006525064 × 10⁻³¹⁹
 Error order: 21, Error: 1.7091090203006525064 × 10⁻³¹⁹, New Error: 1.7091090203006459914 × 10⁻³⁸²

"--- Derivative Order: 5 - xI=1 ---"

$$\begin{bmatrix} 4I & 1+4I & 2+4I & 3+4I & 4+4I \\ 3I & 1+3I & 2+3I & 3+3I & 4+3I \\ 2I & 1+2I & 2+2I & 3+2I & 4+2I \\ I & 1+I & 2+I & 3+I & 4+I \\ 0 & 1 & 2 & 3 & 4 \end{bmatrix}$$

$$\begin{array}{cccccccc} \frac{1222831049}{3978000} - \frac{20758677731 I}{6630000} & \frac{349316683}{276250} + \frac{125951589337 I}{828750} & \frac{26485404909}{110500} - \frac{192829757173 I}{442000} & - \frac{17376728533}{165750} + \frac{34903034183 I}{497250} & \frac{2613753557}{1657500} - \frac{2613753557 I}{1657500} & & & & \\ - \frac{24644881757}{276250} + \frac{153036626113 I}{828750} & - \frac{38605705559}{4875} + \frac{275748708739 I}{14625} & - \frac{76466134796}{1625} + \frac{107727242279 I}{1625} & - \frac{4152760597}{375} + \frac{4152760597 I}{375} & - \frac{34903034183}{497250} + \frac{17376728533 I}{165750} & & & & \\ \frac{16678009739}{88400} - \frac{2133677398 I}{2125} & - \frac{100322597201}{1625} + \frac{168780019068 I}{1625} & \frac{42769210911}{125} - \frac{42769210911 I}{125} & - \frac{107727242279}{1625} + \frac{76466134796 I}{1625} & \frac{192829757173}{442000} - \frac{26485404909 I}{110500} & & & & \\ - \frac{68953193}{21250} + \frac{89424246089 I}{191250} & - \frac{42527587421}{1625} + \frac{42527587421 I}{1625} & - \frac{168780019068}{1625} + \frac{100322597201 I}{1625} & - \frac{275748708739}{14625} + \frac{38605705559 I}{4875} & - \frac{125951589337}{828750} - \frac{349316683 I}{276250} & & & & \\ \frac{574403647}{44200} - \frac{574403647 I}{44200} & - \frac{89424246089}{191250} + \frac{68953193 I}{21250} & \frac{2133677398}{2125} - \frac{16678009739 I}{88400} & - \frac{153036626113}{828750} + \frac{24644881757 I}{276250} & \frac{20758677731}{6630000} - \frac{1222831049 I}{3978000} & & & & \end{array}$$

$$\frac{d^5}{dx^5} u(xI) = \frac{1}{19890000 \Delta x I^5} ((6114155245 - 62276033193 I) u_{il+4I} + (25150801176 + 3022838144088 I) u_{il+1+4I} + (4767372883620 - 8677339072785 I) u_{il+2+4I} + (-2085207423960 + 1396121367320 I) u_{il+3+4I} + (31365042684 - 31365042684 I) u_{il+4+4I} + (-1774431486504 + 3672879026712 I) u_{il+3I} + (-157511278680720 + 375018243885040 I) u_{il+1+3I} + (-935945489903040 + 1318581445494960 I) u_{il+2+3I} + (-220262422064880 + 220262422064880 I) u_{il+3+3I} + (-1396121367320 + 2085207423960 I) u_{il+4+3I} + (3752552191275 - 19971220445280 I) u_{il+2I} + (-1227948589740240 + 2065867433392320 I) u_{il+1+2I} + (6805436840158320 - 6805436840158320 I) u_{il+2+2I} + (-1318581445494960 + 935945489903040 I) u_{il+3+2I} + (8677339072785 - 4767372883620 I) u_{il+4+2I} + (-64540188648 + 9300121593256 I) u_{il+1I} + (-520537670033040 + 520537670033040 I) u_{il+1+1I} + (-2065867433392320 + 1227948589740240 I) u_{il+2+1I} + (-375018243885040 + 157511278680720 I) u_{il+3+1I} - (3022838144088 + 25150801176 I) u_{il+4+1I} + (258481641150 - 258481641150 I) u_{ilI} + (-9300121593256 + 64540188648 I) u_{il+1I} + (19971220445280 - 3752552191275 I) u_{il+2I} + (-3672879026712 + 1774431486504 I) u_{il+3I} + (62276033193 - 6114155245 I) u_{il+4I}), O(\Delta x I^{20}), \text{ Quadrant I}$$

Error order: 20, Error: 7.3878336550595243247 × 10⁻⁶⁴, New Error: 7.3597899415446598874 × 10⁻¹²⁴
 Error order: 20, Error: 7.3597899415446598874 × 10⁻¹²⁴, New Error: 7.3597619511778833909 × 10⁻¹⁸⁴
 Error order: 20, Error: 7.3597619511778833909 × 10⁻¹⁸⁴, New Error: 7.3597619231875698935 × 10⁻²⁴⁴
 Error order: 20, Error: 7.3597619231875698935 × 10⁻²⁴⁴, New Error: 7.3597619231595795800 × 10⁻³⁰⁴
 Error order: 20, Error: 7.3597619231595795800 × 10⁻³⁰⁴, New Error: 7.3597619231595515897 × 10⁻³⁶⁴

--- Derivative Order: 6 - x1=1 ---

$$\begin{array}{ccccc} 4I & 1+4I & 2+4I & 3+4I & 4+4I \\ 3I & 1+3I & 2+3I & 3+3I & 4+3I \\ 2I & 1+2I & 2+2I & 3+2I & 4+2I \\ I & 1+I & 2+I & 3+I & 4+I \\ 0 & 1 & 2 & 3 & 4 \end{array}$$

$$\begin{array}{cccccccc} \frac{65401869319}{4420000} + \frac{50473497181 I}{2652000} & - \frac{112214177059}{138125} - \frac{114476078827 I}{138125} & \frac{17404815459}{17000} + \frac{1618240018413 I}{442000} & \frac{15871688231}{82875} - \frac{26152114629 I}{27625} & \frac{37852766411 I}{2210000} & & & & \\ - \frac{191605562087}{414375} - \frac{205116577043 I}{138125} & - \frac{90428274644}{1625} - \frac{702501239926 I}{4875} & - \frac{2461873314}{25} - \frac{987675471948 I}{1625} & - \frac{581312600878 I}{4875} & - \frac{15871688231}{82875} - \frac{26152114629 I}{27625} & & & & \\ \frac{221295624681}{55250} + \frac{570321909543 I}{88400} & - \frac{335671009638}{1625} - \frac{1417757560116 I}{1625} & \frac{906552119709 I}{250} & \frac{2461873314}{25} - \frac{987675471948 I}{1625} & - \frac{17404815459}{17000} + \frac{1618240018413 I}{442000} & & & & \\ - \frac{905337930043}{414375} - \frac{341953013673 I}{138125} & - \frac{434118851874 I}{1625} & \frac{335671009638}{1625} - \frac{1417757560116 I}{1625} & \frac{90428274644}{1625} - \frac{702501239926 I}{4875} & \frac{112214177059}{138125} - \frac{114476078827 I}{138125} & & & & \\ \frac{15294778547 I}{132600} & \frac{905337930043}{414375} - \frac{341953013673 I}{138125} & - \frac{221295624681}{55250} + \frac{570321909543 I}{88400} & \frac{191605562087}{414375} - \frac{205116577043 I}{138125} & - \frac{65401869319}{4420000} + \frac{50473497181 I}{2652000} & & & & \end{array}$$

$$\frac{d^6}{dx^6} u(xI) = \frac{1}{13260000 \Delta x I^6} ((196205607957 + 252367485905 I) u_{il+4I} - (10772560997664 + 10989703567392 I) u_{il+1+4I} + (13575756058020 + 48547200552390 I) u_{il+2+4I} + (2539470116960 - 12553015021920 I) u_{il+3+4I} + 227116598466 I u_{il+4+4I} - (6131377986784 + 19691191396128 I) u_{il+3I} - (737894721095040 + 1910803372598720 I) u_{il+1+3I} - (1305777605745600 + 8059431851095680 I) u_{il+2+3I} - 1581170274388160 I u_{il+3+3I} - (2539470116960 + 12553015021920 I) u_{il+4+3I} + (53110949923440 + 85548286431450 I) u_{il+2I} - (2739075438646080 + 11568901690546560 I) u_{il+1+2I} + 48083524429365360 I u_{il+2+2I} + (1305777605745600 - 8059431851095680 I) u_{il+3+2I} + (-13575756058020 + 48547200552390 I) u_{il+4+2I} - (28970813761376 + 32827489312608 I) u_{il+1I} - 3542409831291840 I u_{il+1+1I} + (2739075438646080 - 11568901690546560 I) u_{il+2+1I} + (737894721095040 - 1910803372598720 I) u_{il+3+1I} + (10772560997664 - 10989703567392 I) u_{il+4+1I} + 1529477854700 I u_{ilI} + (28970813761376 - 32827489312608 I) u_{il+1I} + (-53110949923440 + 85548286431450 I) u_{il+2I} + (6131377986784 - 19691191396128 I) u_{il+3I} + (-196205607957 + 252367485905 I) u_{il+4I}), O(\Delta x I^{19}), \text{ Quadrant I}$$

Error order: 19, Error: 2.9208131222517624690 × 10⁻⁶⁰, New Error: 2.9097540409993722534 × 10⁻¹¹⁷
 Error order: 19, Error: 2.9097540409993722534 × 10⁻¹¹⁷, New Error: 2.9097430029020531103 × 10⁻¹⁷⁴
 Error order: 19, Error: 2.9097430029020531103 × 10⁻¹⁷⁴, New Error: 2.9097429918639767486 × 10⁻²³¹
 Error order: 19, Error: 2.9097429918639767486 × 10⁻²³¹, New Error: 2.9097429918529386722 × 10⁻²⁸⁸
 Error order: 19, Error: 2.9097429918529386722 × 10⁻²⁸⁸, New Error: 2.9097429918529276341 × 10⁻³⁴⁵

--- Derivative Order: 7 - x1=1 ---

$$\begin{array}{ccccc} 4I & 1+4I & 2+4I & 3+4I & 4+4I \\ 3I & 1+3I & 2+3I & 3+3I & 4+3I \\ 2I & 1+2I & 2+2I & 3+2I & 4+2I \\ I & 1+I & 2+I & 3+I & 4+I \\ 0 & 1 & 2 & 3 & 4 \end{array}$$

$$\left[\begin{array}{cccccccc} \frac{595984838771}{3536000} - \frac{457813085233 I}{17680000} & \frac{3389338473479}{414375} + \frac{98165925067 I}{414375} & \frac{197409813699}{8500} - \frac{911472963009 I}{68000} & \frac{20725968823}{5525} + \frac{157683439809 I}{27625} & \frac{4558264396819}{53040000} - \frac{4558264396819 I}{53040000} \\ \frac{3917356452149}{414375} + \frac{2231470475353 I}{414375} & \frac{1586218336381}{1625} + \frac{739738752963 I}{1625} & \frac{5644278093804}{1625} + \frac{4136236181826 I}{1625} & \frac{2890583626609}{4875} + \frac{2890583626609 I}{4875} & \frac{157683439809}{27625} + \frac{20725968823 I}{5525} \\ \frac{8855360612679}{176800} - \frac{1549069372767 I}{110500} & \frac{646765645974}{125} + \frac{5378825232564 I}{1625} & \frac{8871705686781}{500} - \frac{8871705686781 I}{500} & \frac{4136236181826}{1625} + \frac{5644278093804 I}{1625} & \frac{911472963009}{68000} - \frac{197409813699 I}{8500} \\ \frac{2959501395739}{138125} + \frac{328064339617 I}{138125} & \frac{6148097038223}{4875} + \frac{6148097038223 I}{4875} & \frac{5378825232564}{1625} + \frac{646765645974 I}{125} & \frac{739738752963}{1625} + \frac{1586218336381 I}{1625} & \frac{98165925067}{414375} + \frac{3389338473479 I}{414375} \\ \frac{5152854524377}{10608000} - \frac{5152854524377 I}{10608000} & \frac{328064339617}{138125} + \frac{2959501395739 I}{138125} & \frac{1549069372767}{110500} - \frac{8855360612679 I}{176800} & \frac{2231470475353}{414375} + \frac{3917356452149 I}{414375} & \frac{457813085233}{17680000} - \frac{595984838771 I}{3536000} \end{array} \right]$$

$$\frac{d^7}{dxI^7} u(xI) = \frac{1}{53040000 \Delta x I^7} (7 (- (1277110368795 + 196205607957 I) u_{iI+4I} + (61976474943616 + 1795034058368 I) u_{iI+1+4I} - (175976748211680 + 101564130163860 I) u_{iI+2+4I} + (28424185814400 + 43250314919040 I) u_{iI+3+4I} - (651180628117 + 651180628117 I) u_{iI+4+4I} + (71631660839296 + 40804031549312 I) u_{iI+3I} + (7396309499925120 + 3449296128101760 I) u_{iI+1+3I} + (26318462425966080 + 19286678424971520 I) u_{iI+2+3I} + (4492792836786560 + 4492792836786560 I) u_{iI+3+3I} + (43250314919040 + 28424185814400 I) u_{iI+4+3I} - (379515454829100 + 106221899846880 I) u_{iI+2I} + (39205085557098240 + 25080693655841280 I) u_{iI+1+2I} - (134444362750532640 + 134444362750532640 I) u_{iI+2+2I} + (19286678424971520 + 26318462425966080 I) u_{iI+3+2I} - (101564130163860 + 175976748211680 I) u_{iI+4+2I} + (162349790851968 + 17996672344704 I) u_{iI+1I} + (9555899396552320 + 9555899396552320 I) u_{iI+1+1I} + (25080693655841280 + 39205085557098240 I) u_{iI+2+1I} + (3449296128101760 + 7396309499925120 I) u_{iI+3+1I} + (1795034058368 + 61976474943616 I) u_{iI+4+1I} - (3680610374555 + 3680610374555 I) u_{iI} + (17996672344704 + 162349790851968 I) u_{iI+1I} - (106221899846880 + 379515454829100 I) u_{iI+2I} + (40804031549312 + 71631660839296 I) u_{iI+3I} - (196205607957 + 1277110368795 I) u_{iI+4I}), O(\Delta x I^{18}), \text{ Quadrant I}$$

Error order: 18, Error: 1.0693150219929743977 × 10⁻⁵⁶, New Error: 1.0652776644634775129 × 10⁻¹¹⁰
 Error order: 18, Error: 1.0652776644634775129 × 10⁻¹¹⁰, New Error: 1.0652736347450061060 × 10⁻¹⁶⁴
 Error order: 18, Error: 1.0652736347450061060 × 10⁻¹⁶⁴, New Error: 1.0652736307152952640 × 10⁻²¹⁸
 Error order: 18, Error: 1.0652736307152952640 × 10⁻²¹⁸, New Error: 1.0652736307112655532 × 10⁻²⁷²
 Error order: 18, Error: 1.0652736307112655532 × 10⁻²⁷², New Error: 1.0652736307112615235 × 10⁻³²⁶

"--- Derivative Order: 8 - xI=1 ---"

$$\begin{bmatrix} 4 I & 1 + 4 I & 2 + 4 I & 3 + 4 I & 4 + 4 I \\ 3 I & 1 + 3 I & 2 + 3 I & 3 + 3 I & 4 + 3 I \\ 2 I & 1 + 2 I & 2 + 2 I & 3 + 2 I & 4 + 2 I \\ I & 1 + I & 2 + I & 3 + I & 4 + I \\ 0 & 1 & 2 & 3 & 4 \end{bmatrix}$$

$$\left[\begin{array}{cccccccc} \frac{12195416683093}{13260000} - \frac{3092738978 I}{4875} & \frac{5468926550444}{138125} + \frac{1144915443238 I}{31875} & \frac{37529907186807}{221000} - \frac{141413897457 I}{3250} & \frac{3630553621534}{82875} - \frac{768267018652 I}{82875} & \frac{10603004112533}{13260000} \\ \frac{9467258520524}{138125} + \frac{2243299291842 I}{138125} & \frac{32089793166368}{4875} + \frac{10966019082676 I}{4875} & \frac{44873081599374}{1625} + \frac{1312349852142 I}{325} & \frac{8881380163852}{1625} & \frac{3630553621534}{82875} + \frac{768267018652 I}{82875} \\ \frac{64900262883519}{221000} - \frac{97105925889 I}{650} & \frac{4775878096794}{125} + \frac{12617796645846 I}{1625} & \frac{160904808102717}{1000} & \frac{44873081599374}{1625} - \frac{1312349852142 I}{325} & \frac{37529907186807}{221000} + \frac{141413897457 I}{3250} \\ \frac{43655001092962}{414375} + \frac{32029056989804 I}{414375} & \frac{53872314181756}{4875} & \frac{4775878096794}{125} - \frac{12617796645846 I}{1625} & \frac{32089793166368}{4875} - \frac{10966019082676 I}{4875} & \frac{5468926550444}{138125} - \frac{1144915443238 I}{31875} \\ \frac{683937714271}{176800} & \frac{43655001092962}{414375} - \frac{32029056989804 I}{414375} & \frac{64900262883519}{221000} + \frac{97105925889 I}{650} & \frac{9467258520524}{138125} - \frac{2243299291842 I}{138125} & \frac{12195416683093}{13260000} + \frac{3092738978 I}{4875} \end{array} \right]$$

$$\frac{d^8}{dxI^8} u(xI) = \frac{1}{13260000 \Delta x I^8} (7 ((1742202383299 - 1201750002880 I) u_{iI+4I} + (-75002421263232 + 68040689198144 I) u_{iI+1+4I} + (321684918744060 - 82424100232080 I) u_{iI+2+4I} - (82984082777920 + 17560388997760 I) u_{iI+3+4I} + 1514714873219 u_{iI+4+4I} + (-129836688281472 + 30765247430976 I) u_{iI+3I} + (-12469176773217280 + 4261081700696960 I) u_{iI+1+3I} + (-52309192264413120 + 7649124852484800 I) u_{iI+2+3I} - 10353151733861760 u_{iI+3+3I} + (-82984082777920 + 17560388997760 I) u_{iI+4+3I} + (556287967573020 - 282994412590800 I) u_{iI+2I} + (-72375021215415360 + 14708745804300480 I) u_{iI+1+2I} + 304799679348861060 u_{iI+2+2I} - (52309192264413120 + 7649124852484800 I) u_{iI+3+2I} + (321684918744060 + 82424100232080 I) u_{iI+4+2I} + (-199565719282112 + 146418546239104 I) u_{iI+1I} - 20933242082053760 u_{iI+1+1I} - (72375021215415360 + 14708745804300480 I) u_{iI+2+1I} - (12469176773217280 + 4261081700696960 I) u_{iI+3+1I} - (75002421263232 + 68040689198144 I) u_{iI+4+1I} + 7327904081475 u_{iI} - (199565719282112 + 146418546239104 I) u_{iI+1I} + (556287967573020 + 282994412590800 I) u_{iI+2I} - (129836688281472 + 30765247430976 I) u_{iI+3I} + (1742202383299 + 1201750002880 I) u_{iI+4I}), O(\Delta x I^{17}), \text{ Quadrant I}$$

Error order: 17, Error: 3.6390845609315405202 × 10⁻⁵³, New Error: 3.6253877812286483392 × 10⁻¹⁰⁴
 Error order: 17, Error: 3.6253877812286483392 × 10⁻¹⁰⁴, New Error: 3.6253741102830955906 × 10⁻¹⁵⁵
 Error order: 17, Error: 3.6253741102830955906 × 10⁻¹⁵⁵, New Error: 3.6253740966121758395 × 10⁻²⁰⁶
 Error order: 17, Error: 3.6253740966121758395 × 10⁻²⁰⁶, New Error: 3.6253740965985049198 × 10⁻²⁵⁷
 Error order: 17, Error: 3.6253740965985049198 × 10⁻²⁵⁷, New Error: 3.6253740965984912488 × 10⁻³⁰⁸

"--- Derivative Order: 9 - xI=1 ---"

$$\begin{bmatrix} 4 I & 1 + 4 I & 2 + 4 I & 3 + 4 I & 4 + 4 I \\ 3 I & 1 + 3 I & 2 + 3 I & 3 + 3 I & 4 + 3 I \\ 2 I & 1 + 2 I & 2 + 2 I & 3 + 2 I & 4 + 2 I \\ I & 1 + I & 2 + I & 3 + I & 4 + I \\ 0 & 1 & 2 & 3 & 4 \end{bmatrix}$$

$$\begin{array}{cccccccc}
-\frac{4639108467}{3250} + \frac{53906128521 I}{8125} & \frac{362930639001}{16250} - \frac{5250697917087 I}{16250} & -\frac{897275968533}{1625} + \frac{5905482671151 I}{6500} & \frac{744271033443}{3250} - \frac{479271279291 I}{3250} & -\frac{112203100527}{32500} + \frac{112203100527 I}{32500} \\
\frac{3809124960081}{16250} - \frac{5710731446343 I}{16250} & \frac{31019676366693}{1625} - \frac{60160971852051 I}{1625} & \frac{164569192619076}{1625} - \frac{217325917255419 I}{1625} & \frac{2921019871119}{125} - \frac{2921019871119 I}{125} & \frac{479271279291}{3250} - \frac{744271033443 I}{3250} \\
-\frac{873953333001}{1300} + \frac{226490810364 I}{125} & \frac{210663294739821}{1625} - \frac{307766419667028 I}{1625} & -\frac{84586823164746}{125} + \frac{84586823164746 I}{125} & \frac{217325917255419}{1625} - \frac{164569192619076 I}{1625} & -\frac{5905482671151}{6500} + \frac{897275968533 I}{1625} \\
\frac{173250480669}{1250} - \frac{903746382693 I}{1250} & \frac{73077514438341}{1625} - \frac{73077514438341 I}{1625} & \frac{307766419667028}{1625} - \frac{210663294739821 I}{1625} & \frac{60160971852051}{1625} - \frac{31019676366693 I}{1625} & \frac{5250697917087}{16250} - \frac{362930639001 I}{16250} \\
-\frac{18863939199}{1300} + \frac{18863939199 I}{1300} & \frac{903746382693}{1250} - \frac{173250480669 I}{1250} & -\frac{226490810364}{125} + \frac{873953333001 I}{1300} & \frac{5710731446343}{16250} - \frac{3809124960081 I}{16250} & -\frac{53906128521}{8125} + \frac{4639108467 I}{3250}
\end{array}$$

$$\frac{d^9}{dx^9} u(xI) = \frac{1}{32500 \Delta x I^9} (21 (-2209099270 + 10267834004 I) u_{il+41} + (34564822762 - 500066468294 I) u_{il+1+41} + (-854548541460 + 1406067302655 I) u_{il+2+41} + (354414777830 - 228224418710 I) u_{il+3+41} + (-5343004787 + 5343004787 I) u_{il+4+41} + (362773805722 - 543879185366 I) u_{il+31} + (29542548920660 - 57296163668620 I) u_{il+1+31} + (156732564399120 - 206977064052780 I) u_{il+2+31} + (36165007928140 - 36165007928140 I) u_{il+3+31} + (228224418710 - 354414777830 I) u_{il+4+31} + (-1040420634525 + 2804171937840 I) u_{il+21} + (200631709276020 - 293110875873360 I) u_{il+1+21} + (-1047265429658760 + 1047265429658760 I) u_{il+2+21} + (206977064052780 - 156732564399120 I) u_{il+3+21} + (-1406067302655 + 854548541460 I) u_{il+4+21} + (214500595114 - 1118924092858 I) u_{il+11} + (69597632798420 - 69597632798420 I) u_{il+1+11} + (293110875873360 - 200631709276020 I) u_{il+2+11} + (57296163668620 - 29542548920660 I) u_{il+3+11} + (500066468294 - 34564822762 I) u_{il+4+11} + (-22457070475 + 22457070475 I) u_{il} + (1118924092858 - 214500595114 I) u_{il+1} + (-2804171937840 + 1040420634525 I) u_{il+2} + (543879185366 - 362773805722 I) u_{il+3} + (-10267834004 + 2209099270 I) u_{il+4}), O(\Delta x I^{16}), \text{ Quadrant I}$$

Error order: 16, Error: 1.152693422224552523 × 10⁻⁴⁹, New Error: 1.1483701924812111994 × 10⁻⁹⁷
Error order: 16, Error: 1.1483701924812111994 × 10⁻⁹⁷, New Error: 1.1483658773769744063 × 10⁻¹⁴⁵
Error order: 16, Error: 1.1483658773769744063 × 10⁻¹⁴⁵, New Error: 1.1483658730618782848 × 10⁻¹⁹³
Error order: 16, Error: 1.1483658730618782848 × 10⁻¹⁹³, New Error: 1.1483658730575631887 × 10⁻²⁴¹
Error order: 16, Error: 1.1483658730575631887 × 10⁻²⁴¹, New Error: 1.1483658730575588736 × 10⁻²⁸⁹

--- Derivative Order: 10 - x1=1 ---

$$\begin{bmatrix} 4I & 1+4I & 2+4I & 3+4I & 4+4I \\ 3I & 1+3I & 2+3I & 3+3I & 4+3I \\ 2I & 1+2I & 2+2I & 3+2I & 4+2I \\ I & 1+I & 2+I & 3+I & 4+I \\ 0 & 1 & 2 & 3 & 4 \end{bmatrix}$$

$$\begin{array}{cccccccc}
-\frac{255973965891}{13000} - \frac{85041479061 I}{2600} & \frac{1892892278109}{1625} + \frac{2268884329677 I}{1625} & -\frac{875568381093}{650} - \frac{7569789083577 I}{1300} & -\frac{108100091547}{325} + \frac{487414740939 I}{325} & -\frac{44924422431 I}{1625} \\
\frac{611614744419}{1625} + \frac{3760675466373 I}{1625} & \frac{21417266783388}{325} + \frac{71975829052134 I}{325} & \frac{7827605321886}{65} + \frac{301203582319836 I}{325} & \frac{60201018819102 I}{325} & \frac{108100091547}{325} + \frac{487414740939 I}{325} \\
-\frac{1300005785043}{325} - \frac{2521555722819 I}{260} & \frac{68946797958066}{325} + \frac{401046643728612 I}{325} & -\frac{131876879143779 I}{25} & -\frac{7827605321886}{65} + \frac{301203582319836 I}{325} & \frac{875568381093}{650} - \frac{7569789083577 I}{1300} \\
\frac{3342448384191}{1625} + \frac{5293319430903 I}{1625} & \frac{110394544229718 I}{325} & -\frac{68946797958066}{325} + \frac{401046643728612 I}{325} & -\frac{21417266783388}{325} + \frac{71975829052134 I}{325} & -\frac{1892892278109}{1625} + \frac{2268884329677 I}{1625} \\
-\frac{26557160343 I}{260} & -\frac{3342448384191}{1625} + \frac{5293319430903 I}{1625} & \frac{1300005785043}{325} - \frac{2521555722819 I}{260} & -\frac{611614744419}{1625} + \frac{3760675466373 I}{1625} & \frac{255973965891}{13000} - \frac{85041479061 I}{2600}
\end{array}$$

$$\frac{d^{10}}{dx^{10}} u(xI) = \frac{1}{13000 \Delta x I^{10}} (21 (-12189236471 + 20247971205 I) u_{il+41} + (721101820232 + 864336887496 I) u_{il+1+41} - (833874648660 + 3604661468370 I) u_{il+2+41} + (-205904936280 + 928409030360 I) u_{il+3+41} - 17114065688 I u_{il+4+41} + (232996093112 + 1432638272904 I) u_{il+31} + (40794793873120 + 137096817242160 I) u_{il+1+31} + (74548622113200 + 573721109180640 I) u_{il+2+31} + 114668607274480 I u_{il+3+31} + (205904936280 + 928409030360 I) u_{il+4+31} - (2476201495320 + 6003704101950 I) u_{il+21} + (131327234205840 + 763898369006880 I) u_{il+1+21} - 3265522721655480 I u_{il+2+21} + (-74548622113200 + 573721109180640 I) u_{il+3+21} + (833874648660 - 3604661468370 I) u_{il+4+21} + (1273313670168 + 2016502640344 I) u_{il+11} + 210275322342320 I u_{il+1+11} + (-131327234205840 + 763898369006880 I) u_{il+2+11} + (-40794793873120 + 137096817242160 I) u_{il+3+11} + (-721101820232 + 864336887496 I) u_{il+4+11} - 63231334150 I u_{il} + (-1273313670168 + 2016502640344 I) u_{il+1} + (2476201495320 - 6003704101950 I) u_{il+2} + (-232996093112 + 1432638272904 I) u_{il+3} + (12189236471 - 20247971205 I) u_{il+4}), O(\Delta x I^{15}), \text{ Quadrant I}$$

Error order: 15, Error: 3.3970703921767000476 × 10⁻⁴⁶, New Error: 3.3843801657771191708 × 10⁻⁹¹
Error order: 15, Error: 3.3843801657771191708 × 10⁻⁹¹, New Error: 3.3843674993070642164 × 10⁻¹³⁶
Error order: 15, Error: 3.3843674993070642164 × 10⁻¹³⁶, New Error: 3.3843674866406178881 × 10⁻¹⁸¹
Error order: 15, Error: 3.3843674866406178881 × 10⁻¹⁸¹, New Error: 3.3843674866279514418 × 10⁻²²⁶
Error order: 15, Error: 3.3843674866279514418 × 10⁻²²⁶, New Error: 3.3843674866279387754 × 10⁻²⁷¹

--- Derivative Order: 1 - x1=1 ---

$$\begin{bmatrix} 5I & 1+5I & 2+5I & 3+5I & 4+5I & 5+5I \\ 4I & 1+4I & 2+4I & 3+4I & 4+4I & 5+4I \\ 3I & 1+3I & 2+3I & 3+3I & 4+3I & 5+3I \\ 2I & 1+2I & 2+2I & 3+2I & 4+2I & 5+2I \\ I & 1+I & 2+I & 3+I & 4+I & 5+I \\ 0 & 1 & 2 & 3 & 4 & 5 \end{bmatrix}$$

$$\begin{pmatrix} \frac{1}{5} & -\frac{5375}{442} - \frac{13945 I}{442} & -\frac{145960}{377} - \frac{15580 I}{377} & -\frac{57810}{221} + \frac{54530 I}{221} & \frac{6095}{697} + \frac{17750 I}{697} & \frac{1}{10} - \frac{I}{10} \\ -\frac{785}{34} + \frac{2475 I}{68} & -\frac{309140}{17} - \frac{77285 I}{17} & \frac{646816}{5} - \frac{1495762 I}{5} & \frac{5578788}{25} + \frac{4689416 I}{25} & -\frac{77285}{8} + \frac{77285 I}{8} & -\frac{17750}{697} - \frac{6095 I}{697} \\ -\frac{26240}{39} - \frac{2460 I}{13} & -\frac{848946}{5} + \frac{2142578 I}{5} & \frac{103086300}{13} + \frac{68724200 I}{13} & \frac{17181050}{3} - \frac{17181050 I}{3} & -\frac{4689416}{25} - \frac{5578788 I}{25} & -\frac{54530}{221} + \frac{57810 I}{221} \\ -\frac{3690}{13} - \frac{13120 I}{13} & \frac{2991524}{5} + \frac{1293632 I}{5} & -8590525 + 8590525 I & -\frac{68724200}{13} - \frac{103086300 I}{13} & \frac{1495762}{5} - \frac{646816 I}{5} & \frac{15580}{377} + \frac{145960 I}{377} \\ \frac{2475}{17} - \frac{1570 I}{17} & \frac{77285}{2} - \frac{77285 I}{2} & -\frac{1293632}{5} - \frac{2991524 I}{5} & -\frac{2142578}{5} + \frac{848946 I}{5} & \frac{77285}{17} + \frac{309140 I}{17} & \frac{13945}{442} + \frac{5375 I}{442} \\ -\frac{347416769}{52553800} + \frac{347416769 I}{52553800} & \frac{1570}{17} - \frac{2475 I}{17} & \frac{13120}{13} + \frac{3690 I}{13} & \frac{2460}{13} + \frac{26240 I}{39} & -\frac{2475}{68} + \frac{785 I}{34} & -\frac{I}{5} \end{pmatrix}$$

$$\frac{d}{dx} u(xI) = \frac{1}{157661400 \Delta x I} (31532280 u_{iI+5I} - (1917262500 + 4974181500 I) u_{iI+1+5I} - (61040472000 + 6515556000 I) u_{iI+2+5I} + (-41241654000 + 38901702000 I) u_{iI+3+5I} + (1378689000 + 4015050000 I) u_{iI+4+5I} + (15766140 - 15766140 I) u_{iI+5+5I} + (-3640123500 + 5738411250 I) u_{iI+4I} - (2867026188000 + 716756547000 I) u_{iI+1+4I} + (20395583220480 - 47164786197360 I) u_{iI+2+4I} + (35182381055328 + 29573595669696 I) u_{iI+3+4I} + (-1523107662375 + 1523107662375 I) u_{iI+4+4I} - (4015050000 + 1378689000 I) u_{iI+5+4I} - (106077824000 + 29834388000 I) u_{iI+3I} + (-26769202976880 + 67560369417840 I) u_{iI+1+3I} + (1250210029140000 + 833473352760000 I) u_{iI+2+3I} + (902929465490000 - 902929465490000 I) u_{iI+3+3I} - (29573595669696 + 35182381055328 I) u_{iI+4+3I} + (-38901702000 + 41241654000 I) u_{iI+5+3I} - (44751582000 + 159116736000 I) u_{iI+2I} + (94329572394720 + 40791166440960 I) u_{iI+1+2I} + (-1354394198235000 + 1354394198235000 I) u_{iI+2+2I} - (833473352760000 + 1250210029140000 I) u_{iI+3+2I} + (47164786197360 - 20395583220480 I) u_{iI+4+2I} + (6515556000 + 61040472000 I) u_{iI+5+2I} + (22953645000 - 14560494000 I) u_{iI+1I} + (6092430649500 - 6092430649500 I) u_{iI+1+1I} - (40791166440960 + 94329572394720 I) u_{iI+2+1I} + (-67560369417840 + 26769202976880 I) u_{iI+3+1I} + (716756547000 + 2867026188000 I) u_{iI+4+1I} + (4974181500 + 1917262500 I) u_{iI+5+1I} + (-1042250307 + 1042250307 I) u_{iI} + (14560494000 - 22953645000 I) u_{iI+1} + (159116736000 + 44751582000 I) u_{iI+2} + (29834388000 + 106077824000 I) u_{iI+3} + (-5738411250 + 3640123500 I) u_{iI+4} - 31532280 I u_{iI+5}), O(\Delta x I^{35}), \text{ Quadrant } I$$

Error order: 35, Error: 1.3170634086809360830 × 10⁻¹¹⁶, New Error: 1.3106907240242612008 × 10⁻²²¹
 Error order: 35, Error: 1.3106907240242612008 × 10⁻²²¹, New Error: 1.3106843667972445504 × 10⁻³²⁶
 Error order: 35, Error: 1.3106843667972445504 × 10⁻³²⁶, New Error: 1.3106843604400329664 × 10⁻⁴³¹
 Error order: 35, Error: 1.3106843604400329664 × 10⁻⁴³¹, New Error: 1.3106843604336757548 × 10⁻⁵³⁶
 Error order: 35, Error: 1.3106843604336757548 × 10⁻⁵³⁶, New Error: 1.3106843604336693976 × 10⁻⁶⁴¹

"--- Derivative Order: 2 - xI=1 ---"

$$\begin{pmatrix} 5 I & 1 + 5 I & 2 + 5 I & 3 + 5 I & 4 + 5 I & 5 + 5 I \\ 4 I & 1 + 4 I & 2 + 4 I & 3 + 4 I & 4 + 4 I & 5 + 4 I \\ 3 I & 1 + 3 I & 2 + 3 I & 3 + 3 I & 4 + 3 I & 5 + 3 I \\ 2 I & 1 + 2 I & 2 + 2 I & 3 + 2 I & 4 + 2 I & 5 + 2 I \\ I & 1 + I & 2 + I & 3 + I & 4 + I & 5 + I \\ 0 & 1 & 2 & 3 & 4 & 5 \end{pmatrix}$$

$$\begin{pmatrix} -\frac{347416769}{131384500} + \frac{336906009 I}{131384500} & \frac{164007308677}{290359745} + \frac{300349711933 I}{1161438980} & \frac{2331855217}{416585} - \frac{1851561099 I}{416585} & \frac{1576696776}{7081945} - \frac{46742870953 I}{7081945} & -\frac{39703135721}{89341460} - \frac{19498524379 I}{89341460} & \frac{342161389 I}{131384500} \\ -\frac{56378902439}{357365840} - \frac{276934692821 I}{357365840} & \frac{342470529}{1156} - \frac{995879307 I}{5780} & \frac{6990940109}{3250} + \frac{18050467537 I}{3250} & -\frac{8639816987}{1625} + \frac{721432991 I}{1625} & -\frac{42605943 I}{170} & \frac{39703135721}{89341460} - \frac{19498524379 I}{89341460} \\ \frac{14086426129}{1249755} - \frac{22290035461 I}{3749265} & -\frac{5196047084}{1625} - \frac{12549608413 I}{1625} & -\frac{28705734965}{169} + \frac{5562464073 I}{169} & \frac{17271547919 I}{117} & \frac{8639816987}{1625} + \frac{721432991 I}{1625} & -\frac{1576696776}{7081945} - \frac{46742870953 I}{7081945} \\ \frac{13403226729}{833170} + \frac{8227077787 I}{833170} & -\frac{17687846317}{1625} + \frac{6686128069 I}{1625} & -\frac{5682731423 I}{26} & \frac{28705734965}{169} + \frac{5562464073 I}{169} & -\frac{6990940109}{3250} + \frac{18050467537 I}{3250} & -\frac{2331855217}{416585} - \frac{1851561099 I}{416585} \\ -\frac{79384328389}{89341460} + \frac{255046035121 I}{89341460} & \frac{321139869 I}{340} & \frac{17687846317}{1625} + \frac{6686128069 I}{1625} & \frac{5196047084}{1625} - \frac{12549608413 I}{1625} & -\frac{342470529}{1156} - \frac{995879307 I}{5780} & -\frac{164007308677}{290359745} + \frac{300349711933 I}{1161438980} \\ -\frac{44790771896407 I}{522647541000} & \frac{79384328389}{89341460} + \frac{255046035121 I}{89341460} & -\frac{13403226729}{833170} + \frac{8227077787 I}{833170} & -\frac{14086426129}{1249755} - \frac{22290035461 I}{3749265} & \frac{56378902439}{357365840} - \frac{276934692821 I}{357365840} & \frac{347416769}{131384500} + \frac{336906009 I}{131384500} \end{pmatrix}$$

$$\frac{d^2}{dx^2} u(xI) = \frac{1}{1045295082000 \Delta x I^2} ((-2764047814164 + 2680424207604 I) u_{iI+5I} + (590426311237200 + 270314740739700 I) u_{iI+1+5I} + (5851091110496400 - 4645937109610800 I) u_{iI+2+5I} + (232720444137600 - 6899247752662800 I) u_{iI+3+5I} - (464526687935700 + 228132735234300 I) u_{iI+4+5I} + 2722236010884 I u_{iI+5+5I} - (164908289634075 + 810033976501425 I) u_{iI+4I} + (309673667555050500 - 180101685445098300 I) u_{iI+1+4I} + (2248490865998228904 + 5805558444377462472 I) u_{iI+2+4I} + (-5557635819009943344 + 464067912298369392 I) u_{iI+3+4I} - 261975192246307800 I u_{iI+4+4I} + (464526687935700 - 228132735234300 I) u_{iI+5+4I} + (11781886814295600 - 6214461886526800 I) u_{iI+3I} - (3342401515535779008 + 8072642433929061456 I) u_{iI+1+3I} + (-177550080379348770000 + 34404830410109994000 I) u_{iI+2+3I} + 154306530754342174000 I u_{iI+3+3I} + (5557635819009943344 + 464067912298369392 I) u_{iI+4+3I} - (232720444137600 + 6899247752662800 I) u_{iI+5+3I} + (16815688254203400 + 10321691791570200 I) u_{iI+2I} + (-11377857702358100304 + 4300908792706373328 I) u_{iI+1+2I} - 228466584953413911000 I u_{iI+2+2I} + (177550080379348770000 + 34404830410109994000 I) u_{iI+3+2I} + (-2248490865998228904 + 5805558444377462472 I) u_{iI+4+2I} - (5851091110496400 + 4645937109610800 I) u_{iI+5+2I} + (-928796642151300 + 2984038610915700 I) u_{iI+1I} + 987311546175953700 I u_{iI+1+1I} + (11377857702358100304 + 4300908792706373328 I) u_{iI+2+1I} + (3342401515535779008 - 8072642433929061456 I) u_{iI+3+1I} - (309673667555050500 + 180101685445098300 I) u_{iI+4+1I} + (-590426311237200 + 270314740739700 I) u_{iI+5+1I} - 89581543792814 I u_{iI} + (928796642151300 + 2984038610915700 I) u_{iI+1} + (-16815688254203400 + 10321691791570200 I) u_{iI+2} - (11781886814295600 + 6214461886526800 I) u_{iI+3} + (164908289634075 - 810033976501425 I) u_{iI+4} + (2764047814164 + 2680424207604 I) u_{iI+5}), O(\Delta x I^{34}), \text{ Quadrant } I$$

Error order: 34, Error: 1.2313076082347133980 × 10⁻¹¹², New Error: 1.2253548525056844567 × 10⁻²¹⁴
 Error order: 34, Error: 1.2253548525056844567 × 10⁻²¹⁴, New Error: 1.2253489141768876904 × 10⁻³¹⁶
 Error order: 34, Error: 1.2253489141768876904 × 10⁻³¹⁶, New Error: 1.2253489082385732973 × 10⁻⁴¹⁸
 Error order: 34, Error: 1.2253489082385732973 × 10⁻⁴¹⁸, New Error: 1.2253489082326349829 × 10⁻⁵²⁰
 Error order: 34, Error: 1.2253489082326349829 × 10⁻⁵²⁰, New Error: 1.2253489082326290446 × 10⁻⁶²²

--- Derivative Order: 1 - x1=1 ---

6 I	1 + 6 I	2 + 6 I	3 + 6 I	4 + 6 I	5 + 6 I	6 + 6 I
5 I	1 + 5 I	2 + 5 I	3 + 5 I	4 + 5 I	5 + 5 I	6 + 5 I
4 I	1 + 4 I	2 + 4 I	3 + 4 I	4 + 4 I	5 + 4 I	6 + 4 I
3 I	1 + 3 I	2 + 3 I	3 + 3 I	4 + 3 I	5 + 3 I	6 + 3 I
2 I	1 + 2 I	2 + 2 I	3 + 2 I	4 + 2 I	5 + 2 I	6 + 2 I
I	1 + I	2 + I	3 + I	4 + I	5 + I	6 + I
0	1	2	3	4	5	6

$\frac{I}{6}$	$\frac{486216}{8177} + \frac{607176 I}{8177}$	$\frac{406809}{340} + \frac{1200663 I}{340}$	$-\frac{80032}{15} + \frac{160064 I}{15}$	$-\frac{1365363}{442} + \frac{237168 I}{221}$	$-\frac{998136}{13481} + \frac{35640 I}{13481}$	$-\frac{1}{12} + \frac{I}{12}$
$-\frac{95256}{1105} + \frac{17064 I}{221}$	$\frac{8775216}{221} - \frac{43876080 I}{221}$	$-\frac{1531275192}{493} + \frac{6945583464 I}{493}$	$\frac{479711808}{17} - \frac{799519680 I}{17}$	$-\frac{6287442264}{697} + \frac{5655626712 I}{697}$	$\frac{8775216}{85} - \frac{8775216 I}{85}$	$-\frac{35640}{13481} + \frac{998136 I}{13481}$
$-\frac{242109}{68} + \frac{159759 I}{34}$	$-\frac{127240632}{17} + \frac{293969736 I}{17}$	$-\frac{8477407107}{10} + \frac{8477407107 I}{5}$	$-\frac{118248960672}{25} + \frac{157665280896 I}{25}$	$-\frac{8477407107}{8} + \frac{8477407107 I}{8}$	$-\frac{5655626712}{697} + \frac{6287442264 I}{697}$	$-\frac{237168}{221} + \frac{1365363 I}{442}$
$\frac{80032 I}{3}$	$\frac{159903936}{5} - \frac{479711808 I}{5}$	$-\frac{78832640448}{13} + \frac{118248960672 I}{13}$	$\frac{1240884155200}{39} - \frac{1240884155200 I}{39}$	$-\frac{157665280896}{25} + \frac{118248960672 I}{25}$	$\frac{799519680}{17} - \frac{479711808 I}{17}$	$-\frac{160064}{15} + \frac{80032 I}{15}$
$\frac{242109}{34} + \frac{159759 I}{17}$	$-\frac{873133992}{85} + \frac{2821231944 I}{85}$	$-\frac{8477407107}{4} + \frac{8477407107 I}{4}$	$-\frac{118248960672}{13} + \frac{78832640448 I}{13}$	$-\frac{8477407107}{5} + \frac{8477407107 I}{10}$	$-\frac{6945583464}{493} + \frac{1531275192 I}{493}$	$-\frac{1200663}{340} - \frac{406809 I}{340}$
$\frac{95256}{221} + \frac{85320 I}{221}$	$\frac{8775216}{17} - \frac{8775216 I}{17}$	$-\frac{2821231944}{85} + \frac{873133992 I}{85}$	$\frac{479711808}{5} - \frac{159903936 I}{5}$	$-\frac{293969736}{17} + \frac{127240632 I}{17}$	$\frac{43876080}{221} - \frac{8775216 I}{221}$	$-\frac{607176}{8177} - \frac{486216 I}{8177}$
$-\frac{927858939623}{118613926600} + \frac{927858939623 I}{118613926600}$	$-\frac{85320}{221} - \frac{95256 I}{221}$	$-\frac{159759}{17} - \frac{242109 I}{34}$	$-\frac{80032}{3}$	$-\frac{159759}{34} + \frac{242109 I}{68}$	$-\frac{17064}{221} + \frac{95256 I}{1105}$	$-\frac{1}{6}$

$$\frac{d}{dx} u(xI) = \frac{1}{355841779800 \Delta x I} (59306963300 I u_{iI+6I} + (21158856158400 + 26422720862400 I) u_{iI+5I} + (425763642937230 + 1256606055470610 I) u_{iI+4I} + (-1898581954730240 + 3797163909460480 I) u_{iI+3I} + (-1099215384599700 + 381874584758400 I) u_{iI+2I} + (-26346598228800 + 940746312000 I) u_{iI+1I} + (-29653481650 + 29653481650 I) u_{iI} + (-30675171562560 + 27475493803200 I) u_{iI-1I} + (1412935963606800 - 70646798180304000 I) u_{iI-2I} + (-1105256977048411200 + 5013242964663710400 I) u_{iI-3I} + (10041264914693875200 - 16735441524489792000 I) u_{iI-4I} + (-3209949276343617600 + 2887386334408180800 I) u_{iI-5I} + (36736335053758080 - 36736335053758080 I) u_{iI-6I} + (-940746312000 + 26346598228800 I) u_{iI-7I} + (-1266948492141150 + 1672027261737300 I) u_{iI-8I} + (-2663384291397460800 + 6153336121504478400 I) u_{iI-9I} + (-301661563304404903860 + 603323126608809807720 I) u_{iI-10I} + (-1683116825000987361024 + 2244155766667983148032 I) u_{iI-11I} + (-377076954130506129825 + 377076954130506129825 I) u_{iI-12I} + (-2887386334408180800 + 3209949276343617600 I) u_{iI-13I} + (-381874584758400 + 1099215384599700 I) u_{iI-14I} + 9492909773651200 I u_{iI-15I} + (11380100236653058560 - 34140300709959175680 I) u_{iI-16I} + (-2157842083334599180800 + 3236763125001898771200 I) u_{iI-17I} + (11322010931076600640000 - 11322010931076600640000 I) u_{iI-18I} + (-2244155766667983148032 + 1683116825000987361024 I) u_{iI-19I} + (16735441524489792000 - 10041264914693875200 I) u_{iI-20I} + (-3797163909460480 + 1898581954730240 I) u_{iI-21I} + (2533896984282300 + 3344054523474600 I) u_{iI-22I} + (-3655265337848928960 + 11810731719783222720 I) u_{iI-23I} + (-754153908261012259650 + 754153908261012259650 I) u_{iI-24I} + (-3236763125001898771200 + 2157842083334599180800 I) u_{iI-25I} + (-603323126608809807720 + 301661563304404903860 I) u_{iI-26I} + (-5013242964663710400 + 1105256977048411200 I) u_{iI-27I} + (-1256606055470610 + 425763642937230 I) u_{iI-28I} + (153375857812800 + 137377469016000 I) u_{iI-29I} + (183681675268790400 - 183681675268790400 I) u_{iI-30I} + (-11810731719783222720 + 3655265337848928960 I) u_{iI-31I} + (34140300709959175680 - 11380100236653058560 I) u_{iI-32I} + (-6153336121504478400 + 2663384291397460800 I) u_{iI-33I} + (70646798180304000 - 14129359636060800 I) u_{iI-34I} + (-26422720862400 + 21158856158400 I) u_{iI-35I} + (-2783576818869 + 2783576818869 I) u_{iI-36I} + (137377469016000 + 153375857812800 I) u_{iI-37I} + (-3344054523474600 + 2533896984282300 I) u_{iI-38I} - 9492909773651200 u_{iI-39I} + (-1672027261737300 + 1266948492141150 I) u_{iI-40I} + (-27475493803200 + 30675171562560 I) u_{iI-41I} - 59306963300 u_{iI-42I}), O(\Delta x I^{48}), \text{ Quadrant 1}$$

Error order: 48, Error: 4.1530070968264853331 × 10⁻¹⁶², New Error: 4.1287317532652883928 × 10⁻³⁰⁶
 Error order: 48, Error: 4.1287317532652883928 × 10⁻³⁰⁶, New Error: 4.1287075490789837283 × 10⁻⁴⁵⁰
 Error order: 48, Error: 4.1287075490789837283 × 10⁻⁴⁵⁰, New Error: 4.1287075248748684418 × 10⁻⁵⁹⁴
 Error order: 48, Error: 4.1287075248748684418 × 10⁻⁵⁹⁴, New Error: 4.1287075248506643265 × 10⁻⁷³⁸
 Error order: 48, Error: 4.1287075248506643265 × 10⁻⁷³⁸, New Error: 4.1287075248506401224 × 10⁻⁸⁸²

--- Derivative Order: 1 - x1=1 ---

-1 + I	I
-1	0
$-\frac{1}{2} - \frac{I}{2}$	-1
-I	$\frac{3}{2} + \frac{3I}{2}$

$$\frac{d}{dx} u(xI) = \frac{-(1 + I) u_{iI-1I} - 2 u_{iI+1I} - 2 I u_{iI-1I} + (3 + 3 I) u_{iI}}{2 \Delta x I}, O(\Delta x I^3), \text{ Quadrant 2}$$

Error order: 3, Error: 1.2551984055224618565 × 10⁻⁹, New Error: 1.2561999571536308731 × 10⁻¹⁸
 Error order: 3, Error: 1.2561999571536308731 × 10⁻¹⁸, New Error: 1.2562009591051340038 × 10⁻²⁷
 Error order: 3, Error: 1.2562009591051340038 × 10⁻²⁷, New Error: 1.2562009601070859069 × 10⁻³⁶
 Error order: 3, Error: 1.2562009601070859069 × 10⁻³⁶, New Error: 1.2562009601080878588 × 10⁻⁴⁵
 Error order: 3, Error: 1.2562009601080878588 × 10⁻⁴⁵, New Error: 1.2562009601080888608 × 10⁻⁵⁴

$$\frac{d^2}{dx^2} u(xI) = \frac{I u_{iI-2I+2I} + (2 + 2 I) u_{iI-1I+2I} + 2 u_{iI+2I} + (-2 + 2 I) u_{iI-2I+1I} - 2 I u_{iI-1I+1I} - (6 + 6 I) u_{iI+1I} - 2 u_{iI-2I} + (6 - 6 I) u_{iI-1I} + 9 I u_{iI}}{2 \Delta x I^2}, O(\Delta x I^3), \text{ Quadrant 2}$$

Error order: 3, Error: 2.5053860393813961664 × 10⁻⁹, New Error: 2.5073851440192233001 × 10⁻¹⁸

Error order:, 3, *Error:*, 2.5073851440192233001 $\times 10^{-18}$, *New Error:*, 2.5073871439224231613 $\times 10^{-27}$
Error order:, 3, *Error:*, 2.5073871439224231613 $\times 10^{-27}$, *New Error:*, 2.5073871459223271595 $\times 10^{-36}$
Error order:, 3, *Error:*, 2.5073871459223271595 $\times 10^{-36}$, *New Error:*, 2.5073871459243270635 $\times 10^{-45}$
Error order:, 3, *Error:*, 2.5073871459243270635 $\times 10^{-45}$, *New Error:*, 2.5073871459243290635 $\times 10^{-54}$

$$\frac{\partial^2}{\partial x \partial x^2} u(x1, x2) = \frac{I u_{i1-1+1, i2-1+1} + (1+I) u_{i1-1+1, i2+1} + (-1+I) u_{i1-1+1, i2-1} - 3 I u_{i1-1+1, i2} + (1+I) u_{i1+1, i2-1+1} + 2 u_{i1+1, i2+1} + 2 I u_{i1+1, i2-1} - (3+3I) u_{i1+1, i2} + (-1+I) u_{i1-1, i2-1+1} + 2 I u_{i1-1, i2+1} - 2 u_{i1-1, i2-1} + (3-3I) u_{i1-1, i2} - 3 I u_{i1, i2-1+1} - (3+3I) u_{i1, i2+1} + (3-3I) u_{i1, i2-1} + 9 I u_{i1, i2}}{2 \Delta x1 \Delta x2},$$

$O(\Delta x1^3 \Delta x2^3)$, *Quadrant 2*

Error order:, 3, *Error:*, 1.4583123925533946011 $\times 10^{-8}$, *New Error:*, 1.4599234365010185246 $\times 10^{-17}$
Error order:, 3, *Error:*, 1.4599234365010185246 $\times 10^{-17}$, *New Error:*, 1.4599250484357806400 $\times 10^{-26}$
Error order:, 3, *Error:*, 1.4599250484357806400 $\times 10^{-26}$, *New Error:*, 1.4599250500477162929 $\times 10^{-35}$
Error order:, 3, *Error:*, 1.4599250500477162929 $\times 10^{-35}$, *New Error:*, 1.4599250500493282285 $\times 10^{-44}$
Error order:, 3, *Error:*, 1.4599250500493282285 $\times 10^{-44}$, *New Error:*, 1.4599250500493298405 $\times 10^{-53}$

$$\frac{d^3}{dx1^3} u(x1) = \frac{(1-I) u_{i1-3+31} - 6 I u_{i1-2+31} - (6+6I) u_{i1-1+31} - 4 u_{i1+31} + 6 u_{i1-3+21} + (3-3I) u_{i1-2+21} + 24 I u_{i1-1+21} + (18+18I) u_{i1+21} + (6+6I) u_{i1-3+1} - 24 u_{i1-2+1} + (-9+9I) u_{i1-1+1} - 54 I u_{i1+1} + 4 I u_{i1-3} - (18+18I) u_{i1-2} + 54 u_{i1-1} + (-27+27I) u_{i1}}{4 \Delta x1^3}, O(\Delta x1^3), \text{ Quadrant 2}$$

Error order:, 3, *Error:*, 3.7505779038859320350 $\times 10^{-9}$, *New Error:*, 3.7535705748790767972 $\times 10^{-18}$
Error order:, 3, *Error:*, 3.7535705748790767972 $\times 10^{-18}$, *New Error:*, 3.7535735687461424571 $\times 10^{-27}$
Error order:, 3, *Error:*, 3.7535735687461424571 $\times 10^{-27}$, *New Error:*, 3.7535735717400107179 $\times 10^{-36}$
Error order:, 3, *Error:*, 3.7535735717400107179 $\times 10^{-36}$, *New Error:*, 3.7535735717430045861 $\times 10^{-45}$
Error order:, 3, *Error:*, 3.7535735717430045861 $\times 10^{-45}$, *New Error:*, 3.7535735717430075800 $\times 10^{-54}$

$$\frac{\partial^3}{\partial x1^2 \partial x2} u(x1, x2) = \frac{1}{4 \Delta x1^2 \Delta x2} ((1-I) u_{i1-2+21, i2-1+1} - 2 I u_{i1-2+21, i2+1} + 2 u_{i1-2+21, i2-1} + (-3+3I) u_{i1-2+21, i2} - 4 I u_{i1-1+21, i2-1+1} - (4+4I) u_{i1-1+21, i2+1} + (4-4I) u_{i1-1+21, i2-1} + 12 I u_{i1-1+21, i2} - (2+2I) u_{i1+21, i2-1+1} - 4 u_{i1+21, i2+1} - 4 I u_{i1+21, i2-1} + (6+6I) u_{i1+21, i2} + 4 u_{i1-2+1, i2-1+1} + (4-4I) u_{i1-2+1, i2+1} + (4+4I) u_{i1-2+1, i2-1} - 12 u_{i1-2+1, i2} + (-2+2I) u_{i1-1+1, i2-1+1} + 4 I u_{i1-1+1, i2+1} - 4 u_{i1-1+1, i2-1} + (6-6I) u_{i1-1+1, i2} + 12 I u_{i1+1, i2-1+1} + (12+12I) u_{i1+1, i2+1} + (-12+12I) u_{i1+1, i2-1} - 36 I u_{i1+1, i2} + (2+2I) u_{i1-2, i2-1+1} + 4 u_{i1-2, i2+1} + 4 I u_{i1-2, i2-1} - (6+6I) u_{i1-2, i2} - 12 u_{i1-1, i2-1+1} + (-12+12I) u_{i1-1, i2+1} - (12+12I) u_{i1-1, i2-1} + 36 u_{i1-1, i2} + (9-9I) u_{i1, i2-1+1} - 18 I u_{i1, i2+1} + 18 u_{i1, i2-1} + (-27+27I) u_{i1, i2}), O(\Delta x1^3 \Delta x2^3), \text{ Quadrant 2}$$

Error order:, 3, *Error:*, 1.7889356997034403112 $\times 10^{-8}$, *New Error:*, 1.7908096748166071238 $\times 10^{-17}$
Error order:, 3, *Error:*, 1.7908096748166071238 $\times 10^{-17}$, *New Error:*, 1.7908115497747376914 $\times 10^{-26}$
Error order:, 3, *Error:*, 1.7908115497747376914 $\times 10^{-26}$, *New Error:*, 1.7908115516496968045 $\times 10^{-35}$
Error order:, 3, *Error:*, 1.7908115516496968045 $\times 10^{-35}$, *New Error:*, 1.7908115516515717636 $\times 10^{-44}$
Error order:, 3, *Error:*, 1.7908115516515717636 $\times 10^{-44}$, *New Error:*, 1.7908115516515736386 $\times 10^{-53}$

$$\frac{\partial^3}{\partial x1 \partial x2 \partial x3} u(x1, x2, x3) = \frac{1}{4 \Delta x1 \Delta x2 \Delta x3} ((1-I) u_{i1-1+1, i2-1+1, i3-1+1} - 2 I u_{i1-1+1, i2-1+1, i3+1} + 2 u_{i1-1+1, i2-1+1, i3-1} + (-3+3I) u_{i1-1+1, i2-1+1, i3} - 2 I u_{i1-1+1, i2+1, i3-1+1} - (2+2I) u_{i1-1+1, i2+1, i3+1} + (2-2I) u_{i1-1+1, i2+1, i3-1} + 6 I u_{i1-1+1, i2+1, i3} + 2 u_{i1-1+1, i2-1, i3-1+1} + (2-2I) u_{i1-1+1, i2-1, i3+1} + (2+2I) u_{i1-1+1, i2-1, i3-1} - 6 u_{i1-1+1, i2-1, i3} + (-3+3I) u_{i1-1+1, i2, i3-1+1} + 6 I u_{i1-1+1, i2, i3+1} - 6 u_{i1-1+1, i2, i3-1} + (9-9I) u_{i1-1+1, i2, i3} - 2 I u_{i1+1, i2-1+1, i3-1+1} - (2+2I) u_{i1+1, i2-1+1, i3+1} + (2-2I) u_{i1+1, i2-1+1, i3-1} + 6 I u_{i1+1, i2-1+1, i3} - (2+2I) u_{i1+1, i2+1, i3-1+1} - 4 u_{i1+1, i2+1, i3+1} - 4 I u_{i1+1, i2+1, i3-1} + (6+6I) u_{i1+1, i2+1, i3} + (2-2I) u_{i1+1, i2-1, i3-1+1} - 4 I u_{i1+1, i2-1, i3+1} + 4 u_{i1+1, i2-1, i3-1} + (-6+6I) u_{i1+1, i2-1, i3} + 6 I u_{i1+1, i2, i3-1+1} + (6+6I) u_{i1+1, i2, i3+1} + (-6+6I) u_{i1+1, i2, i3-1} - 18 I u_{i1+1, i2, i3} + 2 u_{i1-1, i2-1+1, i3-1+1} + (2-2I) u_{i1-1, i2-1+1, i3+1} + (2+2I) u_{i1-1, i2-1+1, i3-1} - 6 u_{i1-1, i2-1+1, i3} + (2-2I) u_{i1-1, i2+1, i3-1+1} - 4 I u_{i1-1, i2+1, i3+1} + 4 u_{i1-1, i2+1, i3-1} + (-6+6I) u_{i1-1, i2+1, i3} + (2+2I) u_{i1-1, i2-1, i3-1+1} + 4 u_{i1-1, i2-1, i3+1} + 4 I u_{i1-1, i2-1, i3-1} - (6+6I) u_{i1-1, i2-1, i3} - 6 u_{i1-1, i2, i3-1+1} + (-6+6I) u_{i1-1, i2, i3+1} - (6+6I) u_{i1-1, i2, i3-1} + 18 u_{i1-1, i2, i3} + (-3+3I) u_{i1, i2-1+1, i3-1+1} + 6 I u_{i1, i2-1+1, i3} - 6 u_{i1, i2-1+1, i3} + (9-9I) u_{i1, i2-1+1, i3} + 6 I u_{i1, i2+1, i3-1+1} + (6+6I) u_{i1, i2+1, i3+1} + (-6+6I) u_{i1, i2+1, i3-1} - 18 I u_{i1, i2+1, i3} - 6 u_{i1, i2-1, i3-1+1} + (-6+6I) u_{i1, i2-1, i3+1} - (6+6I) u_{i1, i2-1, i3-1} + 18 u_{i1, i2-1, i3} + (9-9I) u_{i1, i2, i3-1+1} - 18 I u_{i1, i2, i3+1} + 18 u_{i1, i2, i3-1} + (-27+27I) u_{i1, i2, i3}), O(\Delta x1^3 \Delta x2^3 \Delta x3^3), \text{ Quadrant 2}$$

Error order:, 3, *Error:*, 1.7408938423053469948 $\times 10^{-7}$, *New Error:*, 1.7440192668256897380 $\times 10^{-16}$
Error order:, 3, *Error:*, 1.7440192668256897380 $\times 10^{-16}$, *New Error:*, 1.7440223950588843024 $\times 10^{-25}$
Error order:, 3, *Error:*, 1.7440223950588843024 $\times 10^{-25}$, *New Error:*, 1.7440223981871203053 $\times 10^{-34}$
Error order:, 3, *Error:*, 1.7440223981871203053 $\times 10^{-34}$, *New Error:*, 1.7440223981902485413 $\times 10^{-43}$
Error order:, 3, *Error:*, 1.7440223981902485413 $\times 10^{-43}$, *New Error:*, 1.7440223981902516696 $\times 10^{-52}$

$$\frac{d^4}{dx1^4} u(x1) = \frac{1}{4 \Delta x1^4} (-u_{i1-4+41} + (-4+4I) u_{i1-3+41} + 12 I u_{i1-2+41} + (8+8I) u_{i1-1+41} + 4 u_{i1+41} - (4+4I) u_{i1-4+31} - 12 u_{i1-3+31} + (12-12I) u_{i1-2+31} - 56 I u_{i1-1+31} - (24+24I) u_{i1+31} - 12 I u_{i1-4+21} + (12+12I) u_{i1-3+21} + 66 u_{i1-2+21} + (-36+36I) u_{i1-1+21} + 108 I u_{i1+21} + (8-8I) u_{i1-4+1} + 56 I u_{i1-3+1} - (36+36I) u_{i1-2+1} - 108 u_{i1-1+1} + (108-108I) u_{i1+1} + 4 u_{i1-4} + (-24+24I) u_{i1-3} - 108 I u_{i1-2} + (108+108I) u_{i1-1} - 81 u_{i1}), O(\Delta x1^3), \text{ Quadrant 2}$$

Error order:, 3, *Error:*, 4.9907889614188968021 $\times 10^{-9}$, *New Error:*, 4.9947712240573210882 $\times 10^{-18}$
Error order:, 3, *Error:*, 4.9947712240573210882 $\times 10^{-18}$, *New Error:*, 4.9947752079123652123 $\times 10^{-27}$
Error order:, 3, *Error:*, 4.9947752079123652123 $\times 10^{-27}$, *New Error:*, 4.9947752118962218468 $\times 10^{-36}$
Error order:, 3, *Error:*, 4.9947752118962218468 $\times 10^{-36}$, *New Error:*, 4.9947752119002057035 $\times 10^{-45}$
Error order:, 3, *Error:*, 4.9947752119002057035 $\times 10^{-45}$, *New Error:*, 4.9947752119002096873 $\times 10^{-54}$

$$\frac{\partial^4}{\partial x1^3 \partial x2} u(x1, x2) = \frac{1}{4 \Delta x1^3 \Delta x2} (-u_{i1-3+31, i2-1+1} + (-1+I) u_{i1-3+31, i2+1} - (1+I) u_{i1-3+31, i2-1} + 3 u_{i1-3+31, i2} + (-3+3I) u_{i1-2+31, i2-1+1} + 6 I u_{i1-2+31, i2+1} - 6 u_{i1-2+31, i2-1} + (9-9I) u_{i1-2+31, i2} + 6 I u_{i1-1+31, i2-1+1} + (6+6I) u_{i1-1+31, i2+1} + (-6+6I) u_{i1-1+31, i2-1} - 18 I u_{i1-1+31, i2} + (2+2I) u_{i1+31, i2-1+1} + 4 u_{i1+31, i2+1} + 4 I u_{i1+31, i2-1} - (6+6I) u_{i1+31, i2} - (3+3I) u_{i1-3+21, i2-1+1} - 6 u_{i1-3+21, i2+1} - 6 I u_{i1-3+21, i2-1} + (9+9I) u_{i1-3+21, i2} - 3 u_{i1-2+21, i2-1+1} + (-3+3I) u_{i1-2+21, i2+1} - (3+3I) u_{i1-2+21, i2-1} + 9 u_{i1-2+21, i2} + (12-12I) u_{i1-1+21, i2-1+1} - 24 I u_{i1-1+21, i2+1} + 24 u_{i1-1+21, i2-1} + (-36+36I) u_{i1-1+21, i2} - 18 I u_{i1+21, i2-1+1} - (18+18I) u_{i1+21, i2+1} + (18-18I) u_{i1+21, i2-1} + 54 I u_{i1+21, i2} - 6 I u_{i1-3+1, i2-1+1} - (6+6I) u_{i1-3+1, i2+1} + (6-6I) u_{i1-3+1, i2-1} + 18 I u_{i1-3+1, i2} + (12+12I) u_{i1-2+1, i2-1+1} + 24 u_{i1-2+1, i2+1} + 24 I u_{i1-2+1, i2-1} - (36+36I) u_{i1-2+1, i2} + 9 u_{i1-1+1, i2-1+1} + (9-9I) u_{i1-1+1, i2+1} + (9+9I) u_{i1-1+1, i2-1} - 27 u_{i1-1+1, i2} + (-27+27I) u_{i1+1, i2-1+1} + 54 I u_{i1+1, i2+1} - 54 u_{i1+1, i2-1} + (81-81I) u_{i1+1, i2} + (2-2I) u_{i1-3, i2-1+1} - 4 I u_{i1-3, i2+1} + 4 u_{i1-3, i2-1} + (-6+6I) u_{i1-3, i2} + 18 I u_{i1-2, i2-1+1} + (18+18I) u_{i1-2, i2+1} + (-18+18I) u_{i1-2, i2-1} - 54 I u_{i1-2, i2} - (27+27I) u_{i1-1, i2-1+1} - 54 u_{i1-1, i2+1} - 54 I u_{i1-1, i2-1} + (81+81I) u_{i1-1, i2} + 27 u_{i1, i2-1+1} + (27-27I) u_{i1, i2+1} + (27+27I) u_{i1, i2-1} - 81 u_{i1, i2}), O(\Delta x1^3 \Delta x2^3), \text{ Quadrant 2}$$

Error order:, 2, *Error:*, 2.6648046522746709287 × 10⁻²⁴, *New Error:*, 2.6648046522764421462 × 10⁻³⁰
Error order:, 2, *Error:*, 2.6648046522764421462 × 10⁻³⁰, *New Error:*, 2.6648046522764439174 × 10⁻³⁶

$$\frac{d^4}{dx^4} u(xI) = \frac{-4 u_{iI-2+2I} + (-4 + 12I) u_{iI-1+2I} + (8 + 6I) u_{iI+2I} - (4 + 12I) u_{iI-2+I} - 4 u_{iI-1+I} + (8 - 24I) u_{iI+1} + (8 - 6I) u_{iI-2} + (8 + 24I) u_{iI-1} - 16 u_{iI}}{\Delta x I^4}, O(\Delta x I^2), \text{ Quadrant 2}$$

Error order:, 2, *Error:*, 5.3048239860075447412 × 10⁻⁶, *New Error:*, 5.3083511206859331083 × 10⁻¹²
Error order:, 2, *Error:*, 5.3083511206859331083 × 10⁻¹², *New Error:*, 5.3083546489923415958 × 10⁻¹⁸
Error order:, 2, *Error:*, 5.3083546489923415958 × 10⁻¹⁸, *New Error:*, 5.3083546525206491781 × 10⁻²⁴
Error order:, 2, *Error:*, 5.3083546525206491781 × 10⁻²⁴, *New Error:*, 5.3083546525241774857 × 10⁻³⁰
Error order:, 2, *Error:*, 5.3083546525241774857 × 10⁻³⁰, *New Error:*, 5.3083546525241810140 × 10⁻³⁶

$$\frac{\partial^4}{\partial x I^2 \partial x^2} u(xI, x2)$$

$$= \frac{1}{\Delta x I^2 \Delta x^2} (-4 u_{iI-1+1, i2-1+1} + (-2 + 6I) u_{iI-1+1, i2+1} - (2 + 6I) u_{iI-1+1, i2-1} + 8 u_{iI-1+1, i2} + (-2 + 6I) u_{iI+1, i2-1+1} + (8 + 6I) u_{iI+1, i2+1} - 10 u_{iI+1, i2-1} + (4 - 12I) u_{iI+1, i2} - (2 + 6I) u_{iI-1, i2-1+1} - 10 u_{iI-1, i2+1} + (8 - 6I) u_{iI-1, i2-1} + (4 + 12I) u_{iI-1, i2} + 8 u_{iI, i2-1+1} + (4 - 12I) u_{iI, i2+1} + (4 + 12I) u_{iI, i2-1} - 16 u_{iI, i2}), O(\Delta x I^2 \Delta x^2), \text{ Quadrant 2}$$

Error order:, 2, *Error:*, 0.000022937979462335016065, *New Error:*, 2.2958493358951327330 × 10⁻¹¹
Error order:, 2, *Error:*, 2.2958493358951327330 × 10⁻¹¹, *New Error:*, 2.2958513882015232290 × 10⁻¹⁷
Error order:, 2, *Error:*, 2.2958513882015232290 × 10⁻¹⁷, *New Error:*, 2.2958513902538305377 × 10⁻²³
Error order:, 2, *Error:*, 2.2958513902538305377 × 10⁻²³, *New Error:*, 2.2958513902558828450 × 10⁻²⁹
Error order:, 2, *Error:*, 2.2958513902558828450 × 10⁻²⁹, *New Error:*, 2.2958513902558848974 × 10⁻³⁵

$$\frac{d^6}{dx^6} u(xI) = \frac{1}{\Delta x I^6} (8I u_{iI-3+3I} + (36 + 12I) u_{iI-2+3I} + (36 - 48I) u_{iI-1+3I} - (18 + 26I) u_{iI+3I} + (-36 + 12I) u_{iI-3+2I} + 72I u_{iI-2+2I} - (54 + 18I) u_{iI-1+2I} + (-72 + 96I) u_{iI+2I} - (36 + 48I) u_{iI-3+1} + (54 - 18I) u_{iI-2+1} - 144I u_{iI-1+1} + (144 + 48I) u_{iI+1} + (18 - 26I) u_{iI-3} + (72 + 96I) u_{iI-2} + (-144 + 48I) u_{iI-1} - 64I u_{iI}), O(\Delta x I^2), \text{ Quadrant 2}$$

Error order:, 2, *Error:*, 7.9255022653067256088 × 10⁻⁶, *New Error:*, 7.9307718704595795035 × 10⁻¹²
Error order:, 2, *Error:*, 7.9307718704595795035 × 10⁻¹², *New Error:*, 7.930771418126943655 × 10⁻¹⁸
Error order:, 2, *Error:*, 7.930771418126943655 × 10⁻¹⁸, *New Error:*, 7.930771470840492340 × 10⁻²⁴
Error order:, 2, *Error:*, 7.930771470840492340 × 10⁻²⁴, *New Error:*, 7.930771470893205888 × 10⁻³⁰
Error order:, 2, *Error:*, 7.930771470893205888 × 10⁻³⁰, *New Error:*, 7.930771470893258602 × 10⁻³⁶

$$\frac{\partial^6}{\partial x I^4 \partial x^2} u(xI, x2) = \frac{1}{\Delta x I^4 \Delta x^2} (8I u_{iI-2+2I, i2-1+1} + (12 + 4I) u_{iI-2+2I, i2+1} + (-12 + 4I) u_{iI-2+2I, i2-1} - 16I u_{iI-2+2I, i2} + (24 + 8I) u_{iI-1+2I, i2-1+1} + (24 - 32I) u_{iI-1+2I, i2+1} + 40I u_{iI-1+2I, i2-1} - (48 + 16I) u_{iI-1+2I, i2} + (12 - 16I) u_{iI+2I, i2-1+1} - (18 + 26I) u_{iI+2I, i2+1} + (30 + 10I) u_{iI+2I, i2-1} + (-24 + 32I) u_{iI+2I, i2} + (-24 + 8I) u_{iI-2+1, i2-1+1} + 40I u_{iI-2+1, i2+1} - (24 + 32I) u_{iI-2+1, i2-1} + (48 - 16I) u_{iI-2+1, i2} + 8I u_{iI-1+1, i2-1+1} + (12 + 4I) u_{iI-1+1, i2+1} + (-12 + 4I) u_{iI-1+1, i2-1} - 16I u_{iI-1+1, i2} - (48 + 16I) u_{iI+1, i2-1+1} + (-48 + 64I) u_{iI+1, i2+1} - 80I u_{iI+1, i2-1} + (96 + 32I) u_{iI+1, i2} - (12 + 16I) u_{iI-2, i2-1+1} + (-30 + 10I) u_{iI-2, i2+1} + (18 - 26I) u_{iI-2, i2-1} + (24 + 32I) u_{iI-2, i2} + (48 - 16I) u_{iI-1, i2-1+1} - 80I u_{iI-1, i2+1} + (48 + 64I) u_{iI-1, i2-1} + (-96 + 32I) u_{iI-1, i2} + 32I u_{iI, i2-1+1} + (48 + 16I) u_{iI, i2+1} + (-48 + 16I) u_{iI, i2-1} - 64I u_{iI, i2}), O(\Delta x I^2 \Delta x^2), \text{ Quadrant 2}$$

Error order:, 2, *Error:*, 0.000029887523308456315603, *New Error:*, 2.9912637069844857910 × 10⁻¹¹
Error order:, 2, *Error:*, 2.9912637069844857910 × 10⁻¹¹, *New Error:*, 2.9912662194135824663 × 10⁻¹⁷
Error order:, 2, *Error:*, 2.9912662194135824663 × 10⁻¹⁷, *New Error:*, 2.9912662219260126192 × 10⁻²³
Error order:, 2, *Error:*, 2.9912662219260126192 × 10⁻²³, *New Error:*, 2.9912662219285250493 × 10⁻²⁹
Error order:, 2, *Error:*, 2.9912662219285250493 × 10⁻²⁹, *New Error:*, 2.9912662219285275618 × 10⁻³⁵

$$\frac{\partial^6}{\partial x I^2 \partial x^2 \partial x^3} u(xI, x2, x3) = \frac{1}{\Delta x I^2 \Delta x^2 \Delta x^3} (8I u_{iI-1+1, i2-1+1, i3-1+1} + (12 + 4I) u_{iI-1+1, i2-1+1, i3+1} + (-12 + 4I) u_{iI-1+1, i2-1+1, i3-1} - 16I u_{iI-1+1, i2-1+1, i3} + (12 + 4I) u_{iI-1+1, i2+1, i3-1+1} + (12 - 16I) u_{iI-1+1, i2+1, i3+1} + 20I u_{iI-1+1, i2+1, i3-1} - (24 + 8I) u_{iI-1+1, i2+1, i3} + (-12 + 4I) u_{iI-1+1, i2-1, i3-1+1} + 20I u_{iI-1+1, i2-1, i3+1} - (12 + 16I) u_{iI-1+1, i2-1, i3-1} + (24 - 8I) u_{iI-1+1, i2-1, i3} - 16I u_{iI-1+1, i2, i3-1+1} - (24 + 8I) u_{iI-1+1, i2, i3+1} + (24 - 8I) u_{iI-1+1, i2, i3-1} + 32I u_{iI-1+1, i2, i3} + (12 + 4I) u_{iI+1, i2-1+1, i3-1+1} + (12 - 16I) u_{iI+1, i2-1+1, i3+1} + 20I u_{iI+1, i2-1+1, i3-1} - (24 + 8I) u_{iI+1, i2-1+1, i3} + (12 - 16I) u_{iI+1, i2+1, i3-1+1} - (18 + 26I) u_{iI+1, i2+1, i3+1} + (30 + 10I) u_{iI+1, i2+1, i3-1} + (-24 + 32I) u_{iI+1, i2+1, i3} + 20I u_{iI+1, i2-1, i3-1+1} + (30 + 10I) u_{iI+1, i2-1, i3+1} + (-30 + 10I) u_{iI+1, i2-1, i3-1} - 40I u_{iI+1, i2-1, i3} - (24 + 8I) u_{iI+1, i2, i3-1+1} + (-24 + 32I) u_{iI+1, i2, i3+1} - 40I u_{iI+1, i2, i3-1} + (48 + 16I) u_{iI+1, i2, i3} + (-12 + 4I) u_{iI-1, i2-1+1, i3-1+1} + 20I u_{iI-1, i2-1+1, i3+1} - (12 + 16I) u_{iI-1, i2-1+1, i3-1} + (24 - 8I) u_{iI-1, i2-1+1, i3} + 20I u_{iI-1, i2+1, i3-1+1} + (30 + 10I) u_{iI-1, i2+1, i3+1} + (-30 + 10I) u_{iI-1, i2+1, i3-1} - 40I u_{iI-1, i2+1, i3} - (12 + 16I) u_{iI-1, i2-1, i3-1+1} + (-30 + 10I) u_{iI-1, i2-1, i3+1} + (18 - 26I) u_{iI-1, i2-1, i3-1} + (24 + 32I) u_{iI-1, i2-1, i3} + (24 - 8I) u_{iI-1, i2, i3-1+1} - 40I u_{iI-1, i2, i3+1} + (24 + 32I) u_{iI-1, i2, i3-1} + (-48 + 16I) u_{iI-1, i2, i3} - 16I u_{iI, i2-1+1, i3-1+1} - (24 + 8I) u_{iI, i2-1+1, i3+1} + (24 - 8I) u_{iI, i2-1+1, i3-1} + 32I u_{iI, i2-1+1, i3} - (24 + 8I) u_{iI, i2+1, i3-1+1} + (-24 + 32I) u_{iI, i2+1, i3+1} - 40I u_{iI, i2+1, i3-1} + (48 + 16I) u_{iI, i2+1, i3} + (24 - 8I) u_{iI, i2-1, i3-1+1} - 40I u_{iI, i2-1, i3+1} + (24 + 32I) u_{iI, i2-1, i3-1} + (-48 + 16I) u_{iI, i2-1, i3} + 32I u_{iI, i2, i3-1+1} + (48 + 16I) u_{iI, i2, i3+1} + (-48 + 16I) u_{iI, i2, i3-1} - 64I u_{iI, i2, i3}), O(\Delta x I^2 \Delta x^2 \Delta x^3), \text{ Quadrant 2}$$

Error order:, 2, *Error:*, 0.00017463312212311794546, *New Error:*, 1.7487690046800375440 × 10⁻¹⁰
Error order:, 2, *Error:*, 1.7487690046800375440 × 10⁻¹⁰, *New Error:*, 1.7487714441615121565 × 10⁻¹⁶
Error order:, 2, *Error:*, 1.7487714441615121565 × 10⁻¹⁶, *New Error:*, 1.7487714466009953343 × 10⁻²²
Error order:, 2, *Error:*, 1.7487714466009953343 × 10⁻²², *New Error:*, 1.7487714466034348175 × 10⁻²⁸
Error order:, 2, *Error:*, 1.7487714466034348175 × 10⁻²⁸, *New Error:*, 1.7487714466034372570 × 10⁻³⁴

$$\frac{d^8}{dx^8} u(xI) = \frac{1}{\Delta x I^8} (16 u_{iI-4+4I} + (32 - 96I) u_{iI-3+4I} - (192 + 144I) u_{iI-2+4I} + (-208 + 144I) u_{iI-1+4I} + (28 + 96I) u_{iI+4I} + (32 + 96I) u_{iI-4+3I} + 352 u_{iI-3+3I} + (48 - 144I) u_{iI-2+3I} + (448 + 336I) u_{iI-1+3I} + (416 - 288I) u_{iI+3I} + (-192 + 144I) u_{iI-4+2I} + (48 + 144I) u_{iI-3+2I} - 936 u_{iI-2+2I} + (-96 + 288I) u_{iI-1+2I} - (768 + 576I) u_{iI+2I} - (208 + 144I) u_{iI-4+1} + (448 - 336I) u_{iI-3+1} - (96 + 288I) u_{iI-2+1} + 1408 u_{iI-1+1} + (-256 + 768I) u_{iI+1} + (28 - 96I) u_{iI-4} + (416 + 288I) u_{iI-3} + (-768 + 576I) u_{iI-2} - (256 + 768I) u_{iI-1} + 256 u_{iI}), O(\Delta x I^2), \text{ Quadrant 2}$$

Error order:, 2, *Error:*, 0.000010525193475566861742, *New Error:*, 1.0532191598784572573 × 10⁻¹¹
Error order:, 2, *Error:*, 1.0532191598784572573 × 10⁻¹¹, *New Error:*, 1.0532198599225626413 × 10⁻¹⁷
Error order:, 2, *Error:*, 1.0532198599225626413 × 10⁻¹⁷, *New Error:*, 1.0532198606226069795 × 10⁻²³

+ 28672 I) $u_{i,-1} - 16384 I u_{i,i}$), $O(\Delta x I^2)$, *Quadrant 2*

Error order:, 2, *Error:*, 0.000018199598489840352508, *New Error:*, $1.8211699286234818633 \times 10^{-11}$
Error order:, 2, *Error:*, $1.8211699286234818633 \times 10^{-11}$, *New Error:*, $1.8211711391021001829 \times 10^{-17}$
Error order:, 2, *Error:*, $1.8211711391021001829 \times 10^{-17}$, *New Error:*, $1.8211711403125792039 \times 10^{-23}$
Error order:, 2, *Error:*, $1.8211711403125792039 \times 10^{-23}$, *New Error:*, $1.8211711403137896829 \times 10^{-29}$
Error order:, 2, *Error:*, $1.8211711403137896829 \times 10^{-29}$, *New Error:*, $1.8211711403137908934 \times 10^{-35}$

$$\frac{d^{16}}{dx I^{16}} u(xI) = \frac{1}{\Delta x I^{16}} (256 u_{i,-8+8I} + (1024 - 3072 I) u_{i,-7+8I} - (14336 + 10752 I) u_{i,-6+8I} + (-46592 + 32256 I) u_{i,-5+8I} + (31360 + 107520 I) u_{i,-4+8I} + (141568 + 5376 I) u_{i,-3+8I} + (39424 - 104832 I) u_{i,-2+8I} - (39296 + 31872 I) u_{i,-1+8I} + (-8432 + 5376 I) u_{i,+8I} + (1024 + 3072 I) u_{i,-8+7I} + 31744 u_{i,-7+7I} + (39424 - 118272 I) u_{i,-6+7I} - (186368 + 139776 I) u_{i,-5+7I} + (-116480 + 80640 I) u_{i,-4+7I} - (62720 + 215040 I) u_{i,-3+7I} - (495488 + 18816 I) u_{i,-2+7I} + (-129536 + 344448 I) u_{i,-1+7I} + (78592 + 63744 I) u_{i,+7I} + (-14336 + 10752 I) u_{i,-8+6I} + (39424 + 118272 I) u_{i,-7+6I} + 270592 u_{i,-6+6I} + (-3584 + 10752 I) u_{i,-5+6I} + (663040 + 497280 I) u_{i,-4+6I} + (757120 - 524160 I) u_{i,-3+6I} + (78400 + 268800 I) u_{i,-2+6I} + (990976 + 37632 I) u_{i,-1+6I} + (157696 - 419328 I) u_{i,+6I} - (46592 + 32256 I) u_{i,-8+5I} + (-186368 + 139776 I) u_{i,-7+5I} - (3584 + 10752 I) u_{i,-6+5I} - 1100288 u_{i,-5+5I} + (-264320 + 792960 I) u_{i,-4+5I} - (1379840 + 1034880 I) u_{i,-3+5I} + (-1514240 + 1048320 I) u_{i,-2+5I} - (250880 + 860160 I) u_{i,-1+5I} - (1132544 + 43008 I) u_{i,+5I} + (31360 - 107520 I) u_{i,-8+4I} - (116480 + 80640 I) u_{i,-7+4I} + (663040 - 497280 I) u_{i,-6+4I} - (264320 + 792960 I) u_{i,-5+4I} + 2420320 u_{i,-4+4I} + (528640 - 1585920 I) u_{i,-3+4I} + (2652160 + 1989120 I) u_{i,-2+4I} + (931840 - 645120 I) u_{i,-1+4I} + (501760 + 1720320 I) u_{i,+4I} + (141568 - 5376 I) u_{i,-8+3I} + (-62720 + 215040 I) u_{i,-7+3I} + (757120 + 524160 I) u_{i,-6+3I} + (-1379840 + 1034880 I) u_{i,-5+3I} + (528640 + 1585920 I) u_{i,-4+3I} - 4401152 u_{i,-3+3I} + (28672 - 86016 I) u_{i,-2+3I} - (2981888 + 2236416 I) u_{i,-1+3I} + (1490944 - 1032192 I) u_{i,+3I} + (39424 + 104832 I) u_{i,-8+2I} + (-495488 + 18816 I) u_{i,-7+2I} + (78400 - 268800 I) u_{i,-6+2I} - (1514240 + 1048320 I) u_{i,-5+2I} + (2652160 - 1989120 I) u_{i,-4+2I} + (28672 + 86016 I) u_{i,-3+2I} + 4329472 u_{i,-2+2I} + (-1261568 + 3784704 I) u_{i,-1+2I} - (917504 + 688128 I) u_{i,+2I} + (-39296 + 31872 I) u_{i,-8+1I} - (129536 + 344448 I) u_{i,-7+1I} + (990976 - 37632 I) u_{i,-6+1I} + (-250880 + 860160 I) u_{i,-5+1I} + (931840 + 645120 I) u_{i,-4+1I} + (-2981888 + 2236416 I) u_{i,-3+1I} - (1261568 + 3784704 I) u_{i,-2+1I} + 2031616 u_{i,-1+1I} + (-131072 + 393216 I) u_{i,+1I} - (8432 + 5376 I) u_{i,-8I} + (78592 - 63744 I) u_{i,-7I} + (157696 + 419328 I) u_{i,-6I} + (-1132544 + 43008 I) u_{i,-5I} + (501760 - 1720320 I) u_{i,-4I} + (1490944 + 1032192 I) u_{i,-3I} + (-917504 + 688128 I) u_{i,-2I} - (131072 + 393216 I) u_{i,-1I} + 65536 u_{i,i}), $O(\Delta x I^2)$, *Quadrant 2*$$

Error order:, 2, *Error:*, 0.000020716591890422433700, *New Error:*, $2.0730366226469010797 \times 10^{-11}$
Error order:, 2, *Error:*, $2.0730366226469010797 \times 10^{-11}$, *New Error:*, $2.0730380005339764530 \times 10^{-17}$
Error order:, 2, *Error:*, $2.0730380005339764530 \times 10^{-17}$, *New Error:*, $2.0730380019118639867 \times 10^{-23}$
Error order:, 2, *Error:*, $2.0730380019118639867 \times 10^{-23}$, *New Error:*, $2.0730380019132418743 \times 10^{-29}$
Error order:, 2, *Error:*, $2.0730380019132418743 \times 10^{-29}$, *New Error:*, $2.0730380019132432521 \times 10^{-35}$

"--- Derivative Order: 3 - xI=1 ---"

$$\begin{bmatrix} -1 + I & I \\ -1 & 0 \end{bmatrix}$$

$$\begin{bmatrix} 3 - 3I & -3 - 3I \\ 3 + 3I & -3 + 3I \end{bmatrix}$$

$$\frac{d^3}{dx I^3} u(xI) = \frac{(3 - 3I) u_{i,-1+1I} - (3 + 3I) u_{i,+1I} + (3 + 3I) u_{i,-1I} + (-3 + 3I) u_{i,i}}{\Delta x I^3}, O(\Delta x I), \text{ Quadrant 2}$$

Error order:, 1, *Error:*, 0.0037667228090923972650, *New Error:*, $3.7686009997843763388 \times 10^{-6}$
Error order:, 1, *Error:*, $3.7686009997843763388 \times 10^{-6}$, *New Error:*, $3.7686028784437262264 \times 10^{-9}$
Error order:, 1, *Error:*, $3.7686028784437262264 \times 10^{-9}$, *New Error:*, $3.7686028803223860450 \times 10^{-12}$
Error order:, 1, *Error:*, $3.7686028803223860450 \times 10^{-12}$, *New Error:*, $3.7686028803242647048 \times 10^{-15}$
Error order:, 1, *Error:*, $3.7686028803242647048 \times 10^{-15}$, *New Error:*, $3.7686028803242665835 \times 10^{-18}$

$$\frac{d^6}{dx I^6} u(xI) = \frac{18(-I u_{i,-2+2I} - 2 u_{i,-1+2I} + I u_{i,+2I} + 2 u_{i,-2+1I} + 2 u_{i,+1I} + I u_{i,-2I} - 2 u_{i,-1I} - I u_{i,i})}{\Delta x I^6}, O(\Delta x I), \text{ Quadrant 2}$$

Error order:, 1, *Error:*, 0.0074846893393681049747, *New Error:*, $7.4921553406456446294 \times 10^{-6}$
Error order:, 1, *Error:*, $7.4921553406456446294 \times 10^{-6}$, *New Error:*, $7.4921628103731061396 \times 10^{-9}$
Error order:, 1, *Error:*, $7.4921628103731061396 \times 10^{-9}$, *New Error:*, $7.4921628178428373286 \times 10^{-12}$
Error order:, 1, *Error:*, $7.4921628178428373286 \times 10^{-12}$, *New Error:*, $7.4921628178503070597 \times 10^{-15}$
Error order:, 1, *Error:*, $7.4921628178503070597 \times 10^{-15}$, *New Error:*, $7.4921628178503145295 \times 10^{-18}$

$$\frac{\partial^6}{\partial x I^3 \partial x_2^3} u(xI, x_2) = \frac{18(-I u_{i,-1+1,i_2-1+1I} - u_{i,-1+1,i_2+1I} + u_{i,-1+1,i_2-1I} + I u_{i,-1+1,i_2} - u_{i,+1,i_2-1+1I} + I u_{i,+1,i_2+1I} - I u_{i,+1,i_2-1I} + u_{i,+1,i_2} + u_{i,-1,i_2-1+1I} - I u_{i,-1,i_2+1I} + I u_{i,-1,i_2-1I} - u_{i,-1,i_2} + I u_{i,i_2-1+1I} + u_{i,i_2+1I} - u_{i,i_2-1I} - I u_{i,i_2})}{\Delta x I^3 \Delta x_2^3}, O(\Delta x I \Delta x_2), \text{ Quadrant 2}$$

Error order:, 1, *Error:*, 0.024889306568846594925, *New Error:*, 0.000024920325811296032805
Error order:, 1, *Error:*, 0.000024920325811296032805, *New Error:*, $2.4920356849879384083 \times 10^{-8}$
Error order:, 1, *Error:*, $2.4920356849879384083 \times 10^{-8}$, *New Error:*, $2.4920356880917986783 \times 10^{-11}$
Error order:, 1, *Error:*, $2.4920356880917986783 \times 10^{-11}$, *New Error:*, $2.4920356880949025386 \times 10^{-14}$
Error order:, 1, *Error:*, $2.4920356880949025386 \times 10^{-14}$, *New Error:*, $2.4920356880949056424 \times 10^{-17}$

$$\frac{d^9}{dx I^9} u(xI) = \frac{1}{\Delta x I^9} (54(- (1 + I) u_{i,-3+3I} + (-3 + 3I) u_{i,-2+3I} + (3 + 3I) u_{i,-1+3I} + (1 - I) u_{i,+3I} + (3 - 3I) u_{i,-3+2I} - (3 + 3I) u_{i,-2+2I} + (3 - 3I) u_{i,-1+2I} - (3 + 3I) u_{i,+2I} + (3 + 3I) u_{i,-3+1I} + (-3 + 3I) u_{i,-2+1I} + (3 + 3I) u_{i,-1+1I} + (-3 + 3I) u_{i,+1I} + (-1 + I) u_{i,-3I} - (3 + 3I) u_{i,-2I} + (3 - 3I) u_{i,-1I} + (1 + I) u_{i,i}), O(\Delta x I), \text{ Quadrant 2}$$

Error order:, 1, *Error:*, 0.011154372915023325985, *New Error:*, 0.000011171066859739871062

Error order:, 1, *Error:*, 0.000011171066859739871062, *New Error:*, 1.1171083566183191042 $\times 10^{-8}$
Error order:, 1, *Error:*, 1.1171083566183191042 $\times 10^{-8}$, *New Error:*, 1.1171083582889646866 $\times 10^{-11}$
Error order:, 1, *Error:*, 1.1171083582889646866 $\times 10^{-11}$, *New Error:*, 1.1171083582906353322 $\times 10^{-14}$
Error order:, 1, *Error:*, 1.1171083582906353322 $\times 10^{-14}$, *New Error:*, 1.1171083582906370029 $\times 10^{-17}$

$$\frac{\partial^9}{\partial x I^6 \partial x^2} u(xI, x2) = \frac{1}{\Delta x I^6 \Delta x^2} (54 (- (1 + I) u_{iI-2+2I, i2-1+1} + (-1 + I) u_{iI-2+2I, i2+1} + (1 - I) u_{iI-2+2I, i2-1} + (1 + I) u_{iI-2+2I, i2} + (-2 + 2I) u_{iI-1+2I, i2-1+1} + (2 + 2I) u_{iI-1+2I, i2+1} - (2 + 2I) u_{iI-1+2I, i2-1} + (2 - 2I) u_{iI-1+2I, i2} + (1 + I) u_{iI+2I, i2-1+1} + (1 - I) u_{iI+2I, i2+1} + (-1 + I) u_{iI+2I, i2-1} - (1 + I) u_{iI+2I, i2} + (2 - 2I) u_{iI-2+1, i2-1+1} - (2 + 2I) u_{iI-2+1, i2+1} + (2 + 2I) u_{iI-2+1, i2-1} + (-2 + 2I) u_{iI-2+1, i2} + (2 - 2I) u_{iI+1, i2-1+1} - (2 + 2I) u_{iI+1, i2+1} + (-2 + 2I) u_{iI+1, i2} + (1 + I) u_{iI-2, i2-1+1} + (1 - I) u_{iI-2, i2+1} + (-1 + I) u_{iI-2, i2-1} - (1 + I) u_{iI-2, i2} + (-2 + 2I) u_{iI-1, i2-1+1} + (2 + 2I) u_{iI-1, i2+1} - (2 + 2I) u_{iI-1, i2-1} + (2 - 2I) u_{iI-1, i2}), O(\Delta x I \Delta x^2), \text{ Quadrant 2}$$

Error order:, 1, *Error:*, 0.034625433569931691722, *New Error:*, 0.000034685873532720930291
Error order:, 1, *Error:*, 0.000034685873532720930291, *New Error:*, 3.4685934025456060444 $\times 10^{-8}$
Error order:, 1, *Error:*, 3.4685934025456060444 $\times 10^{-8}$, *New Error:*, 3.4685934085948848377 $\times 10^{-11}$
Error order:, 1, *Error:*, 3.4685934085948848377 $\times 10^{-11}$, *New Error:*, 3.4685934086009341165 $\times 10^{-14}$
Error order:, 1, *Error:*, 3.4685934086009341165 $\times 10^{-14}$, *New Error:*, 3.4685934086009401658 $\times 10^{-17}$

$$\frac{\partial^9}{\partial x I^3 \partial x^2 \partial x^3} u(xI, x2, x3) = \frac{1}{\Delta x I^3 \Delta x^2 \Delta x^3} (54 (- (1 + I) u_{iI-1+1, i2-1+1, i3-1+1} + (-1 + I) u_{iI-1+1, i2-1+1, i3+1} + (1 - I) u_{iI-1+1, i2-1+1, i3-1} + (1 + I) u_{iI-1+1, i2-1+1, i3} + (-1 + I) u_{iI-1+1, i2+1, i3-1+1} + (1 + I) u_{iI-1+1, i2+1, i3+1} - (1 + I) u_{iI-1+1, i2+1, i3-1} + (1 - I) u_{iI-1+1, i2+1, i3} + (1 - I) u_{iI-1+1, i2-1, i3-1+1} - (1 + I) u_{iI-1+1, i2-1, i3+1} + (1 + I) u_{iI-1+1, i2-1, i3-1} + (-1 + I) u_{iI-1+1, i2-1, i3} + (1 + I) u_{iI-1+1, i2, i3-1+1} + (1 - I) u_{iI-1+1, i2, i3+1} - (1 + I) u_{iI-1+1, i2, i3-1} + (1 + I) u_{iI+1, i2-1+1, i3-1+1} + (1 + I) u_{iI+1, i2-1+1, i3} - (1 + I) u_{iI+1, i2-1+1, i3+1} + (1 - I) u_{iI+1, i2-1, i3-1+1} + (-1 + I) u_{iI+1, i2-1, i3+1} + (1 - I) u_{iI+1, i2-1, i3-1} + (1 + I) u_{iI+1, i2-1, i3} + (1 - I) u_{iI+1, i2, i3-1+1} - (1 + I) u_{iI+1, i2, i3+1} + (1 + I) u_{iI+1, i2, i3-1} + (-1 + I) u_{iI+1, i2, i3} + (1 - I) u_{iI-1, i2-1+1, i3-1+1} - (1 + I) u_{iI-1, i2-1+1, i3+1} + (1 + I) u_{iI-1, i2-1+1, i3-1} + (1 + I) u_{iI-1, i2-1+1, i3} + (1 - I) u_{iI-1, i2+1, i3-1+1} + (1 - I) u_{iI-1, i2+1, i3+1} + (1 - I) u_{iI-1, i2+1, i3-1} + (1 + I) u_{iI-1, i2+1, i3} + (1 + I) u_{iI-1, i2-1, i3-1+1} + (1 - I) u_{iI-1, i2-1, i3+1} + (-1 + I) u_{iI-1, i2-1, i3-1} - (1 + I) u_{iI-1, i2-1, i3} + (-1 + I) u_{iI-1, i2, i3-1+1} + (1 + I) u_{iI-1, i2, i3+1} - (1 + I) u_{iI-1, i2, i3-1} + (1 - I) u_{iI-1, i2, i3} + (1 + I) u_{iI, i2-1+1, i3-1+1} + (1 - I) u_{iI, i2-1+1, i3+1} + (-1 + I) u_{iI, i2-1+1, i3-1} - (1 + I) u_{iI, i2-1+1, i3} + (1 - I) u_{iI, i2+1, i3-1+1} - (1 + I) u_{iI, i2+1, i3+1} + (1 + I) u_{iI, i2+1, i3-1} + (-1 + I) u_{iI, i2+1, i3} + (-1 + I) u_{iI, i2-1, i3-1+1} + (1 + I) u_{iI, i2-1, i3+1} - (1 + I) u_{iI, i2-1, i3-1} + (1 - I) u_{iI, i2-1, i3}), O(\Delta x I \Delta x^2 \Delta x^3), \text{ Quadrant 2}$$

Error order:, 1, *Error:*, 0.12914556057776021854, *New Error:*, 0.00012946728115636711256
Error order:, 1, *Error:*, 0.00012946728115636711256, *New Error:*, 1.2946760327774357202 $\times 10^{-7}$
Error order:, 1, *Error:*, 1.2946760327774357202 $\times 10^{-7}$, *New Error:*, 1.2946760359986534961 $\times 10^{-10}$
Error order:, 1, *Error:*, 1.2946760359986534961 $\times 10^{-10}$, *New Error:*, 1.2946760360018747139 $\times 10^{-13}$
Error order:, 1, *Error:*, 1.2946760360018747139 $\times 10^{-13}$, *New Error:*, 1.2946760360018779351 $\times 10^{-16}$

$$\frac{d^{12}}{dx I^{12}} u(xI) = - \frac{324 (u_{iI-4+4I} - 4I u_{iI-3+4I} - 6 u_{iI-2+4I} + 4I u_{iI-1+4I} + u_{iI+4I} + 4I u_{iI-4+3I} + 8 u_{iI-3+3I} + 8 u_{iI-1+3I} - 4I u_{iI+3I} - 6 u_{iI-4+2I} - 12 u_{iI-2+2I} - 6 u_{iI+2I} - 4I u_{iI-4+1} + 8 u_{iI-3+1} + 8 u_{iI-1+1} + 4I u_{iI+1} + u_{iI-4} + 4I u_{iI-3} - 6 u_{iI-2} - 4I u_{iI-1} + u_{iI})}{\Delta x I^{12}}, O(\Delta x I), \text{ Quadrant 2}$$

Error order:, 1, *Error:*, 0.014776242775798389361, *New Error:*, 0.000014805736176138633562
Error order:, 1, *Error:*, 0.000014805736176138633562, *New Error:*, 1.4805765698983317432 $\times 10^{-8}$
Error order:, 1, *Error:*, 1.4805765698983317432 $\times 10^{-8}$, *New Error:*, 1.4805765728506191579 $\times 10^{-11}$
Error order:, 1, *Error:*, 1.4805765728506191579 $\times 10^{-11}$, *New Error:*, 1.4805765728535714454 $\times 10^{-14}$
Error order:, 1, *Error:*, 1.4805765728535714454 $\times 10^{-14}$, *New Error:*, 1.4805765728535743976 $\times 10^{-17}$

$$\frac{\partial^{12}}{\partial x I^9 \partial x^2} u(xI, x2) = \frac{1}{\Delta x I^9 \Delta x^2} (324 (-u_{iI-3+3I, i2-1+1} + I u_{iI-3+3I, i2+1} - I u_{iI-3+3I, i2-1} + u_{iI-3+3I, i2} + 3I u_{iI-2+3I, i2-1+1} + 3 u_{iI-2+3I, i2+1} - 3 u_{iI-2+3I, i2-1} - 3I u_{iI-2+3I, i2} + 3 u_{iI-1+3I, i2-1+1} - 3I u_{iI-1+3I, i2+1} - 3I u_{iI-1+3I, i2-1} - I u_{iI+3I, i2-1+1} - u_{iI+3I, i2+1} + u_{iI+3I, i2-1} + I u_{iI+3I, i2} - 3I u_{iI-3+2I, i2-1+1} - 3 u_{iI-3+2I, i2+1} + 3 u_{iI-3+2I, i2-1} + 3I u_{iI-3+2I, i2} - 3 u_{iI-2+2I, i2-1+1} + 3I u_{iI-2+2I, i2+1} - 3I u_{iI-2+2I, i2-1} + 3 u_{iI-2+2I, i2} - 3I u_{iI-1+2I, i2-1+1} - 3 u_{iI-1+2I, i2+1} + 3 u_{iI-1+2I, i2-1} + 3I u_{iI-1+2I, i2} - 3 u_{iI+1, i2-1+1} + 3I u_{iI+1, i2+1} - 3I u_{iI+1, i2-1} + 3 u_{iI+1, i2} + 3I u_{iI-1+1, i2-1+1} - 3I u_{iI-1+1, i2+1} + 3I u_{iI+1, i2-1+1} + 3 u_{iI+1, i2-1} - 3I u_{iI+1, i2} + I u_{iI-3, i2-1+1} + u_{iI-3, i2+1} - u_{iI-3, i2-1} - I u_{iI-3, i2} - 3 u_{iI-2, i2-1+1} + 3I u_{iI-2, i2+1} - 3I u_{iI-2, i2-1} + 3 u_{iI-2, i2} - 3I u_{iI-1, i2-1+1} - 3 u_{iI-1, i2+1} + 3 u_{iI-1, i2-1} + 3I u_{iI-1, i2} + u_{iI, i2-1+1} - I u_{iI, i2+1} + I u_{iI, i2-1} - u_{iI, i2})). O(\Delta x I \Delta x^2), \text{ Quadrant 2}$$

Error order:, 1, *Error:*, 0.044234494086291876169, *New Error:*, 0.000044333802041623457798
Error order:, 1, *Error:*, 0.000044333802041623457798, *New Error:*, 4.4333901461082029646 $\times 10^{-8}$
Error order:, 1, *Error:*, 4.4333901461082029646 $\times 10^{-8}$, *New Error:*, 4.4333901560501599804 $\times 10^{-11}$
Error order:, 1, *Error:*, 4.4333901560501599804 $\times 10^{-11}$, *New Error:*, 4.4333901560601019374 $\times 10^{-14}$
Error order:, 1, *Error:*, 4.4333901560601019374 $\times 10^{-14}$, *New Error:*, 4.4333901560601118794 $\times 10^{-17}$

$$\frac{\partial^{12}}{\partial x I^6 \partial x^2} u(xI, x2) = \frac{1}{\Delta x I^6 \Delta x^2} (324 (-u_{iI-2+2I, i2-2+2I} + 2I u_{iI-2+2I, i2-1+2I} + u_{iI-2+2I, i2+2I} - 2I u_{iI-2+2I, i2-2+1} - 2I u_{iI-2+2I, i2+1} + u_{iI-2+2I, i2-2} + 2I u_{iI-2+2I, i2-1} - u_{iI-2+2I, i2} + 2I u_{iI-1+2I, i2-2+2I} + 4 u_{iI-1+2I, i2-1+2I} - 2I u_{iI-1+2I, i2+2I} - 4 u_{iI-1+2I, i2-2+1} - 4 u_{iI-1+2I, i2+1} - 2I u_{iI-1+2I, i2-2} + 4 u_{iI-1+2I, i2-1} + 2I u_{iI-1+2I, i2} + u_{iI+2I, i2-2+2I} - 2I u_{iI+2I, i2+2I} - u_{iI+2I, i2-2+1} + 2I u_{iI+2I, i2-2+1} + 2I u_{iI+2I, i2+1} - u_{iI+2I, i2-2} - 2I u_{iI+2I, i2-1} + u_{iI+2I, i2} - 2I u_{iI-2+1, i2-2+2I} - 4 u_{iI-2+1, i2-1+2I} + 2I u_{iI-2+1, i2+2I} + 4 u_{iI-2+1, i2-2+1} + 4 u_{iI-2+1, i2+1} + 2I u_{iI-2+1, i2-2} - 4 u_{iI-2+1, i2-1} - 2I u_{iI-2+1, i2} - 2I u_{iI+1, i2-2+2I} - 4 u_{iI+1, i2-1+2I} + 2I u_{iI+1, i2+2I} + 4 u_{iI+1, i2-2+1} + 4 u_{iI+1, i2+1} + 2I u_{iI+1, i2-2} - 4 u_{iI+1, i2-1} - 2I u_{iI+1, i2} + u_{iI-2, i2-2+2I} - 2I u_{iI-2, i2-1+2I} - u_{iI-2, i2+2I} + 2I u_{iI-2, i2-2+1} + 2I u_{iI-2, i2+1} - u_{iI-2, i2-2} - 2I u_{iI-2, i2-1} + u_{iI-2, i2} + 2I u_{iI-1, i2-2+2I} + 4 u_{iI-1, i2-1+2I} - 2I u_{iI-1, i2+2I} - 4 u_{iI-1, i2-2+1} - 4 u_{iI-1, i2+1} - 2I u_{iI-1, i2-2} + 4 u_{iI-1, i2-1} + 2I u_{iI-1, i2} - u_{iI, i2-2+2I} + 2I u_{iI, i2-1+2I} + u_{iI, i2+2I} - 2I u_{iI, i2-2+1} - 2I u_{iI, i2+1} + u_{iI, i2-2} + 2I u_{iI, i2-1} - u_{iI, i2})). O(\Delta x I \Delta x^2), \text{ Quadrant 2}$$

Error order:, 1, *Error:*, 0.048977359635068445886, *New Error:*, 0.000049099515493247625145
Error order:, 1, *Error:*, 0.000049099515493247625145, *New Error:*, 4.9099637801468212024 $\times 10^{-8}$
Error order:, 1, *Error:*, 4.9099637801468212024 $\times 10^{-8}$, *New Error:*, 4.9099637923776585099 $\times 10^{-11}$
Error order:, 1, *Error:*, 4.9099637923776585099 $\times 10^{-11}$, *New Error:*, 4.9099637923898893473 $\times 10^{-14}$
Error order:, 1, *Error:*, 4.9099637923898893473 $\times 10^{-14}$, *New Error:*, 4.9099637923899015781 $\times 10^{-17}$

$$\frac{\partial^{12}}{\partial x I^6 \partial x^2 \partial x^3} u(xI, x2, x3) = \frac{1}{\Delta x I^6 \Delta x^2 \Delta x^3} (324 (-u_{iI-2+2I, i2-1+1, i3-1+1} + I u_{iI-2+2I, i2-1+1, i3+1} - I u_{iI-2+2I, i2-1+1, i3-1} + u_{iI-2+2I, i2-1+1, i3} + I u_{iI-2+2I, i2+1, i3-1+1} + u_{iI-2+2I, i2+1, i3+1} - u_{iI-2+2I, i2+1, i3-1} - I u_{iI-2+2I, i2+1, i3} - I u_{iI-2+2I, i2-1, i3-1+1} - u_{iI-2+2I, i2-1, i3+1} + u_{iI-2+2I, i2-1, i3-1} + I u_{iI-2+2I, i2-1, i3} + I u_{iI-2+2I, i2-1, i3-1} + (-1 + I) u_{iI-2+2I, i2-1, i3} + (1 - I) u_{iI-2+2I, i2-1, i3-1} + (1 + I) u_{iI-2+2I, i2-1, i3} + (1 - I) u_{iI-2+2I, i2, i3-1+1} - (1 + I) u_{iI-2+2I, i2, i3+1} + (1 + I) u_{iI-2+2I, i2, i3-1} + (-1 + I) u_{iI-2+2I, i2, i3} + (1 - I) u_{iI-2+2I, i2+1, i3-1+1} + (1 - I) u_{iI-2+2I, i2+1, i3+1} - (1 + I) u_{iI-2+2I, i2+1, i3-1} + (1 + I) u_{iI-2+2I, i2+1, i3} + (1 - I) u_{iI-2+2I, i2-1, i3-1+1} - (1 + I) u_{iI-2+2I, i2-1, i3+1} + (1 + I) u_{iI-2+2I, i2-1, i3-1} + (1 + I) u_{iI-2+2I, i2-1, i3} + (1 - I) u_{iI-2+2I, i2, i3-1+1} + (1 - I) u_{iI-2+2I, i2, i3+1} + (1 - I) u_{iI-2+2I, i2, i3-1} + (1 + I) u_{iI-2+2I, i2+1, i3-1+1} + (1 + I) u_{iI-2+2I, i2+1, i3+1} - (1 + I) u_{iI-2+2I, i2+1, i3-1} + (-1 + I) u_{iI-2+2I, i2+1, i3} + (-1 + I) u_{iI-2+2I, i2-1, i3-1+1} + (1 + I) u_{iI-2+2I, i2-1, i3+1} - (1 + I) u_{iI-2+2I, i2-1, i3-1} + (1 - I) u_{iI-2+2I, i2-1, i3}), O(\Delta x I \Delta x^2 \Delta x^3), \text{ Quadrant 2}$$

$$\frac{d}{dxI} u(xI) = \frac{\begin{bmatrix} \frac{1}{4} + \frac{I}{4} & \frac{4}{5} + \frac{8I}{5} & \frac{I}{2} \\ \frac{8}{5} + \frac{4I}{5} & -10 - 10I & 4I \\ \frac{1}{2} & 4 & \frac{57}{20} + \frac{57I}{20} \end{bmatrix} (5 + 5I) u_{iI-2+2I} + (16 + 32I) u_{iI-1+2I} + 10I u_{iI+2I} + (32 + 16I) u_{iI-2+1} - (200 + 200I) u_{iI-1+1} + 80I u_{iI+1} + 10 u_{iI-2} + 80 u_{iI-1} + (57 + 57I) u_{iI}}{20 \Delta xI}, O(\Delta xI^8), \text{ Quadrant 2}$$

Error order.: 8, *Error.*: 1.4863241007178082516 $\times 10^{-25}$, *New Error.*: 1.4889938688543323141 $\times 10^{-49}$
Error order.: 8, *Error.*: 1.4889938688543323141 $\times 10^{-49}$, *New Error.*: 1.4889965410211761448 $\times 10^{-73}$
Error order.: 8, *Error.*: 1.4889965410211761448 $\times 10^{-73}$, *New Error.*: 1.4889965436933453888 $\times 10^{-97}$
Error order.: 8, *Error.*: 1.4889965436933453888 $\times 10^{-97}$, *New Error.*: 1.4889965436960175580 $\times 10^{-121}$
Error order.: 8, *Error.*: 1.4889965436960175580 $\times 10^{-121}$, *New Error.*: 1.4889965436960202302 $\times 10^{-145}$

$$\frac{d^2}{dxI^2} u(xI) = \frac{1}{200 \Delta xI^2} (25I u_{iI-4+4I} + (-80 + 240I) u_{iI-3+4I} + (-434 + 562I) u_{iI-2+4I} + (-320 + 160I) u_{iI-1+4I} - 50 u_{iI+4I} + (80 + 240I) u_{iI-4+3I} - 720I u_{iI-3+3I} + (2640 - 8880I) u_{iI-2+3I} - (560 + 720I) u_{iI-1+3I} - 800 u_{iI+3I} + (434 + 562I) u_{iI-4+2I} - (2640 + 8880I) u_{iI-3+2I} + 45790I u_{iI-2+2I} + (15088 - 12464I) u_{iI-1+2I} + (-3770 + 570I) u_{iI+2I} + (320 + 160I) u_{iI-4+1} + (560 - 720I) u_{iI-3+1} - (15088 + 12464I) u_{iI-2+1} - 16400I u_{iI-1+1} + (-4560 + 4560I) u_{iI+1} + 50 u_{iI-4} + 800 u_{iI-3} + (3770 + 570I) u_{iI-2} + (4560 + 4560I) u_{iI-1} + 3249I u_{iI}), O(\Delta xI^8), \text{ Quadrant 2}$$

Error order.: 8, *Error.*: 2.9667147718918328376 $\times 10^{-25}$, *New Error.*: 2.9720436504078489304 $\times 10^{-49}$
Error order.: 8, *Error.*: 2.9720436504078489304 $\times 10^{-49}$, *New Error.*: 2.9720489840742038818 $\times 10^{-73}$
Error order.: 8, *Error.*: 2.9720489840742038818 $\times 10^{-73}$, *New Error.*: 2.9720489894078750275 $\times 10^{-97}$
Error order.: 8, *Error.*: 2.9720489894078750275 $\times 10^{-97}$, *New Error.*: 2.9720489894132086987 $\times 10^{-121}$
Error order.: 8, *Error.*: 2.9720489894132086987 $\times 10^{-121}$, *New Error.*: 2.9720489894132140323 $\times 10^{-145}$

$$\frac{\partial^2}{\partial xI \partial x2} u(xI, x2) = \frac{1}{200 \Delta xI \Delta x2} (25I u_{iI-2+2I, i2-2+2I} + (-40 + 120I) u_{iI-2+2I, i2-1+2I} + (-25 + 25I) u_{iI-2+2I, i2+2I} + (40 + 120I) u_{iI-2+2I, i2-2+1} - 1000I u_{iI-2+2I, i2-1+1} + (-200 + 200I) u_{iI-2+2I, i2+1} + (25 + 25I) u_{iI-2+2I, i2-2} + (200 + 200I) u_{iI-2+2I, i2-1} + 285I u_{iI-2+2I, i2} + (-40 + 120I) u_{iI-1+2I, i2-2+2I} + (-384 + 512I) u_{iI-1+2I, i2-1+2I} + (-160 + 80I) u_{iI-1+2I, i2+2I} + 640I u_{iI-1+2I, i2-2+1} + (1600 - 4800I) u_{iI-1+2I, i2-1+1} + (-1280 + 640I) u_{iI-1+2I, i2+1} + (80 + 160I) u_{iI-1+2I, i2-2} + (640 + 1280I) u_{iI-1+2I, i2-1} + (-456 + 1368I) u_{iI-1+2I, i2} + (-25 + 25I) u_{iI+2I, i2-2+2I} + (-160 + 80I) u_{iI+2I, i2-1+2I} - 50 u_{iI+2I, i2+2I} + (-80 + 160I) u_{iI+2I, i2-2+1} + (1000 - 1000I) u_{iI+2I, i2-1+1} - 400 u_{iI+2I, i2+1} + 50I u_{iI+2I, i2-2} + 400I u_{iI+2I, i2-1} + (-285 + 285I) u_{iI+2I, i2} + (40 + 120I) u_{iI-2+1, i2-2+2I} + 640I u_{iI-2+1, i2-1+2I} + (-80 + 160I) u_{iI-2+1, i2+2I} + (384 + 512I) u_{iI-2+1, i2-2+1} - (1600 + 4800I) u_{iI-2+1, i2-1+1} + (-640 + 1280I) u_{iI-2+1, i2+1} + (160 + 80I) u_{iI-2+1, i2-2} + (1280 + 640I) u_{iI-2+1, i2-1} + (456 + 1368I) u_{iI-2+1, i2} - 1000I u_{iI-1+1, i2-2+2I} + (1600 - 4800I) u_{iI-1+1, i2-1+2I} + (1000 - 1000I) u_{iI-1+1, i2+2I} - (1600 + 4800I) u_{iI-1+1, i2-2+1} + 40000I u_{iI-1+1, i2-1+1} + (8000 - 8000I) u_{iI-1+1, i2+1} - (1000 + 1000I) u_{iI-1+1, i2-2} - (8000 + 8000I) u_{iI-1+1, i2-1} - 11400I u_{iI-1+1, i2} + (-200 + 200I) u_{iI+1, i2-2+2I} + (-1280 + 640I) u_{iI+1, i2-1+2I} - 400 u_{iI+1, i2+2I} + (-640 + 1280I) u_{iI+1, i2-2+1} + (8000 - 8000I) u_{iI+1, i2-1+1} - 3200 u_{iI+1, i2+1} + 400I u_{iI+1, i2-2} + 3200I u_{iI+1, i2-1} + (-2280 + 2280I) u_{iI+1, i2} + (25 + 25I) u_{iI-2, i2-2+2I} + (80 + 160I) u_{iI-2, i2-1+2I} + 50I u_{iI-2, i2+2I} + (160 + 80I) u_{iI-2, i2-2+1} - (1000 + 1000I) u_{iI-2, i2-1+1} + 400I u_{iI-2, i2+1} + 50 u_{iI-2, i2-2} + 400 u_{iI-2, i2-1} + (285 + 285I) u_{iI-2, i2} + (200 + 200I) u_{iI-1, i2-2+2I} + (640 + 1280I) u_{iI-1, i2-1+2I} + 400I u_{iI-1, i2+2I} + (1280 + 640I) u_{iI-1, i2-2+1} - (8000 + 8000I) u_{iI-1, i2-1+1} + 3200I u_{iI-1, i2+1} + 400 u_{iI-1, i2-2} + 3200 u_{iI-1, i2-1} + (2280 + 2280I) u_{iI-1, i2} + 285I u_{iI, i2-2+2I} + (-456 + 1368I) u_{iI, i2-1+2I} + (-285 + 285I) u_{iI, i2+2I} + (456 + 1368I) u_{iI, i2-2+1} - 11400I u_{iI, i2-1+1} + (-2280 + 2280I) u_{iI, i2+1} + (285 + 285I) u_{iI, i2-2} + (2280 + 2280I) u_{iI, i2-1} + 3249I u_{iI, i2}), O(\Delta xI^8 \Delta x2^8), \text{ Quadrant 2}$$

Error order.: 8, *Error.*: 1.0448482489715095829 $\times 10^{-23}$, *New Error.*: 1.0476264023478687445 $\times 10^{-47}$
Error order.: 8, *Error.*: 1.0476264023478687445 $\times 10^{-47}$, *New Error.*: 1.0476291841950768615 $\times 10^{-71}$
Error order.: 8, *Error.*: 1.0476291841950768615 $\times 10^{-71}$, *New Error.*: 1.0476291869769277667 $\times 10^{-95}$
Error order.: 8, *Error.*: 1.0476291869769277667 $\times 10^{-95}$, *New Error.*: 1.0476291869797096176 $\times 10^{-119}$
Error order.: 8, *Error.*: 1.0476291869797096176 $\times 10^{-119}$, *New Error.*: 1.0476291869797123995 $\times 10^{-143}$

$$\frac{d^3}{dxI^3} u(xI) = \frac{1}{4000 \Delta xI^3} ((-125 + 125I) u_{iI-6+6I} + (-2400 + 1200I) u_{iI-5+6I} + (-14190 + 1920I) u_{iI-4+6I} - (29728 + 6496I) u_{iI-3+6I} - (16110 + 12270I) u_{iI-2+6I} - (2400 + 4800I) u_{iI-1+6I} - 500I u_{iI+6I} + (-1200 + 2400I) u_{iI-6+5I} + (-4200 + 4200I) u_{iI-5+5I} + (117360 - 62880I) u_{iI-4+5I} + (501600 - 96000I) u_{iI-3+5I} + (148320 - 10560I) u_{iI-2+5I} - (8400 + 46800I) u_{iI-1+5I} - 12000I u_{iI+5I} + (-1920 + 14190I) u_{iI-6+4I} + (62880 - 117360I) u_{iI-5+4I} + (58545 - 58545I) u_{iI-4+4I} + (-3547680 + 1991040I) u_{iI-3+4I} + (730584 + 741888I) u_{iI-2+4I} + (232320 + 145440I) u_{iI-1+4I} - (8550 + 104550I) u_{iI+4I} + (6496 + 29728I) u_{iI-6+3I} + (96000 - 501600I) u_{iI-5+3I} + (-1991040 + 3547680I) u_{iI-4+3I} + (11043920 - 11043920I) u_{iI-3+3I} - (8095680 + 1393440I) u_{iI-2+3I} + (1755360 + 1701120I) u_{iI-1+3I} - (136800 + 392800I) u_{iI+3I} + (12270 + 16110I) u_{iI-6+2I} + (10560 - 148320I) u_{iI-5+2I} - (741888 + 730584I) u_{iI-4+2I} + (1393440 + 8095680I) u_{iI-3+2I} + (-4037355 + 4037355I) u_{iI-2+2I} + (4255296 + 292752I) u_{iI-1+2I} - (644670 + 547200I) u_{iI+2I} + (4800 + 2400I) u_{iI-6+1} + (46800 + 8400I) u_{iI-5+1} - (145440 + 232320I) u_{iI-4+1} - (1701120 + 1755360I) u_{iI-3+1} - (292752 + 4255296I) u_{iI-2+1} + (855000 - 855000I) u_{iI-1+1} - 779760 u_{iI+1} + 500 u_{iI-6} + 12000 u_{iI-5} + (104550 + 8550I) u_{iI-4} + (392800 + 136800I) u_{iI-3} + (547200 + 644670I) u_{iI-2} + 779760I u_{iI-1} + (-185193 + 185193I) u_{iI}), O(\Delta xI^8), \text{ Quadrant 2}$$

Error order.: 8, *Error.*: 4.4411897782811868827 $\times 10^{-25}$, *New Error.*: 4.4491671413291151652 $\times 10^{-49}$
Error order.: 8, *Error.*: 4.4491671413291151652 $\times 10^{-49}$, *New Error.*: 4.4491751258595866495 $\times 10^{-73}$
Error order.: 8, *Error.*: 4.4491751258595866495 $\times 10^{-73}$, *New Error.*: 4.4491751338441242927 $\times 10^{-97}$
Error order.: 8, *Error.*: 4.4491751338441242927 $\times 10^{-97}$, *New Error.*: 4.4491751338521088303 $\times 10^{-121}$
Error order.: 8, *Error.*: 4.4491751338521088303 $\times 10^{-121}$, *New Error.*: 4.4491751338521168149 $\times 10^{-145}$

$$\frac{\partial^3}{\partial xI^2 \partial x2} u(xI, x2) = \frac{1}{4000 \Delta xI^2 \Delta x2} ((-125 + 125I) u_{iI-4+4I, i2-2+2I} + (-800 + 400I) u_{iI-4+4I, i2-1+2I} - 250 u_{iI-4+4I, i2+2I} + (-400 + 800I) u_{iI-4+4I, i2-2+1} + (5000 - 5000I) u_{iI-4+4I, i2-1+1} - 2000 u_{iI-4+4I, i2+1} + 250I u_{iI-4+4I, i2-2} + 2000I u_{iI-4+4I, i2-1} + (-1425 + 1425I) u_{iI-4+4I, i2} + (-1600 + 800I) u_{iI-3+4I, i2-2+2I} + (-8960 + 1280I) u_{iI-3+4I, i2-1+2I} - (2400 + 800I) u_{iI-3+4I, i2+2I} + (-6400 + 6400I) u_{iI-3+4I, i2-2+1} + (64000 - 32000I) u_{iI-3+4I, i2-1+1} - (19200 + 6400I) u_{iI-3+4I, i2+1} + (-800 + 2400I) u_{iI-3+4I, i2-2} + (-6400 + 19200I) u_{iI-3+4I, i2-1} + (-18240 + 9120I) u_{iI-3+4I, i2} + (-4980 + 640I) u_{iI-2+4I, i2-2+2I} - (24928 + 4896I) u_{iI-2+4I, i2-1+2I} - (5620 + 4340I) u_{iI-2+4I, i2+2I} + (-22880 + 11040I) u_{iI-2+4I, i2-2+1} + (199200 - 25600I) u_{iI-2+4I, i2-1+1} - (44960 + 34720I) u_{iI-2+4I, i2+1} + (-4340 + 5620I) u_{iI-2+4I, i2-2} + (-34720 + 44960I) u_{iI-2+4I, i2-1} + (-56772 + 7296I) u_{iI-2+4I, i2} - (2400 + 800I) u_{iI-1+4I, i2-2+2I} - (10240 + 7680I) u_{iI-1+4I, i2-1+2I} - (1600 + 3200I) u_{iI-1+4I, i2+2I} - 12800 u_{iI-1+4I, i2-2+1} + (96000 + 32000I) u_{iI-1+4I, i2-1+1} - (12800 + 25600I) u_{iI-1+4I, i2+1} + (-3200 + 1600I) u_{iI-1+4I, i2-2} + (-25600 + 12800I) u_{iI-1+4I, i2-1} - (27360 + 9120I) u_{iI-1+4I, i2} - (250 + 250I) u_{iI+4I, i2-2+2I} - (800 + 1600I) u_{iI+4I, i2-1+2I} - 500I u_{iI+4I, i2+2I} - (1600 + 800I) u_{iI+4I, i2-2+1} + (10000 + 10000I) u_{iI+4I, i2-1+1} - 4000I u_{iI+4I, i2+1} - 500 u_{iI+4I, i2-2} - 4000 u_{iI+4I, i2-1} - (2850 + 2850I) u_{iI+4I, i2} + (-800 + 1600I) u_{iI-4+3I, i2-2+2I} + (-6400 + 6400I) u_{iI-4+3I, i2-1+2I} + (-2400 + 800I) u_{iI-4+3I, i2+2I} + (-1280 + 8960I) u_{iI-4+3I, i2-2+1} + (32000 - 64000I) u_{iI-4+3I, i2-1+1} + (-19200 + 6400I) u_{iI-4+3I, i2+1} + (800 + 2400I) u_{iI-4+3I, i2-2} + (6400 + 19200I) u_{iI-4+3I, i2-1} + (-9120 + 18240I) u_{iI-4+3I, i2} + (3600 - 3600I) u_{iI-3+3I, i2-2+2I} + (23040 - 11520I) u_{iI-3+3I, i2-1+2I} + 7200 u_{iI-3+3I, i2+2I} + (11520 - 23040I) u_{iI-3+3I, i2-2+1} + (-144000 + 144000I) u_{iI-3+3I, i2-1+1} + 57600 u_{iI-3+3I, i2+1} - 7200I u_{iI-3+3I, i2-2} - 57600I u_{iI-3+3I, i2-1} + (41040 - 41040I) u_{iI-3+3I, i2} + (57600 - 31200I) u_{iI-2+3I, i2-2+2I} + (326400$$

--- Derivative Order: 3 - x1=1 ---

$$\begin{bmatrix} -2 + 2 I & -1 + 2 I & 2 I \\ -2 + I & -1 + I & I \\ -2 & -1 & 0 \end{bmatrix}$$

$$\begin{bmatrix} -\frac{381}{40} + \frac{381 I}{40} & -\frac{282}{5} + \frac{168 I}{5} & -\frac{747}{40} + \frac{141 I}{40} \\ -\frac{168}{5} + \frac{282 I}{5} & 318 - 318 I & -\frac{576}{5} + \frac{222 I}{5} \\ -\frac{141}{40} + \frac{747 I}{40} & -\frac{222}{5} + \frac{576 I}{5} & -\frac{1467}{40} + \frac{1467 I}{40} \end{bmatrix}$$

$$\frac{d^3}{dxI^3} u(xI) = \frac{3 \left((-127 + 127 I) u_{iI-2+2I} + (-752 + 448 I) u_{iI-1+2I} + (-249 + 47 I) u_{iI+2I} + (-448 + 752 I) u_{iI-2+I} + (4240 - 4240 I) u_{iI-1+I} + (-1536 + 592 I) u_{iI+I} + (-47 + 249 I) u_{iI-2} + (-592 + 1536 I) u_{iI-1} + (-489 + 489 I) u_{iI} \right)}{40 \Delta x I^3}, O(\Delta x I^6), \text{ Quadrant 2}$$

Error order.: 6, Error.: 1.7056837373410812090 × 10⁻¹⁸, New Error.: 1.7086205915652171093 × 10⁻³⁶
 Error order.: 6, Error.: 1.7086205915652171093 × 10⁻³⁶, New Error.: 1.7086235309488547202 × 10⁻⁵⁴
 Error order.: 6, Error.: 1.7086235309488547202 × 10⁻⁵⁴, New Error.: 1.7086235338882408887 × 10⁻⁷²
 Error order.: 6, Error.: 1.7086235338882408887 × 10⁻⁷², New Error.: 1.7086235338911802749 × 10⁻⁹⁰
 Error order.: 6, Error.: 1.7086235338911802749 × 10⁻⁹⁰, New Error.: 1.7086235338911832143 × 10⁻¹⁰⁸

$$\frac{d^6}{dxI^6} u(xI) = \frac{1}{800 \Delta x I^6} \left(9 \left(-16129 I u_{iI-4+4I} + (38608 - 152400 I) u_{iI-3+4I} + (208054 - 374488 I) u_{iI-2+4I} + (166192 - 146896 I) u_{iI-1+4I} + (29896 - 11703 I) u_{iI+4I} - (38608 + 152400 I) u_{iI-4+3I} + 310752 I u_{iI-3+3I} + (-1092864 + 4609440 I) u_{iI-2+3I} + (33376 + 121728 I) u_{iI-1+3I} + (354640 - 219600 I) u_{iI+3I} - (208054 + 374488 I) u_{iI-4+2I} + (1092864 + 4609440 I) u_{iI-3+2I} - 21006592 I u_{iI-2+2I} + (-3778688 + 8025632 I) u_{iI-1+2I} + (1103194 - 1054056 I) u_{iI+2I} - (166192 + 146896 I) u_{iI-4+I} + (-33376 + 121728 I) u_{iI-3+I} + (3778688 + 8025632 I) u_{iI-2+I} + 1436960 I u_{iI-1+I} + (461616 - 1040592 I) u_{iI+I} - (29896 + 11703 I) u_{iI-4} - (354640 + 219600 I) u_{iI-3} - (1103194 + 1054056 I) u_{iI-2} - (461616 + 1040592 I) u_{iI-1} - 239121 I u_{iI} \right) \right), O(\Delta x I^6), \text{ Quadrant 2}$$

Error order.: 6, Error.: 3.3909808705605056933 × 10⁻¹⁸, New Error.: 3.3968194772585996992 × 10⁻³⁶
 Error order.: 6, Error.: 3.3968194772585996992 × 10⁻³⁶, New Error.: 3.3968253208938927899 × 10⁻⁵⁴
 Error order.: 6, Error.: 3.3968253208938927899 × 10⁻⁵⁴, New Error.: 3.3968253267375331145 × 10⁻⁷²
 Error order.: 6, Error.: 3.3968253267375331145 × 10⁻⁷², New Error.: 3.3968253267433767548 × 10⁻⁹⁰
 Error order.: 6, Error.: 3.3968253267433767548 × 10⁻⁹⁰, New Error.: 3.3968253267433825984 × 10⁻¹⁰⁸

$$\frac{d^6}{dxI^3 dx2^3} u(xI, x2) = \frac{1}{800 \Delta x I^3 \Delta x2^3} \left(9 \left(-16129 I u_{iI-2+2I, i2-2+2I} + (19304 - 76200 I) u_{iI-2+2I, i2-1+2I} + (12827 - 18796 I) u_{iI-2+2I, i2+2I} - (19304 + 76200 I) u_{iI-2+2I, i2-2+I} + 538480 I u_{iI-2+2I, i2-1+I} + (59944 - 135128 I) u_{iI-2+2I, i2+I} - (12827 + 18796 I) u_{iI-2+2I, i2-2} - (59944 + 135128 I) u_{iI-2+2I, i2-1} - 62103 I u_{iI-2+2I, i2} + (19304 - 76200 I) u_{iI-1+2I, i2-2+2I} + (182400 - 336896 I) u_{iI-1+2I, i2-1+2I} + (83096 - 73448 I) u_{iI-1+2I, i2+2I} - 383104 I u_{iI-1+2I, i2-2+I} + (-644480 + 2544000 I) u_{iI-1+2I, i2-1+I} + (444928 - 566656 I) u_{iI-1+2I, i2+I} - (38104 + 104152 I) u_{iI-1+2I, i2-2} - (121472 + 710144 I) u_{iI-1+2I, i2-1} + (74328 - 293400 I) u_{iI-1+2I, i2} + (12827 - 18796 I) u_{iI+2I, i2-2+2I} + (83096 - 73448 I) u_{iI+2I, i2-1+2I} + (29896 - 11703 I) u_{iI+2I, i2+2I} + (38104 - 104152 I) u_{iI+2I, i2-2+I} + (-428240 + 627520 I) u_{iI+2I, i2-1+I} + (177320 - 109800 I) u_{iI+2I, i2+I} - 32105 I u_{iI+2I, i2-2} + (37608 - 205144 I) u_{iI+2I, i2-1} + (49389 - 72372 I) u_{iI+2I, i2} - (19304 + 76200 I) u_{iI-2+1, i2-2+2I} - 383104 I u_{iI-2+1, i2-1+2I} + (38104 - 104152 I) u_{iI-2+1, i2+2I} - (182400 + 336896 I) u_{iI-2+1, i2-2+I} + (644480 + 2544000 I) u_{iI-2+1, i2-1+I} + (121472 - 710144 I) u_{iI-2+1, i2+I} - (83096 + 73448 I) u_{iI-2+1, i2-2} - (444928 + 566656 I) u_{iI-2+1, i2-1} - (74328 + 293400 I) u_{iI-2+1, i2} + 538480 I u_{iI-1+1, i2-2+2I} + (-644480 + 2544000 I) u_{iI-1+1, i2-1+2I} + (-428240 + 627520 I) u_{iI-1+1, i2+2I} + (644480 + 2544000 I) u_{iI-1+1, i2-2+I} - 17977600 I u_{iI-1+1, i2-1+I} + (-2001280 + 4511360 I) u_{iI-1+1, i2+I} + (428240 + 627520 I) u_{iI-1+1, i2-2} + (2001280 + 4511360 I) u_{iI-1+1, i2-1} + 2073360 I u_{iI-1+1, i2} + (59944 - 135128 I) u_{iI+1, i2-2+2I} + (444928 - 566656 I) u_{iI+1, i2-1+2I} + (177320 - 109800 I) u_{iI+1, i2+2I} + (121472 - 710144 I) u_{iI+1, i2-2+I} + (-2001280 + 4511360 I) u_{iI+1, i2-1+I} + (1004416 - 909312 I) u_{iI+1, i2+I} - (37608 + 205144 I) u_{iI+1, i2-2} - 1354880 I u_{iI+1, i2-1} + (230808 - 520296 I) u_{iI+1, i2} - (12827 + 18796 I) u_{iI-2, i2-2+2I} - (38104 + 104152 I) u_{iI-2, i2-1+2I} - 32105 I u_{iI-2, i2+2I} - (83096 + 73448 I) u_{iI-2, i2-2+I} + (428240 + 627520 I) u_{iI-2, i2-1+I} - (37608 + 205144 I) u_{iI-2, i2+I} - (29896 + 11703 I) u_{iI-2, i2-2} - (177320 + 109800 I) u_{iI-2, i2-1} - (49389 + 72372 I) u_{iI-2, i2} - (59944 + 135128 I) u_{iI-1, i2-2+2I} - (121472 + 710144 I) u_{iI-1, i2-1+2I} + (37608 - 205144 I) u_{iI-1, i2+2I} - (444928 + 566656 I) u_{iI-1, i2-2+I} + (2001280 + 4511360 I) u_{iI-1, i2-1+I} - 1354880 I u_{iI-1, i2+I} - (177320 + 109800 I) u_{iI-1, i2-2} - (1004416 + 909312 I) u_{iI-1, i2-1} - (230808 + 520296 I) u_{iI-1, i2} - 62103 I u_{iI, i2-2+2I} + (74328 - 293400 I) u_{iI, i2-1+2I} + (49389 - 72372 I) u_{iI, i2+2I} - (74328 + 293400 I) u_{iI, i2-2+I} + 2073360 I u_{iI, i2-1+I} + (230808 - 520296 I) u_{iI, i2+I} - (49389 + 72372 I) u_{iI, i2-2} - (230808 + 520296 I) u_{iI, i2-1} - 239121 I u_{iI, i2} \right) \right), O(\Delta x I^6 \Delta x2^6), \text{ Quadrant 2}$$

Error order.: 6, Error.: 5.5584536946957959239 × 10⁻¹⁷, New Error.: 5.5724135693362756391 × 10⁻³⁵
 Error order.: 6, Error.: 5.5724135693362756391 × 10⁻³⁵, New Error.: 5.5724275467435248407 × 10⁻⁵³
 Error order.: 6, Error.: 5.5724275467435248407 × 10⁻⁵³, New Error.: 5.5724275607209496374 × 10⁻⁷¹
 Error order.: 6, Error.: 5.5724275607209496374 × 10⁻⁷¹, New Error.: 5.5724275607349270622 × 10⁻⁸⁹
 Error order.: 6, Error.: 5.5724275607349270622 × 10⁻⁸⁹, New Error.: 5.5724275607349410396 × 10⁻¹⁰⁷

$$\frac{d^9}{dxI^9} u(xI) = \frac{1}{32000 \Delta x I^9} \left(27 \left((2048383 + 2048383 I) u_{iI-6+6I} + (21677376 + 36387024 I) u_{iI-5+6I} + (61137165 + 209900139 I) u_{iI-4+6I} + (6412832 + 454347520 I) u_{iI-3+6I} + (-95681997 + 293228931 I) u_{iI-2+6I} + (-51716544 + 66582192 I) u_{iI-1+6I} + (-6894063 + 4319159 I) u_{iI+6I} + (36387024 + 21677376 I) u_{iI-6+5I} + (86764368 + 86764368 I) u_{iI-5+5I} - (853568784 + 1382617632 I) u_{iI-4+5I} - (1916248416 + 6066749856 I) u_{iI-3+5I} - (61955280 + 1804160544 I) u_{iI-2+5I} + (-273510480 + 442914480 I) u_{iI-1+5I} + (-116976240 + 107022720 I) u_{iI+5I} + (209900139 + 61137165 I) u_{iI-6+4I} - (1382617632 + 853568784 I) u_{iI-5+4I} - (1356617403 + 1356617403 I) u_{iI-4+4I} + (23539105632 + 37555397760 I) u_{iI-3+4I} + (51053355 - 8575817571 I) u_{iI-2+4I} + (646386528 - 3285144432 I) u_{iI-1+4I} + (-648774891 + 881904453 I) u_{iI+4I} + (454347520 + 6412832 I) u_{iI-6+3I} - (6066749856 + 1916248416 I) u_{iI-5+3I} + (37555397760 + 23539105632 I) u_{iI-4+3I} - (111051722752 + 111051722752 I) u_{iI-3+3I} + (26964711936 + 78197066016 I) u_{iI-2+3I} + (1364261472 - 22448041824 I) u_{iI-1+3I} + (-1202573952 + 2833727584 I) u_{iI+3I} + (293228931 - 95681997 I) u_{iI-6+2I} - (1804160544 + 61955280 I) u_{iI-5+2I} + (-8575817571 + 51053355 I) u_{iI-4+2I} + (78197066016 + 26964711936 I) u_{iI-3+2I} - (2326436685 + 2326436685 I) u_{iI-2+2I} - (4145378592 + 11613107376 I) u_{iI-1+2I} + (-105801507 + 2986062363 I) u_{iI+2I} + (66582192 - 51716544 I) u_{iI-6+1I} + (442914480 - 273510480 I) u_{iI-5+1I} + (-3285144432 + 646386528 I) u_{iI-4+1I} + (-22448041824 + 1364261472 I) u_{iI-3+1I} - (11613107376 + 4145378592 I) u_{iI-2+1I} + (933598800 + 933598800 I) u_{iI-1+1I} + (424678896 + 1101869568 I) u_{iI+1I} + (4319159 - 6894063 I) u_{iI-6} + (107022720 - 116976240 I) u_{iI-5} + (881904453 - 648774891 I) u_{iI-4} + (2833727584 - 1202573952 I) u_{iI-3} + (2986062363 - 105801507 I) u_{iI-2} + (1101869568 + 424678896 I) u_{iI-1} + (116930169 + 116930169 I) u_{iI} \right) \right), O(\Delta x I^6), \text{ Quadrant 2}$$

Error order.: 6, Error.: 5.0560741476166937960 × 10⁻¹⁸, New Error.: 5.0647797196948563151 × 10⁻³⁶
 Error order.: 6, Error.: 5.0647797196948563151 × 10⁻³⁶, New Error.: 5.0647884327647500454 × 10⁻⁵⁴
 Error order.: 6, Error.: 5.0647884327647500454 × 10⁻⁵⁴, New Error.: 5.0647884414778274413 × 10⁻⁷²
 Error order.: 6, Error.: 5.0647884414778274413 × 10⁻⁷², New Error.: 5.0647884414865405187 × 10⁻⁹⁰
 Error order.: 6, Error.: 5.0647884414865405187 × 10⁻⁹⁰, New Error.: 5.0647884414865492318 × 10⁻¹⁰⁸

$$\begin{bmatrix} -2 + 2I & -1 + 2I & 2I \\ -2 + I & -1 + I & I \\ -2 & -1 & 0 \end{bmatrix}$$

$$\begin{bmatrix} 441 - 441I & 2016 - 1764I & 567 - 441I \\ 1764 - 2016I & -10080 + 10080I & 2268 - 2016I \\ 441 - 567I & 2016 - 2268I & 567 - 567I \end{bmatrix}$$

$$\frac{d^7}{dxI^7} u(xI) = \frac{(441 - 441I) u_{iI-2+2I} + (2016 - 1764I) u_{iI-1+2I} + (567 - 441I) u_{iI+2I} + (1764 - 2016I) u_{iI-2+I} + (-10080 + 10080I) u_{iI-1+I} + (2268 - 2016I) u_{iI+I} + (441 - 567I) u_{iI-2} + (2016 - 2268I) u_{iI-1} + (567 - 567I) u_{iI}}{\Delta xI^7}, O(\Delta xI^2), \text{ Quadrant 2}$$

Error order.: 2, Error.: 0.000010539229410899121343, New Error.: 1.0553248960523411687 × 10⁻¹¹
 Error order.: 2, Error.: 1.0553248960523411687 × 10⁻¹¹, New Error.: 1.0553262989402611935 × 10⁻¹⁷
 Error order.: 2, Error.: 1.0553262989402611935 × 10⁻¹⁷, New Error.: 1.0553263003431500469 × 10⁻²³
 Error order.: 2, Error.: 1.0553263003431500469 × 10⁻²³, New Error.: 1.0553263003445529358 × 10⁻²⁹
 Error order.: 2, Error.: 1.0553263003445529358 × 10⁻²⁹, New Error.: 1.0553263003445543386 × 10⁻³⁵

$$\frac{d^{14}}{dxI^{14}} u(xI) = \frac{1}{\Delta xI^{14}} (-388962 I u_{iI-4+4I} + (222264 - 3333960 I) u_{iI-3+4I} + (1063692 - 8001504 I) u_{iI-2+4I} + (730296 - 3778488 I) u_{iI-1+4I} + (127008 - 500094 I) u_{iI+4I} - (222264 + 3333960 I) u_{iI-4+3I} + 3429216 I u_{iI-3+3I} + (-4635792 + 68584320 I) u_{iI-2+3I} + (-508032 + 4191264 I) u_{iI-1+3I} + (793800 - 4286520 I) u_{iI+3I} - (1063692 + 8001504 I) u_{iI-4+2I} + (4635792 + 68584320 I) u_{iI-3+2I} - 237758976 I u_{iI-2+2I} + (-4508784 + 77728896 I) u_{iI-1+2I} + (1222452 - 10287648 I) u_{iI+2I} - (730296 + 3778488 I) u_{iI-4+I} + (508032 + 4191264 I) u_{iI-3+I} + (4508784 + 77728896 I) u_{iI-2+I} + 4445280 I u_{iI-1+I} + (285768 - 4858056 I) u_{iI+I} - (127008 + 500094 I) u_{iI-4} - (793800 + 4286520 I) u_{iI-3} - (1222452 + 10287648 I) u_{iI-2} - (285768 + 4858056 I) u_{iI-1} - 642978 I u_{iI}), O(\Delta xI^2), \text{ Quadrant 2}$$

Error order.: 2, Error.: 0.000020785707036496218707, New Error.: 2.0813356764959760175 × 10⁻¹¹
 Error order.: 2, Error.: 2.0813356764959760175 × 10⁻¹¹, New Error.: 2.0813384433033251108 × 10⁻¹⁷
 Error order.: 2, Error.: 2.0813384433033251108 × 10⁻¹⁷, New Error.: 2.0813384460701343007 × 10⁻²³
 Error order.: 2, Error.: 2.0813384460701343007 × 10⁻²³, New Error.: 2.0813384460729011099 × 10⁻²⁹
 Error order.: 2, Error.: 2.0813384460729011099 × 10⁻²⁹, New Error.: 2.0813384460729038767 × 10⁻³⁵

$$\frac{\partial^{14}}{\partial xI^7 \partial x2^7} u(xI, x2) = \frac{1}{\Delta xI^7 \Delta x2^7} (-388962 I u_{iI-2+2I, i2-2+2I} + (111132 - 1666980 I) u_{iI-2+2I, i2-1+2I} + (55566 - 444528 I) u_{iI-2+2I, i2+2I} - (111132 + 1666980 I) u_{iI-2+2I, i2-2+I} + 8890560 I u_{iI-2+2I, i2-1+I} + (111132 - 1889244 I) u_{iI-2+2I, i2+I} - (55566 + 444528 I) u_{iI-2+2I, i2-2} - (111132 + 1889244 I) u_{iI-2+2I, i2-1} - 500094 I u_{iI-2+2I, i2} + (111132 - 1666980 I) u_{iI-1+2I, i2-2+2I} + (952560 - 7112448 I) u_{iI-1+2I, i2-1+2I} + (365148 - 1889244 I) u_{iI-1+2I, i2+2I} - 7175952 I u_{iI-1+2I, i2-2+I} + (-2540160 + 38102400 I) u_{iI-1+2I, i2-1+I} + (1016064 - 8065008 I) u_{iI-1+2I, i2+I} - (111132 + 1920996 I) u_{iI-1+2I, i2-2} + (63504 - 8128512 I) u_{iI-1+2I, i2-1} + (142884 - 2143260 I) u_{iI-1+2I, i2} + (55566 - 444528 I) u_{iI+2I, i2-2+2I} + (365148 - 1889244 I) u_{iI+2I, i2-1+2I} + (127008 - 500094 I) u_{iI+2I, i2+2I} + (111132 - 1920996 I) u_{iI+2I, i2-2+I} + (-1270080 + 10160640 I) u_{iI+2I, i2-1+I} + (396900 - 2143260 I) u_{iI+2I, i2+I} - 515970 I u_{iI+2I, i2-2} + (142884 - 2175012 I) u_{iI+2I, i2-1} + (71442 - 571536 I) u_{iI+2I, i2} - (111132 + 1666980 I) u_{iI-2+1, i2-2+2I} - 7175952 I u_{iI-2+1, i2-1+2I} + (111132 - 1920996 I) u_{iI-2+1, i2+2I} - (952560 + 7112448 I) u_{iI-2+1, i2-2+I} + (2540160 + 38102400 I) u_{iI-2+1, i2-1+I} - (63504 + 8128512 I) u_{iI-2+1, i2+I} - (365148 + 1889244 I) u_{iI-2+1, i2-2} - (1016064 + 8065008 I) u_{iI-2+1, i2-1} - (142884 + 2143260 I) u_{iI-2+1, i2} + 8890560 I u_{iI-1+1, i2-2+2I} + (-2540160 + 38102400 I) u_{iI-1+1, i2-1+2I} + (-1270080 + 10160640 I) u_{iI-1+1, i2+2I} + (2540160 + 38102400 I) u_{iI-1+1, i2-2+I} - 203212800 I u_{iI-1+1, i2-1+I} + (-2540160 + 43182720 I) u_{iI-1+1, i2+I} + (1270080 + 10160640 I) u_{iI-1+1, i2-2} + (2540160 + 43182720 I) u_{iI-1+1, i2-1} + 11430720 I u_{iI-1+1, i2} + (111132 - 1889244 I) u_{iI+1, i2-2+2I} + (1016064 - 8065008 I) u_{iI+1, i2-1+2I} + (396900 - 2143260 I) u_{iI+1, i2+I} - (63504 + 8128512 I) u_{iI+1, i2-2+I} + (-2540160 + 43182720 I) u_{iI+1, i2-1+I} + (1079568 - 9144576 I) u_{iI+1, i2+I} - (142884 + 2175012 I) u_{iI+1, i2-2} - 9208080 I u_{iI+1, i2-1} + (142884 - 2429028 I) u_{iI+1, i2} - (55566 + 444528 I) u_{iI-2, i2-2+2I} - (111132 + 1920996 I) u_{iI-2, i2-1+2I} - 515970 I u_{iI-2, i2+2I} - (365148 + 1889244 I) u_{iI-2, i2-2+I} + (1270080 + 10160640 I) u_{iI-2, i2-1+I} - (142884 + 2175012 I) u_{iI-2, i2+I} - (127008 + 500094 I) u_{iI-2, i2-2} - (396900 + 2143260 I) u_{iI-2, i2-1} - (71442 + 571536 I) u_{iI-2, i2} - (111132 + 1889244 I) u_{iI-1, i2-2+2I} + (63504 - 8128512 I) u_{iI-1, i2-1+2I} + (142884 - 2175012 I) u_{iI-1, i2+2I} - (1016064 + 8065008 I) u_{iI-1, i2-2+I} + (2540160 + 43182720 I) u_{iI-1, i2-1+I} - 9208080 I u_{iI-1, i2+I} - (396900 + 2143260 I) u_{iI-1, i2-2} - (1079568 + 9144576 I) u_{iI-1, i2-1} - (142884 + 2429028 I) u_{iI-1, i2} - 500094 I u_{iI, i2-2+2I} + (142884 - 2143260 I) u_{iI, i2-1+2I} + (71442 - 571536 I) u_{iI, i2+I} - (142884 + 2143260 I) u_{iI, i2-2+I} + 11430720 I u_{iI, i2-1+I} + (142884 - 2429028 I) u_{iI, i2+I} - (71442 + 571536 I) u_{iI, i2-2} - (142884 + 2429028 I) u_{iI, i2-1} - 642978 I u_{iI, i2}), O(\Delta xI^2 \Delta x2^2), \text{ Quadrant 2}$$

Error order.: 2, Error.: 0.000089409417074995960638, New Error.: 8.9569410152072423356 × 10⁻¹¹
 Error order.: 2, Error.: 8.9569410152072423356 × 10⁻¹¹, New Error.: 8.9569570287976932665 × 10⁻¹⁷
 Error order.: 2, Error.: 8.9569570287976932665 × 10⁻¹⁷, New Error.: 8.9569570448112980466 × 10⁻²³
 Error order.: 2, Error.: 8.9569570448112980466 × 10⁻²³, New Error.: 8.9569570448273116514 × 10⁻²⁹
 Error order.: 2, Error.: 8.9569570448273116514 × 10⁻²⁹, New Error.: 8.9569570448273276650 × 10⁻³⁵

"--- Derivative Order: 8 - xI=1 ---"

$$\begin{bmatrix} -2 + 2I & -1 + 2I & 2I \\ -2 + I & -1 + I & I \\ -2 & -1 & 0 \end{bmatrix}$$

$$\begin{bmatrix} 504 & 2016 & 504 \\ 2016 & -10080 & 2016 \\ 504 & 2016 & 504 \end{bmatrix}$$

$$\frac{d^8}{dxI^8} u(xI) = \frac{504 (u_{iI-2+2I} + 4 u_{iI-1+2I} + u_{iI+2I} + 4 u_{iI-2+I} - 20 u_{iI-1+I} + 4 u_{iI+I} + u_{iI-2} + 4 u_{iI-1} + u_{iI})}{\Delta xI^8}, O(\Delta xI), \text{ Quadrant 2}$$

Error order.: 1, Error.: 0.0074548401593598494086, New Error.: 7.4622763859961161802 × 10⁻⁶
 Error order.: 1, Error.: 7.4622763859961161802 × 10⁻⁶, New Error.: 7.4622838259340661388 × 10⁻⁹
 Error order.: 1, Error.: 7.4622838259340661388 × 10⁻⁹, New Error.: 7.4622838333740078013 × 10⁻¹²
 Error order.: 1, Error.: 7.4622838333740078013 × 10⁻¹², New Error.: 7.4622838333814477430 × 10⁻¹⁵
 Error order.: 1, Error.: 7.4622838333814477430 × 10⁻¹⁵, New Error.: 7.4622838333814551829 × 10⁻¹⁸

$$\frac{d^{16}}{dx^{16}} u(xI) = \frac{1}{\Delta x^{16}} (254016 (u_{iI-4+41} + 8 u_{iI-3+41} + 18 u_{iI-2+41} + 8 u_{iI-1+41} + u_{iI+41} + 8 u_{iI-4+31} - 8 u_{iI-3+31} - 144 u_{iI-2+31} - 8 u_{iI-1+31} + 8 u_{iI+31} + 18 u_{iI-4+21} - 144 u_{iI-3+21} + 468 u_{iI-2+21} - 144 u_{iI-1+21} + 18 u_{iI+21} + 8 u_{iI-4+1} - 8 u_{iI-3+1} - 144 u_{iI-2+1} - 8 u_{iI-1+1} + 8 u_{iI+1} + u_{iI-4} + 8 u_{iI-3} + 18 u_{iI-2} + 8 u_{iI-1} + u_{iI})), O(\Delta xI), \text{ Quadrant 2}$$

Error order:, 1, *Error:*, 0.014658621527332591175, *New Error:*, 0.000014687880155523541605
Error order:, 1, *Error:*, 0.000014687880155523541605, *New Error:*, 1.4687909443361674616 × 10⁻⁸
Error order:, 1, *Error:*, 1.4687909443361674616 × 10⁻⁸, *New Error:*, 1.4687909472649541978 × 10⁻¹¹
Error order:, 1, *Error:*, 1.4687909472649541978 × 10⁻¹¹, *New Error:*, 1.4687909472678829846 × 10⁻¹⁴
Error order:, 1, *Error:*, 1.4687909472678829846 × 10⁻¹⁴, *New Error:*, 1.4687909472678859134 × 10⁻¹⁷

$$\frac{\partial^{16}}{\partial xI^8 \partial x2^8} u(xI, x2) = \frac{1}{\Delta xI^8 \Delta x2^8} (254016 (u_{iI-2+21, i2-2+21} + 4 u_{iI-2+21, i2-1+21} + u_{iI-2+21, i2+21} + 4 u_{iI-2+21, i2-2+1} - 20 u_{iI-2+21, i2-1+1} + 4 u_{iI-2+21, i2+1} + u_{iI-2+21, i2-2} + 4 u_{iI-2+21, i2-1} + u_{iI-2+21, i2} + 4 u_{iI-1+21, i2-2+21} + 16 u_{iI-1+21, i2-1+21} + 4 u_{iI-1+21, i2+21} + 16 u_{iI-1+21, i2-2+1} - 80 u_{iI-1+21, i2-1+1} + 16 u_{iI-1+21, i2+1} + 4 u_{iI-1+21, i2-2} + 16 u_{iI-1+21, i2-1} + 4 u_{iI-1+21, i2} + u_{iI+21, i2-2+21} + 4 u_{iI+21, i2-1+21} + u_{iI+21, i2+21} + 4 u_{iI+21, i2-2+1} - 20 u_{iI+21, i2-1+1} + 4 u_{iI+21, i2+1} + u_{iI+21, i2-2} + 4 u_{iI+21, i2-1} + u_{iI+21, i2} + 4 u_{iI-2+1, i2-2+21} + 16 u_{iI-2+1, i2-1+21} + 4 u_{iI-2+1, i2+21} + 16 u_{iI-2+1, i2-2+1} - 80 u_{iI-2+1, i2-1+1} + 16 u_{iI-2+1, i2+1} + 4 u_{iI-2+1, i2-2} + 16 u_{iI-2+1, i2-1} + 4 u_{iI-2+1, i2} - 20 u_{iI-1+1, i2-2+21} - 80 u_{iI-1+1, i2-1+21} - 20 u_{iI-1+1, i2+21} - 80 u_{iI-1+1, i2-2+1} + 400 u_{iI-1+1, i2-1+1} - 80 u_{iI-1+1, i2+1} - 20 u_{iI-1+1, i2-2} - 80 u_{iI-1+1, i2-1} - 20 u_{iI-1+1, i2} + 4 u_{iI+1, i2-2+21} + 16 u_{iI+1, i2-1+21} + 4 u_{iI+1, i2+21} + 16 u_{iI+1, i2-2+1} - 80 u_{iI+1, i2-1+1} + 16 u_{iI+1, i2+1} + 4 u_{iI+1, i2-2} + 16 u_{iI+1, i2-1} + 4 u_{iI+1, i2} + u_{iI-2, i2-2+21} + 4 u_{iI-2, i2-1+21} + u_{iI-2, i2+21} + 4 u_{iI-2, i2-2+1} - 20 u_{iI-2, i2-1+1} + 4 u_{iI-2, i2+1} + u_{iI-2, i2-2} + 4 u_{iI-2, i2-1} + u_{iI-2, i2} + 4 u_{iI-1, i2-2+21} + 16 u_{iI-1, i2-1+21} + 4 u_{iI-1, i2+21} + 16 u_{iI-1, i2-2+1} - 80 u_{iI-1, i2-1+1} + 16 u_{iI-1, i2+1} + 4 u_{iI-1, i2-2} + 16 u_{iI-1, i2-1} + 4 u_{iI-1, i2} + u_{iI, i2-2+21} + 4 u_{iI, i2-1+21} + u_{iI, i2+21} + 4 u_{iI, i2-2+1} - 20 u_{iI, i2-1+1} + 4 u_{iI, i2+1} + u_{iI, i2-2} + 4 u_{iI, i2-1} + u_{iI, i2})), O(\Delta xI \Delta x2), \text{ Quadrant 2}$$

Error order:, 1, *Error:*, 0.048490656009356909125, *New Error:*, 0.000048611597966016818846
Error order:, 1, *Error:*, 0.000048611597966016818846, *New Error:*, 4.8611719058821653670 × 10⁻⁸
Error order:, 1, *Error:*, 4.8611719058821653670 × 10⁻⁸, *New Error:*, 4.8611719179914609479 × 10⁻¹¹
Error order:, 1, *Error:*, 4.8611719179914609479 × 10⁻¹¹, *New Error:*, 4.8611719180035702435 × 10⁻¹⁴
Error order:, 1, *Error:*, 4.8611719180035702435 × 10⁻¹⁴, *New Error:*, 4.8611719180035823527 × 10⁻¹⁷

"--- Derivative Order: 1 - x1=1 ---"

$$\begin{bmatrix} -3 + 3I & -2 + 3I & -1 + 3I & 3I \\ -3 + 2I & -2 + 2I & -1 + 2I & 2I \\ -3 + I & -2 + I & -1 + I & I \\ -3 & -2 & -1 & 0 \end{bmatrix}$$

$$\begin{bmatrix} -\frac{1}{6} - \frac{I}{6} & \frac{198}{65} - \frac{171I}{65} & \frac{9}{10} + \frac{9I}{2} & -\frac{1}{3} \\ -\frac{171}{65} + \frac{198I}{65} & \frac{351}{4} + \frac{351I}{4} & \frac{702}{5} - \frac{351I}{5} & -\frac{9}{10} - \frac{36I}{5} \\ \frac{9}{2} + \frac{9I}{10} & -\frac{351}{5} + \frac{702I}{5} & -\frac{351}{2} - \frac{351I}{2} & \frac{72}{5} + \frac{9I}{5} \\ -\frac{I}{3} & -\frac{36}{5} - \frac{9I}{10} & \frac{9}{5} + \frac{72I}{5} & \frac{215}{52} + \frac{215I}{52} \end{bmatrix}$$

$$\frac{d}{dxI} u(xI) = \frac{1}{780 \Delta xI} (- (130 + 130I) u_{iI-3+31} + (2376 - 2052I) u_{iI-2+31} + (702 + 3510I) u_{iI-1+31} - 260 u_{iI+31} + (-2052 + 2376I) u_{iI-3+21} + (68445 + 68445I) u_{iI-2+21} + (109512 - 54756I) u_{iI-1+21} - (702 + 5616I) u_{iI+21} + (3510 + 702I) u_{iI-3+1} + (-54756 + 109512I) u_{iI-2+1} - (136890 + 136890I) u_{iI-1+1} + (11232 + 1404I) u_{iI+1} - 260I u_{iI-3} - (5616 + 702I) u_{iI-2} + (1404 + 11232I) u_{iI-1} + (3225 + 3225I) u_{iI}), O(\Delta xI^{15}), \text{ Quadrant 2}$$

Error order:, 15, *Error:*, 1.6135089038773433110 × 10⁻⁴⁸, *New Error:*, 1.6180574528895215955 × 10⁻⁹³
Error order:, 15, *Error:*, 1.6180574528895215955 × 10⁻⁹³, *New Error:*, 1.6180620078501996890 × 10⁻¹³⁸
Error order:, 15, *Error:*, 1.6180620078501996890 × 10⁻¹³⁸, *New Error:*, 1.6180620124051667848 × 10⁻¹⁸³
Error order:, 15, *Error:*, 1.6180620124051667848 × 10⁻¹⁸³, *New Error:*, 1.6180620124097217519 × 10⁻²²⁸
Error order:, 15, *Error:*, 1.6180620124097217519 × 10⁻²²⁸, *New Error:*, 1.6180620124097263068 × 10⁻²⁷³

$$\frac{d^2}{dxI^2} u(xI) = \frac{1}{304200 \Delta xI^2} (16900I u_{iI-6+61} - (575640 + 42120I) u_{iI-5+61} + (1082376 - 5423112I) u_{iI-4+61} + (8904272 + 6933056I) u_{iI-3+61} + (-6531408 + 2997540I) u_{iI-2+61} - (182520 + 912600I) u_{iI-1+61} + 33800 u_{iI+61} + (575640 - 42120I) u_{iI-6+51} - 7939620I u_{iI-5+51} + (271939356 + 9523332I) u_{iI-4+51} - (44457660 + 66324960I) u_{iI-3+51} + (238083300 + 316249596I) u_{iI-2+51} + (-9253764 + 7830108I) u_{iI-1+51} + (182520 + 1460160I) u_{iI+51} - (1082376 + 5423112I) u_{iI-6+41} + (-271939356 + 9523332I) u_{iI-5+41} + 5478241977I u_{iI-4+41} + (10226942388 + 3596136804I) u_{iI-3+41} + (5261859954 - 7053640542I) u_{iI-2+41} - (345838896 + 500579352I) u_{iI-1+41} + (-18443646 + 3577392I) u_{iI+41} + (-8904272 + 6933056I) u_{iI-6+31} + (44457660 - 66324960I) u_{iI-5+31} + (-10226942388 + 3596136804I) u_{iI-4+31} - 3741342800I u_{iI-3+31} - (21183209208 + 6386005224I) u_{iI-2+31} + (624817908 + 414269856I) u_{iI-1+31} - (838500 + 64903020I) u_{iI+31} + (6531408 + 2997540I) u_{iI-6+21} + (-238083300 + 316249596I) u_{iI-5+21} - (5261859954 + 7053640542I) u_{iI-4+21} + (21183209208 - 6386005224I) u_{iI-3+21} + 21518697330I u_{iI-2+21} - (753497316 + 1568923668I) u_{iI-1+21} + (77940954 - 4605822I) u_{iI+21} + (182520 - 912600I) u_{iI-6+1} + (9253764 + 7830108I) u_{iI-5+1} + (345838896 - 500579352I) u_{iI-4+1} + (-624817908 + 414269856I) u_{iI-3+1} + (753497316 - 1568923668I) u_{iI-2+1} - 754811460I u_{iI-1+1} + (31695300 + 40751100I) u_{iI+1} - 33800 u_{iI-6} + (-182520 + 1460160I) u_{iI-5} + (18443646 + 3577392I) u_{iI-4} + (838500 - 64903020I) u_{iI-3} - (77940954 + 4605822I) u_{iI-2} + (-31695300 + 40751100I) u_{iI-1} + 10400625I u_{iI}), O(\Delta xI^{15}), \text{ Quadrant 2}$$

Error order:, 15, *Error:*, 3.2205766544457950319 × 10⁻⁴⁸, *New Error:*, 3.2296555945898634641 × 10⁻⁹³
Error order:, 15, *Error:*, 3.2296555945898634641 × 10⁻⁹³, *New Error:*, 3.2296646863277438902 × 10⁻¹³⁸
Error order:, 15, *Error:*, 3.2296646863277438902 × 10⁻¹³⁸, *New Error:*, 3.2296646954194945804 × 10⁻¹⁸³
Error order:, 15, *Error:*, 3.2296646954194945804 × 10⁻¹⁸³, *New Error:*, 3.2296646954285863311 × 10⁻²²⁸
Error order:, 15, *Error:*, 3.2296646954285863311 × 10⁻²²⁸, *New Error:*, 3.2296646954285954228 × 10⁻²⁷³

$$+ 2322525608200 I) u_{i,i,2+1} + (134634052280 - 94377850980 I) u_{i,i,2-3} - (1303679771380 + 2980410224540 I) u_{i,i,2-2} + (-4321502838940 + 2322525608200 I) u_{i,i,2-1} + 549421912900 I u_{i,i,2}), O(\Delta x I^{11} \Delta x^{21}), \text{ Quadrant 2}$$

Error order:, 11, *Error:*, 1.0035311485757177049 $\times 10^{-31}$, *New Error:*, 1.0076569164282427556 $\times 10^{-64}$
Error order:, 11, *Error:*, 1.0076569164282427556 $\times 10^{-64}$, *New Error:*, 1.0076610506739818804 $\times 10^{-97}$
Error order:, 11, *Error:*, 1.0076610506739818804 $\times 10^{-97}$, *New Error:*, 1.0076610548082361091 $\times 10^{-130}$
Error order:, 11, *Error:*, 1.0076610548082361091 $\times 10^{-130}$, *New Error:*, 1.0076610548123703633 $\times 10^{-163}$
Error order:, 11, *Error:*, 1.0076610548123703633 $\times 10^{-163}$, *New Error:*, 1.0076610548123744975 $\times 10^{-196}$

"--- Derivative Order: 6 - x1=1 ---"

$$\begin{bmatrix} -3 + 3 I & -2 + 3 I & -1 + 3 I & 3 I \\ -3 + 2 I & -2 + 2 I & -1 + 2 I & 2 I \\ -3 + I & -2 + I & -1 + I & I \\ -3 & -2 & -1 & 0 \end{bmatrix}$$

$$\begin{bmatrix} \frac{583107 I}{130} & -\frac{4806558}{65} & -\frac{107976 I}{65} & \frac{2385243}{65} & -\frac{9691041 I}{130} & 5284 + \frac{216134 I}{65} \\ \frac{4806558}{65} & -\frac{107976 I}{65} & -\frac{10597869 I}{5} & -\frac{12287808}{5} & -\frac{2518002 I}{5} & -\frac{5339691}{130} + \frac{14618751 I}{130} \\ -\frac{2385243}{65} & -\frac{9691041 I}{130} & \frac{12287808}{5} & -\frac{2518002 I}{5} & \frac{32006547 I}{10} & -\frac{1992798}{13} - \frac{4566612 I}{65} \\ -5284 + \frac{216134 I}{65} & \frac{5339691}{130} + \frac{14618751 I}{130} & \frac{1992798}{13} & -\frac{4566612 I}{65} & -\frac{1104562 I}{65} & \end{bmatrix}$$

$$\frac{d^6}{dx I^6} u(xI) = \frac{1}{130 \Delta x I^6} (583107 I u_{i,i,-3+31} - (9613116 + 215952 I) u_{i,i,-2+31} + (4770486 - 9691041 I) u_{i,i,-1+31} + (686920 + 432268 I) u_{i,i,+31} + (9613116 - 215952 I) u_{i,i,-3+21} - 275544594 I u_{i,i,-2+21} - (319483008 + 65468052 I) u_{i,i,-1+21} + (-5339691 + 14618751 I) u_{i,i,+21} - (4770486 + 9691041 I) u_{i,i,-3+1}$$

$$+ (319483008 - 65468052 I) u_{i,i,-2+1} + 416085111 I u_{i,i,-1+1} - (19927980 + 9133224 I) u_{i,i,+1} + (-686920 + 432268 I) u_{i,i,-3} + (5339691 + 14618751 I) u_{i,i,-2} + (19927980 - 9133224 I) u_{i,i,-1} - 2209124 I u_{i,i}), O(\Delta x I^{10}), \text{ Quadrant 2}$$

Error order:, 10, *Error:*, 1.2198499428822304468 $\times 10^{-30}$, *New Error:*, 1.2231786373122938161 $\times 10^{-60}$
Error order:, 10, *Error:*, 1.2231786373122938161 $\times 10^{-60}$, *New Error:*, 1.2231819705487581417 $\times 10^{-90}$
Error order:, 10, *Error:*, 1.2231819705487581417 $\times 10^{-90}$, *New Error:*, 1.2231819738819991522 $\times 10^{-120}$
Error order:, 10, *Error:*, 1.2231819738819991522 $\times 10^{-120}$, *New Error:*, 1.2231819738853323933 $\times 10^{-150}$
Error order:, 10, *Error:*, 1.2231819738853323933 $\times 10^{-150}$, *New Error:*, 1.2231819738853357265 $\times 10^{-180}$

"--- Derivative Order: 7 - x1=1 ---"

$$\begin{bmatrix} -3 + 3 I & -2 + 3 I & -1 + 3 I & 3 I \\ -3 + 2 I & -2 + 2 I & -1 + 2 I & 2 I \\ -3 + I & -2 + I & -1 + I & I \\ -3 & -2 & -1 & 0 \end{bmatrix}$$

$$\begin{bmatrix} -\frac{11382119}{780} + \frac{11382119 I}{780} & -\frac{76695318}{325} & -\frac{78359694 I}{325} & \frac{458968797}{1300} & -\frac{171517731 I}{1300} & \frac{1512938}{195} + \frac{5327714 I}{195} \\ \frac{78359694}{325} + \frac{76695318 I}{325} & \frac{26915427}{4} & -\frac{26915427 I}{4} & -\frac{31599918}{5} & -\frac{45573822 I}{5} & -\frac{601742211}{1300} + \frac{326063997 I}{1300} \\ \frac{171517731}{1300} & -\frac{458968797 I}{1300} & \frac{45573822}{5} + \frac{31599918 I}{5} & -\frac{193478607}{20} + \frac{193478607 I}{20} & -\frac{90244014}{325} & -\frac{207959598 I}{325} \\ -\frac{5327714}{195} & -\frac{1512938 I}{195} & -\frac{326063997}{1300} + \frac{601742211 I}{1300} & \frac{207959598}{325} + \frac{90244014 I}{325} & \frac{35749511}{780} & -\frac{35749511 I}{780} \end{bmatrix}$$

$$\frac{d^7}{dx I^7} u(xI) = \frac{1}{3900 \Delta x I^7} (7 ((-8130085 + 8130085 I) u_{i,i,-3+31} - (131477688 + 134330904 I) u_{i,i,-2+31} + (196700913 - 73507599 I) u_{i,i,-1+31} + (4322680 + 15222040 I) u_{i,i,+31} + (134330904 + 131477688 I) u_{i,i,-3+21} + (3748934475 - 3748934475 I) u_{i,i,-2+21} - (3521133720 + 5078225880 I) u_{i,i,-1+21}$$

$$+ (-257889519 + 139741713 I) u_{i,i,+21} + (73507599 - 196700913 I) u_{i,i,-3+1} + (5078225880 + 3521133720 I) u_{i,i,-2+1} + (-5389761195 + 5389761195 I) u_{i,i,-1+1} - (154704024 + 356502168 I) u_{i,i,+1} - (15222040 + 4322680 I) u_{i,i,-3} + (-139741713 + 257889519 I) u_{i,i,-2} + (356502168 + 154704024 I) u_{i,i,-1} + (25535365 - 25535365 I) u_{i,i}), O(\Delta x I^9), \text{ Quadrant 2}$$

Error order:, 9, *Error:*, 2.9992833845936106430 $\times 10^{-27}$, *New Error:*, 3.0073833924389789578 $\times 10^{-54}$
Error order:, 9, *Error:*, 3.0073833924389789578 $\times 10^{-54}$, *New Error:*, 3.0073915033855351489 $\times 10^{-81}$
Error order:, 9, *Error:*, 3.0073915033855351489 $\times 10^{-81}$, *New Error:*, 3.0073915114964926537 $\times 10^{-108}$
Error order:, 9, *Error:*, 3.0073915114964926537 $\times 10^{-108}$, *New Error:*, 3.0073915115046036112 $\times 10^{-135}$
Error order:, 9, *Error:*, 3.0073915115046036112 $\times 10^{-135}$, *New Error:*, 3.0073915115046117221 $\times 10^{-162}$

"--- Derivative Order: 8 - x1=1 ---"

$$\begin{bmatrix} -3 + 3 I & -2 + 3 I & -1 + 3 I & 3 I \\ -3 + 2 I & -2 + 2 I & -1 + 2 I & 2 I \\ -3 + I & -2 + I & -1 + I & I \\ -3 & -2 & -1 & 0 \end{bmatrix}$$

$$\begin{bmatrix} -\frac{5414976}{65} & -\frac{154098}{65} - \frac{87691338 I}{65} & \frac{17951472}{13} + \frac{7516656 I}{13} & -\frac{641718}{13} + \frac{507654 I}{5} \\ -\frac{154098}{65} + \frac{87691338 I}{65} & \frac{187168464}{5} & \frac{33421878}{5} - \frac{212056866 I}{5} & -\frac{25566912}{13} - \frac{29799504 I}{65} \\ \frac{17951472}{13} - \frac{7516656 I}{13} & \frac{33421878}{5} + \frac{212056866 I}{5} & -\frac{256533984}{5} & \frac{53359362}{65} - \frac{31181094 I}{13} \\ -\frac{641718}{13} - \frac{507654 I}{5} & -\frac{25566912}{13} + \frac{29799504 I}{65} & \frac{53359362}{65} + \frac{31181094 I}{13} & \frac{2871792}{13} \end{bmatrix}$$

$$\frac{d^8}{dx^8} u(xI) = \frac{1}{65 \Delta x I^8} (126 (-42976 u_{iI-3+3I} - (1223 + 695963 I) u_{iI-2+3I} + (712360 + 298280 I) u_{iI-1+3I} + (-25465 + 52377 I) u_{iI+3I} + (-1223 + 695963 I) u_{iI-3+2I} + 19311032 u_{iI-2+2I} + (3448289 - 21878883 I) u_{iI-1+2I} - (1014560 + 236504 I) u_{iI+2I} + (712360 - 298280 I) u_{iI-3+1I} + (3448289$$

$$+ 21878883 I) u_{iI-2+1I} - 26467792 u_{iI-1+1I} + (423487 - 1237345 I) u_{iI+1I} - (25465 + 52377 I) u_{iI-3} + (-1014560 + 236504 I) u_{iI-2} + (423487 + 1237345 I) u_{iI-1} + 113960 u_{iI}), O(\Delta x I^8), \text{ Quadrant 2}$$

$$\text{Error order: 8, Error: } 6.5374451088610107585 \times 10^{-24}, \text{ New Error: } 6.5548766347641314184 \times 10^{-48}$$

$$\text{Error order: 8, Error: } 6.5548766347641314184 \times 10^{-48}, \text{ New Error: } 6.5548940895323880059 \times 10^{-72}$$

$$\text{Error order: 8, Error: } 6.5548940895323880059 \times 10^{-72}, \text{ New Error: } 6.5548941069871795255 \times 10^{-96}$$

$$\text{Error order: 8, Error: } 6.5548941069871795255 \times 10^{-96}, \text{ New Error: } 6.5548941070046343171 \times 10^{-120}$$

$$\text{Error order: 8, Error: } 6.5548941070046343171 \times 10^{-120}, \text{ New Error: } 6.5548941070046517719 \times 10^{-144}$$

"--- Derivative Order: 9 - xI=1 ---"

$$\begin{bmatrix} -3 + 3 I & -2 + 3 I & -1 + 3 I & 3 I \\ -3 + 2 I & -2 + 2 I & -1 + 2 I & 2 I \\ -3 + I & -2 + I & -1 + I & I \\ -3 & -2 & -1 & 0 \end{bmatrix}$$

$$\begin{bmatrix} -\frac{13415976}{65} - \frac{13415976 I}{65} & \frac{211741614}{65} - \frac{218237166 I}{65} & \frac{137000808}{65} + \frac{305368056 I}{65} & -\frac{23278374}{65} + \frac{1925154 I}{13} \\ -\frac{218237166}{65} + \frac{211741614 I}{65} & \frac{451177776}{5} + \frac{451177776 I}{5} & \frac{572126814}{5} - \frac{436461858 I}{5} & -\frac{250405344}{65} - \frac{355205088 I}{65} \\ \frac{305368056}{65} + \frac{137000808 I}{65} & -\frac{436461858}{5} + \frac{572126814 I}{5} & -\frac{590210712}{5} - \frac{590210712 I}{5} & \frac{457771986}{65} - \frac{247619106 I}{65} \\ \frac{1925154}{13} - \frac{23278374 I}{65} & -\frac{355205088}{65} - \frac{250405344 I}{65} & -\frac{247619106}{65} + \frac{457771986 I}{65} & \frac{6087312}{13} + \frac{6087312 I}{13} \end{bmatrix}$$

$$\frac{d^9}{dx^9} u(xI) = \frac{1}{65 \Delta x I^9} (378 (-35492 + 35492 I) u_{iI-3+3I} + (560163 - 577347 I) u_{iI-2+3I} + (362436 + 807852 I) u_{iI-1+3I} + (-61583 + 25465 I) u_{iI+3I} + (-577347 + 560163 I) u_{iI-3+2I} + (15516696 + 15516696 I) u_{iI-2+2I} + (19676319 - 15010593 I) u_{iI-1+2I} - (662448 + 939696 I) u_{iI+2I} + (807852$$

$$+ 362436 I) u_{iI-3+1I} + (-15010593 + 19676319 I) u_{iI-2+1I} - (20298252 + 20298252 I) u_{iI-1+1I} + (1211037 - 655077 I) u_{iI+1I} + (25465 - 61583 I) u_{iI-3} - (939696 + 662448 I) u_{iI-2} + (-655077 + 1211037 I) u_{iI-1} + (80520 + 80520 I) u_{iI}), O(\Delta x I^7), \text{ Quadrant 2}$$

$$\text{Error order: 7, Error: } 1.2533379074191213831 \times 10^{-20}, \text{ New Error: } 1.2566264479794694069 \times 10^{-41}$$

$$\text{Error order: 7, Error: } 1.2566264479794694069 \times 10^{-41}, \text{ New Error: } 1.2566297408348349860 \times 10^{-62}$$

$$\text{Error order: 7, Error: } 1.2566297408348349860 \times 10^{-62}, \text{ New Error: } 1.2566297441276946702 \times 10^{-83}$$

$$\text{Error order: 7, Error: } 1.2566297441276946702 \times 10^{-83}, \text{ New Error: } 1.2566297441309875299 \times 10^{-104}$$

$$\text{Error order: 7, Error: } 1.2566297441309875299 \times 10^{-104}, \text{ New Error: } 1.2566297441309908227 \times 10^{-125}$$

"--- Derivative Order: 10 - xI=1 ---"

$$\begin{bmatrix} -3 + 3 I & -2 + 3 I & -1 + 3 I & 3 I \\ -3 + 2 I & -2 + 2 I & -1 + 2 I & 2 I \\ -3 + I & -2 + I & -1 + I & I \\ -3 & -2 & -1 & 0 \end{bmatrix}$$

$$\begin{bmatrix} -\frac{11347056 I}{13} & \frac{179695908}{13} - \frac{5291244 I}{13} & -\frac{63322560}{13} + \frac{185440752 I}{13} & -1067220 - \frac{4772124 I}{13} \\ -\frac{179695908}{13} - \frac{5291244 I}{13} & 370609344 I & 408124332 + 45598140 I & \frac{28295568}{13} - \frac{242666928 I}{13} \\ \frac{63322560}{13} + \frac{185440752 I}{13} & -408124332 + 45598140 I & -463152816 I & \frac{271763100}{13} + \frac{70600572 I}{13} \\ 1067220 - \frac{4772124 I}{13} & -\frac{28295568}{13} - \frac{242666928 I}{13} & -\frac{271763100}{13} + \frac{70600572 I}{13} & \frac{22238496 I}{13} \end{bmatrix}$$

$$\frac{d^{10}}{dx^{10}} u(xI) = \frac{1}{13 \Delta x I^{10}} (252 (-45028 I u_{iI-3+31} + (713079 - 20997 I) u_{iI-2+31} + (-251280 + 735876 I) u_{iI-1+31} - (55055 + 18937 I) u_{iI+31} - (713079 + 20997 I) u_{iI-3+21} + 19118736 I u_{iI-2+21} + (21054033 + 2352285 I) u_{iI-1+21} + (112284 - 962964 I) u_{iI+21} + (251280 + 735876 I) u_{iI-3+1} + (-21054033 + 2352285 I) u_{iI-2+1} - 23892804 I u_{iI-1+1} + (1078425 + 280161 I) u_{iI+1} + (55055 - 18937 I) u_{iI-3} - (112284 + 962964 I) u_{iI-2} + (-1078425 + 280161 I) u_{iI-1} + 88248 I u_{iI}), O(\Delta x I^6), \text{ Quadrant 2}$$

Error order.: 6, Error.: 2.0874056997987360602 × 10⁻¹⁷, New Error.: 2.0927689960378968453 × 10⁻³⁵
 Error order.: 6, Error.: 2.0927689960378968453 × 10⁻³⁵, New Error.: 2.0927743662252072006 × 10⁻⁵³
 Error order.: 6, Error.: 2.0927743662252072006 × 10⁻⁵³, New Error.: 2.0927743715954014080 × 10⁻⁷¹
 Error order.: 6, Error.: 2.0927743715954014080 × 10⁻⁷¹, New Error.: 2.0927743716007716022 × 10⁻⁸⁹
 Error order.: 6, Error.: 2.0927743716007716022 × 10⁻⁸⁹, New Error.: 2.0927743716007769724 × 10⁻¹⁰⁷

--- Derivative Order: 11 - xI=1 ---

$$\begin{bmatrix} -3 + 3 I & -2 + 3 I & -1 + 3 I & 3 I \\ -3 + 2 I & -2 + 2 I & -1 + 2 I & 2 I \\ -3 + I & -2 + I & -1 + I & I \\ -3 & -2 & -1 & 0 \end{bmatrix}$$

$$\begin{bmatrix} \frac{19967640}{13} - \frac{19967640 I}{13} & \frac{1630077372}{65} + \frac{1489819716 I}{65} & -\frac{2095981272}{65} + \frac{1125703656 I}{65} & -\frac{17497788}{13} - \frac{30670332 I}{13} \\ -\frac{1489819716}{65} - \frac{1630077372 I}{65} & -632032632 + 632032632 I & 623724948 + 745870356 I & \frac{2133103896}{65} - \frac{1878933672 I}{65} \\ -\frac{1125703656}{65} + \frac{2095981272 I}{65} & -745870356 - 623724948 I & 755076168 - 755076168 I & \frac{1681420356}{65} + \frac{2665918332 I}{65} \\ \frac{30670332}{13} + \frac{17497788 I}{13} & \frac{1878933672}{65} - \frac{2133103896 I}{65} & -\frac{2665918332}{65} - \frac{1681420356 I}{65} & -\frac{34038312}{13} + \frac{34038312 I}{13} \end{bmatrix}$$

$$\frac{d^{11}}{dx^{11}} u(xI) = \frac{1}{65 \Delta x I^{11}} (924 ((108050 - 108050 I) u_{iI-3+31} + (1764153 + 1612359 I) u_{iI-2+31} + (-2268378 + 1218294 I) u_{iI-1+31} - (94685 + 165965 I) u_{iI+31} - (1612359 + 1764153 I) u_{iI-3+21} + (-44461170 + 44461170 I) u_{iI-2+21} + (43876755 + 52469235 I) u_{iI-1+21} + (2308554 - 2033478 I) u_{iI+21} + (-1218294 + 2268378 I) u_{iI-3+1} - (52469235 + 43876755 I) u_{iI-2+1} + (53116830 - 53116830 I) u_{iI-1+1} + (1819719 + 2885193 I) u_{iI+1} + (165965 + 94685 I) u_{iI-3} + (2033478 - 2308554 I) u_{iI-2} - (2885193 + 1819719 I) u_{iI-1} + (-184190 + 184190 I) u_{iI}), O(\Delta x I^5), \text{ Quadrant 2}$$

Error order.: 5, Error.: 2.9659630286902993538 × 10⁻¹⁴, New Error.: 2.9733693911032721776 × 10⁻²⁹
 Error order.: 5, Error.: 2.9733693911032721776 × 10⁻²⁹, New Error.: 2.9733768067144425446 × 10⁻⁴⁴
 Error order.: 5, Error.: 2.9733768067144425446 × 10⁻⁴⁴, New Error.: 2.9733768141300629715 × 10⁻⁵⁹
 Error order.: 5, Error.: 2.9733768141300629715 × 10⁻⁵⁹, New Error.: 2.9733768141374785919 × 10⁻⁷⁴
 Error order.: 5, Error.: 2.9733768141374785919 × 10⁻⁷⁴, New Error.: 2.9733768141374860075 × 10⁻⁸⁹

--- Derivative Order: 12 - xI=1 ---

$$\begin{bmatrix} -3 + 3 I & -2 + 3 I & -1 + 3 I & 3 I \\ -3 + 2 I & -2 + 2 I & -1 + 2 I & 2 I \\ -3 + I & -2 + I & -1 + I & I \\ -3 & -2 & -1 & 0 \end{bmatrix}$$

$$\begin{bmatrix} \frac{56282688}{13} & \frac{53588304}{13} + \frac{865895184 I}{13} & -\frac{892140480}{13} - \frac{231517440 I}{13} & \frac{13471920}{13} - 5089392 I \\ \frac{53588304}{13} - \frac{865895184 I}{13} & -1722010752 & -122444784 + 1833079248 I & \frac{1053803520}{13} + \frac{13571712 I}{13} \\ -\frac{892140480}{13} + \frac{231517440 I}{13} & -122444784 - 1833079248 I & 1967499072 & -\frac{218843856}{13} + \frac{1111183920 I}{13} \\ \frac{13471920}{13} + 5089392 I & \frac{1053803520}{13} - \frac{13571712 I}{13} & -\frac{218843856}{13} - \frac{1111183920 I}{13} & -\frac{83825280}{13} \end{bmatrix}$$

$$\frac{d^{12}}{dx^{12}} u(xI) = \frac{1}{13 \Delta x I^{12}} (99792 (564 u_{iI-3+31} + (537 + 8677 I) u_{iI-2+31} - (8940 + 2320 I) u_{iI-1+31} + (135 - 663 I) u_{iI+31} + (537 - 8677 I) u_{iI-3+21} - 224328 u_{iI-2+21} + (-15951 + 238797 I) u_{iI-1+21} + (10560 + 136 I) u_{iI+21} + (-8940 + 2320 I) u_{iI-3+1} - (15951 + 238797 I) u_{iI-2+1} + 256308 u_{iI-1+1} + (-2193 + 11135 I) u_{iI+1} + (135 + 663 I) u_{iI-3} + (10560 - 136 I) u_{iI-2} - (2193 + 11135 I) u_{iI-1} - 840 u_{iI}), O(\Delta x I^4), \text{ Quadrant 2}$$

Error order.: 4, Error.: 3.5022371527875921896 × 10⁻¹¹, New Error.: 3.5106301268541145143 × 10⁻²³
 Error order.: 4, Error.: 3.5106301268541145143 × 10⁻²³, New Error.: 3.5106385298867890789 × 10⁻³⁵
 Error order.: 4, Error.: 3.5106385298867890789 × 10⁻³⁵, New Error.: 3.5106385382898318202 × 10⁻⁴⁷
 Error order.: 4, Error.: 3.5106385382898318202 × 10⁻⁴⁷, New Error.: 3.5106385382982348630 × 10⁻⁵⁹
 Error order.: 4, Error.: 3.5106385382982348630 × 10⁻⁵⁹, New Error.: 3.5106385382982432660 × 10⁻⁷¹

--- Derivative Order: 13 - xI=1 ---

$$\frac{d^{13}}{dx^{13}} u(xI) = \frac{1}{\Delta x I^{13}} \begin{bmatrix} -3 + 3I & -2 + 3I & -1 + 3I & 3I \\ -3 + 2I & -2 + 2I & -1 + 2I & 2I \\ -3 + I & -2 + I & -1 + I & I \\ -3 & -2 & -1 & 0 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} 4590432 + 4590432 I & -63767088 + 74943792 I & -55683936 - 86419872 I & 5887728 - 4490640 I \\ 74943792 - 63767088 I & -1759133376 - 1759133376 I & -1918700784 + 1755241488 I & 82228608 + 76640256 I \\ -86419872 - 55683936 I & 1755241488 - 1918700784 I & 1922592672 + 1922592672 I & -95900112 + 67958352 I \\ -4490640 + 5887728 I & 76640256 + 82228608 I & 67958352 - 95900112 I & -5987520 - 5987520 I \end{bmatrix} \\ + (4590432 + 4590432 I) u_{iI-3+3I} + (-63767088 + 74943792 I) u_{iI-2+3I} - (55683936 + 86419872 I) u_{iI-1+3I} + (5887728 - 4490640 I) u_{iI+3I} + (74943792 - 63767088 I) u_{iI-3+2I} - (1759133376 + 1759133376 I) u_{iI-2+2I} + (-1918700784 + 1755241488 I) u_{iI-1+2I} + (82228608 + 76640256 I) u_{iI+2I} - (86419872 + 55683936 I) u_{iI-3+1I} + (1755241488 - 1918700784 I) u_{iI-2+1I} + (1922592672 + 1922592672 I) u_{iI-1+1I} + (-95900112 + 67958352 I) u_{iI+1I} + (-4490640 + 5887728 I) u_{iI-3} + (76640256 + 82228608 I) u_{iI-2} + (67958352 - 95900112 I) u_{iI-1} - (5987520 + 5987520 I) u_{iI}, \\ O(\Delta x I^3), \text{ Quadrant 2}$$

Error order: 3, Error: 3.3039609062239023203 × 10⁻⁸, New Error: 3.3113817539953484121 × 10⁻¹⁷
Error order: 3, Error: 3.3113817539953484121 × 10⁻¹⁷, New Error: 3.3113891831788203557 × 10⁻²⁶
Error order: 3, Error: 3.3113891831788203557 × 10⁻²⁶, New Error: 3.3113891906080121698 × 10⁻³⁵
Error order: 3, Error: 3.3113891906080121698 × 10⁻³⁵, New Error: 3.3113891906154413616 × 10⁻⁴⁴
Error order: 3, Error: 3.3113891906154413616 × 10⁻⁴⁴, New Error: 3.3113891906154487908 × 10⁻⁵³

$$\frac{d^{14}}{dx^{14}} u(xI) = \frac{1}{\Delta x I^{14}} \begin{bmatrix} -3 + 3I & -2 + 3I & -1 + 3I & 3I \\ -3 + 2I & -2 + 2I & -1 + 2I & 2I \\ -3 + I & -2 + I & -1 + I & I \\ -3 & -2 & -1 & 0 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} 6519744 I & -96399072 + 9779616 I & 16765056 - 97796160 I & 6985440 + 465696 I \\ 96399072 + 9779616 I & -2397403008 I & -2451889440 - 54486432 I & 8382528 + 103384512 I \\ -16765056 - 97796160 I & 2451889440 - 54486432 I & 2506375872 I & -104781600 - 15367968 I \\ -6985440 + 465696 I & -8382528 + 103384512 I & 104781600 - 15367968 I & -7451136 I \end{bmatrix} \\ + (465696 (14 I u_{iI-3+3I} + (-207 + 21 I) u_{iI-2+3I} + (36 - 210 I) u_{iI-1+3I} + (15 + I) u_{iI+3I} + (207 + 21 I) u_{iI-3+2I} - 5148 I u_{iI-2+2I} - (5265 + 117 I) u_{iI-1+2I} + (18 + 222 I) u_{iI+2I} - (36 + 210 I) u_{iI-3+1I} + (5265 - 117 I) u_{iI-2+1I} + 5382 I u_{iI-1+1I} - (225 + 33 I) u_{iI+1I} + (-15 + I) u_{iI-3} \\ + (-18 + 222 I) u_{iI-2} + (225 - 33 I) u_{iI-1} - 16 I u_{iI}), O(\Delta x I^2), \text{ Quadrant 2}$$

Error order: 2, Error: 0.000023368367487369093532, New Error: 2.3415010781725058833 × 10⁻¹¹
Error order: 2, Error: 2.3415010781725058833 × 10⁻¹¹, New Error: 2.3415057471583526938 × 10⁻¹⁷
Error order: 2, Error: 2.3415057471583526938 × 10⁻¹⁷, New Error: 2.3415057518273432003 × 10⁻²³
Error order: 2, Error: 2.3415057518273432003 × 10⁻²³, New Error: 2.3415057518320121908 × 10⁻²⁹
Error order: 2, Error: 2.3415057518320121908 × 10⁻²⁹, New Error: 2.3415057518320168598 × 10⁻³⁵

$$\frac{d^{15}}{dx^{15}} u(xI) = \frac{1}{\Delta x I^{15}} \begin{bmatrix} -3 + 3I & -2 + 3I & -1 + 3I & 3I \\ -3 + 2I & -2 + 2I & -1 + 2I & 2I \\ -3 + I & -2 + I & -1 + I & I \\ -3 & -2 & -1 & 0 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} -2328480 + 2328480 I & -37721376 - 29338848 I & 37721376 - 29338848 I & 2328480 + 2328480 I \\ 29338848 + 37721376 I & 817296480 - 817296480 I & -817296480 - 817296480 I & -29338848 + 37721376 I \\ 29338848 - 37721376 I & 817296480 + 817296480 I & -817296480 + 817296480 I & -29338848 - 37721376 I \\ -2328480 - 2328480 I & -37721376 + 29338848 I & 37721376 + 29338848 I & 2328480 - 2328480 I \end{bmatrix} \\ + (-2328480 + 2328480 I) u_{iI-3+3I} - (37721376 + 29338848 I) u_{iI-2+3I} + (37721376 - 29338848 I) u_{iI-1+3I} + (2328480 + 2328480 I) u_{iI+3I} + (29338848 + 37721376 I) u_{iI-3+2I} + (817296480 - 817296480 I) u_{iI-2+2I} - (817296480 + 817296480 I) u_{iI-1+2I} + (-29338848 + 37721376 I) u_{iI+2I} + (29338848 - 37721376 I) u_{iI-3+1I} + (817296480 + 817296480 I) u_{iI-2+1I} + (-817296480 + 817296480 I) u_{iI-1+1I} - (29338848 + 37721376 I) u_{iI+1I} - (2328480 + 2328480 I) u_{iI-3} + (-37721376 + 29338848 I) u_{iI-2} + (37721376 + 29338848 I) u_{iI-1} + (2328480 - 2328480 I) u_{iI}, \\ O(\Delta x I), \text{ Quadrant 2}$$

Error order: 1, Error: 0.011021452432585754052, New Error: 0.000011037947444832374078
Error order: 1, Error: 0.000011037947444832374078, New Error: 1.1037963952194264516 × 10⁻⁸
Error order: 1, Error: 1.1037963952194264516 × 10⁻⁸, New Error: 1.1037963968701638763 × 10⁻¹¹
Error order: 1, Error: 1.1037963968701638763 × 10⁻¹¹, New Error: 1.1037963968718146137 × 10⁻¹⁴
Error order: 1, Error: 1.1037963968718146137 × 10⁻¹⁴, New Error: 1.1037963968718162644 × 10⁻¹⁷

--- Derivative Order: 1 - x1=1 ---

$$\begin{bmatrix} -4 + 4 I & -3 + 4 I & -2 + 4 I & -1 + 4 I & 4 I \\ -4 + 3 I & -3 + 3 I & -2 + 3 I & -1 + 3 I & 3 I \\ -4 + 2 I & -3 + 2 I & -2 + 2 I & -1 + 2 I & 2 I \\ -4 + I & -3 + I & -2 + I & -1 + I & I \\ -4 & -3 & -2 & -1 & 0 \end{bmatrix}$$

$$\begin{bmatrix} \frac{1}{8} + \frac{I}{8} & -\frac{208}{25} - \frac{144 I}{25} & 18 + 36 I & \frac{16}{17} - \frac{208 I}{17} & \frac{I}{4} \\ -\frac{144}{25} - \frac{208 I}{25} & -\frac{2720}{3} - \frac{2720 I}{3} & -\frac{48960}{13} - \frac{73440 I}{13} & -544 - 1632 I & -\frac{16}{3} - 16 I \\ 36 + 18 I & -\frac{73440}{13} - \frac{48960 I}{13} & 29835 + 29835 I & -4896 - 9792 I & 90 I \\ -\frac{208}{17} + \frac{16 I}{17} & -1632 - 544 I & -9792 - 4896 I & -2720 - 2720 I & 16 - 48 I \\ \frac{1}{4} & -16 - \frac{16 I}{3} & 90 & -48 + 16 I & \frac{237961}{44200} + \frac{237961 I}{44200} \end{bmatrix}$$

$$\frac{d}{dxI} u(xI) = \frac{1}{132600 \Delta xI} \left((16575 + 16575 I) u_{iI-4+4I} - (1103232 + 763776 I) u_{iI-3+4I} + (2386800 + 4773600 I) u_{iI-2+4I} + (124800 - 1622400 I) u_{iI-1+4I} + 33150 I u_{iI+4I} - (763776 + 1103232 I) u_{iI-4+3I} - (120224000 + 120224000 I) u_{iI-3+3I} - (499392000 + 749088000 I) u_{iI-2+3I} - (72134400 + 216403200 I) u_{iI-1+3I} - (707200 + 2121600 I) u_{iI+3I} + (4773600 + 2386800 I) u_{iI-4+2I} - (749088000 + 499392000 I) u_{iI-3+2I} + (3956121000 + 3956121000 I) u_{iI-2+2I} - (649209600 + 1298419200 I) u_{iI-1+2I} + 11934000 I u_{iI+2I} + (-1622400 + 124800 I) u_{iI-4+1I} - (216403200 + 72134400 I) u_{iI-3+1I} - (1298419200 + 649209600 I) u_{iI-2+1I} - (360672000 + 360672000 I) u_{iI-1+1I} + (2121600 - 6364800 I) u_{iI+1I} + 33150 u_{iI-4I} - (2121600 + 707200 I) u_{iI-3I} + 11934000 u_{iI-2I} + (-6364800 + 2121600 I) u_{iI-1I} + (713883 + 713883 I) u_{iI} \right), O(\Delta xI^{24}), \text{ Quadrant 2}$$

Error order:, 24, *Error:*, 8.4115573891884462914 × 10⁻⁷⁹, *New Error:*, 8.4438745930984165460 × 10⁻¹⁵¹
Error order:, 24, *Error:*, 8.4438745930984165460 × 10⁻¹⁵¹, *New Error:*, 8.4439069723663880620 × 10⁻²²³
Error order:, 24, *Error:*, 8.4439069723663880620 × 10⁻²²³, *New Error:*, 8.4439070047457181770 × 10⁻²⁹⁵
Error order:, 24, *Error:*, 8.4439070047457181770 × 10⁻²⁹⁵, *New Error:*, 8.4439070047780975072 × 10⁻³⁶⁷
Error order:, 24, *Error:*, 8.4439070047780975072 × 10⁻³⁶⁷, *New Error:*, 8.4439070047781298865 × 10⁻⁴³⁹

$$\frac{d^2}{dxI^2} u(xI) = \frac{1}{8791380000 \Delta xI^2} \left(274730625 I u_{iI-8+8I} - (5626483200 + 30945657600 I) u_{iI-7+8I} + (277322323824 + 961305754032 I) u_{iI-6+8I} + (1041726816000 - 7114191552000 I) u_{iI-5+8I} + (-9922604357250 + 13088742293250 I) u_{iI-4+8I} + (8067880454400 - 3313171180800 I) u_{iI-3+8I} - (1466548200000 + 1233531000000 I) u_{iI-2+8I} + (53782560000 + 4137120000 I) u_{iI-1+8I} - 549461250 u_{iI+8I} + (5626483200 - 30945657600 I) u_{iI-8+7I} - 2184950976000 I u_{iI-7+7I} + (48392877062400 + 197486458540800 I) u_{iI-6+7I} + (266266494374400 + 343308503116800 I) u_{iI-5+7I} + (2088199702118400 - 3698008175097600 I) u_{iI-4+7I} - (413647359091200 + 145229197401600 I) u_{iI-3+7I} + (-326822932800000 + 65029161600000 I) u_{iI-2+7I} + (3643423680000 - 1508669760000 I) u_{iI-1+7I} + (70331040000 - 23443680000 I) u_{iI+7I} + (-277322323824 + 961305754032 I) u_{iI-8+6I} + (-48392877062400 + 197486458540800 I) u_{iI-7+6I} + 16859601000814000 I u_{iI-6+6I} + (-30934826174304000 + 138148490447136000 I) u_{iI-5+6I} + (-183838522637766000 + 440189168982426000 I) u_{iI-4+6I} + (-114665338043776000 + 150284310992192000 I) u_{iI-3+6I} + (-24425271953550000 + 18250244512110000 I) u_{iI-2+6I} + (-345703263360000 + 286048751040000 I) u_{iI-1+6I} + (-2396139460000 + 1500395520000 I) u_{iI+6I} - (1041726816000 + 7114191552000 I) u_{iI-8+5I} + (-266266494374400 + 343308503116800 I) u_{iI-7+5I} + (30934826174304000 + 138148490447136000 I) u_{iI-6+5I} - 139720014266227200 I u_{iI-5+5I} + (855735385583520000 - 4513611092971968000 I) u_{iI-4+5I} - (77129612703936000 + 6805488950208000 I) u_{iI-3+5I} + (-220189769092800000 + 217492941594240000 I) u_{iI-2+5I} + (288845444160000 + 1418560528320000 I) u_{iI-1+5I} + (25530167520000 - 8369393760000 I) u_{iI+5I} + (9922604357250 + 13088742293250 I) u_{iI-8+4I} - (2088199702118400 + 3698008175097600 I) u_{iI-7+4I} + (183838522637766000 + 440189168982426000 I) u_{iI-6+4I} - (855735385583520000 + 4513611092971968000 I) u_{iI-5+4I} + 18383456298864651150 I u_{iI-4+4I} + (2436378457754372352 - 6934916433823832064 I) u_{iI-3+4I} + (-737741204283704400 + 999045201377293200 I) u_{iI-2+4I} + (13455973790937600 - 6728678517100800 I) u_{iI-1+4I} + (-86237798421450 + 23665221450 I) u_{iI+4I} - (8067880454400 + 3313171180800 I) u_{iI-8+3I} + (413647359091200 - 145229197401600 I) u_{iI-7+3I} + (114665338043776000 + 150284310992192000 I) u_{iI-6+3I} + (77129612703936000 - 6805488950208000 I) u_{iI-5+3I} - (2436378457754372352 + 6934916433823832064 I) u_{iI-4+3I} - 744273814491584000 I u_{iI-3+3I} + (-191742776167392000 + 670480962115680000 I) u_{iI-2+3I} - (5225288546649600 + 3120875483980800 I) u_{iI-1+3I} + (76967239315200 + 23299742169600 I) u_{iI+3I} + (1466548200000 - 123353100000 I) u_{iI-8+2I} + (326822932800000 + 65029161600000 I) u_{iI-7+2I} + (24425271953550000 + 18250244512110000 I) u_{iI-6+2I} + (220189769092800000 + 217492941594240000 I) u_{iI-5+2I} + (737741204283704400 + 999045201377293200 I) u_{iI-4+2I} + (191742776167392000 + 670480962115680000 I) u_{iI-3+2I} + 149648757869286000 I u_{iI-2+2I} + (-2622666338323200 + 64066816569600 I) u_{iI-1+2I} - (26524225962000 + 4984079958000 I) u_{iI+2I} + (-53782560000 + 4137120000 I) u_{iI-8+1I} - (3643423680000 + 1508669760000 I) u_{iI-7+1I} + (345703263360000 + 286048751040000 I) u_{iI-6+1I} + (-288845444160000 + 1418560528320000 I) u_{iI-5+1I} - (13455973790937600 + 6728678517100800 I) u_{iI-4+1I} + (5225288546649600 - 3120875483980800 I) u_{iI-3+1I} + (2622666338323200 + 64066816569600 I) u_{iI-2+1I} - 469943353152000 I u_{iI-1+1I} + (6058296691200 - 3029148345600 I) u_{iI+1I} + 549461250 u_{iI-8I} - (70331040000 + 23443680000 I) u_{iI-7I} + (2396139460000 + 1500395520000 I) u_{iI-6I} - (25530167520000 + 8369393760000 I) u_{iI-5I} + (86237798421450 + 23665221450 I) u_{iI-4I} + (-76967239315200 + 23299742169600 I) u_{iI-3I} + (26524225962000 - 4984079958000 I) u_{iI-2I} - (6058296691200 + 3029148345600 I) u_{iI-1I} + 509628937689 I u_{iI} \right), O(\Delta xI^{24}), \text{ Quadrant 2}$$

Error order:, 24, *Error:*, 1.6789535706962966650 × 10⁻⁷⁸, *New Error:*, 1.6854041103988855381 × 10⁻¹⁵⁰
Error order:, 24, *Error:*, 1.6854041103988855381 × 10⁻¹⁵⁰, *New Error:*, 1.6854105733266243637 × 10⁻²²²
Error order:, 24, *Error:*, 1.6854105733266243637 × 10⁻²²², *New Error:*, 1.6854105797895645064 × 10⁻²⁹⁴
Error order:, 24, *Error:*, 1.6854105797895645064 × 10⁻²⁹⁴, *New Error:*, 1.6854105797960274465 × 10⁻³⁶⁶
Error order:, 24, *Error:*, 1.6854105797960274465 × 10⁻³⁶⁶, *New Error:*, 1.6854105797960339095 × 10⁻⁴³⁸

--- Derivative Order: 2 - x1=1 ---

$$\begin{bmatrix} -4 + 4 I & -3 + 4 I & -2 + 4 I & -1 + 4 I & 4 I \\ -4 + 3 I & -3 + 3 I & -2 + 3 I & -1 + 3 I & 3 I \\ -4 + 2 I & -3 + 2 I & -2 + 2 I & -1 + 2 I & 2 I \\ -4 + I & -3 + I & -2 + I & -1 + I & I \\ -4 & -3 & -2 & -1 & 0 \end{bmatrix}$$

$$\begin{array}{cccccccc} \frac{58109 I}{22100} & -\frac{757232}{27625} & -\frac{4076376 I}{27625} & -\frac{2022309}{11050} & +\frac{6265827 I}{11050} & \frac{751448}{5525} & -\frac{666384 I}{5525} & -\frac{226911}{88400} & +\frac{237961 I}{88400} \\ \frac{757232}{27625} & -\frac{4076376 I}{27625} & -\frac{11068528 I}{585} & \frac{1223784}{65} & -\frac{1272744 I}{13} & \frac{3524496}{325} & -\frac{7402592 I}{325} & \frac{1726888}{16575} & -\frac{11245328 I}{49725} \\ \frac{2022309}{11050} & +\frac{6265827 I}{11050} & -\frac{1223784}{65} & -\frac{1272744 I}{13} & \frac{6126597 I}{10} & \frac{15223752}{325} & -\frac{48853656 I}{325} & -\frac{1942749}{2210} & +\frac{2141649 I}{2210} \\ -\frac{751448}{5525} & -\frac{666384 I}{5525} & -\frac{3524496}{325} & -\frac{7402592 I}{325} & -\frac{15223752}{325} & -\frac{48853656 I}{325} & -\frac{3453776 I}{65} & \frac{3276976}{5525} & -\frac{2080488 I}{5525} \\ \frac{226911}{88400} & +\frac{237961 I}{88400} & -\frac{1726888}{16575} & -\frac{11245328 I}{49725} & \frac{1942749}{2210} & +\frac{2141649 I}{2210} & -\frac{3276976}{5525} & -\frac{2080488 I}{5525} & \frac{112305269 I}{1989000} \end{array}$$

$$\frac{d^2}{dx^2} u(xI) = \frac{1}{3978000 \Delta x I^2} (10459620 I u_{iI-4+4I} - (109041408 + 586998144 I) u_{iI-3+4I} + (-728031240 + 2255697720 I) u_{iI-2+4I} + (541042560 - 479796480 I) u_{iI-1+4I} + (-10210995 + 10708245 I) u_{iI+4I} + (109041408 - 586998144 I) u_{iI-4+3I} - 75265990400 I u_{iI-3+3I} + (74895580800 - 389459664000 I) u_{iI-2+3I} + (43139831040 - 90607726080 I) u_{iI-1+3I} + (414453120 - 899626240 I) u_{iI+3I} + (728031240 + 2255697720 I) u_{iI-4+2I} - (74895580800 + 389459664000 I) u_{iI-3+2I} + 2437160286600 I u_{iI-2+2I} + (186338724480 - 597968749440 I) u_{iI-1+2I} + (-3496948200 + 3854968200 I) u_{iI+2I} - (541042560 + 479796480 I) u_{iI-4+1I} - (43139831040 + 90607726080 I) u_{iI-3+1I} - (186338724480 + 597968749440 I) u_{iI-2+1I} - 211371091200 I u_{iI-1+1I} + (2359422720 - 1497951360 I) u_{iI+1I} + (10210995 + 10708245 I) u_{iI-4} - (414453120 + 899626240 I) u_{iI-3} + (3496948200 + 3854968200 I) u_{iI-2} - (2359422720 + 1497951360 I) u_{iI-1} + 224610538 I u_{iI}), O(\Delta x I^{23}), \text{ Quadrant 2}$$

Error order: 23, Error: 6.4043937133274516971 × 10⁻⁷⁵, New Error: 6.4289536030204865561 × 10⁻¹⁴⁴
 Error order: 23, Error: 6.4289536030204865561 × 10⁻¹⁴⁴, New Error: 6.4289782099889233308 × 10⁻²¹³
 Error order: 23, Error: 6.4289782099889233308 × 10⁻²¹³, New Error: 6.4289782345959389065 × 10⁻²⁸²
 Error order: 23, Error: 6.4289782345959389065 × 10⁻²⁸², New Error: 6.4289782346205459221 × 10⁻³⁵¹
 Error order: 23, Error: 6.4289782346205459221 × 10⁻³⁵¹, New Error: 6.4289782346205705291 × 10⁻⁴²⁰

"--- Derivative Order: 3 - xI=1 ---"

$$\begin{array}{ccccc} -4 + 4 I & -3 + 4 I & -2 + 4 I & -1 + 4 I & 4 I \\ -4 + 3 I & -3 + 3 I & -2 + 3 I & -1 + 3 I & 3 I \\ -4 + 2 I & -3 + 2 I & -2 + 2 I & -1 + 2 I & 2 I \\ -4 + I & -3 + I & -2 + I & -1 + I & I \\ -4 & -3 & -2 & -1 & 0 \end{array}$$

$$\begin{array}{cccccccc} -\frac{107075459}{5304000} & +\frac{107075459 I}{5304000} & \frac{9718926}{10625} & -\frac{556522898 I}{414375} & -\frac{25206789}{4420} & +\frac{16512609 I}{5525} & \frac{162716042}{82875} & +\frac{7019834 I}{82875} & -\frac{213902293}{5304000} & +\frac{680733 I}{353600} \\ \frac{556522898}{414375} & -\frac{9718926 I}{10625} & \frac{421549756}{2925} & -\frac{421549756 I}{2925} & \frac{286146828}{325} & -\frac{196883472 I}{325} & \frac{410622668}{1625} & -\frac{463490108 I}{4875} & \frac{617604974}{248625} & -\frac{250513858 I}{248625} \\ -\frac{16512609}{5525} & +\frac{25206789 I}{4420} & \frac{196883472}{325} & -\frac{286146828 I}{325} & -\frac{459424233}{100} & +\frac{459424233 I}{100} & \frac{2356533264}{1625} & -\frac{1292444772 I}{1625} & -\frac{76197768}{5525} & +\frac{5828247 I}{4420} \\ -\frac{7019834}{82875} & -\frac{162716042 I}{82875} & \frac{463490108}{4875} & -\frac{410622668 I}{1625} & \frac{1292444772}{1625} & -\frac{2356533264 I}{1625} & \frac{371511116}{975} & -\frac{371511116 I}{975} & \frac{193403218}{27625} & +\frac{77146618 I}{82875} \\ -\frac{680733}{353600} & +\frac{213902293 I}{5304000} & \frac{250513858}{248625} & -\frac{617604974 I}{248625} & -\frac{5828247}{4420} & +\frac{76197768 I}{5525} & -\frac{77146618}{82875} & -\frac{193403218 I}{27625} & -\frac{22773831179}{79560000} & +\frac{22773831179 I}{79560000} \end{array}$$

$$\frac{d^3}{dx^3} u(xI) = \frac{1}{79560000 \Delta x I^3} ((-1606131885 + 1606131885 I) u_{iI-4+4I} + (72775317888 - 106852396416 I) u_{iI-3+4I} + (-453722202000 + 237781569600 I) u_{iI-2+4I} + (156207400320 + 6739040640 I) u_{iI-1+4I} + (-3208534395 + 153164925 I) u_{iI+4I} + (106852396416 - 72775317888 I) u_{iI-4+3I} + (11466153363200 - 11466153363200 I) u_{iI-3+3I} + (70048743494400 - 48197073945600 I) u_{iI-2+3I} + (20104085825280 - 7564158562560 I) u_{iI-1+3I} + (197633591680 - 80164434560 I) u_{iI+3I} + (-237781569600 + 453722202000 I) u_{iI-4+2I} + (48197073945600 - 70048743494400 I) u_{iI-3+2I} + (-365517919774800 + 365517919774800 I) u_{iI-2+2I} + (115375868605440 - 63278096037120 I) u_{iI-1+2I} + (-1097247859200 + 104908446000 I) u_{iI+2I} - (6739040640 + 156207400320 I) u_{iI-4+1I} + (7564158562560 - 20104085825280 I) u_{iI-3+1I} + (63278096037120 - 115375868605440 I) u_{iI-2+1I} + (30315307065600 - 30315307065600 I) u_{iI-1+1I} + (557001267840 + 74060753280 I) u_{iI+1I} + (-153164925 + 3208534395 I) u_{iI-4} + (80164434560 - 197633591680 I) u_{iI-3} + (-104908446000 + 1097247859200 I) u_{iI-2} - (74060753280 + 557001267840 I) u_{iI-1} + (-22773831179 + 22773831179 I) u_{iI}), O(\Delta x I^{22}), \text{ Quadrant 2}$$

Error order: 22, Error: 3.5621268670071558183 × 10⁻⁷¹, New Error: 3.5757602619270171947 × 10⁻¹³⁷
 Error order: 22, Error: 3.5757602619270171947 × 10⁻¹³⁷, New Error: 3.5757739214044709379 × 10⁻²⁰³
 Error order: 22, Error: 3.5757739214044709379 × 10⁻²⁰³, New Error: 3.5757739350639745075 × 10⁻²⁶⁹
 Error order: 22, Error: 3.5757739350639745075 × 10⁻²⁶⁹, New Error: 3.5757739350776340111 × 10⁻³³⁵
 Error order: 22, Error: 3.5757739350776340111 × 10⁻³³⁵, New Error: 3.5757739350776476706 × 10⁻⁴⁰¹

"--- Derivative Order: 4 - xI=1 ---"

$$\begin{array}{ccccc} -4 + 4 I & -3 + 4 I & -2 + 4 I & -1 + 4 I & 4 I \\ -4 + 3 I & -3 + 3 I & -2 + 3 I & -1 + 3 I & 3 I \\ -4 + 2 I & -3 + 2 I & -2 + 2 I & -1 + 2 I & 2 I \\ -4 + I & -3 + I & -2 + I & -1 + I & I \\ -4 & -3 & -2 & -1 & 0 \end{array}$$

$$\begin{array}{r} \frac{622579391}{2340000} - \frac{92133162946}{6215625} - \frac{17850865972 I}{6215625} - \frac{63158797197}{1105000} - \frac{19053482099 I}{1105000} - \frac{5200152388}{414375} + \frac{16432976258 I}{1243125} - \frac{11310333127}{39780000} - \frac{1222831049 I}{4972500} \\ \frac{92133162946}{6215625} + \frac{17850865972 I}{6215625} - \frac{27554776532}{14625} - \frac{629167478}{65} + \frac{2788783966 I}{1625} - \frac{166456619464}{73125} + \frac{71702641292 I}{73125} - \frac{9565005284}{414375} + \frac{11065187626 I}{1243125} \\ - \frac{63158797197}{1105000} + \frac{19053482099 I}{1105000} - \frac{629167478}{65} - \frac{2788783966 I}{1625} - \frac{59133008877}{1000} - \frac{116877295842}{8125} + \frac{31865175334 I}{8125} - \frac{22191006479}{221000} - \frac{16678009739 I}{221000} \\ \frac{5200152388}{414375} - \frac{16432976258 I}{1243125} - \frac{166456619464}{73125} - \frac{71702641292 I}{73125} - \frac{116877295842}{8125} - \frac{31865175334 I}{8125} - \frac{68804657756}{14625} - \frac{50176459438}{1243125} + \frac{56282745476 I}{1243125} \\ - \frac{11310333127}{39780000} + \frac{1222831049 I}{4972500} - \frac{9565005284}{414375} - \frac{11065187626 I}{1243125} - \frac{22191006479}{221000} + \frac{16678009739 I}{221000} - \frac{50176459438}{1243125} - \frac{56282745476 I}{1243125} - \frac{554759931179}{198900000} \end{array}$$

$$\frac{d^4}{dx^4} u(xI) = \frac{1}{198900000 \Delta x I^4} (-52919248235 u_{iI-4+4I} + (2948261214272 - 571227711104 I) u_{iI-3+4I} - (11368583495460 + 3429626777820 I) u_{iI-2+4I} + (2496073146240 + 2629276201280 I) u_{iI-1+4I} - (56551665635 + 48913241960 I) u_{iI+4I} + (2948261214272 + 571227711104 I) u_{iI-4+3I} + 374744960835200 u_{iI-3+3I} + (1925252482680000 + 341347157438400 I) u_{iI-2+3I} + (452762004942080 + 195031184314240 I) u_{iI-1+3I} + (4591202536320 + 1770430020160 I) u_{iI+3I} + (-11368583495460 + 3429626777820 I) u_{iI-4+2I} + (1925252482680000 - 341347157438400 I) u_{iI-3+2I} - 11761555465635300 u_{iI-2+2I} + (2861156202212160 + 780059492176320 I) u_{iI-1+2I} - (19971905831100 + 15010208765100 I) u_{iI+2I} + (2496073146240 - 2629276201280 I) u_{iI-4+1I} + (452762004942080 - 195031184314240 I) u_{iI-3+1I} + (2861156202212160 - 780059492176320 I) u_{iI-2+1I} + 935743345481600 u_{iI-1+1I} + (8028233510080 + 9005239276160 I) u_{iI+1I} + (-56551665635 + 48913241960 I) u_{iI-4} + (4591202536320 - 1770430020160 I) u_{iI-3} + (-19971905831100 + 15010208765100 I) u_{iI-2} + (8028233510080 - 9005239276160 I) u_{iI-1} - 554759931179 u_{iI}), O(\Delta x I^{21}), \text{ Quadrant 2}$$

Error order:, 21, Error:, 1.7025998930030488205 × 10⁻⁶⁷, New Error:, 1.7091024987592563262 × 10⁻¹³⁰
 Error order:, 21, Error:, 1.7091024987592563262 × 10⁻¹³⁰, New Error:, 1.7091090137790921653 × 10⁻¹⁹³
 Error order:, 21, Error:, 1.7091090137790921653 × 10⁻¹⁹³, New Error:, 1.7091090202941244310 × 10⁻²⁵⁶
 Error order:, 21, Error:, 1.7091090202941244310 × 10⁻²⁵⁶, New Error:, 1.7091090203006394633 × 10⁻³¹⁹
 Error order:, 21, Error:, 1.7091090203006394633 × 10⁻³¹⁹, New Error:, 1.7091090203006459783 × 10⁻³⁸²

"--- Derivative Order: 5 - xI=1 ---"

$$\begin{bmatrix} -4 + 4 I & -3 + 4 I & -2 + 4 I & -1 + 4 I & 4 I \\ -4 + 3 I & -3 + 3 I & -2 + 3 I & -1 + 3 I & 3 I \\ -4 + 2 I & -3 + 2 I & -2 + 2 I & -1 + 2 I & 2 I \\ -4 + I & -3 + I & -2 + I & -1 + I & I \\ -4 & -3 & -2 & -1 & 0 \end{bmatrix}$$

$$\begin{array}{r} -\frac{2613753557}{1657500} - \frac{2613753557 I}{1657500} - \frac{17376728533}{165750} + \frac{34903034183 I}{497250} - \frac{26485404909}{110500} - \frac{192829757173 I}{442000} - \frac{349316683}{276250} + \frac{125951589337 I}{828750} - \frac{1222831049}{3978000} - \frac{20758677731 I}{6630000} \\ \frac{34903034183}{497250} + \frac{17376728533 I}{165750} - \frac{4152760597}{375} + \frac{4152760597 I}{375} - \frac{76466134796}{1625} + \frac{107727242279 I}{1625} - \frac{38605705559}{4875} + \frac{275748708739 I}{14625} - \frac{24644881757}{276250} + \frac{153036626113 I}{828750} \\ - \frac{192829757173}{442000} - \frac{26485404909 I}{110500} - \frac{107727242279}{1625} + \frac{76466134796 I}{1625} - \frac{42769210911}{125} - \frac{42769210911 I}{125} - \frac{100322597201}{1625} + \frac{168780019068 I}{1625} - \frac{16678009739}{88400} - \frac{2133677398 I}{2125} \\ \frac{125951589337}{828750} - \frac{349316683 I}{276250} - \frac{275748708739}{14625} + \frac{38605705559 I}{4875} - \frac{168780019068}{1625} + \frac{100322597201 I}{1625} - \frac{42527587421}{1625} + \frac{42527587421 I}{1625} - \frac{68953193}{21250} + \frac{89424246089 I}{191250} \\ - \frac{20758677731}{6630000} - \frac{1222831049 I}{3978000} - \frac{153036626113}{828750} + \frac{24644881757 I}{276250} - \frac{2133677398}{2125} - \frac{16678009739 I}{88400} - \frac{89424246089}{191250} + \frac{68953193 I}{21250} - \frac{574403647}{44200} - \frac{574403647 I}{44200} \end{array}$$

$$\frac{d^5}{dx^5} u(xI) = \frac{1}{19890000 \Delta x I^5} (-31365042684 + 31365042684 I) u_{iI-4+4I} + (2085207423960 + 1396121367320 I) u_{iI-3+4I} - (4767372883620 + 8677339072785 I) u_{iI-2+4I} + (-25150801176 + 3022838144088 I) u_{iI-1+4I} - (6114155245 + 62276033193 I) u_{iI+4I} + (1396121367320 + 2085207423960 I) u_{iI-4+3I} + (220262422064880 + 220262422064880 I) u_{iI-3+3I} + (935945489903040 + 1318581445494960 I) u_{iI-2+3I} + (157511278680720 + 375018243885040 I) u_{iI-1+3I} + (1774431486504 + 3672879026712 I) u_{iI+3I} - (8677339072785 + 4767372883620 I) u_{iI-4+2I} + (1318581445494960 + 935945489903040 I) u_{iI-3+2I} - (6805436840158320 + 6805436840158320 I) u_{iI-2+2I} + (1227948589740240 + 2065867433392320 I) u_{iI-1+2I} - (3752552191275 + 19971220445280 I) u_{iI+2I} + (3022838144088 - 25150801176 I) u_{iI-4+1I} + (375018243885040 + 157511278680720 I) u_{iI-3+1I} + (2065867433392320 + 1227948589740240 I) u_{iI-2+1I} + (520537670033040 + 520537670033040 I) u_{iI-1+1I} + (64540188648 + 9300121593256 I) u_{iI+1I} - (62276033193 + 6114155245 I) u_{iI-4} + (3672879026712 + 1774431486504 I) u_{iI-3} - (19971220445280 + 3752552191275 I) u_{iI-2} + (9300121593256 + 64540188648 I) u_{iI-1} - (258481641150 + 258481641150 I) u_{iI}), O(\Delta x I^{20}), \text{ Quadrant 2}$$

Error order:, 20, Error:, 7.3317968561045643657 × 10⁻⁶⁴, New Error:, 7.3597339048811079520 × 10⁻¹²⁴
 Error order:, 20, Error:, 7.3597339048811079520 × 10⁻¹²⁴, New Error:, 7.3597618951412198391 × 10⁻¹⁸⁴
 Error order:, 20, Error:, 7.3597618951412198391 × 10⁻¹⁸⁴, New Error:, 7.3597619231315332299 × 10⁻²⁴⁴
 Error order:, 20, Error:, 7.3597619231315332299 × 10⁻²⁴⁴, New Error:, 7.3597619231595235434 × 10⁻³⁰⁴
 Error order:, 20, Error:, 7.3597619231595235434 × 10⁻³⁰⁴, New Error:, 7.3597619231595515337 × 10⁻³⁶⁴

"--- Derivative Order: 6 - xI=1 ---"

$$\begin{bmatrix} -4 + 4 I & -3 + 4 I & -2 + 4 I & -1 + 4 I & 4 I \\ -4 + 3 I & -3 + 3 I & -2 + 3 I & -1 + 3 I & 3 I \\ -4 + 2 I & -3 + 2 I & -2 + 2 I & -1 + 2 I & 2 I \\ -4 + I & -3 + I & -2 + I & -1 + I & I \\ -4 & -3 & -2 & -1 & 0 \end{bmatrix}$$

$$\frac{d^6}{dx^6} u(xI) = \frac{1}{13260000 \Delta x I^6} \left(\begin{array}{cccccc} -\frac{37852766411 I}{2210000} & \frac{15871688231}{82875} + \frac{26152114629 I}{27625} & \frac{17404815459}{17000} - \frac{1618240018413 I}{442000} & -\frac{112214177059}{138125} + \frac{114476078827 I}{138125} & \frac{65401869319}{4420000} - \frac{50473497181 I}{2652000} & \\ -\frac{15871688231}{82875} + \frac{26152114629 I}{27625} & \frac{581312600878 I}{4875} & -\frac{2461873314}{25} + \frac{987675471948 I}{1625} & -\frac{90428274644}{1625} + \frac{702501239926 I}{4875} & -\frac{191605562087}{414375} + \frac{205116577043 I}{138125} & \\ -\frac{17404815459}{17000} - \frac{1618240018413 I}{442000} & \frac{2461873314}{25} + \frac{987675471948 I}{1625} & -\frac{906552119709 I}{250} & -\frac{335671009638}{1625} + \frac{1417757560116 I}{1625} & \frac{221295624681}{55250} - \frac{570321909543 I}{88400} & \\ \frac{112214177059}{138125} + \frac{114476078827 I}{138125} & \frac{90428274644}{1625} + \frac{702501239926 I}{4875} & \frac{335671009638}{1625} + \frac{1417757560116 I}{1625} & \frac{434118851874 I}{1625} & -\frac{905337930043}{414375} + \frac{341953013673 I}{138125} & \\ -\frac{65401869319}{4420000} - \frac{50473497181 I}{2652000} & \frac{191605562087}{414375} + \frac{205116577043 I}{138125} & -\frac{221295624681}{55250} - \frac{570321909543 I}{88400} & \frac{905337930043}{414375} + \frac{341953013673 I}{138125} & -\frac{15294778547 I}{132600} & \end{array} \right)$$

$$\frac{d^6}{dx^6} u(xI) = \frac{1}{13260000 \Delta x I^6} \left(-227116598466 I u_{iI-4+4I} + (2539470116960 + 12553015021920 I) u_{iI-3+4I} + (13575756058020 - 48547200552390 I) u_{iI-2+4I} + (-10772560997664 + 10989703567392 I) u_{iI-1+4I} + (196205607957 - 252367485905 I) u_{iI+4I} + (-2539470116960 + 12553015021920 I) u_{iI-4+3I} \right. \\ \left. + 1581170274388160 I u_{iI-3+3I} + (-1305777605745600 + 8059431851095680 I) u_{iI-2+3I} + (-737894721095040 + 1910803372598720 I) u_{iI-1+3I} + (-6131377986784 + 19691191396128 I) u_{iI+3I} - (13575756058020 + 48547200552390 I) u_{iI-4+2I} + (1305777605745600 + 8059431851095680 I) u_{iI-3+2I} \right. \\ \left. - 48083524429365360 I u_{iI-2+2I} + (-2739075438646080 + 11568901690546560 I) u_{iI-1+2I} + (53110949923440 - 85548286431450 I) u_{iI+2I} + (10772560997664 + 10989703567392 I) u_{iI-4+1I} + (737894721095040 + 1910803372598720 I) u_{iI-3+1I} + (2739075438646080 + 11568901690546560 I) u_{iI-2+1I} \right. \\ \left. + 3542409831291840 I u_{iI-1+1I} + (-28970813761376 + 32827489312608 I) u_{iI+1I} - (196205607957 + 252367485905 I) u_{iI-4I} + (6131377986784 + 19691191396128 I) u_{iI-3I} - (53110949923440 + 85548286431450 I) u_{iI-2I} + (28970813761376 + 32827489312608 I) u_{iI-1I} - 1529477854700 I u_{iI} \right), O(\Delta x I^{19}),$$

Quadrant 2

Error order:, 19, Error:, 2.8987148181907527217 × 10⁻⁶⁰, New Error:, 2.9097319427484396790 × 10⁻¹¹⁷
 Error order:, 19, Error:, 2.9097319427484396790 × 10⁻¹¹⁷, New Error:, 2.9097429808038021778 × 10⁻¹⁷⁴
 Error order:, 19, Error:, 2.9097429808038021778 × 10⁻¹⁷⁴, New Error:, 2.9097429918418784976 × 10⁻²³¹
 Error order:, 19, Error:, 2.9097429918418784976 × 10⁻²³¹, New Error:, 2.9097429918529165740 × 10⁻²⁸⁸
 Error order:, 19, Error:, 2.9097429918529165740 × 10⁻²⁸⁸, New Error:, 2.9097429918529276120 × 10⁻³⁴⁵

"--- Derivative Order: 7 - xI=1 ---"

$$\begin{bmatrix} -4 + 4 I & -3 + 4 I & -2 + 4 I & -1 + 4 I & 4 I \\ -4 + 3 I & -3 + 3 I & -2 + 3 I & -1 + 3 I & 3 I \\ -4 + 2 I & -3 + 2 I & -2 + 2 I & -1 + 2 I & 2 I \\ -4 + I & -3 + I & -2 + I & -1 + I & I \\ -4 & -3 & -2 & -1 & 0 \end{bmatrix}$$

$$\left(\begin{array}{cccccc} \frac{4558264396819}{53040000} - \frac{4558264396819 I}{53040000} & -\frac{20725968823}{5525} + \frac{157683439809 I}{27625} & \frac{197409813699}{8500} - \frac{911472963009 I}{68000} & -\frac{3389338473479}{414375} + \frac{98165925067 I}{414375} & \frac{595984838771}{3536000} - \frac{457813085233 I}{17680000} & \\ -\frac{157683439809}{27625} + \frac{20725968823 I}{5525} & -\frac{2890583626609}{4875} + \frac{2890583626609 I}{4875} & -\frac{5644278093804}{1625} + \frac{4136236181826 I}{1625} & -\frac{1586218336381}{1625} + \frac{739738752963 I}{1625} & -\frac{3917356452149}{414375} + \frac{2231470475353 I}{414375} & \\ \frac{911472963009}{68000} - \frac{197409813699 I}{8500} & -\frac{4136236181826}{1625} + \frac{5644278093804 I}{1625} & \frac{8871705686781}{500} - \frac{8871705686781 I}{500} & -\frac{646765645974}{125} + \frac{5378825232564 I}{1625} & \frac{8855360612679}{176800} - \frac{1549069372767 I}{110500} & \\ -\frac{98165925067}{414375} + \frac{3389338473479 I}{414375} & -\frac{739738752963}{1625} + \frac{1586218336381 I}{1625} & -\frac{5378825232564}{1625} + \frac{646765645974 I}{125} & -\frac{6148097038223}{4875} + \frac{6148097038223 I}{4875} & -\frac{2959501395739}{138125} + \frac{328064339617 I}{138125} & \\ \frac{457813085233}{17680000} - \frac{595984838771 I}{3536000} & -\frac{2231470475353}{414375} + \frac{3917356452149 I}{414375} & \frac{1549069372767}{110500} - \frac{8855360612679 I}{176800} & -\frac{328064339617}{138125} + \frac{2959501395739 I}{138125} & \frac{5152854524377}{10608000} - \frac{5152854524377 I}{10608000} & \end{array} \right)$$

$$\frac{d^7}{dx^7} u(xI) = \frac{1}{53040000 \Delta x I^7} \left(7 \left((651180628117 - 651180628117 I) u_{iI-4+4I} + (-28424185814400 + 43250314919040 I) u_{iI-3+4I} + (175976748211680 - 101564130163860 I) u_{iI-2+4I} + (-61976474943616 + 1795034058368 I) u_{iI-1+4I} + (1277110368795 - 196205607957 I) u_{iI+4I} + (-43250314919040 \right. \right. \\ \left. \left. + 28424185814400 I) u_{iI-4+3I} + (-4492792836786560 + 4492792836786560 I) u_{iI-3+3I} + (-26318462425966080 + 19286678424971520 I) u_{iI-2+3I} + (-7396309499925120 + 3449296128101760 I) u_{iI-1+3I} + (-71631660839296 + 40804031549312 I) u_{iI+3I} + (101564130163860 \right. \right. \\ \left. \left. - 175976748211680 I) u_{iI-4+2I} + (-19286678424971520 + 26318462425966080 I) u_{iI-3+2I} + (134444362750532640 - 134444362750532640 I) u_{iI-2+2I} + (-39205085557098240 + 25080693655841280 I) u_{iI-1+2I} + (379515454829100 - 106221899846880 I) u_{iI+2I} + (-1795034058368 \right. \right. \\ \left. \left. + 61976474943616 I) u_{iI-4+1I} + (-3449296128101760 + 7396309499925120 I) u_{iI-3+1I} + (-25080693655841280 + 39205085557098240 I) u_{iI-2+1I} + (-9555899396552320 + 9555899396552320 I) u_{iI-1+1I} + (-162349790851968 + 17996672344704 I) u_{iI+1I} + (196205607957 - 1277110368795 I) u_{iI-4I} \right. \right. \\ \left. \left. + (-40804031549312 + 71631660839296 I) u_{iI-3I} + (106221899846880 - 379515454829100 I) u_{iI-2I} + (-17996672344704 + 162349790851968 I) u_{iI-1I} + (3680610374555 - 3680610374555 I) u_{iI} \right) \right), O(\Delta x I^{18}), \text{ Quadrant 2}$$

Error order:, 18, Error:, 1.0612475135472312104 × 10⁻⁵⁶, New Error:, 1.0652695969743196254 × 10⁻¹¹⁰
 Error order:, 18, Error:, 1.0652695969743196254 × 10⁻¹¹⁰, New Error:, 1.0652736266775169481 × 10⁻¹⁶⁴
 Error order:, 18, Error:, 1.0652736266775169481 × 10⁻¹⁶⁴, New Error:, 1.0652736307072277749 × 10⁻²¹⁸
 Error order:, 18, Error:, 1.0652736307072277749 × 10⁻²¹⁸, New Error:, 1.0652736307112574857 × 10⁻²⁷²
 Error order:, 18, Error:, 1.0652736307112574857 × 10⁻²⁷², New Error:, 1.0652736307112615154 × 10⁻³²⁶

"--- Derivative Order: 8 - xI=1 ---"

$$\begin{bmatrix} -4 + 4 I & -3 + 4 I & -2 + 4 I & -1 + 4 I & 4 I \\ -4 + 3 I & -3 + 3 I & -2 + 3 I & -1 + 3 I & 3 I \\ -4 + 2 I & -3 + 2 I & -2 + 2 I & -1 + 2 I & 2 I \\ -4 + I & -3 + I & -2 + I & -1 + I & I \\ -4 & -3 & -2 & -1 & 0 \end{bmatrix}$$

$$\begin{array}{cccccccc} \frac{10603004112533}{13260000} & - \frac{3630553621534}{82875} + \frac{768267018652 \text{ I}}{82875} & \frac{37529907186807}{221000} + \frac{141413897457 \text{ I}}{3250} & - \frac{5468926550444}{138125} - \frac{1144915443238 \text{ I}}{31875} & \frac{12195416683093}{13260000} + \frac{3092738978 \text{ I}}{4875} & & & & \\ - \frac{3630553621534}{82875} - \frac{768267018652 \text{ I}}{82875} & - \frac{8881380163852}{1625} & - \frac{44873081599374}{1625} - \frac{1312349852142 \text{ I}}{325} & - \frac{32089793166368}{4875} - \frac{10966019082676 \text{ I}}{4875} & - \frac{9467258520524}{138125} - \frac{2243299291842 \text{ I}}{138125} & & & & \\ \frac{37529907186807}{221000} - \frac{141413897457 \text{ I}}{3250} & - \frac{44873081599374}{1625} + \frac{1312349852142 \text{ I}}{325} & \frac{160904808102717}{1000} & - \frac{4775878096794}{125} - \frac{12617796645846 \text{ I}}{1625} & \frac{64900262883519}{221000} + \frac{97105925889 \text{ I}}{650} & & & & \\ - \frac{5468926550444}{138125} + \frac{1144915443238 \text{ I}}{31875} & - \frac{32089793166368}{4875} + \frac{10966019082676 \text{ I}}{4875} & - \frac{4775878096794}{125} + \frac{12617796645846 \text{ I}}{1625} & - \frac{53872314181756}{4875} & - \frac{43655001092962}{414375} - \frac{32029056989804 \text{ I}}{414375} & & & & \\ \frac{12195416683093}{13260000} - \frac{3092738978 \text{ I}}{4875} & - \frac{9467258520524}{138125} + \frac{2243299291842 \text{ I}}{138125} & \frac{64900262883519}{221000} - \frac{97105925889 \text{ I}}{650} & - \frac{43655001092962}{414375} + \frac{32029056989804 \text{ I}}{414375} & \frac{683937714271}{176800} & & & & \end{array}$$

$$\frac{d^8}{dxI^8} u(xI) = \frac{1}{13260000 \Delta xI^8} (7 (1514714873219 u_{iI-4+4I} + (-82984082777920 + 17560388997760 \text{ I}) u_{iI-3+4I} + (321684918744060 + 82424100232080 \text{ I}) u_{iI-2+4I} - (75002421263232 + 68040689198144 \text{ I}) u_{iI-1+4I} + (1742202383299 + 1201750002880 \text{ I}) u_{iI+4I} - (82984082777920 + 17560388997760 \text{ I}) u_{iI-4+3I} - 10353151733861760 u_{iI-3+3I} - (52309192264413120 + 7649124852484800 \text{ I}) u_{iI-2+3I} - (12469176773217280 + 4261081700696960 \text{ I}) u_{iI-1+3I} - (129836688281472 + 30765247430976 \text{ I}) u_{iI+3I} + (321684918744060 - 82424100232080 \text{ I}) u_{iI-4+2I} + (-52309192264413120 + 7649124852484800 \text{ I}) u_{iI-3+2I} + 304799679348861060 u_{iI-2+2I} - (72375021215415360 + 14708745804300480 \text{ I}) u_{iI-1+2I} + (556287967573020 + 282994412590800 \text{ I}) u_{iI+2I} + (-75002421263232 + 68040689198144 \text{ I}) u_{iI-4+1I} + (-12469176773217280 + 4261081700696960 \text{ I}) u_{iI-3+1I} + (-72375021215415360 + 14708745804300480 \text{ I}) u_{iI-2+1I} - 20933242082053760 u_{iI-1+1I} - (199565719282112 + 146418546239104 \text{ I}) u_{iI+1I} + (1742202383299 - 1201750002880 \text{ I}) u_{iI-4I} + (-129836688281472 + 30765247430976 \text{ I}) u_{iI-3I} + (556287967573020 - 282994412590800 \text{ I}) u_{iI-2I} + (-199565719282112 + 146418546239104 \text{ I}) u_{iI-1I} + 7327904081475 u_{iI}), O(\Delta xI^{17}), \text{ Quadrant 2}$$

Error order: 17, Error: 3.6117152872432263348 × 10⁻⁵³, New Error: 3.6253604120199890474 × 10⁻¹⁰⁴
 Error order: 17, Error: 3.6253604120199890474 × 10⁻¹⁰⁴, New Error: 3.6253740829138869314 × 10⁻¹⁵⁵
 Error order: 17, Error: 3.6253740829138869314 × 10⁻¹⁵⁵, New Error: 3.6253740965848066308 × 10⁻²⁰⁶
 Error order: 17, Error: 3.6253740965848066308 × 10⁻²⁰⁶, New Error: 3.6253740965984775505 × 10⁻²⁵⁷
 Error order: 17, Error: 3.6253740965984775505 × 10⁻²⁵⁷, New Error: 3.6253740965984912215 × 10⁻³⁰⁸

--- Derivative Order: 9 - x1=1 ---

$$\begin{bmatrix} -4 + 4 \text{ I} & -3 + 4 \text{ I} & -2 + 4 \text{ I} & -1 + 4 \text{ I} & 4 \text{ I} \\ -4 + 3 \text{ I} & -3 + 3 \text{ I} & -2 + 3 \text{ I} & -1 + 3 \text{ I} & 3 \text{ I} \\ -4 + 2 \text{ I} & -3 + 2 \text{ I} & -2 + 2 \text{ I} & -1 + 2 \text{ I} & 2 \text{ I} \\ -4 + \text{ I} & -3 + \text{ I} & -2 + \text{ I} & -1 + \text{ I} & \text{ I} \\ -4 & -3 & -2 & -1 & 0 \end{bmatrix}$$

$$\begin{array}{cccccccc} \frac{112203100527}{32500} + \frac{112203100527 \text{ I}}{32500} & - \frac{744271033443}{3250} - \frac{479271279291 \text{ I}}{3250} & \frac{897275968533}{1625} + \frac{5905482671151 \text{ I}}{6500} & - \frac{362930639001}{16250} - \frac{5250697917087 \text{ I}}{16250} & \frac{4639108467}{3250} + \frac{53906128521 \text{ I}}{8125} & & & & \\ - \frac{479271279291}{3250} - \frac{744271033443 \text{ I}}{3250} & - \frac{2921019871119}{125} - \frac{2921019871119 \text{ I}}{125} & - \frac{164569192619076}{1625} - \frac{217325917255419 \text{ I}}{1625} & - \frac{31019676366693}{1625} - \frac{60160971852051 \text{ I}}{1625} & - \frac{3809124960081}{16250} - \frac{5710731446343 \text{ I}}{16250} & & & & \\ \frac{5905482671151}{6500} + \frac{897275968533 \text{ I}}{1625} & - \frac{217325917255419}{1625} - \frac{164569192619076 \text{ I}}{1625} & \frac{84586823164746}{125} + \frac{84586823164746 \text{ I}}{125} & - \frac{210663294739821}{1625} - \frac{307766419667028 \text{ I}}{1625} & \frac{873953333001}{1300} + \frac{226490810364 \text{ I}}{125} & & & & \\ - \frac{5250697917087}{16250} - \frac{362930639001 \text{ I}}{16250} & - \frac{60160971852051}{1625} - \frac{31019676366693 \text{ I}}{1625} & - \frac{307766419667028}{1625} - \frac{210663294739821 \text{ I}}{1625} & - \frac{73077514438341}{1625} - \frac{73077514438341 \text{ I}}{1625} & - \frac{173250480669}{1250} - \frac{903746382693 \text{ I}}{1250} & & & & \\ \frac{53906128521}{8125} + \frac{4639108467 \text{ I}}{3250} & - \frac{5710731446343}{16250} - \frac{3809124960081 \text{ I}}{16250} & \frac{226490810364}{125} + \frac{873953333001 \text{ I}}{1300} & - \frac{903746382693}{1250} - \frac{173250480669 \text{ I}}{1250} & \frac{18863939199}{1300} + \frac{18863939199 \text{ I}}{1300} & & & & \end{array}$$

$$\frac{d^9}{dxI^9} u(xI) = \frac{1}{32500 \Delta xI^9} (21 ((5343004787 + 5343004787 \text{ I}) u_{iI-4+4I} - (354414777830 + 228224418710 \text{ I}) u_{iI-3+4I} + (854548541460 + 1406067302655 \text{ I}) u_{iI-2+4I} - (34564822762 + 500066468294 \text{ I}) u_{iI-1+4I} + (2209099270 + 10267834004 \text{ I}) u_{iI+4I} - (228224418710 + 354414777830 \text{ I}) u_{iI-4+3I} - (36165007928140 + 36165007928140 \text{ I}) u_{iI-3+3I} - (156732564399120 + 206977064052780 \text{ I}) u_{iI-2+3I} - (29542548920660 + 57296163668620 \text{ I}) u_{iI-1+3I} - (362773805722 + 543879185366 \text{ I}) u_{iI+3I} + (1406067302655 + 854548541460 \text{ I}) u_{iI-4+2I} - (206977064052780 + 156732564399120 \text{ I}) u_{iI-3+2I} + (1047265429658760 + 1047265429658760 \text{ I}) u_{iI-2+2I} - (200631709276020 + 293110875873360 \text{ I}) u_{iI-1+2I} + (1040420634525 + 2804171937840 \text{ I}) u_{iI+2I} - (500066468294 + 34564822762 \text{ I}) u_{iI-4+1I} - (57296163668620 + 29542548920660 \text{ I}) u_{iI-3+1I} - (293110875873360 + 200631709276020 \text{ I}) u_{iI-2+1I} - (69597632798420 + 69597632798420 \text{ I}) u_{iI-1+1I} - (214500595114 + 1118924092858 \text{ I}) u_{iI+1I} + (10267834004 + 2209099270 \text{ I}) u_{iI-4I} - (543879185366 + 362773805722 \text{ I}) u_{iI-3I} + (2804171937840 + 1040420634525 \text{ I}) u_{iI-2I} - (1118924092858 + 214500595114 \text{ I}) u_{iI-1I} + (22457070475 + 22457070475 \text{ I}) u_{iI}), O(\Delta xI^{16}), \text{ Quadrant 2}$$

Error order: 16, Error: 1.1440545707813886140 × 10⁻⁴⁹, New Error: 1.1483615536501534086 × 10⁻⁹⁷
 Error order: 16, Error: 1.1483615536501534086 × 10⁻⁹⁷, New Error: 1.1483658687381433485 × 10⁻¹⁴⁵
 Error order: 16, Error: 1.1483658687381433485 × 10⁻¹⁴⁵, New Error: 1.1483658730532394537 × 10⁻¹⁹³
 Error order: 16, Error: 1.1483658730532394537 × 10⁻¹⁹³, New Error: 1.1483658730575545499 × 10⁻²⁴¹
 Error order: 16, Error: 1.1483658730575545499 × 10⁻²⁴¹, New Error: 1.1483658730575588649 × 10⁻²⁸⁹

--- Derivative Order: 10 - x1=1 ---

$$\begin{bmatrix} -4 + 4 \text{ I} & -3 + 4 \text{ I} & -2 + 4 \text{ I} & -1 + 4 \text{ I} & 4 \text{ I} \\ -4 + 3 \text{ I} & -3 + 3 \text{ I} & -2 + 3 \text{ I} & -1 + 3 \text{ I} & 3 \text{ I} \\ -4 + 2 \text{ I} & -3 + 2 \text{ I} & -2 + 2 \text{ I} & -1 + 2 \text{ I} & 2 \text{ I} \\ -4 + \text{ I} & -3 + \text{ I} & -2 + \text{ I} & -1 + \text{ I} & \text{ I} \\ -4 & -3 & -2 & -1 & 0 \end{bmatrix}$$

$\frac{44924422431 I}{1625}$	$-\frac{108100091547}{325}$	$-\frac{487414740939 I}{325}$	$-\frac{875568381093}{650}$	$+\frac{7569789083577 I}{1300}$	$\frac{1892892278109}{1625}$	$-\frac{2268884329677 I}{1625}$	$-\frac{255973965891}{13000}$	$+\frac{85041479061 I}{2600}$
$\frac{108100091547}{325}$	$-\frac{487414740939 I}{325}$	$-\frac{60201018819102 I}{325}$	$\frac{7827605321886}{65}$	$-\frac{301203582319836 I}{325}$	$\frac{21417266783388}{325}$	$-\frac{71975829052134 I}{325}$	$\frac{611614744419}{1625}$	$-\frac{3760675466373 I}{1625}$
$\frac{875568381093}{650}$	$+\frac{7569789083577 I}{1300}$	$-\frac{7827605321886}{65}$	$-\frac{301203582319836 I}{325}$	$\frac{131876879143779 I}{25}$	$\frac{68946797958066}{325}$	$-\frac{401046643728612 I}{325}$	$-\frac{1300005785043}{325}$	$+\frac{2521555722819 I}{260}$
$-\frac{1892892278109}{1625}$	$-\frac{2268884329677 I}{1625}$	$-\frac{21417266783388}{325}$	$-\frac{71975829052134 I}{325}$	$-\frac{68946797958066}{325}$	$-\frac{401046643728612 I}{325}$	$-\frac{110394544229718 I}{325}$	$\frac{3342448384191}{1625}$	$-\frac{5293319430903 I}{1625}$
$\frac{255973965891}{13000}$	$+\frac{85041479061 I}{2600}$	$-\frac{611614744419}{1625}$	$-\frac{3760675466373 I}{1625}$	$\frac{1300005785043}{325}$	$+\frac{2521555722819 I}{260}$	$-\frac{3342448384191}{1625}$	$-\frac{5293319430903 I}{1625}$	$\frac{26557160343 I}{260}$

$$\frac{d^{10}}{dx^{10}} u(xI) = \frac{1}{13000 \Delta x I^{10}} (21 (17114065688 I u_{iI-4+4I} - (205904936280 + 928409030360 I) u_{iI-3+4I} + (-833874648660 + 3604661468370 I) u_{iI-2+4I} + (721101820232 - 864336887496 I) u_{iI-1+4I} + (-12189236471 + 20247971205 I) u_{iI+4I} + (205904936280 - 928409030360 I) u_{iI-4+3I} - 114668607274480 I u_{iI-3+3I} + (74548622113200 - 573721109180640 I) u_{iI-2+3I} + (40794793873120 - 137096817242160 I) u_{iI-1+3I} + (232996093112 - 1432638272904 I) u_{iI+3I} + (833874648660 + 3604661468370 I) u_{iI-4+2I} - (74548622113200 + 573721109180640 I) u_{iI-3+2I} + 3265522721655480 I u_{iI-2+2I} + (131327234205840 - 763898369006880 I) u_{iI-1+2I} + (-2476201495320 + 6003704101950 I) u_{iI+2I} - (721101820232 + 864336887496 I) u_{iI-4+1I} - (40794793873120 + 137096817242160 I) u_{iI-3+1I} - (131327234205840 + 763898369006880 I) u_{iI-2+1I} - 210275322342320 I u_{iI-1+1I} + (1273313670168 - 2016502640344 I) u_{iI+1I} + (12189236471 + 20247971205 I) u_{iI-4I} - (232996093112 + 1432638272904 I) u_{iI-3I} + (2476201495320 + 6003704101950 I) u_{iI-2I} - (1273313670168 + 2016502640344 I) u_{iI-1I} + 63231334150 I u_{iI}), O(\Delta x I^{15}), \text{ Quadrant 2}$$

Error order:, 15, *Error:*, $3.3717120819521862449 \times 10^{-46}$, *New Error:*, $3.3843548075262591719 \times 10^{-91}$
Error order:, 15, *Error:*, $3.3843548075262591719 \times 10^{-91}$, *New Error:*, $3.3843674739488133565 \times 10^{-136}$
Error order:, 15, *Error:*, $3.3843674739488133565 \times 10^{-136}$, *New Error:*, $3.3843674866152596373 \times 10^{-181}$
Error order:, 15, *Error:*, $3.3843674866152596373 \times 10^{-181}$, *New Error:*, $3.3843674866279260836 \times 10^{-226}$
Error order:, 15, *Error:*, $3.3843674866279260836 \times 10^{-226}$, *New Error:*, $3.3843674866279387500 \times 10^{-271}$

"--- Derivative Order: 1 - xI=1 ---"

-5 + 5 I	-4 + 5 I	-3 + 5 I	-2 + 5 I	-1 + 5 I	5 I
-5 + 4 I	-4 + 4 I	-3 + 4 I	-2 + 4 I	-1 + 4 I	4 I
-5 + 3 I	-4 + 3 I	-3 + 3 I	-2 + 3 I	-1 + 3 I	3 I
-5 + 2 I	-4 + 2 I	-3 + 2 I	-2 + 2 I	-1 + 2 I	2 I
-5 + I	-4 + I	-3 + I	-2 + I	-1 + I	I
-5	-4	-3	-2	-1	0

$-\frac{1}{10}$	$-\frac{I}{10}$	$-\frac{6095}{697}$	$+\frac{17750 I}{697}$	$\frac{57810}{221}$	$+\frac{54530 I}{221}$	$\frac{145960}{377}$	$-\frac{15580 I}{377}$	$\frac{5375}{442}$	$-\frac{13945 I}{442}$	$-\frac{1}{5}$	
$\frac{17750}{697}$	$-\frac{6095 I}{697}$	$\frac{77285}{8}$	$+\frac{77285 I}{8}$	$-\frac{5578788}{25}$	$+\frac{4689416 I}{25}$	$-\frac{646816}{5}$	$-\frac{1495762 I}{5}$	$\frac{309140}{17}$	$-\frac{77285 I}{17}$	$\frac{785}{34}$	$+\frac{2475 I}{68}$
$\frac{54530}{221}$	$+\frac{57810 I}{221}$	$\frac{4689416}{25}$	$-\frac{5578788 I}{25}$	$-\frac{17181050}{3}$	$-\frac{17181050 I}{3}$	$-\frac{103086300}{13}$	$+\frac{68724200 I}{13}$	$\frac{848946}{5}$	$+\frac{2142578 I}{5}$	$\frac{26240}{39}$	$-\frac{2460 I}{13}$
$-\frac{15580}{377}$	$+\frac{145960 I}{377}$	$-\frac{1495762}{5}$	$-\frac{646816 I}{5}$	$\frac{68724200}{13}$	$-\frac{103086300 I}{13}$	$8590525 + 8590525 I$	$-\frac{2991524}{5}$	$+\frac{1293632 I}{5}$	$\frac{3690}{13}$	$-\frac{13120 I}{13}$	
$-\frac{13945}{442}$	$+\frac{5375 I}{442}$	$-\frac{77285}{17}$	$+\frac{309140 I}{17}$	$\frac{2142578}{5}$	$+\frac{848946 I}{5}$	$\frac{1293632}{5}$	$-\frac{2991524 I}{5}$	$-\frac{77285}{2}$	$-\frac{77285 I}{2}$	$-\frac{2475}{17}$	$-\frac{1570 I}{17}$
$-\frac{I}{5}$	$\frac{2475}{68}$	$+\frac{785 I}{34}$	$-\frac{2460}{13}$	$+\frac{26240 I}{39}$	$-\frac{13120}{13}$	$+\frac{3690 I}{13}$	$-\frac{1570}{17}$	$-\frac{2475 I}{17}$	$\frac{347416769}{52553800}$	$+\frac{347416769 I}{52553800}$	

$$\frac{d}{dxI} u(xI) = \frac{1}{157661400 \Delta x I} (-(15766140 + 15766140 I) u_{iI-5+5I} + (-1378689000 + 4015050000 I) u_{iI-4+5I} + (41241654000 + 38901702000 I) u_{iI-3+5I} + (61040472000 - 6515556000 I) u_{iI-2+5I} + (1917262500 - 4974181500 I) u_{iI-1+5I} - 31532280 u_{iI+5I} + (4015050000 - 1378689000 I) u_{iI-5+4I} + (1523107662375 + 1523107662375 I) u_{iI-4+4I} + (-35182381055328 + 29573595669696 I) u_{iI-3+4I} - (20395583220480 + 47164786197360 I) u_{iI-2+4I} + (2867026188000 - 716756547000 I) u_{iI-1+4I} + (3640123500 + 5738411250 I) u_{iI+4I} + (38901702000 + 41241654000 I) u_{iI-5+3I} + (29573595669696 - 35182381055328 I) u_{iI-4+3I} - (902929465490000 + 902929465490000 I) u_{iI-3+3I} + (-1250210029140000 + 833473352760000 I) u_{iI-2+3I} + (26769202976880 + 67560369417840 I) u_{iI-1+3I} + (106077824000 - 29834388000 I) u_{iI+3I} + (-6515556000 + 61040472000 I) u_{iI-5+2I} - (47164786197360 + 20395583220480 I) u_{iI-4+2I} + (833473352760000 - 1250210029140000 I) u_{iI-3+2I} + (1354394198235000 + 1354394198235000 I) u_{iI-2+2I} + (-94329572394720 + 40791166440960 I) u_{iI-1+2I} + (44751582000 - 159116736000 I) u_{iI+2I} + (-4974181500 + 1917262500 I) u_{iI-5+1I} + (-716756547000 + 2867026188000 I) u_{iI-4+1I} + (67560369417840 + 26769202976880 I) u_{iI-3+1I} + (40791166440960 - 94329572394720 I) u_{iI-2+1I} - (6092430649500 + 6092430649500 I) u_{iI-1+1I} - (22953645000 + 14560494000 I) u_{iI+1I} - 31532280 I u_{iI-5} + (5738411250 + 3640123500 I) u_{iI-4} + (-29834388000 + 106077824000 I) u_{iI-3} + (-159116736000 + 44751582000 I) u_{iI-2} - (14560494000 + 22953645000 I) u_{iI-1} + (1042250307 + 1042250307 I) u_{iI}), O(\Delta x I^{35}), \text{ Quadrant 2}$$

Error order:, 35, *Error:*, $1.3043362083879576880 \times 10^{-116}$, *New Error:*, $1.3106779968739737224 \times 10^{-221}$
Error order:, 35, *Error:*, $1.3106779968739737224 \times 10^{-221}$, *New Error:*, $1.3106843540700942629 \times 10^{-326}$
Error order:, 35, *Error:*, $1.3106843540700942629 \times 10^{-326}$, *New Error:*, $1.3106843604273058161 \times 10^{-431}$
Error order:, 35, *Error:*, $1.3106843604273058161 \times 10^{-431}$, *New Error:*, $1.3106843604336630276 \times 10^{-536}$
Error order:, 35, *Error:*, $1.3106843604336630276 \times 10^{-536}$, *New Error:*, $1.3106843604336693848 \times 10^{-641}$

"--- Derivative Order: 2 - xI=1 ---"

$$\begin{bmatrix} -5 + 5I & -4 + 5I & -3 + 5I & -2 + 5I & -1 + 5I & 5I \\ -5 + 4I & -4 + 4I & -3 + 4I & -2 + 4I & -1 + 4I & 4I \\ -5 + 3I & -4 + 3I & -3 + 3I & -2 + 3I & -1 + 3I & 3I \\ -5 + 2I & -4 + 2I & -3 + 2I & -2 + 2I & -1 + 2I & 2I \\ -5 + I & -4 + I & -3 + I & -2 + I & -1 + I & I \\ -5 & -4 & -3 & -2 & -1 & 0 \end{bmatrix}$$

$$\begin{bmatrix} -\frac{342161389 I}{131384500} - \frac{39703135721}{89341460} + \frac{19498524379 I}{89341460} & \frac{1576696776}{7081945} + \frac{46742870953 I}{7081945} & \frac{2331855217}{416585} + \frac{1851561099 I}{416585} & \frac{164007308677}{290359745} - \frac{300349711933 I}{1161438980} & \frac{347416769}{131384500} - \frac{336906009 I}{131384500} \\ \frac{39703135721}{89341460} + \frac{19498524379 I}{89341460} & \frac{42605943 I}{170} - \frac{8639816987}{1625} - \frac{721432991 I}{1625} & \frac{6990940109}{3250} - \frac{18050467537 I}{3250} & \frac{342470529}{1156} + \frac{995879307 I}{5780} & \frac{56378902439}{357365840} + \frac{276934692821 I}{357365840} \\ -\frac{1576696776}{7081945} + \frac{46742870953 I}{7081945} & \frac{8639816987}{1625} - \frac{721432991 I}{1625} & \frac{17271547919 I}{117} - \frac{28705734965}{169} - \frac{5562464073 I}{169} & \frac{5196047084}{1625} + \frac{12549608413 I}{1625} & \frac{14086426129}{1249755} + \frac{22290035461 I}{3749265} \\ -\frac{2331855217}{416585} + \frac{1851561099 I}{416585} & \frac{6990940109}{3250} - \frac{18050467537 I}{3250} & \frac{28705734965}{169} - \frac{5562464073 I}{169} & \frac{5682731423 I}{26} - \frac{17687846317}{1625} - \frac{6686128069 I}{1625} & \frac{13403226729}{833170} - \frac{8227077787 I}{833170} \\ \frac{164007308677}{290359745} - \frac{300349711933 I}{1161438980} & \frac{342470529}{1156} + \frac{995879307 I}{5780} & \frac{5196047084}{1625} + \frac{12549608413 I}{1625} & \frac{17687846317}{1625} - \frac{6686128069 I}{1625} & \frac{321139869 I}{340} - \frac{79384328389}{89341460} - \frac{255046035121 I}{89341460} \\ \frac{347416769}{131384500} - \frac{336906009 I}{131384500} & \frac{56378902439}{357365840} + \frac{276934692821 I}{357365840} & \frac{14086426129}{1249755} + \frac{22290035461 I}{3749265} & \frac{13403226729}{833170} - \frac{8227077787 I}{833170} & \frac{79384328389}{89341460} - \frac{255046035121 I}{89341460} & \frac{44790771896407 I}{522647541000} \end{bmatrix}$$

$$\frac{d^2}{dx^2} u(xI) = \frac{1}{1045295082000 \Delta x I^2} \left(-2722236010884 I u_{iI-5+5I} + (-464526687935700 + 228132735234300 I) u_{iI-4+5I} + (232720444137600 + 6899247752662800 I) u_{iI-3+5I} + (5851091110496400 + 4645937109610800 I) u_{iI-2+5I} + (590426311237200 - 270314740739700 I) u_{iI-1+5I} - (2764047814164 + 2680424207604 I) u_{iI+5I} + (464526687935700 + 228132735234300 I) u_{iI-5+4I} + 261975192246307800 I u_{iI-4+4I} - (5557635819009943344 + 464067912298369392 I) u_{iI-3+4I} + (2248490865998228904 - 5805558444377462472 I) u_{iI-2+4I} + (309673667555050500 + 180101685445098300 I) u_{iI-1+4I} + (-164908289634075 + 810033976501425 I) u_{iI+4I} + (-232720444137600 + 6899247752662800 I) u_{iI-5+3I} + (5557635819009943344 - 464067912298369392 I) u_{iI-4+3I} - 154306530754342174000 I u_{iI-3+3I} - (177550080379348770000 + 34404830410109994000 I) u_{iI-2+3I} + (-3342401515535779008 + 8072642433929061456 I) u_{iI-1+3I} + (11781886814295600 + 6214461886526800 I) u_{iI+3I} + (-5851091110496400 + 4645937109610800 I) u_{iI-5+2I} - (2248490865998228904 + 5805558444377462472 I) u_{iI-4+2I} + (177550080379348770000 - 34404830410109994000 I) u_{iI-3+2I} + 228466584953413911000 I u_{iI-2+2I} - (11377857702358100304 + 4300908792706373328 I) u_{iI-1+2I} + (16815688254203400 - 10321691791570200 I) u_{iI+2I} - (590426311237200 + 270314740739700 I) u_{iI-5+1I} + (-309673667555050500 + 180101685445098300 I) u_{iI-4+1I} + (3342401515535779008 + 8072642433929061456 I) u_{iI-3+1I} + (11377857702358100304 - 4300908792706373328 I) u_{iI-2+1I} - 987311546175953700 I u_{iI-1+1I} - (928796642151300 + 2984038610915700 I) u_{iI+1I} + (2764047814164 - 2680424207604 I) u_{iI-5} + (164908289634075 + 810033976501425 I) u_{iI-4} + (-11781886814295600 + 6214461886526800 I) u_{iI-3} - (16815688254203400 + 10321691791570200 I) u_{iI-2} + (928796642151300 - 2984038610915700 I) u_{iI-1} + 89581543792814 I u_{iI} \Big), O(\Delta x I^{34}), \text{ Quadrant 2}$$

Error order: 34, Error: 1.2194190443276112148 × 10⁻¹¹², New Error: 1.2253429639884096611 × 10⁻²¹⁴
 Error order: 34, Error: 1.2253429639884096611 × 10⁻²¹⁴, New Error: 1.2253489022883704157 × 10⁻³¹⁶
 Error order: 34, Error: 1.2253489022883704157 × 10⁻³¹⁶, New Error: 1.2253489082266847800 × 10⁻⁴¹⁸
 Error order: 34, Error: 1.2253489082266847800 × 10⁻⁴¹⁸, New Error: 1.2253489082326230944 × 10⁻⁵²⁰
 Error order: 34, Error: 1.2253489082326230944 × 10⁻⁵²⁰, New Error: 1.2253489082326290327 × 10⁻⁶²²

"--- Derivative Order: 1 - xI=1 ---"

$$\begin{bmatrix} -6 + 6I & -5 + 6I & -4 + 6I & -3 + 6I & -2 + 6I & -1 + 6I & 6I \\ -6 + 5I & -5 + 5I & -4 + 5I & -3 + 5I & -2 + 5I & -1 + 5I & 5I \\ -6 + 4I & -5 + 4I & -4 + 4I & -3 + 4I & -2 + 4I & -1 + 4I & 4I \\ -6 + 3I & -5 + 3I & -4 + 3I & -3 + 3I & -2 + 3I & -1 + 3I & 3I \\ -6 + 2I & -5 + 2I & -4 + 2I & -3 + 2I & -2 + 2I & -1 + 2I & 2I \\ -6 + I & -5 + I & -4 + I & -3 + I & -2 + I & -1 + I & I \\ -6 & -5 & -4 & -3 & -2 & -1 & 0 \end{bmatrix}$$

$$\begin{bmatrix} \frac{1}{12} + \frac{I}{12} & \frac{998136}{13481} + \frac{35640 I}{13481} & \frac{1365363}{442} + \frac{237168 I}{221} & \frac{80032}{15} + \frac{160064 I}{15} & -\frac{406809}{340} + \frac{1200663 I}{340} & -\frac{486216}{8177} + \frac{607176 I}{8177} & \frac{I}{6} \\ \frac{35640}{13481} + \frac{998136 I}{13481} & -\frac{8775216}{85} - \frac{8775216 I}{85} & \frac{6287442264}{697} + \frac{5655626712 I}{697} & -\frac{479711808}{17} - \frac{799519680 I}{17} & \frac{1531275192}{493} + \frac{6945583464 I}{493} & -\frac{8775216}{221} - \frac{43876080 I}{221} & \frac{95256}{1105} + \frac{17064 I}{221} \\ \frac{237168}{221} + \frac{1365363 I}{442} & \frac{5655626712}{697} + \frac{6287442264 I}{697} & \frac{8477407107}{8} + \frac{8477407107 I}{8} & \frac{118248960672}{25} + \frac{157665280896 I}{25} & \frac{8477407107}{10} + \frac{8477407107 I}{5} & \frac{127240632}{17} + \frac{293969736 I}{17} & \frac{242109}{68} + \frac{159759 I}{34} \\ \frac{160064}{15} + \frac{80032 I}{15} & -\frac{799519680}{17} - \frac{479711808 I}{17} & \frac{157665280896}{25} + \frac{118248960672 I}{25} & \frac{1240884155200}{39} - \frac{1240884155200 I}{39} & \frac{78832640448}{13} + \frac{118248960672 I}{13} & -\frac{159903936}{5} - \frac{479711808 I}{5} & \frac{80032 I}{3} \\ \frac{1200663}{340} - \frac{406809 I}{340} & \frac{6945583464}{493} + \frac{1531275192 I}{493} & \frac{8477407107}{5} + \frac{8477407107 I}{10} & \frac{118248960672}{13} + \frac{78832640448 I}{13} & \frac{8477407107}{4} + \frac{8477407107 I}{4} & \frac{873133992}{85} + \frac{2821231944 I}{85} & -\frac{242109}{34} + \frac{159759 I}{17} \\ \frac{607176}{8177} - \frac{486216 I}{8177} & -\frac{43876080}{221} - \frac{8775216 I}{221} & \frac{293969736}{17} + \frac{127240632 I}{17} & -\frac{479711808}{5} - \frac{159903936 I}{5} & \frac{2821231944}{85} + \frac{873133992 I}{85} & -\frac{8775216}{17} - \frac{8775216 I}{17} & -\frac{95256}{221} + \frac{85320 I}{221} \\ \frac{1}{6} & \frac{17064}{221} + \frac{95256 I}{1105} & \frac{159759}{34} + \frac{242109 I}{68} & \frac{80032}{3} & \frac{159759}{17} - \frac{242109 I}{34} & \frac{85320}{221} - \frac{95256 I}{221} & \frac{927858939623}{118613926600} + \frac{927858939623 I}{118613926600} \end{bmatrix}$$

$$\frac{d}{dx} u(xI) = \frac{1}{355841779800 \Delta x I} \left((29653481650 + 29653481650 I) u_{iI-6+6I} + (26346598228800 + 940746312000 I) u_{iI-5+6I} + (1099215384599700 + 381874584758400 I) u_{iI-4+6I} + (1898581954730240 + 3797163909460480 I) u_{iI-3+6I} + (-425763642937230 + 1256606055470610 I) u_{iI-2+6I} + (-21158856158400 + 26422720862400 I) u_{iI-1+6I} + 59306963300 I u_{iI+6I} + (940746312000 + 26346598228800 I) u_{iI-6+5I} - (36736335053758080 + 36736335053758080 I) u_{iI-5+5I} + (3209949276343617600 + 2887386334408180800 I) u_{iI-4+5I} - (10041264914693875200 + 16735441524489792000 I) u_{iI-3+5I} + (1105256977048411200 + 5013242964663710400 I) u_{iI-2+5I} - (14129359636060800 + 70646798180304000 I) u_{iI-1+5I} + (30675171562560 + 27475493803200 I) u_{iI+5I} + (381874584758400 + 1099215384599700 I) u_{iI-6+4I} + (2887386334408180800$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& + 3209949276343617600 \text{ I} u_{i_i-5+41} + (377076954130506129825 + 377076954130506129825 \text{ I}) u_{i_i-4+41} + (1683116825000987361024 + 2244155766667983148032 \text{ I}) u_{i_i-3+41} + (301661563304404903860 + 603323126608809807720 \text{ I}) u_{i_i-2+41} + (2663384291397460800 + 6153336121504478400 \text{ I}) u_{i_i-1+41} \\
& + (1266948492141150 + 1672027261737300 \text{ I}) u_{i_i+41} + (3797163909460480 + 1898581954730240 \text{ I}) u_{i_i-6+31} - (16735441524489792000 + 10041264914693875200 \text{ I}) u_{i_i-5+31} + (2244155766667983148032 + 1683116825000987361024 \text{ I}) u_{i_i-4+31} - (11322010931076600640000 \\
& + 11322010931076600640000 \text{ I}) u_{i_i-3+31} + (2157842083334599180800 + 3236763125001898771200 \text{ I}) u_{i_i-2+31} - (11380100236653058560 + 34140300709959175680 \text{ I}) u_{i_i-1+31} + 9492909773651200 \text{ I} u_{i_i+31} + (1256606055470610 - 425763642937230 \text{ I}) u_{i_i-6+21} + (5013242964663710400 \\
& + 1105256977048411200 \text{ I}) u_{i_i-5+21} + (603323126608809807720 + 301661563304404903860 \text{ I}) u_{i_i-4+21} + (3236763125001898771200 + 2157842083334599180800 \text{ I}) u_{i_i-3+21} + (754153908261012259650 + 754153908261012259650 \text{ I}) u_{i_i-2+21} + (3655265337848928960 + 11810731719783222720 \text{ I}) u_{i_i-1+21} \\
& + (-2533896984282300 + 3344054523474600 \text{ I}) u_{i_i+21} + (26422720862400 - 21158856158400 \text{ I}) u_{i_i-6+1} - (70646798180304000 + 14129359636060800 \text{ I}) u_{i_i-5+1} + (6153336121504478400 + 2663384291397460800 \text{ I}) u_{i_i-4+1} - (34140300709959175680 + 11380100236653058560 \text{ I}) u_{i_i-3+1} \\
& + (11810731719783222720 + 3655265337848928960 \text{ I}) u_{i_i-2+1} - (183681675268790400 + 183681675268790400 \text{ I}) u_{i_i-1+1} + (-153375857812800 + 137377469016000 \text{ I}) u_{i_i+1} + 59306963300 u_{i_i-6} + (27475493803200 + 30675171562560 \text{ I}) u_{i_i-5} + (1672027261737300 + 1266948492141150 \text{ I}) u_{i_i-4} \\
& + 9492909773651200 u_{i_i-3} + (3344054523474600 - 2533896984282300 \text{ I}) u_{i_i-2} + (137377469016000 - 153375857812800 \text{ I}) u_{i_i-1} + (2783576818869 + 2783576818869 \text{ I}) u_{i_i}), O(\Delta x I^{48}), \text{ Quadrant 2}
\end{aligned}$$

Error order:, 48, *Error:*, 4.1045501315863644267 × 10⁻¹⁶², *New Error:*, 4.1286832965781701071 × 10⁻³⁰⁶
Error order:, 48, *Error:*, 4.1286832965781701071 × 10⁻³⁰⁶, *New Error:*, 4.1287075006222966103 × 10⁻⁴⁵⁰
Error order:, 48, *Error:*, 4.1287075006222966103 × 10⁻⁴⁵⁰, *New Error:*, 4.1287075248264117546 × 10⁻⁵⁹⁴
Error order:, 48, *Error:*, 4.1287075248264117546 × 10⁻⁵⁹⁴, *New Error:*, 4.1287075248506158699 × 10⁻⁷³⁸
Error order:, 48, *Error:*, 4.1287075248506158699 × 10⁻⁷³⁸, *New Error:*, 4.1287075248506400740 × 10⁻⁸⁸²

"--- Derivative Order: 1 - x1=1 ---"

$$\begin{bmatrix} -1 & 0 \\ -1 - \text{I} & -\text{I} \end{bmatrix}$$

$$\begin{bmatrix} \text{I} & \frac{3}{2} - \frac{3\text{I}}{2} \\ -\frac{1}{2} + \frac{\text{I}}{2} & -1 \end{bmatrix}$$

$$\frac{d}{dxI} u(xI) = \frac{2 \text{I} u_{i_i-1} + (3 - 3 \text{I}) u_{i_i} + (-1 + \text{I}) u_{i_i-1-1} - 2 u_{i_i-1}}{2 \Delta x I}, O(\Delta x I^3), \text{ Quadrant 3}$$

Error order:, 3, *Error:*, 1.2551984055224618565 × 10⁻⁹, *New Error:*, 1.2561999571536308731 × 10⁻¹⁸
Error order:, 3, *Error:*, 1.2561999571536308731 × 10⁻¹⁸, *New Error:*, 1.2562009591051340038 × 10⁻²⁷
Error order:, 3, *Error:*, 1.2562009591051340038 × 10⁻²⁷, *New Error:*, 1.2562009601070859069 × 10⁻³⁶
Error order:, 3, *Error:*, 1.2562009601070859069 × 10⁻³⁶, *New Error:*, 1.2562009601080878588 × 10⁻⁴⁵
Error order:, 3, *Error:*, 1.2562009601080878588 × 10⁻⁴⁵, *New Error:*, 1.2562009601080888608 × 10⁻⁵⁴

$$\frac{d^2}{dxI^2} u(xI) = \frac{-2 u_{i_i-2} + (6 + 6 \text{I}) u_{i_i-1} - 9 \text{I} u_{i_i} - (2 + 2 \text{I}) u_{i_i-2-1} + 2 \text{I} u_{i_i-1-1} + (-6 + 6 \text{I}) u_{i_i-1} - \text{I} u_{i_i-2-21} + (2 - 2 \text{I}) u_{i_i-1-21} + 2 u_{i_i-21}}{2 \Delta x I^2}, O(\Delta x I^3), \text{ Quadrant 3}$$

Error order:, 3, *Error:*, 2.5053860393813961664 × 10⁻⁹, *New Error:*, 2.5073851440192233001 × 10⁻¹⁸
Error order:, 3, *Error:*, 2.5073851440192233001 × 10⁻¹⁸, *New Error:*, 2.5073871439224231613 × 10⁻²⁷
Error order:, 3, *Error:*, 2.5073871439224231613 × 10⁻²⁷, *New Error:*, 2.5073871459223271595 × 10⁻³⁶
Error order:, 3, *Error:*, 2.5073871459223271595 × 10⁻³⁶, *New Error:*, 2.5073871459243270635 × 10⁻⁴⁵
Error order:, 3, *Error:*, 2.5073871459243270635 × 10⁻⁴⁵, *New Error:*, 2.5073871459243290635 × 10⁻⁵⁴

$$\frac{\partial^2}{\partial x I \partial x 2} u(xI, x2) = \frac{-2 u_{i_i-1, i2-1} + (3 + 3 \text{I}) u_{i_i-1, i2} - (1 + \text{I}) u_{i_i-1, i2-1-1} - 2 \text{I} u_{i_i-1, i2-1} + (3 + 3 \text{I}) u_{i_i, i2-1} - 9 \text{I} u_{i_i, i2} + 3 \text{I} u_{i_i, i2-1-1} + (-3 + 3 \text{I}) u_{i_i, i2-1} - (1 + \text{I}) u_{i_i-1-1, i2-1} + 3 \text{I} u_{i_i-1-1, i2} - \text{I} u_{i_i-1-1, i2-1-1} + (1 - \text{I}) u_{i_i-1-1, i2-1} - 2 \text{I} u_{i_i-1, i2-1} + (-3 + 3 \text{I}) u_{i_i-1, i2} + (1 - \text{I}) u_{i_i-1, i2-1-1} + 2 u_{i_i-1, i2-1}}{2 \Delta x I \Delta x 2},$$

O($\Delta x I^3 \Delta x 2^3$), *Quadrant 3*

Error order:, 3, *Error:*, 1.4583123925533946011 × 10⁻⁸, *New Error:*, 1.4599234365010185246 × 10⁻¹⁷
Error order:, 3, *Error:*, 1.4599234365010185246 × 10⁻¹⁷, *New Error:*, 1.4599250484357806400 × 10⁻²⁶
Error order:, 3, *Error:*, 1.4599250484357806400 × 10⁻²⁶, *New Error:*, 1.4599250500477162929 × 10⁻³⁵
Error order:, 3, *Error:*, 1.4599250500477162929 × 10⁻³⁵, *New Error:*, 1.4599250500493282285 × 10⁻⁴⁴
Error order:, 3, *Error:*, 1.4599250500493282285 × 10⁻⁴⁴, *New Error:*, 1.4599250500493298405 × 10⁻⁵³

$$\frac{d^3}{dxI^3} u(xI) = \frac{-4 \text{I} u_{i_i-3} + (-18 + 18 \text{I}) u_{i_i-2} + 54 u_{i_i-1} - (27 + 27 \text{I}) u_{i_i} + (6 - 6 \text{I}) u_{i_i-3-1} - 24 u_{i_i-2-1} - (9 + 9 \text{I}) u_{i_i-1-1} + 54 \text{I} u_{i_i-1} + 6 u_{i_i-3-21} + (3 + 3 \text{I}) u_{i_i-2-21} - 24 \text{I} u_{i_i-1-21} + (18 - 18 \text{I}) u_{i_i-21} + (1 + \text{I}) u_{i_i-3-31} + 6 \text{I} u_{i_i-2-31} + (-6 + 6 \text{I}) u_{i_i-1-31} - 4 u_{i_i-31}}{4 \Delta x I^3}, O(\Delta x I^3), \text{ Quadrant 3}$$

Error order:, 3, *Error:*, 3.7505779038859320350 × 10⁻⁹, *New Error:*, 3.7535705748790767972 × 10⁻¹⁸
Error order:, 3, *Error:*, 3.7535705748790767972 × 10⁻¹⁸, *New Error:*, 3.7535735687461424571 × 10⁻²⁷
Error order:, 3, *Error:*, 3.7535735687461424571 × 10⁻²⁷, *New Error:*, 3.7535735717400107179 × 10⁻³⁶
Error order:, 3, *Error:*, 3.7535735717400107179 × 10⁻³⁶, *New Error:*, 3.7535735717430045861 × 10⁻⁴⁵
Error order:, 3, *Error:*, 3.7535735717430045861 × 10⁻⁴⁵, *New Error:*, 3.7535735717430075800 × 10⁻⁵⁴

$$\frac{\partial^3}{\partial x I^2 \partial x 2} u(xI, x2) = \frac{1}{4 \Delta x I^2 \Delta x 2} (-4 \text{I} u_{i_i-2, i2-1} + (-6 + 6 \text{I}) u_{i_i-2, i2} + (2 - 2 \text{I}) u_{i_i-2, i2-1-1} + 4 u_{i_i-2, i2-1} + (-12 + 12 \text{I}) u_{i_i-1, i2-1} + 36 u_{i_i-1, i2} - 12 u_{i_i-1, i2-1-1} - (12 + 12 \text{I}) u_{i_i-1, i2-1} + 18 u_{i_i, i2-1} - (27 + 27 \text{I}) u_{i_i, i2} + (9 + 9 \text{I}) u_{i_i, i2-1-1} + 18 \text{I} u_{i_i, i2-1} + (4 - 4 \text{I}) u_{i_i-2-1, i2-1} - 12 u_{i_i-2-1, i2} + 4 u_{i_i-2-1, i2-1-1}$$

$$+ (4 + 4 \text{I}) u_{i_i-2-1, i2-1} - 4 u_{i_i-1-1, i2-1} + (6 + 6 \text{I}) u_{i_i-1-1, i2} - (2 + 2 \text{I}) u_{i_i-1-1, i2-1-1} - 4 \text{I} u_{i_i-1-1, i2-1} - (12 + 12 \text{I}) u_{i_i-1, i2-1} + 36 \text{I} u_{i_i-1, i2} - 12 \text{I} u_{i_i-1, i2-1-1} + (12 - 12 \text{I}) u_{i_i-1, i2-1} + 2 u_{i_i-2-21, i2-1} - (3 + 3 \text{I}) u_{i_i-2-21, i2} + (1 + \text{I}) u_{i_i-2-21, i2-1-1} + 2 \text{I} u_{i_i-2-21, i2-1} + (4 + 4 \text{I}) u_{i_i-1-21, i2-1}$$

$$- 12 \text{I} u_{i_i-1-21, i2} + 4 \text{I} u_{i_i-1-21, i2-1-1} + (-4 + 4 \text{I}) u_{i_i-1-21, i2-1} + 4 \text{I} u_{i_i-21, i2-1} + (6 - 6 \text{I}) u_{i_i-21, i2} + (-2 + 2 \text{I}) u_{i_i-21, i2-1-1} - 4 u_{i_i-21, i2-1}), O(\Delta x I^3 \Delta x 2^3), \text{ Quadrant 3}$$

Error order:, 3, *Error:*, 1.7889356997034403112 × 10⁻⁸, *New Error:*, 1.7908096748166071238 × 10⁻¹⁷

$$\begin{bmatrix} -1 & 0 \\ -1 - I & -I \end{bmatrix}$$

$$\begin{bmatrix} 3 - 3I & -3 - 3I \\ 3 + 3I & -3 + 3I \end{bmatrix}$$

$$\frac{d^3}{dxI^3} u(xI) = \frac{(3 - 3I) u_{iI-1} - (3 + 3I) u_{iI} + (3 + 3I) u_{iI-1} + (-3 + 3I) u_{iI-1}}{\Delta xI^3}, O(\Delta xI), \text{ Quadrant 3}$$

Error order:, 1, *Error:*, 0.0037667228090923972650, *New Error:*, 3.7686009997843763388 × 10⁻⁶
Error order:, 1, *Error:*, 3.7686009997843763388 × 10⁻⁶, *New Error:*, 3.7686028784437262264 × 10⁻⁹
Error order:, 1, *Error:*, 3.7686028784437262264 × 10⁻⁹, *New Error:*, 3.7686028803223860450 × 10⁻¹²
Error order:, 1, *Error:*, 3.7686028803223860450 × 10⁻¹², *New Error:*, 3.7686028803242647048 × 10⁻¹⁵
Error order:, 1, *Error:*, 3.7686028803242647048 × 10⁻¹⁵, *New Error:*, 3.7686028803242665835 × 10⁻¹⁸

$$\frac{d^6}{dxI^6} u(xI) = \frac{18(-I u_{iI-2} - 2 u_{iI-1} + I u_{iI} + 2 u_{iI-2} + 2 u_{iI-1} + I u_{iI-2-2I} - 2 u_{iI-1-2I} - I u_{iI-2I})}{\Delta xI^6}, O(\Delta xI), \text{ Quadrant 3}$$

Error order:, 1, *Error:*, 0.0074846893393681049747, *New Error:*, 7.4921553406456446294 × 10⁻⁶
Error order:, 1, *Error:*, 7.4921553406456446294 × 10⁻⁶, *New Error:*, 7.4921628103731061396 × 10⁻⁹
Error order:, 1, *Error:*, 7.4921628103731061396 × 10⁻⁹, *New Error:*, 7.4921628178428373286 × 10⁻¹²
Error order:, 1, *Error:*, 7.4921628178428373286 × 10⁻¹², *New Error:*, 7.4921628178503070597 × 10⁻¹⁵
Error order:, 1, *Error:*, 7.4921628178503070597 × 10⁻¹⁵, *New Error:*, 7.4921628178503145295 × 10⁻¹⁸

$$\frac{\partial^6}{\partial xI^3 \partial x2^3} u(xI, x2) = \frac{18(-I u_{iI-1, i2-1} - u_{iI-1, i2} + u_{iI-1, i2-1} + I u_{iI-1, i2-1} - u_{iI, i2} + I u_{iI, i2} - I u_{iI, i2-1} + u_{iI, i2} + u_{iI-1, i2-1} - I u_{iI-1, i2} + I u_{iI-1, i2-1} - u_{iI-1, i2-1} + I u_{iI-1, i2-1} + u_{iI-1, i2} - u_{iI-1, i2-1} - I u_{iI-1, i2-1})}{\Delta xI^3 \Delta x2^3}, O(\Delta xI \Delta x2), \text{ Quadrant 3}$$

Error order:, 1, *Error:*, 0.024889306568846594925, *New Error:*, 0.000024920325811296032805
Error order:, 1, *Error:*, 0.000024920325811296032805, *New Error:*, 2.4920356849879384083 × 10⁻⁸
Error order:, 1, *Error:*, 2.4920356849879384083 × 10⁻⁸, *New Error:*, 2.4920356880917986783 × 10⁻¹¹
Error order:, 1, *Error:*, 2.4920356880917986783 × 10⁻¹¹, *New Error:*, 2.4920356880949025386 × 10⁻¹⁴
Error order:, 1, *Error:*, 2.4920356880949025386 × 10⁻¹⁴, *New Error:*, 2.4920356880949056424 × 10⁻¹⁷

$$\frac{d^9}{dxI^9} u(xI)$$

$$= \frac{1}{\Delta xI^9} (54(- (1 + I) u_{iI-3} + (-3 + 3I) u_{iI-2} + (3 + 3I) u_{iI-1} + (1 - I) u_{iI} + (3 - 3I) u_{iI-3-1} - (3 + 3I) u_{iI-2-1} + (3 - 3I) u_{iI-1-1} - (3 + 3I) u_{iI-1} + (3 + 3I) u_{iI-3-2} + (-3 + 3I) u_{iI-2-2} + (3 + 3I) u_{iI-1-2} + (-3 + 3I) u_{iI-2} + (-1 + I) u_{iI-3-3} - (3 + 3I) u_{iI-2-3} + (3 - 3I) u_{iI-1-3} + (1 + I) u_{iI-3-1})), O(\Delta xI), \text{ Quadrant 3}$$

Error order:, 1, *Error:*, 0.011154372915023325985, *New Error:*, 0.000011171066859739871062
Error order:, 1, *Error:*, 0.000011171066859739871062, *New Error:*, 1.1171083566183191042 × 10⁻⁸
Error order:, 1, *Error:*, 1.1171083566183191042 × 10⁻⁸, *New Error:*, 1.1171083582889646866 × 10⁻¹¹
Error order:, 1, *Error:*, 1.1171083582889646866 × 10⁻¹¹, *New Error:*, 1.1171083582906353322 × 10⁻¹⁴
Error order:, 1, *Error:*, 1.1171083582906353322 × 10⁻¹⁴, *New Error:*, 1.1171083582906370029 × 10⁻¹⁷

$$\frac{\partial^9}{\partial xI^6 \partial x2^3} u(xI, x2) = \frac{1}{\Delta xI^6 \Delta x2^3} (54(- (1 + I) u_{iI-2, i2-1} + (-1 + I) u_{iI-2, i2} + (1 - I) u_{iI-2, i2-1} + (1 + I) u_{iI-2, i2-1} + (-2 + 2I) u_{iI-1, i2-1} + (2 + 2I) u_{iI-1, i2} - (2 + 2I) u_{iI-1, i2-1} + (2 - 2I) u_{iI-1, i2-1} + (1 + I) u_{iI, i2-1} + (1 - I) u_{iI, i2} + (-1 + I) u_{iI, i2-1} - (1 + I) u_{iI, i2-1} + (2 - 2I) u_{iI-2-1, i2-1} - (2 + 2I) u_{iI-2-1, i2} + (2 + 2I) u_{iI-2-1, i2-1} + (-2 + 2I) u_{iI-2-1, i2-1} + (2 - 2I) u_{iI-1, i2-1} + (-2 + 2I) u_{iI-1, i2-1} + (1 + I) u_{iI-2-2, i2-1} + (1 - I) u_{iI-2-2, i2} + (-1 + I) u_{iI-2-2, i2-1} - (1 + I) u_{iI-2-2, i2-1} + (-2 + 2I) u_{iI-1-2, i2-1} + (2 + 2I) u_{iI-1-2, i2} - (2 + 2I) u_{iI-1-2, i2-1} + (2 - 2I) u_{iI-1-2, i2-1} - (1 + I) u_{iI-2, i2-1} + (-1 + I) u_{iI-2, i2} + (1 - I) u_{iI-2, i2-1} + (1 + I) u_{iI-2, i2-1})), O(\Delta xI \Delta x2), \text{ Quadrant 3}$$

Error order:, 1, *Error:*, 0.034625433569931691722, *New Error:*, 0.000034685873532720930291
Error order:, 1, *Error:*, 0.000034685873532720930291, *New Error:*, 3.4685934025456060444 × 10⁻⁸
Error order:, 1, *Error:*, 3.4685934025456060444 × 10⁻⁸, *New Error:*, 3.4685934085948848377 × 10⁻¹¹
Error order:, 1, *Error:*, 3.4685934085948848377 × 10⁻¹¹, *New Error:*, 3.4685934086009341165 × 10⁻¹⁴
Error order:, 1, *Error:*, 3.4685934086009341165 × 10⁻¹⁴, *New Error:*, 3.4685934086009401658 × 10⁻¹⁷

$$\frac{\partial^9}{\partial xI^3 \partial x2^3 \partial x3^3} u(xI, x2, x3) = \frac{1}{\Delta xI^3 \Delta x2^3 \Delta x3^3} (54(- (1 + I) u_{iI-1, i2-1, i3-1} + (-1 + I) u_{iI-1, i2-1, i3} + (1 - I) u_{iI-1, i2-1, i3-1} + (1 + I) u_{iI-1, i2-1, i3-1} + (-1 + I) u_{iI-1, i2, i3-1} + (1 + I) u_{iI-1, i2, i3} - (1 + I) u_{iI-1, i2, i3-1} + (1 - I) u_{iI-1, i2, i3-1} + (1 - I) u_{iI-1, i2-1, i3-1} - (1 + I) u_{iI-1, i2-1, i3} + (1 + I) u_{iI-1, i2-1, i3-1} + (-1 + I) u_{iI-1, i2-1, i3} + (1 - I) u_{iI-1, i2-1, i3-1} + (1 + I) u_{iI-1, i2-1, i3-1} - (1 + I) u_{iI-1, i2-1, i3} + (1 + I) u_{iI-1, i2-1, i3-1} - (1 + I) u_{iI-1, i2-1, i3} + (1 + I) u_{iI-1, i2-1, i3-1} + (-1 + I) u_{iI-1, i2-1, i3} + (1 - I) u_{iI-1, i2-1, i3-1} - (1 + I) u_{iI-1, i2-1, i3} + (1 + I) u_{iI-1, i2-1, i3-1} + (1 + I) u_{iI-1, i2-1, i3} - (1 + I) u_{iI-1, i2-1, i3-1} + (1 - I) u_{iI-1, i2-1, i3} + (1 - I) u_{iI-1, i2-1, i3-1} - (1 + I) u_{iI-1, i2-1, i3} + (1 + I) u_{iI-1, i2-1, i3-1} + (-1 + I) u_{iI-1, i2-1, i3} + (-1 + I) u_{iI-1, i2-1, i3-1} - (1 + I) u_{iI-1, i2-1, i3} + (1 + I) u_{iI-1, i2-1, i3-1} + (1 + I) u_{iI-1, i2-1, i3} - (1 + I) u_{iI-1, i2-1, i3-1} + (1 - I) u_{iI-1, i2-1, i3} + (1 - I) u_{iI-1, i2-1, i3-1})), O(\Delta xI \Delta x2 \Delta x3), \text{ Quadrant 3}$$

Error order:, 1, *Error:*, 0.12914556057776021854, *New Error:*, 0.00012946728115636711256
Error order:, 1, *Error:*, 0.00012946728115636711256, *New Error:*, 1.2946760327774357202 × 10⁻⁷
Error order:, 1, *Error:*, 1.2946760327774357202 × 10⁻⁷, *New Error:*, 1.2946760359986534961 × 10⁻¹⁰

$$\begin{aligned}
& + u_{iI-1-1,i2-1,i3-1,i4-1-1} + I u_{iI-1-1,i2-1,i3-1,i4-1} - u_{iI-1-1,i2-1,i3,i4-1} + I u_{iI-1-1,i2-1,i3,i4} - I u_{iI-1-1,i2-1,i3,i4-1-1} + u_{iI-1-1,i2-1,i3,i4-1} + u_{iI-1-1,i2-1,i3-1-1,i4-1} - I u_{iI-1-1,i2-1,i3-1-1,i4} + I u_{iI-1-1,i2-1,i3-1-1,i4-1-1} - u_{iI-1-1,i2-1,i3-1-1,i4-1} + I u_{iI-1-1,i2-1,i3-1-1,i4} - u_{iI-1-1,i2-1,i3-1,i4-1-1} \\
& - I u_{iI-1-1,i2-1,i3-1,i4-1} - u_{iI-1-1,i2,i3-1,i4-1} + I u_{iI-1-1,i2,i3-1,i4} - I u_{iI-1-1,i2,i3-1,i4-1-1} + u_{iI-1-1,i2,i3-1,i4-1} + I u_{iI-1-1,i2,i3,i4-1} - u_{iI-1-1,i2,i3,i4-1-1} - I u_{iI-1-1,i2,i3,i4-1} - I u_{iI-1-1,i2,i3-1-1,i4-1} - u_{iI-1-1,i2,i3-1-1,i4} + u_{iI-1-1,i2,i3-1-1,i4-1-1} + I u_{iI-1-1,i2,i3-1-1,i4-1} + u_{iI-1-1,i2,i3-1-1,i4-1} \\
& - I u_{iI-1-1,i2,i3-1,i4} + I u_{iI-1-1,i2,i3-1,i4-1-1} - u_{iI-1-1,i2,i3-1,i4-1} + u_{iI-1-1,i2,i3-1,i4-1} - I u_{iI-1-1,i2-1-1,i3-1,i4-1} - I u_{iI-1-1,i2-1-1,i3-1,i4} + I u_{iI-1-1,i2-1-1,i3-1,i4-1-1} - u_{iI-1-1,i2-1-1,i3-1,i4-1} - I u_{iI-1-1,i2-1-1,i3,i4-1} - u_{iI-1-1,i2-1-1,i3,i4-1-1} + I u_{iI-1-1,i2-1-1,i3,i4-1} + I u_{iI-1-1,i2-1-1,i3-1-1,i4-1} \\
& + u_{iI-1-1,i2-1-1,i3-1-1,i4} - u_{iI-1-1,i2-1-1,i3-1-1,i4-1-1} - I u_{iI-1-1,i2-1-1,i3-1-1,i4-1} - u_{iI-1-1,i2-1-1,i3-1,i4-1} + I u_{iI-1-1,i2-1-1,i3-1,i4} - I u_{iI-1-1,i2-1-1,i3-1,i4-1-1} + u_{iI-1-1,i2-1-1,i3-1,i4-1} + I u_{iI-1-1,i2-1,i3-1,i4-1} - u_{iI-1-1,i2-1,i3-1,i4-1-1} - I u_{iI-1-1,i2-1,i3-1,i4-1} + u_{iI-1-1,i2-1,i3-1,i4-1} \\
& - I u_{iI-1-1,i2-1,i3,i4} + I u_{iI-1-1,i2-1,i3,i4-1-1} - u_{iI-1-1,i2-1,i3,i4-1} - u_{iI-1-1,i2-1,i3-1-1,i4-1} + I u_{iI-1-1,i2-1,i3-1-1,i4} - I u_{iI-1-1,i2-1,i3-1-1,i4-1-1} + u_{iI-1-1,i2-1,i3-1-1,i4-1} - I u_{iI-1-1,i2-1,i3-1,i4-1} - u_{iI-1-1,i2-1,i3-1,i4} + u_{iI-1-1,i2-1,i3-1,i4-1-1} + I u_{iI-1-1,i2-1,i3-1,i4-1} + u_{iI-1-1,i2-1,i3-1,i4-1} \\
& - I u_{iI-1-1,i2-1,i3-1,i4-1} - u_{iI-1-1,i2-1,i3-1,i4-1} - I u_{iI-1-1,i2-1,i3,i4-1} - u_{iI-1-1,i2-1,i3,i4} + u_{iI-1-1,i2-1,i3,i4-1-1} + I u_{iI-1-1,i2-1,i3,i4-1} + I u_{iI-1-1,i2-1,i3-1-1,i4-1} + u_{iI-1-1,i2-1,i3-1-1,i4-1} - u_{iI-1-1,i2-1,i3-1,i4-1} - I u_{iI-1-1,i2-1,i3-1,i4-1} \\
& + I u_{iI-1-1,i2-1-1,i3-1,i4-1} + u_{iI-1-1,i2-1-1,i3-1,i4} - u_{iI-1-1,i2-1-1,i3-1,i4-1-1} - I u_{iI-1-1,i2-1-1,i3-1,i4-1} + u_{iI-1-1,i2-1-1,i3,i4-1} - I u_{iI-1-1,i2-1-1,i3,i4-1-1} - u_{iI-1-1,i2-1-1,i3,i4-1} - u_{iI-1-1,i2-1-1,i3-1-1,i4-1} + I u_{iI-1-1,i2-1-1,i3-1-1,i4} - I u_{iI-1-1,i2-1-1,i3-1-1,i4-1-1} \\
& - u_{iI-1-1,i2-1-1,i3-1,i4} + u_{iI-1-1,i2-1-1,i3-1,i4-1-1} + I u_{iI-1-1,i2-1-1,i3-1,i4-1} - u_{iI-1-1,i2-1,i3-1,i4-1} + I u_{iI-1-1,i2-1,i3-1,i4} - I u_{iI-1-1,i2-1,i3-1,i4-1-1} + u_{iI-1-1,i2-1,i3-1,i4-1} + I u_{iI-1-1,i2-1,i3,i4-1} + u_{iI-1-1,i2-1,i3,i4} - u_{iI-1-1,i2-1,i3,i4-1-1} - I u_{iI-1-1,i2-1,i3,i4-1} \\
& + I u_{iI-1-1,i2-1,i3-1-1,i4-1} + u_{iI-1-1,i2-1,i3-1,i4-1} - I u_{iI-1-1,i2-1,i3-1,i4} + I u_{iI-1-1,i2-1,i3-1,i4-1-1} - u_{iI-1-1,i2-1,i3-1,i4-1}
\end{aligned}$$

Error order:, 1, *Error:*, 0.55950979949288606369, *New Error:*, 0.00056187824969459219388
Error order:, 1, *Error:*, 0.00056187824969459219388, *New Error:*, 5.6188062315570277894 × 10⁻⁷
Error order:, 1, *Error:*, 5.6188062315570277894 × 10⁻⁷, *New Error:*, 5.6188062552916890747 × 10⁻¹⁰
Error order:, 1, *Error:*, 5.6188062552916890747 × 10⁻¹⁰, *New Error:*, 5.6188062553154237360 × 10⁻¹³
Error order:, 1, *Error:*, 5.6188062553154237360 × 10⁻¹³, *New Error:*, 5.6188062553154474707 × 10⁻¹⁶

$$\frac{d^{15}}{dxI^{15}} u(xI) = \frac{1}{\Delta xI^{15}} (972 ((-1 + I) u_{iI-5} + (5 + 5 I) u_{iI-4} + (10 - 10 I) u_{iI-3} - (10 + 10 I) u_{iI-2} + (-5 + 5 I) u_{iI-1} + (1 + I) u_i - (5 + 5 I) u_{iI-5-1} + (-15 + 15 I) u_{iI-4-1} + (10 + 10 I) u_{iI-3-1} + (-10 + 10 I) u_{iI-2-1} + (15 + 15 I) u_{iI-1-1} + (5 - 5 I) u_{iI-1} + (10 - 10 I) u_{iI-5-2-1} - (10 + 10 I) u_{iI-4-2-1} + (20 - 20 I) u_{iI-3-2-1} - (20 + 20 I) u_{iI-2-2-1} + (10 - 10 I) u_{iI-1-2-1} - (10 + 10 I) u_{iI-2-1} + (10 + 10 I) u_{iI-5-3-1} + (-10 + 10 I) u_{iI-4-3-1} + (20 + 20 I) u_{iI-3-3-1} + (-20 + 20 I) u_{iI-2-3-1} + (10 + 10 I) u_{iI-1-3-1} + (-10 + 10 I) u_{iI-3-1} + (-5 + 5 I) u_{iI-5-4-1} - (15 + 15 I) u_{iI-4-4-1} + (10 - 10 I) u_{iI-3-4-1} - (10 + 10 I) u_{iI-2-4-1} + (15 - 15 I) u_{iI-1-4-1} + (5 + 5 I) u_{iI-4-1} - (1 + I) u_{iI-5-5-1} + (5 - 5 I) u_{iI-4-5-1} + (10 + 10 I) u_{iI-3-5-1} + (-10 + 10 I) u_{iI-2-5-1} - (5 + 5 I) u_{iI-1-5-1} + (1 - I) u_{iI-5-1}), O(\Delta xI), \text{ Quadrant 3}$$

Error order:, 1, *Error:*, 0.018350764110021452911, *New Error:*, 0.000018396560714870429059
Error order:, 1, *Error:*, 0.000018396560714870429059, *New Error:*, 1.8396606568630554057 × 10⁻⁸
Error order:, 1, *Error:*, 1.8396606568630554057 × 10⁻⁸, *New Error:*, 1.8396606614484371384 × 10⁻¹¹
Error order:, 1, *Error:*, 1.8396606614484371384 × 10⁻¹¹, *New Error:*, 1.8396606614530225202 × 10⁻¹⁴
Error order:, 1, *Error:*, 1.8396606614530225202 × 10⁻¹⁴, *New Error:*, 1.8396606614530271056 × 10⁻¹⁷

"--- Derivative Order: 1 - x1=1 ---"

$$\begin{bmatrix} -2 & -1 & 0 \\ -2 - I & -1 - I & -I \\ -2 - 2 I & -1 - 2 I & -2 I \end{bmatrix}$$

$$\begin{bmatrix} \frac{1}{2} & 4 & \frac{57}{20} - \frac{57 I}{20} \\ \frac{8}{5} - \frac{4 I}{5} & -10 + 10 I & -4 I \\ \frac{1}{4} - \frac{I}{4} & \frac{4}{5} - \frac{8 I}{5} & -\frac{I}{2} \end{bmatrix}$$

$$\frac{d}{dxI} u(xI) = \frac{10 u_{iI-2} + 80 u_{iI-1} + (57 - 57 I) u_i + (32 - 16 I) u_{iI-2-1} + (-200 + 200 I) u_{iI-1-1} - 80 I u_{iI-1} + (5 - 5 I) u_{iI-2-2-1} + (16 - 32 I) u_{iI-1-2-1} - 10 I u_{iI-2-1}}{20 \Delta xI}, O(\Delta xI^8), \text{ Quadrant 3}$$

Error order:, 8, *Error:*, 1.4863241007178082516 × 10⁻²⁵, *New Error:*, 1.4889938688543323141 × 10⁻⁴⁹
Error order:, 8, *Error:*, 1.4889938688543323141 × 10⁻⁴⁹, *New Error:*, 1.4889965410211761448 × 10⁻⁷³
Error order:, 8, *Error:*, 1.4889965410211761448 × 10⁻⁷³, *New Error:*, 1.4889965436933453888 × 10⁻⁹⁷
Error order:, 8, *Error:*, 1.4889965436933453888 × 10⁻⁹⁷, *New Error:*, 1.4889965436960175580 × 10⁻¹²¹
Error order:, 8, *Error:*, 1.4889965436960175580 × 10⁻¹²¹, *New Error:*, 1.4889965436960202302 × 10⁻¹⁴⁵

$$\frac{d^2}{dxI^2} u(xI) = \frac{1}{200 \Delta xI^2} (50 u_{iI-4} + 800 u_{iI-3} + (3770 - 570 I) u_{iI-2} + (4560 - 4560 I) u_{iI-1} - 3249 I u_i + (320 - 160 I) u_{iI-4-1} + (560 + 720 I) u_{iI-3-1} + (-15088 + 12464 I) u_{iI-2-1} + 16400 I u_{iI-1-1} - (4560 + 4560 I) u_{iI-1} + (434 - 562 I) u_{iI-4-2-1} + (-2640 + 8880 I) u_{iI-3-2-1} - 45790 I u_{iI-2-2-1} + (15088 + 12464 I) u_{iI-1-2-1} - (3770 + 570 I) u_{iI-2-1} + (80 - 240 I) u_{iI-4-3-1} + 720 I u_{iI-3-3-1} + (2640 + 8880 I) u_{iI-2-3-1} + (-560 + 720 I) u_{iI-1-3-1} - 800 u_{iI-3-1} - 25 I u_{iI-4-4-1} - (80 + 240 I) u_{iI-3-4-1} - (434 + 562 I) u_{iI-2-4-1} - (320 + 160 I) u_{iI-1-4-1} - 50 u_{iI-4-1}), O(\Delta xI^8), \text{ Quadrant 3}$$

Error order:, 8, *Error:*, 2.9667147718918328376 × 10⁻²⁵, *New Error:*, 2.9720436504078489304 × 10⁻⁴⁹
Error order:, 8, *Error:*, 2.9720436504078489304 × 10⁻⁴⁹, *New Error:*, 2.9720489840742038818 × 10⁻⁷³
Error order:, 8, *Error:*, 2.9720489840742038818 × 10⁻⁷³, *New Error:*, 2.9720489894078750275 × 10⁻⁹⁷
Error order:, 8, *Error:*, 2.9720489894078750275 × 10⁻⁹⁷, *New Error:*, 2.9720489894132086987 × 10⁻¹²¹
Error order:, 8, *Error:*, 2.9720489894132086987 × 10⁻¹²¹, *New Error:*, 2.9720489894132140323 × 10⁻¹⁴⁵

$$\frac{\partial^2}{\partial xI \partial x2} u(xI, x2) = \frac{1}{200 \Delta xI \Delta x2} (50 u_{iI-2,i2-2} + 400 u_{iI-2,i2-1} + (285 - 285 I) u_{iI-2,i2} + (160 - 80 I) u_{iI-2,i2-2-1} + (-1000 + 1000 I) u_{iI-2,i2-1-1} - 400 I u_{iI-2,i2-1} + (25 - 25 I) u_{iI-2,i2-2-2-1} + (80 - 160 I) u_{iI-2,i2-1-2-1} - 50 I u_{iI-2,i2-2-1} + 400 u_{iI-1,i2-2} + 3200 u_{iI-1,i2-1} + (2280 - 2280 I) u_{iI-1,i2} + (1280 - 640 I) u_{iI-1,i2-2-1} + (-8000 + 8000 I) u_{iI-1,i2-1-1} - 3200 I u_{iI-1,i2-1} + (200 - 200 I) u_{iI-1,i2-2-2-1} + (640 - 1280 I) u_{iI-1,i2-1-2-1} - 400 I u_{iI-1,i2-2-1} + (285 - 285 I) u_{iI,i2-2} + (2280 - 2280 I) u_{iI,i2-1} - 3249 I u_{iI,i2} + (456 - 1368 I) u_{iI,i2-2-1} + 11400 I u_{iI,i2-1-1} - (2280 + 2280 I) u_{iI,i2-1} - 285 I u_{iI,i2-2-2-1} - (456 + 1368 I) u_{iI,i2-1-2-1} - (285 + 285 I) u_{iI,i2-2-1} + (160 - 80 I) u_{iI-2-1,i2-2} + (1280 - 640 I) u_{iI-2-1,i2-1} + (456 - 1368 I) u_{iI-2-1,i2} + (384 - 512 I) u_{iI-2-1,i2-2-1} + (-1600 + 4800 I) u_{iI-2-1,i2-1-1} - (640 + 1280 I) u_{iI-2-1,i2-1-2-1} + (40 - 120 I) u_{iI-2-1,i2-2-2-1} - 640 I u_{iI-2-1,i2-1-2-1} - (80 + 160 I) u_{iI-2-1,i2-2-1} + (-1000 + 1000 I) u_{iI-1-1,i2-2} + (-8000 + 8000 I) u_{iI-1-1,i2-1} + 11400 I u_{iI-1-1,i2} + (-1600 + 4800 I) u_{iI-1-1,i2-2-1} - 40000 I u_{iI-1-1,i2-1-1} + (8000 + 8000 I) u_{iI-1-1,i2-1} + 1000 I u_{iI-1-1,i2-2-2-1} + (1600 + 4800 I) u_{iI-1-1,i2-1-2-1} + (1000 + 1000 I) u_{iI-1-1,i2-2-1} - 400 I u_{iI-1,i2-2}$$

"--- Derivative Order: 2 - x1=1 ---"

$$\begin{bmatrix} -2 & -1 & 0 \\ -2 - I & -1 - I & -I \\ -2 - 2I & -1 - 2I & -2I \end{bmatrix}$$

$$\begin{bmatrix} \frac{47}{20} - \frac{57I}{20} & \frac{74}{5} - \frac{114I}{5} & -\frac{153I}{10} \\ \frac{18}{5} - \frac{62I}{5} & 94I & -\frac{74}{5} - \frac{114I}{5} \\ -\frac{13I}{5} & -\frac{18}{5} - \frac{62I}{5} & -\frac{47}{20} - \frac{57I}{20} \end{bmatrix}$$

$$\frac{d^2}{dxI^2} u(xI) = \frac{(47 - 57I) u_{iI-2} + (296 - 456I) u_{iI-1} - 306I u_{iI} + (72 - 248I) u_{iI-2-1} + 1880I u_{iI-1-1} - (296 + 456I) u_{iI-1} - 52I u_{iI-2-2-1} - (72 + 248I) u_{iI-1-2-1} - (47 + 57I) u_{iI-2-1}}{20 \Delta xI^2}, O(\Delta xI^7), \text{ Quadrant 3}$$

Error order: 7, Error: 5.9908519308332219769 × 10⁻²², New Error: 6.0014028824841454417 × 10⁻⁴³
 Error order: 7, Error: 6.0014028824841454417 × 10⁻⁴³, New Error: 6.0014134427306611295 × 10⁻⁶⁴
 Error order: 7, Error: 6.0014134427306611295 × 10⁻⁶⁴, New Error: 6.0014134532909169455 × 10⁻⁸⁵
 Error order: 7, Error: 6.0014134532909169455 × 10⁻⁸⁵, New Error: 6.0014134533014772013 × 10⁻¹⁰⁶
 Error order: 7, Error: 6.0014134533014772013 × 10⁻¹⁰⁶, New Error: 6.0014134533014877616 × 10⁻¹²⁷

$$\frac{d^4}{dxI^4} u(xI) = \frac{1}{200 \Delta xI^4} (- (520 + 2679I) u_{iI-4} - (12080 + 38304I) u_{iI-3} - (77602 + 149358I) u_{iI-2} - (139536 + 90576I) u_{iI-1} - 46818 u_{iI} - (10752 + 15760I) u_{iI-4-1} + (15384 - 17880I) u_{iI-3-1} + (741488 + 529888I) u_{iI-2-1} + 279728 u_{iI-1-1} + (-139536 + 90576I) u_{iI-1} - (31124 + 20300I) u_{iI-4-2-1} + (425008 + 112416I) u_{iI-3-2-1} - 2057370 u_{iI-2-2-1} + (741488 - 529888I) u_{iI-1-2-1} + (-77602 + 149358I) u_{iI-2-1} - (12896 + 3744I) u_{iI-4-3-1} + 31072 u_{iI-3-3-1} + (425008 - 112416I) u_{iI-2-3-1} + (15384 + 17880I) u_{iI-1-3-1} + (-12080 + 38304I) u_{iI-3-1} - 1352 u_{iI-4-4-1} + (-12896 + 3744I) u_{iI-3-4-1} + (-31124 + 20300I) u_{iI-2-4-1} + (-10752 + 15760I) u_{iI-1-4-1} + (-520 + 2679I) u_{iI-4-1}), O(\Delta xI^7), \text{ Quadrant 3}$$

Error order: 7, Error: 1.1933920444207835779 × 10⁻²¹, New Error: 1.1954938192445738148 × 10⁻⁴²
 Error order: 7, Error: 1.1954938192445738148 × 10⁻⁴², New Error: 1.1954959228709569144 × 10⁻⁶³
 Error order: 7, Error: 1.1954959228709569144 × 10⁻⁶³, New Error: 1.1954959249745851502 × 10⁻⁸⁴
 Error order: 7, Error: 1.1954959249745851502 × 10⁻⁸⁴, New Error: 1.1954959249766887784 × 10⁻¹⁰⁵
 Error order: 7, Error: 1.1954959249766887784 × 10⁻¹⁰⁵, New Error: 1.1954959249766908820 × 10⁻¹²⁶

$$\frac{\partial^4}{\partial xI^2 \partial x2^2} u(xI, x2) = \frac{1}{200 \Delta xI^2 \Delta x2^2} (- (520 + 2679I) u_{iI-2, i2-2} - (6040 + 19152I) u_{iI-2, i2-1} - (8721 + 7191I) u_{iI-2, i2} - (5376 + 7880I) u_{iI-2, i2-2-1} + (53580 + 44180I) u_{iI-2, i2-1-1} - (19952 + 2280I) u_{iI-2, i2-1} - (1482 + 1222I) u_{iI-2, i2-2-2-1} - (8760 + 3776I) u_{iI-2, i2-1-2-1} - 2729 u_{iI-2, i2-2-1} - (6040 + 19152I) u_{iI-1, i2-2} - (60160 + 134976I) u_{iI-1, i2-1} - (69768 + 45288I) u_{iI-1, i2} - (45888 + 53120I) u_{iI-1, i2-2-1} + (428640 + 278240I) u_{iI-1, i2-1-1} - 147776 u_{iI-1, i2-1} - (11856 + 7696I) u_{iI-1, i2-2-2-1} - (67200 + 20288I) u_{iI-1, i2-1-2-1} + (-19952 + 2280I) u_{iI-1, i2-2-1} - (8721 + 7191I) u_{iI, i2-2} - (69768 + 45288I) u_{iI, i2-1} - 46818 u_{iI, i2} - (37944 + 11016I) u_{iI, i2-2-1} + 287640 u_{iI, i2-1-1} + (-69768 + 45288I) u_{iI, i2-1} - 7956 u_{iI, i2-2-2-1} + (-37944 + 11016I) u_{iI, i2-1-2-1} + (-8721 + 7191I) u_{iI, i2-2-1} - (5376 + 7880I) u_{iI-2-1, i2-2} - (45888 + 53120I) u_{iI-2-1, i2-1} - (37944 + 11016I) u_{iI-2-1, i2} - (28160 + 17856I) u_{iI-2-1, i2-2-1} + (233120 + 67680I) u_{iI-2-1, i2-1-1} + (-67200 + 20288I) u_{iI-2-1, i2-1} - (6448 + 1872I) u_{iI-2-1, i2-2-2-1} - 33344 u_{iI-2-1, i2-1-2-1} + (-8760 + 3776I) u_{iI-2-1, i2-2-1} + (53580 + 44180I) u_{iI-1-1, i2-2} + (428640 + 278240I) u_{iI-1-1, i2-1} + 287640 u_{iI-1-1, i2} + (233120 + 67680I) u_{iI-1-1, i2-2-1} - 1767200 u_{iI-1-1, i2-1-1} + (428640 - 278240I) u_{iI-1-1, i2-1} + 48880 u_{iI-1-1, i2-2-2-1} + (233120 - 67680I) u_{iI-1-1, i2-1-2-1} + (53580 - 44180I) u_{iI-1-1, i2-2-1} - (19952 + 2280I) u_{iI-1, i2-2} - 147776 u_{iI-1, i2-1} + (-69768 + 45288I) u_{iI-1, i2} + (-67200 + 20288I) u_{iI-1, i2-2-1} + (428640 - 278240I) u_{iI-1, i2-1-1} + (-60160 + 134976I) u_{iI-1, i2-1} + (-11856 + 7696I) u_{iI-1, i2-2-2-1} + (-45888 + 53120I) u_{iI-1, i2-1-2-1} + (-6040 + 19152I) u_{iI-1, i2-2-1} - (1482 + 1222I) u_{iI-2-2, i2-2} - (11856 + 7696I) u_{iI-2-2, i2-1} - 7956 u_{iI-2-2, i2} - (6448 + 1872I) u_{iI-2-2, i2-2-1} + 48880 u_{iI-2-2, i2-1-1} + (-11856 + 7696I) u_{iI-2-2, i2-1} - 1352 u_{iI-2-2, i2-2-2-1} + (-6448 + 1872I) u_{iI-2-2, i2-1-2-1} + (-1482 + 1222I) u_{iI-2-2, i2-2-1} - (8760 + 3776I) u_{iI-1-2, i2-2} - (67200 + 20288I) u_{iI-1-2, i2-1} + (-37944 + 11016I) u_{iI-1-2, i2} - 33344 u_{iI-1-2, i2-2-1} + (233120 - 67680I) u_{iI-1-2, i2-1-1} + (-45888 + 53120I) u_{iI-1-2, i2-1} + (-6448 + 1872I) u_{iI-1-2, i2-2-2-1} + (-28160 + 17856I) u_{iI-1-2, i2-1-2-1} + (-5376 + 7880I) u_{iI-1-2, i2-2-1} - 2729 u_{iI-2, i2-2} + (-19952 + 2280I) u_{iI-2, i2-1} + (-8721 + 7191I) u_{iI-2, i2} + (-8760 + 3776I) u_{iI-2, i2-2-1} + (53580 - 44180I) u_{iI-2, i2-1-1} + (-6040 + 19152I) u_{iI-2, i2-1} + (-1482 + 1222I) u_{iI-2, i2-2-2-1} + (-5376 + 7880I) u_{iI-2, i2-1-2-1} + (-520 + 2679I) u_{iI-2, i2-2-1}), O(\Delta xI^7 \Delta x2^7), \text{ Quadrant 3}$$

Error order: 7, Error: 2.8549593196373321864 × 10⁻²⁰, New Error: 2.8623574917559394457 × 10⁻⁴¹
 Error order: 7, Error: 2.8623574917559394457 × 10⁻⁴¹, New Error: 2.8623648995149059793 × 10⁻⁶²
 Error order: 7, Error: 2.8623648995149059793 × 10⁻⁶², New Error: 2.8623649069226745410 × 10⁻⁸³
 Error order: 7, Error: 2.8623649069226745410 × 10⁻⁸³, New Error: 2.8623649069300823095 × 10⁻¹⁰⁴
 Error order: 7, Error: 2.8623649069300823095 × 10⁻¹⁰⁴, New Error: 2.8623649069300897173 × 10⁻¹²⁵

$$\frac{d^6}{dxI^6} u(xI) = \frac{1}{4000 \Delta xI^6} (- (177143 + 96273I) u_{iI-6} - (4126632 + 1667592I) u_{iI-5} - (34022778 + 8266896I) u_{iI-4} - (114519488 + 1430496I) u_{iI-3} + (-130509306 + 63232758I) u_{iI-2} + (-41574384 + 64047024I) u_{iI-1} + 14326308I u_{iI} - (2105496 + 191784I) u_{iI-6-1} - (15997896 + 2218944I) u_{iI-5-1} + (84947064 - 39566328I) u_{iI-4-1} + (703177968 - 302885520I) u_{iI-3-1} + (365324784 - 513361008I) u_{iI-2-1} + 7263216I u_{iI-1-1} + (41574384 + 64047024I) u_{iI-1} + (-7441860 + 2378784I) u_{iI-6-2-1} + (31597032 - 35124504I) u_{iI-5-2-1} + (272041155 - 131037189I) u_{iI-4-2-1} + (-1596470832 + 2103584784I) u_{iI-3-2-1} + 273086724I u_{iI-2-2-1} - (365324784 + 513361008I) u_{iI-1-2-1} + (130509306 + 63232758I) u_{iI-2-1} + (-8914368 + 7375360I) u_{iI-6-3-1} + (88515552 - 149818656I) u_{iI-5-3-1} + (-316278192 + 1249980816I) u_{iI-4-3-1} - 4790222032I u_{iI-3-3-1} + (1596470832 + 2103584784I) u_{iI-2-3-1} - (703177968 + 302885520I) u_{iI-1-3-1} + (114519488 - 1430496I) u_{iI-3-1} + (-2976168 + 4624152I) u_{iI-6-4-1} + (11535168 - 43342848I) u_{iI-5-4-1} - 41745624I u_{iI-4-4-1} + (316278192 + 1249980816I) u_{iI-3-4-1} - (272041155 + 131037189I) u_{iI-2-4-1} - (84947064 + 39566328I) u_{iI-1-4-1} + (34022778 - 8266896I) u_{iI-4-1} + (-292032 + 1005888I) u_{iI-6-5-1} + 2778048I u_{iI-5-5-1} - (11535168 + 43342848I) u_{iI-4-5-1} - (88515552 + 149818656I) u_{iI-3-5-1} - (31597032 + 35124504I) u_{iI-2-5-1} + (15997896 - 2218944I) u_{iI-1-5-1} + (4126632 - 1667592I) u_{iI-5-1} + 70304I u_{iI-6-6-1} + (292032 + 1005888I) u_{iI-5-6-1} + (2976168 + 4624152I) u_{iI-4-6-1} + (8914368 + 7375360I) u_{iI-3-6-1} + (7441860 + 2378784I) u_{iI-2-6-1} + (2105496 - 191784I) u_{iI-1-6-1} + (177143 - 96273I) u_{iI-6-1}), O(\Delta xI^7), \text{ Quadrant 3}$$

Error order: 7, Error: 1.7829491382814962559 × 10⁻²¹, New Error: 1.7860892275995521155 × 10⁻⁴²
 Error order: 7, Error: 1.7860892275995521155 × 10⁻⁴², New Error: 1.7860923704551330190 × 10⁻⁶³
 Error order: 7, Error: 1.7860923704551330190 × 10⁻⁶³, New Error: 1.7860923735979913678 × 10⁻⁸⁴
 Error order: 7, Error: 1.7860923735979913678 × 10⁻⁸⁴, New Error: 1.7860923736011342262 × 10⁻¹⁰⁵
 Error order: 7, Error: 1.7860923736011342262 × 10⁻¹⁰⁵, New Error: 1.7860923736011373690 × 10⁻¹²⁶

$$\begin{aligned}
& + 3955901952 I) u_{ij-2-3, i, i2-1-21} + (55479456 + 1199115168 I) u_{ij-2-3, i, i2-21} - (31878944 + 2589408 I) u_{ij-1-3, i, i2-2} + (-206732800 + 20797440 I) u_{ij-1-3, i, i2-1} + (-75845856 + 43204128 I) u_{ij-1-3, i, i2} + (-106491904 + 29435392 I) u_{ij-1-3, i, i2-2-1} + (657640960 - 374612480 I) u_{ij-1-3, i, i2-1-1} \\
& + (-123328512 + 167215616 I) u_{ij-1-3, i, i2-1} + (-19698208 + 11220704 I) u_{ij-1-3, i, i2-2-21} + (-79632896 + 76587008 I) u_{ij-1-3, i, i2-1-21} + (-14031840 + 28741600 I) u_{ij-1-3, i, i2-21} + (38012320 - 98626560 I) u_{ij-3, i, i2-2} + (127358720 - 674730240 I) u_{ij-3, i, i2-1} - (66034560 + 280803360 I) u_{ij-3, i, i2} \\
& + (6260480 - 365070080 I) u_{ij-3, i, i2-2-1} + (572569600 + 2434777600 I) u_{ij-3, i, i2-1-1} - (414723840 + 547252480 I) u_{ij-3, i, i2-1} - (17150080 + 72928480 I) u_{ij-3, i, i2-2-21} - (168308480 + 324017920 I) u_{ij-3, i, i2-1-21} - (77984160 + 71348480 I) u_{ij-3, i, i2-21} + (4016121 - 758063 I) u_{ij-4-4, i, i2-2} + (24774144 \\
& - 9548368 I) u_{ij-4-4, i, i2-1} + (7887081 - 7887081 I) u_{ij-4-4, i, i2} + (12129008 - 7225792 I) u_{ij-4-4, i, i2-2-1} + (-68386960 + 68386960 I) u_{ij-4-4, i, i2-1-1} + (9548368 - 24774144 I) u_{ij-4-4, i, i2-1} + (2048383 - 2048383 I) u_{ij-4-4, i, i2-2-21} + (7225792 - 12129008 I) u_{ij-4-4, i, i2-1-21} + (758063 \\
& - 4016121 I) u_{ij-4-4, i, i2-21} + (36133024 - 16776192 I) u_{ij-3-4, i, i2-2} + (211230464 - 149522688 I) u_{ij-3-4, i, i2-1} + (55644288 - 93402912 I) u_{ij-3-4, i, i2} + (97308416 - 97308416 I) u_{ij-3-4, i, i2-2-1} + (-482478080 + 809873920 I) u_{ij-3-4, i, i2-1-1} + (30918912 - 256942336 I) u_{ij-3-4, i, i2-1} + (14451584 \\
& - 24258016 I) u_{ij-3-4, i, i2-2-21} + (39241984 - 131901184 I) u_{ij-3-4, i, i2-1-21} - (2450592 + 39762176 I) u_{ij-3-4, i, i2-21} + (83468974 - 69406382 I) u_{ij-2-4, i, i2-2} + (452045600 - 541267840 I) u_{ij-2-4, i, i2-1} + (81386226 - 284863038 I) u_{ij-2-4, i, i2} + (188406784 - 324227232 I) u_{ij-2-4, i, i2-2-1} + (-705680160 \\
& + 2469978080 I) u_{ij-2-4, i, i2-1-1} - (97874048 + 698381536 I) u_{ij-2-4, i, i2-1} + (21137118 - 73982834 I) u_{ij-2-4, i, i2-2-21} + (11314016 - 374823168 I) u_{ij-2-4, i, i2-1-21} - (34204510 + 103026050 I) u_{ij-2-4, i, i2-21} + (28766080 - 48285920 I) u_{ij-1-4, i, i2-2} + (127246592 - 342233344 I) u_{ij-1-4, i, i2-1} - (9435744 \\
& + 153100032 I) u_{ij-1-4, i, i2} + (36011776 - 190785792 I) u_{ij-1-4, i, i2-2-1} + (81815040 + 1327493120 I) u_{ij-1-4, i, i2-1-1} - (168308480 + 324017920 I) u_{ij-1-4, i, i2-1} - (2450592 + 39762176 I) u_{ij-1-4, i, i2-2-21} - (59166976 + 184919808 I) u_{ij-1-4, i, i2-1-21} - (34477696 + 44388128 I) u_{ij-1-4, i, i2-21} + (1508935 \\
& - 7994145 I) u_{ij-4, i, i2-2} + (277376 - 52848432 I) u_{ij-4, i, i2-1} - (8896377 + 20341911 I) u_{ij-4, i, i2} - (4592752 + 27724736 I) u_{ij-4, i, i2-2-1} + (77138320 + 176379760 I) u_{ij-4, i, i2-1-1} - (38992080 + 35674240 I) u_{ij-4, i, i2-1} - (2310511 + 5283073 I) u_{ij-4, i, i2-2-21} - (17238848 + 22194064 I) u_{ij-4, i, i2-1-21} \\
& - (6894063 + 4319159 I) u_{ij-4, i, i2-21}), O(\Delta x I^6 \Delta x2^6), \textit{Quadrant 3}
\end{aligned}$$

Error order: 6, Error: 5.9739699224214801807 × 10⁻¹⁷, New Error: 5.9886191333116262428 × 10⁻³⁵
Error order: 6, Error: 5.9886191333116262428 × 10⁻³⁵, New Error: 5.9886338004868488434 × 10⁻⁵³
Error order: 6, Error: 5.9886338004868488434 × 10⁻⁵³, New Error: 5.9886338151540420452 × 10⁻⁷¹
Error order: 6, Error: 5.9886338151540420452 × 10⁻⁷¹, New Error: 5.9886338151687092384 × 10⁻⁸⁹
Error order: 6, Error: 5.9886338151687092384 × 10⁻⁸⁹, New Error: 5.9886338151687239056 × 10⁻¹⁰⁷

"--- Derivative Order: 4 - x1=1 ---"

$$\begin{bmatrix} -2 & -1 & 0 \\ -2 - I & -1 - I & -I \\ -2 - 2 I & -1 - 2 I & -2 I \end{bmatrix}$$

$$\begin{bmatrix} -\frac{663}{10} - 36 I & -\frac{2046}{5} - 126 I & -\frac{1503}{10} \\ -\frac{1266}{5} - 54 I & 1662 & -\frac{2046}{5} + 126 I \\ -\frac{543}{10} & -\frac{1266}{5} + 54 I & -\frac{663}{10} + 36 I \end{bmatrix}$$

$$\frac{d^4}{dx I^4} u(xI) = \frac{3 \left(-(221 + 120 I) u_{ij-2} - (1364 + 420 I) u_{ij-1} - 501 u_{ij} - (844 + 180 I) u_{ij-2-1} + 5540 u_{ij-1-1} + (-1364 + 420 I) u_{ij-1} - 181 u_{ij-2-21} + (-844 + 180 I) u_{ij-1-21} + (-221 + 120 I) u_{ij-21} \right)}{10 \Delta x I^4}, O(\Delta x I^5), \textit{Quadrant 3}$$

Error order: 5, Error: 3.8549867487973772508 × 10⁻¹⁵, New Error: 3.8614293070021089023 × 10⁻³⁰
Error order: 5, Error: 3.8614293070021089023 × 10⁻³⁰, New Error: 3.8614357549461586846 × 10⁻⁴⁵
Error order: 5, Error: 3.8614357549461586846 × 10⁻⁴⁵, New Error: 3.8614357613941081232 × 10⁻⁶⁰
Error order: 5, Error: 3.8614357613941081232 × 10⁻⁶⁰, New Error: 3.8614357614005560727 × 10⁻⁷⁵
Error order: 5, Error: 3.8614357614005560727 × 10⁻⁷⁵, New Error: 3.8614357614005625206 × 10⁻⁹⁰

$$\begin{aligned}
\frac{d^8}{dx I^8} u(xI) &= \frac{1}{100 \Delta x I^8} \left(9 \left((34441 + 53040 I) u_{ij-4} + (502088 + 513000 I) u_{ij-3} + (1905538 + 1266000 I) u_{ij-2} + (1366728 + 420840 I) u_{ij-1} + 251001 u_{ij} + (329848 + 282120 I) u_{ij-4-1} - (297448 + 129600 I) u_{ij-3-1} - (13563744 + 4331520 I) u_{ij-2-1} - 1477288 u_{ij-1-1} + (1366728 - 420840 I) u_{ij-1} + (759938 \right. \right. \\
& + 347280 I) u_{ij-4-21} - (8441504 + 1719360 I) u_{ij-3-21} + 35906708 u_{ij-2-21} + (-13563744 + 4331520 I) u_{ij-1-21} + (1905538 - 1266000 I) u_{ij-21} + (305528 + 65160 I) u_{ij-4-31} - 516008 u_{ij-3-31} + (-8441504 + 1719360 I) u_{ij-2-31} + (-297448 + 129600 I) u_{ij-1-31} + (502088 - 513000 I) u_{ij-31} \\
& \left. + 32761 u_{ij-4-41} + (305528 - 65160 I) u_{ij-3-41} + (759938 - 347280 I) u_{ij-2-41} + (329848 - 282120 I) u_{ij-1-41} + (34441 - 53040 I) u_{ij-41} \right) \right), O(\Delta x I^5), \textit{Quadrant 3}
\end{aligned}$$

Error order: 5, Error: 7.6486008792619547759 × 10⁻¹⁵, New Error: 7.6613834280903688512 × 10⁻³⁰
Error order: 5, Error: 7.6613834280903688512 × 10⁻³⁰, New Error: 7.6613962213251429998 × 10⁻⁴⁵
Error order: 5, Error: 7.6613962213251429998 × 10⁻⁴⁵, New Error: 7.6613962341183884659 × 10⁻⁶⁰
Error order: 5, Error: 7.6613962341183884659 × 10⁻⁶⁰, New Error: 7.6613962341311817114 × 10⁻⁷⁵
Error order: 5, Error: 7.6613962341311817114 × 10⁻⁷⁵, New Error: 7.6613962341311945046 × 10⁻⁹⁰

$$\begin{aligned}
\frac{\partial^8}{\partial x I^4 \partial x2^4} u(xI, x2) &= \frac{1}{100 \Delta x I^4 \Delta x2^4} \left(9 \left((34441 + 53040 I) u_{ij-2, i2-2} + (251044 + 256500 I) u_{ij-2, i2-1} + (110721 + 60120 I) u_{ij-2, i2} + (164924 + 141060 I) u_{ij-2, i2-2-1} - (1224340 + 664800 I) u_{ij-2, i2-1-1} + (351844 + 70860 I) u_{ij-2, i2-1} + (40001 + 21720 I) u_{ij-2, i2-2-21} + (208124 + 61500 I) u_{ij-2, i2-1-21} \right. \right. \\
& + 63241 u_{ij-2, i2-21} + (251044 + 256500 I) u_{ij-1, i2-2} + (1684096 + 1145760 I) u_{ij-1, i2-1} + (683364 + 210420 I) u_{ij-1, i2} + (1075616 + 600000 I) u_{ij-1, i2-2-1} - (7556560 + 2326800 I) u_{ij-1, i2-1-1} + 2036896 u_{ij-1, i2-1} + (246884 + 76020 I) u_{ij-1, i2-2-21} + (1226816 + 108960 I) u_{ij-1, i2-1-21} + (351844 \\
& - 70860 I) u_{ij-1, i2-21} + (110721 + 60120 I) u_{ij, i2-2} + (683364 + 210420 I) u_{ij, i2-1} + 251001 u_{ij, i2} + (422844 + 90180 I) u_{ij, i2-2-1} - 2775540 u_{ij, i2-1-1} + (683364 - 210420 I) u_{ij, i2-1} + 90681 u_{ij, i2-2-21} + (422844 - 90180 I) u_{ij, i2-1-21} + (110721 - 60120 I) u_{ij, i2-21} + (164924 + 141060 I) u_{ij-2-1, i2-2} \\
& + (1075616 + 600000 I) u_{ij-2-1, i2-1} + (422844 + 90180 I) u_{ij-2-1, i2} + (679936 + 303840 I) u_{ij-2-1, i2-2-1} - (4675760 + 997200 I) u_{ij-2-1, i2-1-1} + (1226816 - 108960 I) u_{ij-2-1, i2-1} + (152764 + 32580 I) u_{ij-2-1, i2-2-21} + 744736 u_{ij-2-1, i2-1-21} + (208124 - 61500 I) u_{ij-2-1, i2-21} - (1224340 \\
& + 664800 I) u_{ij-1-1, i2-2} - (7556560 + 2326800 I) u_{ij-1-1, i2-1} - 2775540 u_{ij-1-1, i2} - (4675760 + 997200 I) u_{ij-1-1, i2-2-1} + 30691600 u_{ij-1-1, i2-1-1} + (-7556560 + 2326800 I) u_{ij-1-1, i2-1} - 1002740 u_{ij-1-1, i2-2-21} + (-4675760 + 997200 I) u_{ij-1-1, i2-1-21} + (-1224340 + 664800 I) u_{ij-1-1, i2-21} + (351844 \\
& + 70860 I) u_{ij-1, i2-2} + 2036896 u_{ij-1, i2-1} + (683364 - 210420 I) u_{ij-1, i2} + (1226816 - 108960 I) u_{ij-1, i2-2-1} + (-7556560 + 2326800 I) u_{ij-1, i2-1-1} + (1684096 - 1145760 I) u_{ij-1, i2-1} + (246884 - 76020 I) u_{ij-1, i2-2-21} + (1075616 - 600000 I) u_{ij-1, i2-1-21} + (251044 - 256500 I) u_{ij-1, i2-21} + (40001 \\
& + 21720 I) u_{ij-2-21, i2-2} + (246884 + 76020 I) u_{ij-2-21, i2-1} + 90681 u_{ij-2-21, i2} + (152764 + 32580 I) u_{ij-2-21, i2-2-1} - 1002740 u_{ij-2-21, i2-1-1} + (246884 - 76020 I) u_{ij-2-21, i2-1} + 32761 u_{ij-2-21, i2-2-21} + (152764 - 32580 I) u_{ij-2-21, i2-1-21} + (40001 - 21720 I) u_{ij-2-21, i2-21} + (208124 \\
& + 61500 I) u_{ij-1-21, i2-2} + (1226816 + 108960 I) u_{ij-1-21, i2-1} + (422844 - 90180 I) u_{ij-1-21, i2} + 744736 u_{ij-1-21, i2-2-1} + (-4675760 + 997200 I) u_{ij-1-21, i2-1-1} + (1075616 - 600000 I) u_{ij-1-21, i2-1} + (152764 - 32580 I) u_{ij-1-21, i2-2-21} + (679936 - 303840 I) u_{ij-1-21, i2-1-21} + (164924 \\
& - 141060 I) u_{ij-1-21, i2-21} + 63241 u_{ij-21, i2-2} + (351844 - 70860 I) u_{ij-21, i2-1} + (110721 - 60120 I) u_{ij-21, i2} + (208124 - 61500 I) u_{ij-21, i2-2-1} + (-1224340 + 664800 I) u_{ij-21, i2-1-1} + (251044 - 256500 I) u_{ij-21, i2-1} + (40001 - 21720 I) u_{ij-21, i2-2-21} + (164924 - 141060 I) u_{ij-21, i2-1-21} + (34441 \\
& - 53040 I) u_{ij-21, i2-21} \left. \right) \right), O(\Delta x I^5 \Delta x2^5), \textit{Quadrant 3}
\end{aligned}$$

Error order: 5, Error: 8.69691824701934466568 × 10⁻¹⁴, New Error: 8.7178591581056801622 × 10⁻²⁹
Error order: 5, Error: 8.7178591581056801622 × 10⁻²⁹, New Error: 8.7178801242328196519 × 10⁻⁴⁴

$$\begin{aligned}
& + (71442 + 571536 I) u_{iI, i2-21} + (-365148 + 1889244 I) u_{iI-2-1, i2-2} + (-1016064 + 8065008 I) u_{iI-2-1, i2-1} + (-142884 + 2143260 I) u_{iI-2-1, i2} + (-952560 + 7112448 I) u_{iI-2-1, i2-2-1} + (2540160 - 38102400 I) u_{iI-2-1, i2-1-1} + (-63504 + 8128512 I) u_{iI-2-1, i2-1} + (-111132 + 1666980 I) u_{iI-2-1, i2-2-21} \\
& + 7175952 I u_{iI-2-1, i2-1-21} + (111132 + 1920996 I) u_{iI-2-1, i2-21} + (1270080 - 10160640 I) u_{iI-1-1, i2-2} + (2540160 - 43182720 I) u_{iI-1-1, i2-1} - 11430720 I u_{iI-1-1, i2} + (2540160 - 38102400 I) u_{iI-1-1, i2-2-1} + 203212800 I u_{iI-1-1, i2-1-1} - (2540160 + 43182720 I) u_{iI-1-1, i2-1} - 8890560 I u_{iI-1-1, i2-2-21} \\
& - (2540160 + 38102400 I) u_{iI-1-1, i2-1-21} - (1270080 + 10160640 I) u_{iI-1-1, i2-21} + (-142884 + 2175012 I) u_{iI-1, i2-2} + 9208080 I u_{iI-1, i2-1} + (142884 + 2429028 I) u_{iI-1, i2} + (-63504 + 8128512 I) u_{iI-1, i2-2-1} - (2540160 + 43182720 I) u_{iI-1, i2-1-1} + (1079568 + 9144576 I) u_{iI-1, i2-1} + (111132 \\
& + 1889244 I) u_{iI-1, i2-2-21} + (1016064 + 8065008 I) u_{iI-1, i2-1-21} + (396900 + 2143260 I) u_{iI-1, i2-21} + (-55566 + 444528 I) u_{iI-2-21, i2-2} + (-111132 + 1889244 I) u_{iI-2-21, i2-1} + 500094 I u_{iI-2-21, i2} + (-111132 + 1666980 I) u_{iI-2-21, i2-2-1} - 8890560 I u_{iI-2-21, i2-1-1} + (111132 + 1889244 I) u_{iI-2-21, i2-1} \\
& + 388962 I u_{iI-2-21, i2-2-21} + (111132 + 1666980 I) u_{iI-2-21, i2-1-21} + (55566 + 444528 I) u_{iI-2-21, i2-21} + (-111132 + 1920996 I) u_{iI-1-21, i2-2} + (63504 + 8128512 I) u_{iI-1-21, i2-1} + (142884 + 2143260 I) u_{iI-1-21, i2} + 7175952 I u_{iI-1-21, i2-2-1} - (2540160 + 38102400 I) u_{iI-1-21, i2-1-1} + (1016064 \\
& + 8065008 I) u_{iI-1-21, i2-1} + (111132 + 1666980 I) u_{iI-1-21, i2-2-21} + (952560 + 7112448 I) u_{iI-1-21, i2-1-21} + (365148 + 1889244 I) u_{iI-1-21, i2-21} + 515970 I u_{iI-21, i2-2} + (142884 + 2175012 I) u_{iI-21, i2-1} + (71442 + 571536 I) u_{iI-21, i2} + (111132 + 1920996 I) u_{iI-21, i2-2-1} - (1270080 \\
& + 10160640 I) u_{iI-21, i2-1-1} + (396900 + 2143260 I) u_{iI-21, i2-1} + (55566 + 444528 I) u_{iI-21, i2-2-21} + (365148 + 1889244 I) u_{iI-21, i2-1-21} + (127008 + 500094 I) u_{iI-21, i2-21}), O(\Delta x I^2 \Delta x^2), \text{ Quadrant 3}
\end{aligned}$$

Error order:, 2, *Error:*, 0.000089409417074995960638, *New Error:*, 8.9569410152072423356 × 10⁻¹¹
Error order:, 2, *Error:*, 8.9569410152072423356 × 10⁻¹¹, *New Error:*, 8.9569570287976932665 × 10⁻¹⁷
Error order:, 2, *Error:*, 8.9569570287976932665 × 10⁻¹⁷, *New Error:*, 8.9569570448112980466 × 10⁻²³
Error order:, 2, *Error:*, 8.9569570448112980466 × 10⁻²³, *New Error:*, 8.9569570448273116514 × 10⁻²⁹
Error order:, 2, *Error:*, 8.9569570448273116514 × 10⁻²⁹, *New Error:*, 8.9569570448273276650 × 10⁻³⁵

"--- Derivative Order: 8 - x1=1 ---"

$$\begin{bmatrix} -2 & -1 & 0 \\ -2 - I & -1 - I & -I \\ -2 - 2I & -1 - 2I & -2I \end{bmatrix}$$

$$\begin{bmatrix} 504 & 2016 & 504 \\ 2016 & -10080 & 2016 \\ 504 & 2016 & 504 \end{bmatrix}$$

$$\frac{d^8}{dx I^8} u(xI) = \frac{504 (u_{iI-2} + 4 u_{iI-1} + u_{iI} + 4 u_{iI-2-1} - 20 u_{iI-1-1} + 4 u_{iI-1} + u_{iI-2-21} + 4 u_{iI-1-21} + u_{iI-21})}{\Delta x I^8}, O(\Delta x I), \text{ Quadrant 3}$$

Error order:, 1, *Error:*, 0.0074548401593598494086, *New Error:*, 7.4622763859961161802 × 10⁻⁶
Error order:, 1, *Error:*, 7.4622763859961161802 × 10⁻⁶, *New Error:*, 7.4622838259340661388 × 10⁻⁹
Error order:, 1, *Error:*, 7.4622838259340661388 × 10⁻⁹, *New Error:*, 7.4622838333740078013 × 10⁻¹²
Error order:, 1, *Error:*, 7.4622838333740078013 × 10⁻¹², *New Error:*, 7.462283833814477430 × 10⁻¹⁵
Error order:, 1, *Error:*, 7.462283833814477430 × 10⁻¹⁵, *New Error:*, 7.462283833814551829 × 10⁻¹⁸

$$\frac{d^{16}}{dx I^{16}} u(xI)$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& = \frac{1}{\Delta x I^{16}} (254016 (u_{iI-4} + 8 u_{iI-3} + 18 u_{iI-2} + 8 u_{iI-1} + u_{iI} + 8 u_{iI-4-1} - 8 u_{iI-3-1} - 144 u_{iI-2-1} - 8 u_{iI-1-1} + 8 u_{iI-1} + 18 u_{iI-4-21} - 144 u_{iI-3-21} + 468 u_{iI-2-21} - 144 u_{iI-1-21} + 18 u_{iI-21} + 8 u_{iI-4-31} - 8 u_{iI-3-31} - 144 u_{iI-2-31} - 8 u_{iI-1-31} + 8 u_{iI-31} + u_{iI-4-41} + 8 u_{iI-3-41} + 18 u_{iI-2-41} \\
& + 8 u_{iI-1-41} + u_{iI-41})), O(\Delta x I), \text{ Quadrant 3}
\end{aligned}$$

Error order:, 1, *Error:*, 0.014658621527332591175, *New Error:*, 0.000014687880155523541605
Error order:, 1, *Error:*, 0.000014687880155523541605, *New Error:*, 1.4687909443361674616 × 10⁻⁸
Error order:, 1, *Error:*, 1.4687909443361674616 × 10⁻⁸, *New Error:*, 1.4687909472649541978 × 10⁻¹¹
Error order:, 1, *Error:*, 1.4687909472649541978 × 10⁻¹¹, *New Error:*, 1.4687909472678829846 × 10⁻¹⁴
Error order:, 1, *Error:*, 1.4687909472678829846 × 10⁻¹⁴, *New Error:*, 1.4687909472678859134 × 10⁻¹⁷

$$\frac{\partial^{16}}{\partial x I^8 \partial x^2} u(xI, x2) = \frac{1}{\Delta x I^8 \Delta x^2} (254016 (u_{iI-2, i2-2} + 4 u_{iI-2, i2-1} + u_{iI-2, i2} + 4 u_{iI-2, i2-2-1} - 20 u_{iI-2, i2-1-1} + 4 u_{iI-2, i2-1} + u_{iI-2, i2-2-21} + 4 u_{iI-2, i2-1-21} + u_{iI-2, i2-21} + 4 u_{iI-1, i2-2} + 16 u_{iI-1, i2-1} + 4 u_{iI-1, i2} + 16 u_{iI-1, i2-2-1} - 80 u_{iI-1, i2-1-1} + 16 u_{iI-1, i2-1} + 4 u_{iI-1, i2-2-21} + 16 u_{iI-1, i2-1-21} + 4 u_{iI-1, i2-21}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& + u_{iI, i2-2} + 4 u_{iI, i2-1} + u_{iI, i2} + 4 u_{iI, i2-2-1} - 20 u_{iI, i2-1-1} + 4 u_{iI, i2-1} + u_{iI, i2-2-21} + 4 u_{iI, i2-1-21} + u_{iI, i2-21} + 4 u_{iI-2-1, i2-2} + 16 u_{iI-2-1, i2-1} + 4 u_{iI-2-1, i2} + 16 u_{iI-2-1, i2-2-1} - 80 u_{iI-2-1, i2-1-1} + 16 u_{iI-2-1, i2-1} + 4 u_{iI-2-1, i2-2-21} + 16 u_{iI-2-1, i2-1-21} + 4 u_{iI-2-1, i2-21} - 20 u_{iI-1-1, i2-2} - 80 u_{iI-1-1, i2-1} \\
& - 20 u_{iI-1-1, i2} - 80 u_{iI-1-1, i2-2-1} + 400 u_{iI-1-1, i2-1-1} - 80 u_{iI-1-1, i2-1} - 20 u_{iI-1-1, i2-2-21} - 80 u_{iI-1-1, i2-1-21} - 20 u_{iI-1-1, i2-21} + 4 u_{iI-1, i2-2} + 16 u_{iI-1, i2-1} + 4 u_{iI-1, i2} + 16 u_{iI-1, i2-2-1} - 80 u_{iI-1, i2-1-1} + 16 u_{iI-1, i2-1} + 4 u_{iI-1, i2-2-21} + 16 u_{iI-1, i2-1-21} + 4 u_{iI-1, i2-21} + u_{iI-2-21, i2-2} + 4 u_{iI-2-21, i2-1} \\
& + u_{iI-2-21, i2} + 4 u_{iI-2-21, i2-2-1} - 20 u_{iI-2-21, i2-1-1} + 4 u_{iI-2-21, i2-1} + u_{iI-2-21, i2-2-21} + 4 u_{iI-2-21, i2-1-21} + u_{iI-2-21, i2-21} + 4 u_{iI-1-21, i2-2} + 16 u_{iI-1-21, i2-1} + 4 u_{iI-1-21, i2} + 16 u_{iI-1-21, i2-2-1} - 80 u_{iI-1-21, i2-1-1} + 16 u_{iI-1-21, i2-1} + 4 u_{iI-1-21, i2-2-21} + 16 u_{iI-1-21, i2-1-21} + 4 u_{iI-1-21, i2-21} \\
& + u_{iI-21, i2-2} + 4 u_{iI-21, i2-1} + u_{iI-21, i2} + 4 u_{iI-21, i2-2-1} - 20 u_{iI-21, i2-1-1} + 4 u_{iI-21, i2-1} + u_{iI-21, i2-2-21} + 4 u_{iI-21, i2-1-21} + u_{iI-21, i2-21}), O(\Delta x I \Delta x^2), \text{ Quadrant 3}
\end{aligned}$$

Error order:, 1, *Error:*, 0.048490656009356909125, *New Error:*, 0.000048611597966016818846
Error order:, 1, *Error:*, 0.000048611597966016818846, *New Error:*, 4.8611719058821653670 × 10⁻⁸
Error order:, 1, *Error:*, 4.8611719058821653670 × 10⁻⁸, *New Error:*, 4.8611719179914609479 × 10⁻¹¹
Error order:, 1, *Error:*, 4.8611719179914609479 × 10⁻¹¹, *New Error:*, 4.8611719180035702435 × 10⁻¹⁴
Error order:, 1, *Error:*, 4.8611719180035702435 × 10⁻¹⁴, *New Error:*, 4.8611719180035823527 × 10⁻¹⁷

"--- Derivative Order: 1 - x1=1 ---"

$$\begin{bmatrix} -3 & -2 & -1 & 0 \\ -3 - I & -2 - I & -1 - I & -I \\ -3 - 2I & -2 - 2I & -1 - 2I & -2I \\ -3 - 3I & -2 - 3I & -1 - 3I & -3I \end{bmatrix}$$

